

GOVERNED BY ALGORITHMS: FACEBOOK, FOUCAULT, AND THE DIGITAL STATE

by Peter Thorsten Brønholt

Thesis submitted June 2021 in partial fulfilment of requirements

of the University of the West of Scotland

for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

Abstract:

The objective of this thesis is to propose and analyse the digital state through an exploration of the governmentalities of Facebook. In this thesis, the digital state is proposed as the newest iteration of the Foucauldian technology called “state”, and Facebook is proposed as the most salient site for its exploration and analysis. This thesis provides original contribution to Foucauldian theory, as well as to the social sciences and related fields in general and the intersection between political theory and social media studies in particular. It does so through the development of the concept of the digital state, through the digital genealogy employed to analyse the governmentality of the digital state of Facebook, and through its far-reaching insights about the subjects of the digital age, both individually and collectively.

A methodological approach based on Foucauldian scholarship termed digital genealogy is proposed and developed. In the digital genealogical approach the researcher combines a critical, hermeneutic approach with digital tools of information gathering, allowing him to take advantage of the breadth and depth of the connected communities of the digital world. It is found, first, that the digital state wields similar tools and technologies to the modern state, as described by Foucault and others; second, that the particular nature of algorithmic adaptation of the digital milieu to personalise content makes the digital state more than just a hyperlinked version of the modern state. The current and coming subjects of digital modernity exist across the offline-online divide, and this entails a radical difference from the pre-digital subjects that came before. While a double subjection is taking place in the digital realm, as well as in the space related to an offline state, the emerging nature of that subjection in the digital is so different from the double subjection so well known to Foucauldians as to constitute a triple subjection. This triple subjection unique to the regime of the digital state births insights about the user-citizens of the dawning age, and leads to cautions about the subjects we are to become. The thesis emphasises the radical difference to those that came before the dawning trans-human life-form which most humans have already become without their reflective knowledge. Finally, the thesis proposes recommendations for individuals and political entities, seeking to weather the tide of digital modernity and the subjects created by the digital state. A tide, it is argued, which cannot be stemmed, only steered.

Disclaimer: I hereby declare this thesis to be my own original work, based on research conducted while enrolled as a doctoral student/candidate at the University of the West of Scotland under the supervision of Professor David McGillivray (lead), Dr Carlton Brick, and Dr Matthew Frew. Prior to this my work has not been submitted for a DBA, DProf, EngD, PhD or a comparable academic award.

This is the first publication based on this research. Any material quoted in this thesis is clearly marked as such, using citation marks or italics with indentation, and/or referenced using the Harvard citation system in the CTR style and listed in the Bibliography.

All the material analysed is obtained by lawful means and is or has been freely available via the Internet and/or through library services (patents, court case documents, and miscellaneous). No personal or confidential information has been used or cited in this work, and in illustrative screenshots of various Facebook features all names and faces but the researcher's own have been obscured.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

List of Figures	VI
Acknowledgements	VII
1. Introduction	1
1.1 Study aim and objective.....	4
1.2 A brief history of social media	5
1.2.1 Facebook Inc.	9
1.2.2 Key Concepts.....	10
1.3 Thesis structure.....	11
2. Wrapping a Foucauldian frame.....	17
2.1 Foucault's oeuvre.....	17
2.1.1 Foucauldian "science"	21
2.1.2 The genealogical method.....	25
2.1.3 Discourse analysis	26
2.1.4 Relativity, particularism, and critique	28
2.2 Foucault for Facebook	30
2.2.1 Enter the matrix	32
3 Power and subjection	37
3.1 The power of Foucault	38
3.2 The power of others	42
3.2.1 Lukes, Bachrach, Baratz & Dahl	42
3.2.2 Digital power in Luhmannic light	49
3.2.3 Stray, but never falter	51
3.3 Subject(s) and freedom.....	52
3.4 Governmentality	55
4. The digital state	61
4.1 The concept of state	61
4.1.1 Defining a state	62
4.1.2 The Foucauldian state.....	65
4.1.3 Governmentality of the modern state.....	71
4.1.4 Questions of state and power.....	76
4.2 Facebook as a state.....	78
4.2.1 States, corporations, and other institutions	80
4.2.2 Garrett and the corporation as a sovereign	83
4.2.3 The classic state of Facebook.....	87
4.2.4 The economic and monetary power of Facebook	93
4.2.5 The public welfare of Facebook.....	98
4.2.6 Wider theoretical considerations	100

4.2.7 Facebook is a state (of sorts)	102
4.3 The state of digital modernity.....	105
4.3.1 A digital place for the digital state	105
4.3.2 Cyber policy.....	108
5. Casting webs on the net	111
5.1 The ones who came before	111
5.1.1 Studies of homo digitalis.....	112
5.1.2 Studies of social media and digital platforms	115
5.1.3 Scraping and other mathesis of code	118
5.2 Foucault of the machine	119
5.2.1 Studying digital subjects	120
5.2.2 Analysing Facebook.....	122
5.3 Methods.....	124
5.3.1 Discourse analysis	124
5.3.2 Data sources.....	125
5.3.3 Digital Genealogy	130
5.4 Sins and penitence.....	132
5.4.1 Shedding a positivist light on things	133
5.4.2 Who framed the Foucauldian rabbit?.....	136
6. The structure of Facebook.....	141
6.1 The digital constitution of self	141
6.1.1 Facebook profile	142
6.1.2 Facebook status and Photos	145
6.1.3 (Facebook) Messenger.....	148
6.1.4 News Feed.....	151
6.1.5 Other places and pages.....	154
6.2 Laws, policing and ethereal governance.....	155
6.2.1 Inappropriate or abusive things.....	156
6.2.2 Independent oversight, self-subjection, and constitutional monarchy.....	158
6.2.3 The medium of least resistance	159
7. The governmentality of the digital state	165
7.1 Hacking the user	166
7.2 Trust me, I'm an engineer	169
7.2.1 Move fast and break things	171
7.2.2 Moving forward, pushing through.....	175
7.2.3 The governmentality of Facebook Inc.	176
7.3 Governing the Facebook subject	178
7.3.1 Self-subjectivisation and conduct of self	178
7.3.2 Cyber panopticon.....	181

7.3.3 The digital pastorate	182
8. The digital subject.....	185
8.1 The re-enchantment of life and the world	186
8.1.1 Re-animated flesh of concrete, steel, and dead fur	187
8.1.2 Digitised humanity	188
8.2 Triply subjected.....	191
8.2.1 How best to train the digital subject.....	197
8.2.2 Nurture, nature, and randomised A/B.....	200
8.2.3. Governed by algorithms	201
9. The digital State	205
9.1 Digitised governmentality.....	205
9.1.1 Shaping idea and matter	207
9.1.2 Digital modernity	209
9.2 The inevitability of subjection.....	210
9.2.1 The acceleration of everything.	211
9.2.2 Accelerated societies	213
9.2.3 Resistance is futile	214
9.3 Rebooté la resistance.....	215
9.3.1 Let the voiceless speak	217
10. In the land of the coded, the program is sovereign.....	221
10.1 Dreams of digital domination	221
10.1.1 Why Foucault?	223
10.2 Deus est machina ex machine	225
10.3 Digital modernity	227
10.4 To Utopia and beyond	228
Bibliography	231

List of Figures

Figure 1: Screenshot of Facebook.com source code, viewed in Google Chrome.....	129
Figure 2: Researcher's 'Basic Information' (Facebook), March 2019.....	143
Figure 3: Researcher's Facebook profile preview, September 2020	144
Figure 4: Researcher's Facebook activity log as seen by user, March 2019.	144
Figure 5: Researcher's Photos tab on Facebook (contacts anonymised), July 2020.	146
Figure 6: Researcher's Facebook Messenger (contacts anonymised), September 2019.	149
Figure 7: 'Remove' dialogue from researcher's Facebook Messenger, September 2019	150
Figure 8: Researcher's Facebook News Feed (contacts anonymised), September 2019	152
Figure 9: 'Reactions' to content, September, 2019 (Facebook, 2019C).	153
Figure 10: Editing dialogue for 'basic info' on Facebook, step one, September 2020	160
Figure 11: Editing dialogue for 'basic info' on Facebook, step two, September 2020	160
Figure 12: Illustration of 'How users see programmers' and vice versa (Vas, 2013).....	167
Figure 13: Trust me, I'm an engineer (Google Image Search)	170
Figure 14: Move fast and break things (Deerkoski, 2014)	172
Figure 15: Double subjection (self, sovereign)	192
Figure 16: Relations of subjection to the modern state	193
Figure 17: Double subjection (self, sovereign), aided by algorithms.....	194
Figure 18: Triple subjection (self, sovereign, algorithms).....	195

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am immensely grateful to my eminent supervisors, Professor David McGillivray, Dr Matthew Frew and Dr Carlton Brick. To Carlton for challenging and engaging with my Foucauldian efforts, to Matt for mind-mapping our discussions forward across, time, space, and spheres – and, finally, to David who stands for me as the Kantian ideal of what a supervisor can be. Though the work, ideas, and insights in this thesis are my own, any chance that they have emerged comprehensible is due to David’s support, advice, re-reads, immensely helpful comments, and all too polite suggestions.

I thank the University of the West of Scotland for funding me and my project. There, in Paisley, I learned more than could have been summed up in any ranking list. I am not a quiet worker, and at the UWS I have found that not just David and other PGR Coordinators, but also Professor Milan Radosavljevic of the Doctoral College and Professor Craig Mahoney were willing to listen to, take in, and take serious feedback and critique. No institution is above reproach, but when leaders are willing to listen, changes can always be made for the better. I also thank the Department of Political Science at the University of Copenhagen who gave me the training that enabled my turn towards academia, and who welcomed me back as a visiting PhD Candidate and External Lecturer. Special thanks goes to Professor Jens Hoff, not only for supervising my MA and BA theses, but especially for comments, edits and helpful talks.

Through my studies, I have been lucky to meet distinguished scholars of all shades, stripes, and levels. So many have been great friends, colleagues, and supports, and drawing out in detail all the blessings they have bestowed upon me would be a thesis unto itself. Therefore, in no particular order, I wish to deeply thank already or soon to-be Doctors Carolina Silveira, Sean Kippin, Jesús Eduardo Russián, Nicola Hay, Greis Cifuentes, Rachid Hallouz, Oluseyi Kezia Ife, Daniel McKay, Katey Teppin, Shad Tembo, Ramesh Gupta, Ioannis Rigkos-Zitthen, Yevgeniy Golovchenko, Regitze Helene Rohlfing Frederiksen, Paw Hansen, Malte Dahl, Benjamin Carl Egerod, Simon Polichinel von der Maase, Kristin Anabel Eggeling, and Ioanna Noula.

I must also thank my family. None of this would have been possible without all the love and support I have been surrounded with as my passions have dragged me out there and back again, yet again. Wherever I

have landed, I was sure to always carry home with me, through visits and messages (even snail-mail letters!) from my loving parents, Lis Lynge Brønholt and Niels Brønholt, my lovely sisters, Anna Julie Brønholt Hanash and Maria Gry Brønholt Thøgersen, their amazing spouses Sofian Brønholt Hanash and Jens-Erik Brønholt Thøgersen, and all the kids, Silke, Johan, Aya and Lina. I love you all deeply and am immensely proud and grateful that we have each other, always.

To my friends from outside the academy, a special shoutout to Lars and Sebastian, who have visited me here, there, and everywhere, and always been ready to trounce me in chess, Warcraft III, and Race for the Galaxy. Also, big thanks to Linda, Jesper, Einar, Sandro, Danny, and Joseph for providing D&D, discussions, and diversions through the years.

Finally, I thank my amazing partner and spouse-to-be, Wiebke. I could never have imagined that finishing the PhD would be the second-biggest thing to happen in my life in 2020-2021, but here we are. And I couldn't be happier. What a ride.

As the bumblebee flies

so the human believes

in itself

1. INTRODUCTION

Power relations are rooted in the system of social networks

(Michel Foucault, 1982, p. 793)

The era of the digital had humble beginnings, but was discursively loaded with all the potentials of a new age, a new space; a new social reality. Famously epitomised by John Perry Barlow's ... *Declaration of the Independence of Cyberspace* (1996), the shapers of this brave new digital world saw in the Internet endless possibility, and ultimate freedom (Snowden, 2019). Now, decades later, reality has more than caught up with this dream of leaving behind the "weary giants of flesh and steel" (Barlow, 1996), and we live in the digital age.

The digitalisation of the human subject has brought about many changes, many of which can be hard to define separately or even as singular things (Kaufmann & Jeandesboz, 2017; O'Hara, 2020). As with most major events in the history of any species, it did not happen overnight. It has been several hundred years since Hegel wrote about the master-servant (or slave) dialectic, and as Foucault and others have argued, it seems reasonable to assume that were it not for the enlightenment period in general, and Sigmund Freud in particular, then our (modern) notion of an individual – a singular, definable human entity – might not even exist. Add to that the bio-politics of the pre-modern and modern (nation) state in Foucault and as depicted by Victor Hugo in *Les Misérables* (1862): 'Now bring me prisoner 24601!' If Jean Valjean had not been assigned a number, Javert could not have called him out. And though he might be the source of some resistance, he is ultimately doubly subjected in the Foucauldian sense, like the rest of us. Like we are to Facebook. Thrice subjected, perhaps even, in our case.

Through the ages, human society has undergone many changes. Changes in norms, organisations, definitions, ends, and means. Some, we hope, for the better. As the centuries passed, a form of organisation called "state" appeared: an amalgam of techniques of governance of self and others, as seen in a Foucauldian view (Foucault, 1979B). Neither the concept of state, its techniques, its governance, nor

the governed self are static. Whether one attempts theory or empirics, these are yet others of the so-famed “moving targets” of “social science” (Foucault, 1989 [1966]). Moving though they may be, they are significant. The state is here to stay, if not necessarily as an entity by that name or as more than a fleeting feature of a human time soon to have passed. For the eternal temporality that is the here and now, the state looms inexorably across those vast expanses of time, place, and understanding.

The emergence, changes, and mutations of state forms, rationalities, and power have been well documented (Willoughby, 1896; Weber, 1905; Weber, 2002[1922]; Foucault, 1995 [1975]; 2006 [1979]; 1979A; Anderson, 2006 [1983]; Gellner, 1983; Brubaker, 1997; Rose, O'Malley, & Valverde, 2009; Dean & Villadsen, 2016). In the information-overloaded society of the 2nd or 3rd modernity there are many stories to tell, and many stories of state. This is another such story. Not a story of nation states, not really. Not a story of cities and physicalities, at least not in a traditional sense. Perhaps it is not even a story of a state in a complete sense. Rather, this is the story of a transformation. A story of a new form of state and power; a form of power imbued in something, which some would say is not, and perhaps never will be, truly a state. Others would say that social media has long since become that, and perhaps more besides (van Dijck, Poell, & de Waal, 2018). This is a story about the logics, and workings of the digital state, a story of power – of techniques and subjections that emerged quite recently, but which have come to capture and dominate striking amounts of our energy, our time, and our attention. We live increasingly mediated lives; we perform and experience our existence, implicitly and explicitly accepting the structures and rules that bind us, our lives, and our performance of self: our subjection of self and others. We may still be human, whatever that means, but as such we are increasingly governed by algorithms.

As we enter the third decade of the second millennia of our increasingly standardised counting, our daily lives are embedded in technology, and our social reality is mediated by machines and algorithms, as our forebears' once were by the letters, the scribes, and the village gossips (Anderson, 2006 [1983]; Harari, 2015). As the reach and societal importance of social media platforms grow, so does the power mediated through them; the power embedded in their coded structures. Whatever entity controls the form and flow of information and social contact – an entity that enables some actions but not others, that polices the

content of those same actions, that connects people and their accounts – through this entity flows a substantial amount of power in almost any theoretical sense of the word. Even as the numbers, the studies, and the arguments are yet to come, it seems uncontroversial to state that Facebook has grown to immense political, sociological, and human importance. Facebook itself might be supplanted or annexed into something else, but the techniques of Facebook as an abstract – an empirical example of something new, something which I will introduce as the arena of the ‘digital state’ – seem here to stay. Whether the digital state continues in the “private” corporate hands they are now, in the hands of those other entities already called state, or something else entirely is not the focus here. Nor is the focus to understand Facebook for its own sake. In a sense, much of what Facebook is – much of the story behind it – is not needed to tell the story about the (digital) state of Facebook. In this thesis, Facebook is important not merely as a company or an actor, but as a site where we can observe the ‘governmentality’ of the digital state (Foucault, 2006 [1979]).

As with all aspects of human life, the online arenas of existence are immersed in power. Some of it is created, warped, and adapted by and on these planes, but much of it simply re-affirmed and re-appearing as seen before and elsewhere. In this digital sphere, the collection of technologies of self and others called state (Foucault, 1997 [1978]) has been slow to make its entry. In the now of my writing, the long-saturated social world online is only starting to be colonised from the state centres of the offline world. As these “offline states” stretch their techniques of self and others into and paste them onto the digital, they are often still rooted in and connected to those techniques and rationalities that were before and still remain in and around offline subjects (including the offline part of the various legal subjects that exist in both planes). In the online sphere, however, entities and economics of power have emerged that seem all but sui generis of this new state of being. In building and ordering the world online, and its connections to what worlds we see elsewhere, Facebook, Google, Amazon, and others have emerged as looming sovereigns of the digital (Zuboff, 2019; MacKinnon, 2012). They differ in important ways, and in some cases act as mere facilitators or proxies of state institutions that exist outside their realms. The idea that private corporations can be seen as agents of the public state is nothing new (Miller, 1960). Some digital corporations, like Google, are so connected to the political arena in the US and elsewhere that it can be difficult to set the

limits as to where one ends and the other – in new forms and arenas – begins (Zuboff, 2019). Others, like Amazon, are so connected to infrastructural institutions of (the US) state and neo-liberal entities of micro-power in economic and labour markets, as to challenge the possibility of an analysis differentiating between the offline and online – the public and the private – at all.

Though these trends and aspects all apply to this entity, which is by no means an ideal type, Facebook can be first and foremost understood as a digital sovereign that creates, shapes, and governs a delimited social space in the online world. And so, with its 2.6 billion monthly users (Facebook, 2020C) Facebook emerges as the most salient proxy for an exploration of power and subjection by, of, and in a digital state. By extension, Facebook as an entity and a meta-physical place, provides the onus and site of this study. The aim is not to explore Facebook for what it is in the now, nor even all that it has been in the past. In the view adopted here, Facebook is a proxy for a digital state structure – a centre of digital state power. That does not imply that Facebook is or is not “a state”. It simply means that techniques of power and subjection which we can collectively call digital state are to be found at work there. Future work might find one or more – even all – of these techniques, or some of their modalities and their targets, to be originating in one or more of the institutions of formal nation states. This distinction is not important here. Certainly, in a certain sense Facebook can be seen as “a state”. An aside, but a relevant one which I will address along the way (see Chapter 4). This study deals with features and logics inherent to state power in the digital realm, governing wholly or partially digital subjects. The aim is to uncover the logics embedded in what the digital state of Facebook is and does. Not to understand the thing itself, but rather to lay bare the emerging power of the state that is to come and which operates in this digital milieu. The techniques of a type of state power and rationality that might rule us all, whether it will have been historically and discursively rooted in “the nation state” of these last few flashes of history, in the unassailable “corporation” as it has emerged in the stretch of the liberal eras, or in something else entirely.

1.1 Study aim and objective

The objective of this study is to uncover the governmentality of the digital state. This will be done through a digital genealogy of the techniques of subjection on Facebook. This implies an emulation of Foucault’s

genealogical method, which is performed on digital artefacts and through technologies existing in and concerning the coded space of the digital. Hence, I term it a 'digital genealogy', the "digital" part of the name referring only to the object(s) and mediation, not the genealogy itself, which is not otherwise seen as substantially different from the Foucauldian approach that is emulated (see Chapter 5). In this thesis I explore Facebook as a space, a place, and a site of state power. I will uncover and describe those rationalities of governance embedded in the applied techniques of subjection and power –the 'governmentalities'**Invalid source specified.** of the digital state of Facebook. Constructing a view and a truth about these will enable me to say something, not just about the digital sovereigns that are and will be, but also about humans and other subjects in the social world of today and tomorrow. The goal is to explore an emerging arena, site, and type of state, power, and subjection. In doing so, I show how the life-worlds and existence of human subjects are increasingly migrating to digital spaces, the (meta-)physicality of which will be discussed in greater detail, as I move into a discussion of what I propose as an era of 'digital modernity'.

A Foucauldian genealogy and a discourse analysis are not to be seen as "methods" to ascertain "objective" truths. They need to be situated in the concrete discursive objects, relative truths, and histories told that bind and connect the discourses to be analysed. For this reason, I pre-empt the analysis here and sketch out the situation of the site containing the object even before its operationalisation. In the coming chapters I explain more explicitly what hen, egg, and coop we are talking about and how. But now, I sketch out these digital birds that cluck and tweet. The meta-physical area of human conscience that emerged at the end of a millennia.

1.2 A brief history of social media

As with many concepts in wide common usage, most people today recognise the term social media (often abbreviated SoMe) and have an idea what it refers to. At the same time the term is not clearly defined in the literature (Obar & Wildman, 2015, p. 745). Social media widely refers to platforms that enable creating and/or sharing and/or interacting with media content with social contacts, and is to be seen in contrast with broadcast media (e.g. radio and television). It is often emphasised how social media utilises Web 2.0

technologies allowing platforms to adapt to the individual users, and enabling the users to interact with content, potentially engaging with the original content creator (Gillespie, 2010; Sujon & Dyer, 2020). In this narrative, traditional broadcast media is viewed as unidirectional, with arduously produced content sent explicitly from one active originator to multiple passive users. Feedback is only possible through various loops wrought with gatekeepers and the demand for time, skill, and energy on the part of the person seeking to initiate communication from users back to the broadcasting entity. Social media, on the other hand, is generally seen as multidirectional. It can be argued that since some social media content generators are economically or culturally “bigger” than others, and include private individuals and institutions including broadcast media organisations, there are still degrees of unidirectionality embedded in parts of the information flow structure. Complete unidirectionality, though, is generally seen as unfeasible, as interaction (with digital personas, if not necessarily with actual humans linked to that persona) is the social and attentional capital that builds audience on these platforms.

Social media platforms are said to have “evolved” from the internet sites and chat platforms of the late 1990s (Helmond, 2015). Indeed, the original Internet can in concept be said to have been a social media platform in itself. Up through the 1990s, what emerged as the World Wide Web – a 1989 protocol for use via/on the Internet – became populated with web sites featuring static content (Miscellaneous, 2020C). Each person “visiting” a site would see the same text and graphics. In the same period various “chat” services, allowing users to write instant messages to each other from computer to computer was created, using both local (Local Area Network) and global (Internet) networks. In time, websites dedicated to chats and discussions emerged on the Internet, allowing social (mainly text-based) interaction in various forms. At the time, web browsers were not yet the centre of attention for computer users, and the 1990s also saw the rise and fall of various stand-alone messaging clients operating via the Internet, such as ICQ, AOL Messenger, Yahoo Messenger, and later Microsoft/MSN Messenger. The latter was renamed several times and finally integrated into the still existing messaging and video-chat program, Skype. Add to that chats in and about online computer games. It is important to note that through the development sketched out so far, by far the most sites and services were inherently anonymous (Žižek, 1998; Clarke, 1994; Clarke, 2014). The few sites and services that registered IP addresses tended not to connect them to specific user

accounts, other than by registering their e-mail address (itself registerable without logging any personal information) and not at all to physical persons in the “offline world”¹. In this environment, where users could create and play with varying identities as they pleased, one form of web site that emerged were the “weblogs” – blogs. With content ranging from amateur news coverage and comment, over public diaries to short stories, coding instructions, and bad jokes, the blogs gained increasing attention also in the academy, sparking among others Sunstein’s important 2001 book, *Republic.com*, on the potential threat to deliberative democracy posed by the personalised blogosphere and online news sites (Sunstein, 2007).

In the newest millennia, internet services and sites have increasingly moved towards ‘nonymity’ (Zhao, Grasmuck, & Martin, 2008), with users being named and identified wherever they virtually go. Most users today are identified not only in terms of their unique online identities being linked up to their offline ones, but also in terms of all but every action taken on every site being logged and linked to that identity (including typing a search term in a box and deleting it without pressing ‘Enter’) (Palmås, 2011). This enables data brokers to retain the sum of all that can be collected through what Haggerty and Ericson (2000) term ‘the surveillant assemblage’: a mutable collection of technologies and techniques of surveillance. This development was spearheaded by Google and Facebook – but arguably also by an increasing degree of spill-over from the virtual to the physical, political world (MacKinnon, 2012, p. 120; Zuboff, 2019). As Haggerty and Ericsson (2000), and others have pointed out this digital panopticon – a milieu where everyone is always potentially being observed – is inexorably linked to Foucauldian thinking. There is, perhaps, an irony to how the plasticity of the Internet of yore was hailed for how it allowed users to play with identities, including markers of gender and race – not to mention sexuality (Žižek, 1998; Clarke, 1994). This Internet carried within it a unique capacity to define and change the link from subjects to their often self-assigned quantified identities – again including whatever markers were/are deemed relevant as data points for social interaction, interests and, most especially, advertisements. Seeped in structures of ‘infopower’ – the disciplinary bio-power unique to the informational age, as developed by Koopman (2019)

¹ Then, as now, most standard internet connections have dynamic internet addresses (due to this being cheaper for Internet Service Providers(ISP)’s for various technical reasons) (ConnectWise, 2017).

– the internet that was allowed the users to freely define what they wanted to be socially albeit within the often binaries of quantified social identity markers (Clarke, 1994). This changed over time. Increasingly connected to the perceived empirically “true” offline identities certified by nation states, the identities available to online subjects became fixed and ever more meaningful, as content was shaped and shared according to those markers. Much like the proposed traits of quantitative psychology transitioned from unverified theory to objective, empirical truth up to the middle of the last century (Koopman, 2019), the legion categories of big data are now used by algorithms to differentiate content and users in an increasingly individualised and individualising governance of the digital subject.

As the first decade after the Y2K (the turn of the second millennium, CE) and its microchip challenges progressed, the personal homepages, blogging sites, and chat forums became integrated into a form that first complemented, but increasingly supplanted their presence and attention on the Internet: The social media platform (Helmond, 2015; Gillespie, 2010). Many sites can now be said to carry this nomenclature, and indeed some, such as LinkedIn, have in some form existed since before they could be said to fit any such description and exist still. The traditional historiographic narrative is to mention the erstwhile “big three”, in order of appearance: Myspace, launched in 2003, Facebook, launched in 2004, and Twitter, launched in 2006. Many others could be named, not least in a wider, less western-centric narrative, but these are the ones most commonly mentioned when discussing the emergence of social media sites (later, platforms cf. Helmond 2015). Of the three, Facebook is now by far the biggest, whether measured in terms of users, employees, influence or capital (or power, cf. Fuchs, 2013). At the time of writing, Facebook is by far the biggest social network ever to have existed, in terms of users, revenue, and influence. Facebook currently claims to have 2.6 billion monthly active users, at least half of them active daily, and via mobile (Facebook, 2020C). With a revenue of \$ 55,838 million for 2018, \$ 70,679 million for 2019, and \$ 85,965 million for 2020 (Facebook, 2019A; 2021A), the economic and social influence of the Facebook company, (hereafter Facebook Inc.) even viewed in isolation from the nature of its platform and services, is immense (Fuchs D., 2013).

1.2.1 Facebook Inc.

Soon encompassing a third of the world's population, the social media platform Facebook is the largest gathering of humans ever seen, in relative and total, albeit not physical terms. Whether it is seen as a company, a platform, a community, or something different entirely, there is no denying Facebook Inc.'s increasing importance and influence in shaping the lives of contemporary humans and their societies. At the core of what it does, Facebook Inc. controls information – knowledge flows. And as Foucault taught us:

... power produces knowledge (and not simply by encouraging it because it serves power or by applying it because it is useful); ... power and knowledge directly imply one another; ... there is no power relation without the correlative constitution of a field of knowledge, nor any knowledge that does not presuppose and constitute at the same time power relations.

(Foucault, 1995 [1975], p. 27)

The structures on Facebook control the flow of power and exercises power in everything it does, in ways resembling a modern nation state migrated to the digital realm (see Chapter 4). For the overall thesis, however, it is important to remember that the object here is not Facebook-as-a-state (or not), but rather the digital state of Facebook. This digital state is to be understood as a collection of techniques of governance and subjection, which are unique to the digital age, and which I analyse as they appear on and in relation to Facebook. Facebook is the site, not the object of analysis – a point that should become clearer as I lay out the Foucauldian frame. For now, let us just consider the Facebook and the Facebook Inc. we know.

It would be hard for most contemporary humans to imagine a daily life without Facebook (or the Russian VKontakte or the Chinese Wechat, respectively). Even those who are not active or passive users of social media, are influenced by it, as content and interaction originating there tends to blend through to other media and personal contacts into their personal lives. This change into a digitally mediated social humanity has been marked both by the radical change some argue it to be to humans both as a species and as individuals, and by its rapidity (Capurro, 2017). At the time of writing, online social platforms as the all-

pervading, integral part of daily lives it seems to be today have barely been in existence in 20 years. Part of the change to the social interaction of humans in which social media has taken such a prominent part is through its colonisation or co-optation of other forms of mediation of social contact, such as phone calls, short text messages (SMS), and internet-based messaging services (Helmond, 2015). For this reason, the digitisation of daily lives should not be seen as exclusively the story of how social media platforms grew and established or took over increasing shares of the mediation of social life. Rather, this should be seen as a story unto itself, embedded in a wider narrative of what some term as the transition, as a species, to *homo digitalis* (Mbembe, quoted in Bangstad & Nielsen, 2019; Montag & Diefenbach, 2018).

In the chapters to come, I establish a theoretical footing for my claims and my methods and expand on the concepts I use. I also situate the digital state as a theoretical concept to follow and intersect with the modern state, as treated by Foucault. This allows me to conduct a digital genealogy, including a discourse analysis of structures, policies and documents on, by, of, and about Facebook to ascertain a view of the governmentalities of the digital state, as seen through this lens. These governmentalities – this digital state as an abstract, rooted in the concrete digital state of Facebook – will then allow me to discuss the implications of this new form of state governing the increasingly digitised subjects of digital modernity.

1.2.2 Key Concepts

This thesis is primarily grounded in Foucauldian political theory, but it overlaps with areas of media studies, philosophy and social science more broadly, not to mention computer science. As such, several concepts merit brief explanation in this opening chapter. The more philosopho-technical terms, such as the Foucauldian notions of power, will be properly introduced and discussed in subsequent chapters.

One field of “science” to lend concepts to this work is the philosophy of technology. From here emerge the concepts of ‘digital persona’ (Clarke, 1994; 2014) and ‘data double’ (Haggerty & Ericson, 2000). The data double is a given person as seen through a digital lens. Related to the broader understanding of the ‘avatar’ of the Internet of “old” (see Clarke, 1994), it is a summation of what can be known about a person from their profile(s) online. The digital persona is a hat-tip to Jungian notions of self and employs Erving Goffman’s insights into front and back stage behaviour (Goffman, 2012 [1959]; Gregg, 2015). It implies a

separate reflection of the human self, potentially one for each digital profile a given person might have, exhibiting (or even having) different psychological traits for each of the personas in the online realm that the person in question embodies, which might again be different to whatever persona she might have in the “offline world”. Although the theory prescribes that the same person might potentially have several different digital personas, it can be said that the modern-day governance (not least of the Internet), both private and public, implicitly challenges this (Clarke, 2014; Koopman, How We Became Our Data: A genealogy of the informational person, 2019). The data double reflects this latter point. It refers less to the psychological implications of a given (assumed) identity but relates to the largely quantitative data attached to a given person’s online activity, and observable through the ‘surveillant assemblage’ (Haggerty & Ericson, 2000) of modern technology. The data double is basically a collection of data from cookies, geographical data, and content filled out in web forms. It can be used to identify probable psychological traits of the user (as, famously, Cambridge Analytica was doing up until their demise / rebranding in 2018), but in itself it does not imply anything but the “digital footprints” of the user, the ‘data sweat’ of the digital subject (Gregg, 2015). The analogue version of it would be one’s physical case file at the doctor’s, combined with school files, police records and the likes. Finally, in this thesis some relatively well-known concepts will also be employed, such as ‘meta-physical’, ‘virtual’, and ‘cyberspace’. These will generally be used in their colloquial sense, but it should be noted that they are employed deliberately, taking into account the literal meaning of their constituent parts (insofar as any meaning can be literal cf. Saussure). That is to say, no ghosts are implied when there is talk of a meta-physical space – apart perhaps from the *geists* of time and the machine.

1.3 Thesis structure

This thesis will uncover the governmentalities of and on Facebook, leading into a reflection on their wider meaning, the user-citizens they subject and govern, and the world they shape. The main influence and inspiration for this work is the writing of Michel Foucault and those who have by themselves or others been labelled Foucauldians, but the structure of this thesis imitates the standards of contemporary (social) science. This is in part as a result of the process of researching and writing this thesis, but mainly due to it

emerging as the most sensible way to structure the argument built here for the intended audience. The structure serves to show how results that emerge as equally theoretical and political are founded in empirical research and an analysis that I would claim as “scientific”, even as the Foucauldian nature of my framework demand I routinely problematise this and other labels of truth-assertion.

The thesis has two main parts, framed by this introduction and a conclusion. The first part features descriptions and reflections on philosophy, theory, and methods. The second section employs the tools laid out to perform an analysis, discusses the findings and seeks to extract and transpose meaning from proclaimed fact.

This first chapter introduces and summarises the thesis. It introduces social media in general and Facebook in particular, introducing the site of this study with an overview of its brief history. It poses that Facebook is a meaningful site to perform an analysis of the governmentality of the digital state, introduces some key concepts, and summarises what results and claims build up the main narrative of the text, chapter by chapter. Chapter 2 introduces Foucault, his oeuvre and some of the core concepts guiding this thesis. This wider frame of Foucauldian thinking moves first to discuss a critical view on “science” – one of many words Foucault would set citation marks around (Visker, 1995). It reviews the work undertaken by Foucault and many of the concepts to emerge from this work, such as ‘sovereign power’, ‘pastoral power’, (double) ‘subjection’, ‘discourse’, and ‘governmentality’ and revisits the methods and methodologies of Foucault. Special attention is paid to ‘the genealogical method’, and ‘discourse analysis’. Finally, the chapter takes Foucault to Facebook, arguing that the purported ontological truth of a social action is irrelevant to the researcher focused on the epistemological reality for the social subjects. Simply put, if something affects and/or is experienced by the user-citizens, then it is worth researching. Chapter 3 follows the Foucauldian path into an exploration of power, further enriched by other important theorists of power. It establishes a Foucauldian view of power, not merely as a resource, tool, or ability to be wielded, but rather as a pervasive feature of all sociality. In this view, power is the one side of the Knowledge-Power duality, where both are mutually constitutive and, in a sense, two sides of the same (Foucault, 1995 [1975]). This is contrasted to the various “faces of power” as seen through the lenses of Bachrach, Baratz, and Lukes, touching on

Habermas, and related to the connections established by Luhmann. Finally, the chapter discusses whether Foucauldian theories and concepts measure up to other ways of charting the paths up the mountain of meaning that I attempt to scale. It concludes that the theories of Foucault are indeed fit for purpose, and though other theories of power are important to consider, this work remains based on Foucault. Chapter 4 conceptualises the digital state. It first explores the state, building on the Foucauldian conception of it, leading into a discussion of the governmentality of the modern state. This leads to a turn towards a wayward elephant that crawled into the room, where I explore scholarship that compares corporations to states, moving on to consider whether Facebook Inc. could be seen as such. I find that it can, though perhaps some bigger companies can be considered even more ripe for the title of state. Then follows a discussion of the digital state, employing a Foucauldian view of both state, structure, and subjects. It is again suggested that in order to sidestep the ontological problem of “actual” physicality of online spaces, one need mainly look to the epistemological reality that social subjects experience in this meta-physicality. If subjects can be said to spend part of their lives and their time “there”, in Cyberspace, then it is real and of consequence to philosophers, social scientists, and historians alike (Lessig, 2006). The chapter concludes by asserting Facebook as a site for exploration of the digital state. Chapter 5 rounds off the theoretical section of this thesis, with a focus on methods. It starts by recalling the work that has gone before, on digital humans, and on social media, also employing the concept of platforms (Helmond, 2015; van Dijck, Poell, & de Waal, 2018). It then moves on to explore the methods other scholars have been used to explore online spaces. Specific attention is paid to discourse analysis, critical media studies, and statistical/computational methods. It then considers how Foucault is to be wielded in the digital and proposes digital genealogy. A genealogy of the rising age where all data is accessed and treated via digital means. This approach is further developed, along with a presentation of the material being analysed and how. Finally, the chapter considers the potential problems and biases of the approach.

Chapter 6 sets off the second part of the book and the analysis. It wields the methodo-philosophical construct pieced together in the former sections and turns the attention on the subject of enquiry: the digital state of Facebook. It lays out and analyses the meta-physical structures of the site, recounting the historical and current constitution of the main parts of this digital reality. It then moves on to explore the

legal-normative constitution and governance of the space, as presented by Facebook Inc. itself. The chapter concludes that the meta-physical space is infused with, and governed with, governmentalities similar to those of the modern state, as determined by Foucault. Chapter 7 carries the analysis further. It explores the epistemic truths and identities surrounding those who code (read: create), govern, and exist on Facebook. It looks at how coders employ 'dark patterns' to steer and further condition the already conditioned (docile) users (Waldman, 2019), and explores the prevailing engineering ethos, treated by other scholars (Coleman, 2013; 2014; Pariser, 2011). It emerges that digital governmentality is encoded with an ethos of progression over reflection, and an objectification of user-subjects to mirror that of the modern state towards the citizen-subjects treated by Foucault. These users then move into focus, as I explore how the digital human subjects are made possible, produced, and subjected, with particular focus on how they are enabled to construct, perform, and subject themselves. The chapter concludes by highlighting the pervasiveness of pastoral power in the digital realm and its profound effects on the digital subject. Chapter 8 moves into the discussion about what all of this means. In this chapter, I explore the digital subject to the full extent that it has been uncovered and pre-empted. I look here at how an increasingly disenchanted, disciplined, formatted/quantified, and operationalised life-world is now being re-enchanted by the transposition/expansion of not just the life-world of each-user citizen, but the very human subject itself grafted onto the digital plane. I argue that digital human subjects – speaking and literate human subjects notwithstanding – are not contained in the physical bodies of themselves and others. I argue that a digital existence of the subject is increasingly becoming an integral part of the social and self-referential subjects that populate our societies. This is not to be misunderstood as simply an assertion that human subjects perform their sociality and lives through a digital medium, nor one stating that they co-exist on the physical and meta-physical (digital) plane (Bucher, 2018). While both of these observations are held to be enlightening and important, the assertion here is that the human subject is literally more than that which is contained in the human body and its brain. My claim is that the digital human of today exists concurrently in the digital and physical plane, both as the double subject theorised by Foucault, and as something more. I propose that internal, external, self-referential, social, and personal subjections and performances of self all exist co-dependently in the part of homo digitalis found offline as

well as online. I further argue that this, and the way in which this digital subject is currently and with increasing intensity governed (by algorithms), implies a third modality to be added to Foucault's famous and important (double) subjection of the self. In the digital state each subject is subjected to the sovereign and to itself. Both submissions according to the precepts of the sovereign. As the subject – and sovereign – migrates and spreads into the realm of the digital, however, something changes. The self-referential algorithms that govern this space are rooted in, and similar to, the governmentalities that went before them. But the shifting of discourse and power that defines the singular and collective subjects – both submissions and the struggle with and against them – increasingly takes place on the digital plane. In this space, though pervaded by the same governmentalities as the former submissions – indeed infused with them by these submissions – the subjects, the submissions, and the governmentalities begin to shift in a way particular to the digital subject in the digital space. And this is where the third submission happens. Chapter 9 gathers the threads and lays out what has been laid bare. It describes the governmentality of the digital state and what it means to exist as a subject in an increasingly coded social world. This leads me to propose the time in which we live as a time of digital modernity – a potential new chapter in the history of the human subject. The thesis chapter moves on to discuss the main currents of digital modernity as they have emerged from the analysis of the digital state of Facebook. It emphasises how increasingly abstracting techniques of governance – decisions about the self and others outsourced to black boxed processes of computation – can be self-accelerating and lead to alarming ends. As the pastoral power of the digital state is realised, not just the means but also the ends signifying the measurable, secular salvation of individual and collective digital subjects are defined by automated systems, running according to the opaque logics embedded in them. The algorithms of machine-powered pastoral power set the goals for salvation according to the governmentalities built into them, leading to potentially bleak ends. In response, I propose that in order to curb the potentially ill effects of digital state power, transparency and digital empowerment is needed. For such transparency to be possible, the governed subjects need access to gaze upon the techniques of power, and the decision-making power of the digital parts of their selves need to be put more under their own control. The algorithms must be infused with translating modules to allow for the scrutiny of the user-citizens whom they govern, and the web browsers and other user apps must have

added features designed to produce resistance from the user, rather than domination of the user. Tools should be built to allow the digital subjects to understand, question, and challenge their subjection.

Chapter 10 sums up the findings and assertions, delving into the implications and recommendations. I reiterate the view of Facebook as a state, the triply subjected digital human subject, and the implications for individual and collective subjects. I suggest that given what we know now, as evidenced here and elsewhere, a re-orientation might be worth considering; maybe there are other utopias to steer by than the seemingly misanthropic one we seem currently headed toward. Finally, I suggest some steps towards enabling reflection, knowledge, and resistance. In line with Foucault's stated aims, it is posed that though it is perhaps not clear what action should be taken to challenge or change power and its effects on the subjects, making such actions and changes possible is an important first step. An example of such an enabling action could be to develop, demand, and employ AI decoders that can look into the black boxed workings of "machine intelligence" and make its actions, reasons, and effects open for scrutiny, question, and change. Add to this other attempts to open up power and its effects as possible targets of struggle and re-negotiation, such as user-empowering apps, general education, coding classes, and calls to illegalise business practices found to be damaging to humans individually and collectively (c.f. Zuboff), then perhaps the future looks less bleak after all. The human subject may still be free, even as we are increasingly **governed by algorithms.**

Having pre-empted the theories, and laid out the main tenets and assertions to be read, I now move on to a deeper dive. To embark on the journey mapped out above, I invite you, dear reader, first to join me as we visit that most revered – and sometimes reviled – French person so central to this text. Let us speak of Michel Foucault.

2. WRAPPING A FOUCAULDIAN FRAME

This chapter is intended both as a presentation of Foucault, and as a guide to the reader. It introduces my understanding of Foucault in relation to this project, and what this understanding means to the rest of the thesis. The first step is an introduction of the theorist himself and some of his key concepts. Refraining from extensively biographing him, I will investigate his oeuvre and draw out the concepts considered of main importance to an understanding of Foucault in general and to this Foucauldian study, in particular. I will present the Foucauldian frame and build my conception of how this can be brought to bear for an analysis of the digital state.

The research object of this thesis is the governmentality of the digital state, as found through an analysis of the techniques of subjection on Facebook. This project is situated in a Foucauldian frame. This is easily stated, but the concept of governmentality and the praxis of genealogy and discourse analysis when put together open up a potential Pandora's Box of theories, methods, and operationalisations. Further, this box, with all its contents, is lodged in larger considerations about its purpose, shape, and design – considerations about epistemology, truth, and “science” set in quotation marks. This has implications for the objects and methods of analysis, but of immediate importance are the implications for the narrative style and the way in which concepts are utilised – when possible, explicitly without operationalisation and hard definitions (see below). All of this merit further explanation.

2.1 Foucault's oeuvre

Foucault is widely recognised as one of the most influential thinkers of the 21st century. His work is considered of increasing importance to the understanding and study of a digitised humanity, especially his analysis of the Panopticon prison design, proposed by Jeremy Bentham which is seen as increasingly relevant to a life-world where most actions taken by most humans are potentially surveillanced, and they know it.

Paul-Michel (called Michel by himself and others) Foucault (1926-1984) was born and raised in France, where he spent most of his life and career, while also working and traveling extensively abroad, most

notably in Sweden, Poland, West Germany, Tunisia, and the US (Miscellaneous, 2020A). He is widely considered one of the most influential academics of recent history, and his work has profoundly influenced Philosophy, History, International Relations, Social Science of various types, and the Humanities. An astounding body of work has been indirectly attributed to him, as Foucauldians of different disciplines have wielded aspects of his philosophy, epistemology, methods, or theories. Notably, various sub-fields, such as Governmentality Studies and Gender Studies would be hard to imagine in their current form was it not for Foucault and the inspiration he has given later important thinkers such as Judith Butler.

Talking about “Foucault’s oeuvre” is a potentially duplicitous undertaking. On the one hand, wanting to summarise the thoughts of and understand the human subject at the centre of such insights as the author, Foucault, has given us is only human. But it is also something inherently at odds with at least the first of these goals. To emulate Foucault is to never look for an essence, but always strive to understand the effects, floating from an ever-shifting unfathomable essence with a centre that may not even be. Thus, when someone asks ‘who is the real Foucault (at whatever time and place)?’ I should smile and answer, first, in a poor imitation of one who actually speaks French, ‘Qu’importe qui parle?’ – what does it matter, who’s speaking? (Foucault, 1969). In *What Is an Author?* (1975) Foucault considers the role of the author at various times and in various disciplines and explicitly scolds ‘tiresome’ (sic) questions such as ‘[w]ho is the real author?’ (ibid., p. 314). Instead of trying to pin down the “real” author, Foucault encourages us to consider the ‘author-function’ in terms of its operations (ibid.): what subjects and discourses are made possible by the utterances of a given author and a given reference. These points are relevant to consider when met with those who would seek to synthesise Foucault, either as unchanging, eternal persona or as the Foucault who wrote a particular piece, at a particular time, perhaps to contrast “the early Foucault” with “the later Foucault”. There can be value in such comparison, as Foucault himself was at times critical of his own work, e.g.:

... my objective in *The Order of Things* had been to analyse verbal clusters as discursive layers which fall outside the familiar categories of a book, a work, or an author. But while I considered 'natural history,' the 'analysis of wealth,' and 'political economy' in general terms, I neglected a

similar analysis of the author and his works; it is perhaps due to this omission that I employed the names of authors throughout this book in a naive and often crude fashion. I spoke of Buffon, Cuvier, Ricardo, and others as well, but failed to realize that I had allowed their names to function ambiguously.

(Foucault, 1975)

Here and elsewhere, Foucault strongly advocated and reminded us to locate what knowledge we seek as situated in truths and discourses. Thus, as folly as it might seem to describe Foucault in definite terms, it does make sense to get a sense (if you will pardon the wordplay) of some of the things he did, even as no attempt shall be made here to pin him down one way or the other. Whatever he was and was not. Whatever and whether that matters, Foucault did do important things, and he did share some considerations about what, how, and why. Considerations which bear revisiting.

Though his work was cut short by an illness that was not yet commonly known and treatable, what Foucault did accomplish stands as an impressive life's work. Foucault received his academic formation in and around Paris at the middle of the 20th century, immersed in existentialism and structuralism. Gutting & Oksala (2018) mentions early influences such as Heidegger, as well as Marx, Jean Hyppolite, and their reading of Hegel, not to mention Louis Althusser, Georges Ganguilhem, and Maurice Merleau-Ponty, whose lectures Foucault attended. Over his career, Foucault shifted both focus and methodology as his studies progressed. In 1982, reflecting on his work so far, he described his then-view of 'the goal of [his] work during the last twenty years' (Foucault, 1982, p. 777). According to that particular Foucault, his focus had explicitly not been the analysis of power. In this view, though he may not always have been consciously or at least explicitly aware of it as he wrote his works, he sees a general theme – a grander project – which he considers his main focus: to 'create a history of the different modes by which, in our culture, human beings are made into subjects' (ibid.). He goes on to show how this focus most especially involves power, not as a thing unto itself, but rather as something encoded in social relations and implicit in those techniques that make subjects subjects. He explicitly rejects formulating a theory of power, because '[s]ince a theory assumes a prior objectification, it cannot be asserted as a basis for analytical work' (ibid. p.778). This can

be seen as an example of how Foucault rejects, skews, or simply side-steps the established practices of many parts of history, academia, and (social) science. Perhaps somewhat surprisingly to his critics, Foucault spent more time than most on exploring scientific methods in general, and of 'the human sciences' in particular (Foucault, 2002 [1972]). His goal was not to further a unitary method of science along its path to full understanding and mastery of an objectively existing world. Rather, these explorations were aimed at analysing that underlying theme of techniques of power-knowledge that makes humans – and potentially everything they can imagine existing – into (quantifiable) objects (ibid.) - objects which can be seen, mastered, and manipulated with the mathematical logics of human gods: subjects to be governed. Thus, Foucault did not accept (nor truly deny) the various claims of a unitary method of science, based on universally rational methods and empirical findings. He wanted to understand how these claims, these situated truths, worked. How, irrespective of whether they represent some objective truth and whether such a one can even exist, these techniques influenced the discourses of truth and power – two inseparable sides of the truth-power dyad.

This returns us to Foucault's own retrospective estimation of his work. Foucault argues that a theory of power would necessitate 'objectifying' (in contemporary scientific parlance he might have said 'operationalising') the object of analysis, power (Foucault, 1982, p. 778). This, he claims, is logically incompatible with analytical work. The devil is in the detail, though, and he further states that to do an analysis, we do need to formulate a 'conceptualisation'. Those mincing words, then, might comment that he is trying to have his cake, eat it, and then claim concurrently that the cake does and does not exist, wasting valuable words to do so. In this, Foucault would likely have lauded them for their critical stance (Foucault, 1975), but asserted that he meant every word exactly as stated. As also evidenced by his usage and analysis of the concept of discourse, before then mostly associated with linguistic and grammatical analysis, most prominently by Saussure, Foucault was expressively meticulous in his choice of words (Metzger, 2019; Arribas-Ayllon & Walkerdine, 2011). Indeed, some of his enduring popularity can likely be ascribed just as much to his ability to turn a phrase with poetic precision, as the prescient profoundness and pernicious provocation of his propositions. If one is to write, even to convey, one might as well try to entertain, add *aesthetique* to form.

Foucault often interacted actively with the field of history as well as historicism, and has termed himself a 'historian of the present' (O'Farrell, 2013). Not least because of the insights he uncovered and shared, his work made great inroads into the philosophy of science, and the methodological debates of especially social science (but also medical science and others). His level of reflection and abstraction led his work to acquire an avid readership by students of all things related to power, society, and knowledge. In his many works, Foucault's methods, concepts, and rhetoric has shifted and been refined. Thus, like other great thinkers before him – most especially Hegel, whose 'young Hegelian' followers eventually espoused the likes of Marx and Engels – there are those who speak of different Foucault's across time, themes, and methods. While I recognise the importance, relevance, and fascination of such works, digging deeper into Foucault as related to his personal, professional, and philosophical journey, a genealogy of Foucault and his concepts is not my aim here. I reflect openly on my take, usage, and imitation of Foucauldian style, concepts, and methods, and while I do so informed by those who have produced interesting and important musings on Foucault's shifting relation to Marx(ists) and Nietzsche, I do not aim to condense those debates. My aim is to introduce Foucauldian concepts in general, and the Foucault I employ in particular. I do not seek to lay the ideal-typical, universal author Foucault bare. My focus is on the work and how I can use it to create knowledge – perhaps even "science".

2.1.1 Foucauldian "science"

As we might expect, Foucault did not spend much time describing each step on his path to knowledge of what subject he might be treating. There are exceptions, such as the introductory chapter to *The Order of Things* (1989 [1966]), and certain interviews (e.g. Foucault, 1991) but in the main he did not explain himself in the manner most would-be scientists, historians, and scholars now feel compelled to do. Further, his methods and focus, if perhaps not his epistemology, shifted slightly as he worked his way through studies of separate subjects, over time evolving into a more and more coherent oeuvre (Visker, 1995).

To some, the lack of a succinctly formulated Foucauldian method and rationality might appear as a "carte blanche" – a license to claim personal opinions as fact in unnecessarily complex words. Nothing could be further from the truth (Flyvbjerg, 1998). When one reads Foucault, his meticulous, deliberate systematique

is at the forefront. It is woven into a complicated language, yes, but that language is intended and serves to convey and communicate complex thoughts and structures, not to hinder understanding or mask subjectivity. Indeed, a core point of Foucault's is that though we might strive for objectivity as an ideal, subjectivity is an inescapable condition of knowledge creation. As is power. This does not necessarily mean that objectivity is a wholly hollow ideal, but it does underline that a claim to aim for such will necessarily be situated in discourses lending it the relative strength and status of truth:

Positives do not characterize forms of knowledge – whether they are a priori, necessary conditions or forms of rationality that have, in turn, been put into operation by history. But neither do they define the state of knowledge at a given moment in time: they do not draw up a list of what, from that moment, had been demonstrated to be true and had assumed the status of definitively acquired knowledge, and a list of what, on the other hand, had been accepted without either proof or adequate demonstration, or of what had been accepted as a common belief or a belief demanded by the power of the imagination. To analyse positives is to show in accordance with which rules a discursive practice may form groups of objects, enunciations, concepts, or theoretical choices. The elements thus formed do not constitute a science, with a defined structure of ideality; their system of relations is certainly less strict; but neither are they items of knowledge piled up one on top of another, derived from heterogeneous experiments, traditions, or discoveries, and linked only by the identity of the subject that possesses them. They are that on the basis of which coherent (or incoherent) propositions are built up, more or less exact descriptions developed, verifications carried out, theories deployed. They form the precondition of what is later revealed and which later functions as an item of knowledge or an illusion, an accepted truth or an exposed error, a definitive acquisition or an obstacle surmounted.

(Foucault, 2002 [1972], p. 200)

Foucault openly distanced himself from defining his work as “science”. At the same time, however, his practice and method (a term which in itself is potentially misrepresentative in a Foucauldian context) was both rigorous and clearly defined. Presumably, contemporary readers who term themselves social

scientists would easily accept that the presentation of his work in *Archaeology of Knowledge* (2002 [1972]) as espousing a (potentially “qualitative”) scientific theory and method. At least until they arrived at his objections towards the end of the book:

It is true that I have never presented archaeology as a science, or even as the beginnings of a future science. ... The word archaeology is not supposed to carry any suggestion of anticipation; it simply indicates a possible line of attack for the analysis of verbal performances: the specification of a level – that of the statement and the archive; the determination and illumination of a domain – the enunciative regularities, the positivities; the application of such concepts as rules of formation, archaeological derivation, and historical *a priori*. But in almost all its dimensions and over almost all its crests, the enterprise is related to the sciences, and to analyses of a scientific type, or to theories subject to rigorous criteria.

(Foucault, 2002 [1972], pp. 227-228, italics in original)

What might further erode the ground for a claim to Foucauldian scientificity is that Foucauldian techniques and theories are hard to sum up in short, concise, and exclusive statements; it lends itself poorly to positivist formulation. This stands in sharp contrast to most theories of the “natural sciences”, which has heavily influenced discourses about wording, form, and manner of authoritative knowledge creation:

Moreover, we find that by means of this emergence of structure (as an invariable relation within a totality of elements) the relation of the human sciences to mathematics has been opened up once more, and in a wholly new dimension; it is no longer a matter of knowing whether one can quantify results, or whether human behaviour is susceptible of being introduced into the field of a measurable probability; the question that arises is that of knowing whether it is possible without a play on words to employ the notion of structure, or at least whether it is the same structure that is referred to in mathematics and in the human sciences: a question that is central if one wishes to know the possibilities and rights, the conditions and limitations, of a justified formalization.

(Foucault, 1989 [1966], pp. 416-417)

When reading Foucault's work, it appears very convincing – at least to his fans, who are then often by themselves or others termed 'Foucauldians' (sometimes spelled 'Foucaultians'). Embedded in some of his work is a description and critique of what is sometimes called positivism, as well as other epistemes (Foucault, 1989 [1966]) – perhaps especially in the “human” or “social sciences” (Visker, 1995). It is no wonder, then, that avowed proponents of ‘the scientific method’ (Foucault, 1989 [1966], p. 263) – an inherently positivist ideal – are often unimpressed with such seemingly cumbersome, French abstractions. It can certainly be argued that for the Enlightenment project of uncovering ever higher levels of individual and collective knowledge about a rationally governed world just waiting to be discovered (Foucault, 1997 [1984]), such work which often circles around how those ideas came to be and what they mean might seem an unnecessary and vain waste of time. Worse yet, the work by Foucault himself, as well as much Foucauldian (and other post-structural) work often skirts large parts of the narrative structures and formats expected by researchers avowing to all-encompassing “quantitative” and “qualitative” paradigms. To some, this potentially challenges the systematic passing on of knowledge and the rigid testing of the underlying logic and methods of the work according to the precepts of much science, if not academia tout court. An explicit obfuscation added to the implicit insult of problematising the progress of science from a linear view of history.

Being avowedly Foucauldian in nature, this thesis might be met with similar criticism. While the narrative structure does match a typical “scientific” work more than does some of Foucault's works, and while the approaches, concepts, and methods are sought laid out in a concise manner whenever possible, the theory surrounding not just the thesis, but indeed the attempt to analyse and understand the object, the digital state, is firmly inspired by Foucault and Foucauldians. For this reason, it is important to understand how the Foucauldian notion shifts perspective from an objectivist stance of recording and reporting objectively existing truths to a recognition that the creation of truth is inherently wrought with power and politics. This point counts double, when dealing with a coded space for human interaction. Before moving Foucault into the digital, however, we need the vocabulary to do so. Let us consider further some of the central Foucauldian concepts as we move towards an understanding of the genealogical method which I will apply to analyse the digital state of Facebook.

While he never gave what one could call a systematic account of his methods, Foucault did write and talk explicitly about them, and later scholars have been able to build on his work and his techniques, as well as report on them (Dean & Villadsen, 2016; Kendall & Wickham, 1999; Visker, 1995). Some of the central ideas of Foucauldian thinking include 'archaeology', 'genealogy', 'discourse', 'episteme', and 'discourse analysis'. The terms are meant in a somewhat figurative sense. Thus, what is meant by the former of these is not archaeology in the traditional sense, but rather an 'archaeology of knowledge' (Foucault, 2002 [1972]). The researcher attempts to "dig" out the remnants of a literary "civilisation" (dead or living) in an attempt to identify prevailing discourses – how meaning, knowledge, and truth was/is construed and constructed within the larger system of thought at play, the 'episteme' (ibid.). In later works, Foucault further developed his approach and employed 'the genealogical method', which I will employ in the digital. Aware of Kuhn and to a higher degree recognising Kuhn's predecessor, Canguilhem (Simons, 2017), Foucault also employed the term 'paradigm'. Later scholars have at times used episteme and paradigm in overlapping senses, as they are somewhat similar in meaning. For nuance, one might say that paradigm more explicitly implies a system of thought related to a particular (philosophy and method of) science at a given time, whilst episteme could be seen as more broadly indicating a wider system of thought and discourse prevalent at a given point or given points in time, at given places.

2.1.2 The genealogical method

One of Foucault's most influential techniques (and an important building block of his methodology) is 'the genealogical method' (Koopman, 2019; Saar, 2002). Whether named an approach, a method(ology), a tool or a technique, 'genealogy' has been employed in a myriad of contexts. It is inspired by Nietzsche, but according to Saar (2002) not truly based on anything Nietzsche did (Meldgaard, 2014). Genealogy refers to the tracing of lines of descent, at one point in history referring to the musings that informed claims to nobility and titles. It was later employed in the sedimentary, evolutionary tracing of how an amoeba became a woman. In the Foucauldian usage of the term, it denotes a similar tracing of discourses and truths. Saar (2002) highlights how Foucault employs genealogy in a somewhat 'loose' and 'varied' fashion, sometimes denoting 'a specific methodological term or title for a critical historical-political project (namely his own)' (sic), while 'in other passages it is used rather broadly and synonymously with 'history' or

'genesis''. (ibid. p. 231, citation marks in original). Saar proposes that genealogy be divided up into three 'aspects or levels' of the complex whole. One as a 'historical method', a second as an evaluatory 'critique', and a third as a 'textual practice' (ibid.). He further suggests that on all these levels 'there is a decisive and constitutive relation between genealogy and subjectivity of the 'self'' (ibid. p. 232. Citation in original). Saar further emphasises how genealogy can be seen to carry before it an imperative of critical self-reflection: the uncovering of how bits and pieces of the structures of thought and meaning to which we append our individual and collective self-understanding came to be, opening up the possibility that they can be different (though generally not suggesting how and whether this would be normatively better or worse). An important distinction from (other types of) critical scholarly work is that the genealogical critique is always embedded in the abstract thing – culture, society, thought – it attempts to critique. As the saying goes, 'there is nothing outside the discourse' – and the discourse under analysis is inherently and undeniably part of the episteme, paradigm or even governmentality under scrutiny (Laclau & Mouffe, 1985). Finally, Saar highlights how a certain narrative style is part and parcel of the genealogical account. According to him, to attempt a truly Foucauldian piece of genealogical writing one should feature and employ 'hyperbole and exaggerating gesture, the theatrical effect ... directed towards an audience ... that is supposed to recognize themselves' (Saar, 2002, p. 239). Finally, it should circle playfully around that which seems to mean so much to Foucault, yet carries so little clarity of meaning. It should deal with *power*, but subtly, since the real object is the techniques creating the (human) subject (Foucault, 1982); the modern 'I' that is shaped by, governed by, and enveloped in power(-knowledge) (ibid.). In other words, the genealogical method is inescapably related to (analysing) discourse. This leads to the elusive term – or technique – that will be employed to tease out the governmentalities of the digital state. This leads me to talk about discourse analysis.

2.1.3 Discourse analysis

Discourse analysis appears quite instructive in the descriptiveness of its name, but has been understood, used, and appeared in many ways and types of study, by no means linked just to Foucault (Metzger, 2019; Arribas-Ayllon & Walkerdine, 2011). We might limit ourselves to considering 'Foucauldian discourse analysis', but this in and of itself is a varied and heterogeneous concept. Rather than attempting to cover

any and all ways it has been employed, Arribas-Ayllon & Walkerdine (2011, p. 91) note that 'It is customary to offer the disclaimer that there are no set rules or procedures for conducting Foucauldian-inspired analyses of discourse' and instead present:

[T]hree broad dimensions for the analysis of 'discursive practices'. Firstly, the analysis of discourse entails historical inquiry, otherwise known as 'genealogy'. Secondly, analysis attends to mechanisms of power and offers a description of their functioning. And lastly, analysis is directed to subjectification – the material/signifying practices in which subjects are made up.

(Arribas-Ayllon & Walkerdine, 2011, p. 91, citation marks in original)

This bears resemblance to the genealogical method presented above. While this does not mean that those two are the same, it does underline that they are connected. The connection made here by Arribas-Ayllon & Walkerdine is meaningful and helpful towards their goal of writing an instructive and exemplary piece of and on Foucauldian discourse analysis. But it is not to be mistaken for an objective, empirical claim of a static ranking of the two concepts in "the real world". Some instances of genealogy deployed as a method could be recast as (Foucauldian) discourse analysis and vice versa. One often finds that part of tracing genealogies implies analysing discourse, whilst analysing discourse would often seem almost eerily void of context, if not embedded in some degree of genealogical tracing situating the discourses historically. Still, some famous and important Foucauldians such as Nikolas Rose clearly distance themselves from their reading of what others have self-labelled as discourse analysis, favouring their conception of 'governmentality studies', leaning on and employing the genealogical method, but resisting the connection to some Foucauldian work which they in turn relate to discourse analysis as a discursive other (Rose, O'Malley, & Valverde, 2009). In this study, I attempt to continue the lines drawn by Foucault, and I employ the works of other scholars to understand and inform my approach, rather than delimit it. In other words, I would not employ the somewhat restrictive label of governmentality studies, though I do lean on Rose, O'Malley, & Valverde in order to better understand the term 'governmentality' and its implications (see Chapter 3). In fact, due to the simple fact of my having done my research through the digital, I label my approach to the analysis of the digital state not just a genealogy, but a digital genealogy (see Chapter 5).

2.1.4 Relativity, particularism, and critique

Genealogy is 'a practice of critique' (Koopman, 2019, p. 23). This does not mean, however that it can easily be lumped in with other critical approaches. Critical analysis carried out in the wider materialist (Marxist in a broad sense) tradition, such as the Frankfurt School, comes with an explicit normative aim towards emancipation and the betterment of (the underprivileged in) society (Flyvbjerg, 1998) (see also the review of Lukes in Chapter 3). In this tradition, the researcher will – indeed should – evaluate what she finds in her analysis and attempt to sketch the way forward towards a better future. In other words, the researcher, in her privileged position, should be aware of her position of relative power and the responsibility that comes with it, and act accordingly. Foucault expressly disagreed (*ibid.*). The Foucauldian ideology of scholarship is both emancipatory, critical, and aimed at strengthening the freedoms and liberties of subjects. But the critique of power and authoritative truths leads the Foucauldian to a perhaps more pessimistic conception of the self. In this case the recognition that the researcher is in a position of power leads to an ideal of empowerment of those potentially subjected by the discourses of the researcher, rather than a responsibility to steer them. In practice this means that in a Foucauldian approach one should steer away from normative evaluation, but rather seek to describe as truthfully as possible what, from one's particular view, is (Kendall & Wickham, 1999). The idea is that if you lay bare the discourses – the power-knowledge structures of subjection, then you empower the subjects of those discourses to consider for themselves whether they want to be subjected in this way, or if maybe they want to resist some of the truth about them assigned within and without. Add to this the non-essentialist, overlapping nature of Foucauldian concepts. On the one hand, I and others can present relatively clear and narrow definitions of the concepts relevant to the work at hand. On the other hand, the determined scholar can often find contradictions to parts of these definitions, not just in the work of other Foucauldians, but in the work of Foucault himself (Visker, 1995). As such, the concepts, though extensively defined and described, in practice appear elastic and mutable. Further, due to the explicitly particularist position the tradition is laden with circular, tautological definitions and relative positions. In a critical view, these can be seen as subjective to a fault, even as it is coupled with an express aim to be un-normative. No wonder, Habermas was famously

frustrated with Foucault and his ilk! They are ever leading us towards such dangerous notions as 'contextualism, relativism and nihilism' (Flyvbjerg, 1998, p. 212).

For my part, I sympathise with Habermas and other critics. I recognise that if the aim of a work such as this is to be emancipatory and empowering, then there should perhaps be some limit to how vague and esoteric it can be. On the other hand, if one adopts a Foucauldian epistemology and approach, it is a hard task indeed to set a limit between where this ends and the associated ideology and the ethical framework begins. They are interconnected and to a far extent one implies the other. As for the critique of relativism, I would emphasise particularism in reply. I do not see the Foucauldian approach – at least as I understand and seek to employ it – as relativist, but rather as particularist. What I mean to imply by that is that it is not all relative. Rather the opposite. In this frame everything is contingent, lodged in very particular structures of power-knowledge, which we may employ genealogy and discourse analysis to understand better. Uncovering and formulating where the truths and discursive relations around given discursive objects are, and realising in what ways, according to what logics (governmentality) subjects are constituted as subjects by themselves and others does indeed enable us to consider each for ourselves, and collectively whether this is as we would want it to be. It is contextual, indeed, but this is based on an epistemological assertion that everything we can construct and engage in discourses about is by necessity contextual. It is relative, but it is relative to particular positions in immense webs of truth-power-knowledge.

Further, there is a response to the view that the explicitly self-effacing positioning can be seen as pessimistic (and might very well come off as ironic, given the somewhat sarcastic tone also associated with the tradition as per Saar, above): Power is productive. Another implication of the Foucauldian frame is that there can be no freedom from subjection – but this is not a bad thing. Constituting yourself as a subject of a democratic state might also mean to constitute yourself as a democratic subject who has free speech. In the same light, some of the subjections of the digital state which I will uncover might not necessarily be bad – but they might also not be good. In any case, in a Foucauldian frame this is not for me to say – at least not directly. When I finally do utter a normative opinion and concrete recommendations based on this research it is with the caveat that this should be considered problematic given the Foucauldian frame,

and it is based on the implications of this ethical framework. It seems to me that enabling resistance to power was a core part of Foucault's project, and in the digital this might imply some concrete recommendations to go along with the cold descriptions of the techniques of the digital state. As a last spoiler for Chapter 9, let me say that if I find that the subject is in part digital then maybe some concrete changes are required for resistance to be enabled and thus ensure that relations of power-knowledge do not turn into relations of violence and domination.

Though more could be said, this introduction to Foucault, shall serve as the ontological groundwork for this thesis. Employing such terms as ontology and epistemology in relation to Foucault can be tricky, however. In this Foucauldian framework, the ontological standpoint outlined above includes not just that which is – something that is as much skirted as clearly stated – but also that which can generate knowledge. In other words, while the methods are yet to come, they are themselves enveloped in an expressly described and discursively placed ontology of science, knowledge and power. But what does all of this mean for Facebook, the digital state? Moving now into a more practical turn, I will now consider what this framework means when applied to a virtual and digital social space. How will I view Facebook, seen through the eyes of Foucault?

2.2 Foucault for Facebook

In the following chapters, I bring Foucault into the digital sphere and through a tracing of the structures and techniques in play in and on Facebook I ascertain the governmentalities of the digital state. This also means that I spend time on how subjects – especially user-citizens – are subjected and constituted as well as empowered to subject and constitute themselves in this space. This is further connected to the human subject and perhaps even her condition in the digitised world she now inhabits.

When reading Foucault one is brought to realise how the governance of each individual in and by the state as we know it, is historically contingent, recent, and not at all given by any laws of nature, sociology, or psychology (Koopman, 2019). In his works it becomes clear how the most recent history of humans traces an upwards trajectory of abstraction and individualisation, not just in concepts, but in concrete tools and

techniques of governance. Where the dauphin to be educated by La Perrière in sixteenth century France was to govern a society based on family units with patriarchal masters at all levels, the state of today is characterised by an expectation that each subject govern herself subordinate only to herself, as the Hegelian master, and the collective, realised as the state. Thus, more than anything else, the last few hundred years of history has seen a move from a messy collection of disparate loci of power and dominance toward a rationalisation and re-centring of powers towards a more duopolistic system infused with the assumption that power rests – and should rest – solely in the omnis and the singulatum. The singular free individual, and the supreme collective of those free individuals, organised as “state”. It follows from the tendency of this logic that all that is not yet governed by the one or the other – either the singular individual through the allegedly closest to value-free approximation of collective individual utility: the unregulated market or the whole of the individuals through the institutions of (sometimes representative, sometimes populist, sometimes direct) democracy established as institutional sovereign of whatever borders have been drawn one way or the other: the state. For governance to be good, then, it must be exercised by the free individual either as one or the other: the person or the state. This is the liberalism Foucault is talking about.

A second Foucauldian realisation is how the variant of the above called neo-liberalism carries an inherent scepticism towards the conscious collective of the individual called state, and thus aims to shift power relations, divisions, and technologies towards the impersonal, perhaps inhuman, unconscious collective of the unregulated market (Davies, 2014). Foucault lends us not just the vocabulary to analyse and understand these abstract and confusing insights, but he also allows us to access them on many different levels at the same time. With Foucault we can open up a complex but clearly articulated conception of the multi- and cross-linear relations that encompass, constrain, and empower humanity across time, space, and brains. Bringing this back to the study of Facebook, a Foucauldian conception only strengthens the view some have already awoken to: The eerie feeling that whatever a state is, Facebook increasingly feels like such a thing (MacKinnon, 2012). Perhaps not in a classical, Weberian sense – at least at first glance – but a state none-the-less. When subjecting oneself to and on Facebook, when using the site, it seems almost ideal-typically reminiscent of the Foucauldian double subjection of the subject-state relation. To exist

digitally, one must construct and govern oneself as an individual subject, which empowers one to act as one of the collective subjects, individualised and governed by the code of the site. While it is not completely clear who is the putative sovereign of this digital space – Facebook Inc., the unconscious collective, the nation states increasingly operating on and through Facebook – the user conduct on the site is certainly being conducted (see Chapter 4 for further considerations about Facebook as “a state”).

2.2.1 Enter the matrix

Given the above, it follows that (social) actions taken in a digital space are only real insofar and in the sense that they impact people – social subjects. Indeed, depending on ontological standpoint, the same could be said of actions taken in any realm or on any plane, be it in the world we describe as physical, a dream, or a fleeting thought. From this follows an epistemological standpoint that to ascertain social actions of people played out, one needs not have seen or even registered the action itself, but only its effect. The ontological question of whether an action can be considered to have objectively happened or not fades from relevance in light of an epistemology that asserts primacy to actions that have happened according to individuals who experienced them. If something exists discursively, then it exists for the purposes of discursive analysis.

A “realist” position would, at least in the classical sense, reject such a notion, whereas an ideal-typical “idealist” or “constructivist” would hold that meaning – truth, what is – the (social) reality is created in the mind, if not the eye of the beholder. In this thesis and inasmuch as such a definition makes sense to the Foucauldian standpoint I adopt, I assume an interpretive constructivist standpoint which recognises the reality of a given action for social actors, irrespective of any physical or objective truth to the empirical existence of the action itself. The focus is on the truth, the discursive relations, and the subjections they imply and create. In Plato’s cave, I look at neither the shadows on the wall nor the glimpsed reality of the philosopher, but consider both valid, as the point of interest is their validity to and effect on the persons experiencing them. In this sense, from the epistemological position I occupy, I view a ‘like’ on Facebook as comparable to a pat on the shoulder in the analogue world of purported physical reality while neither is the object of analysis. The object of analysis is the structure of power-knowledge that produced that pat and the meaning it is assigned. Although the pat and the like are not necessarily the same type of action,

they are equally valid social actions - as is a slap to the face - since they have meaning for actors (Bucher, 2017). From this point of view, the meta-physical world of the internet is as true a place as the observable universe of our physical bodies. The physics and structures are different, but from a social-psychological point of view, they are essentially in the same category. Each in their plane are a whole, the basis of existence, knowledge, and social relations. In each of these life-worlds, there are smaller units, clusters of social meaning or power-knowledge.

For the humans born so far, the spaces occupied in the physical realm are concentrated on Earth, and abstractly subdivided into various geographical and conceptual groupings, an important category in this instance being states. In Cyberspace, the data doubles of current humanity populate many spaces sporadically and concurrently (Lessig, 2006). Some few humans barely exist as digital individuals, in the base sense of the word. Their online personas are so vague as to be, possibly, several different people, making the persona divisible into several persons. This may be either by informed choice, by lack of access, or by slight, sporadic usage. But most users have relatively well-defined data doubles, allowing almost all sites to recognise them and register their actions to their ever-growing profiles (Palmås, 2011, p. 342; MacKinnon, 2012, p. 30; Pariser, 2011, p. 108). Asserting that the possible ontological differences between digital and offline social reality is skewed in an epistemological assertion of their similarity in type and importance to researchers, is less a direct answer to such a critique than a sidestep. I fully recognise that a strong positivist-realist position might necessarily feel obliged to maintain that epistemologically treating offline and online actions as the same (for my purposes) constitutes an implicit ontological assertion of similar sameness and thus reject my position. To answer such a critique, I can only maintain that though such a critique is logically sound it still assumes a formal logical linearity between epistemology and ontology, which is not a priori given. Indeed, my framework could operate with ontological variation of the two, even as the epistemological same-ness is maintained.

This ontological sidestep is not the only way of dealing with the physicality of the digital as different from other non-informational social spaces. In his book, *How we became our data*, Colin Koopman (2019) proposes 'infopower' as a Foucauldian concept analogous to disciplinary power, but 'a mode of power in

its own right: a distinctive modality of power that fastens its subjects to their data. ... [T]he normalizing operations and surveillance techniques of disciplinary power are analogous to the fastening operations and formatting techniques of infopower' (ibid. p. 15; 12). I recognise the value and heuristic gains afforded by Koopman's conception, and will return to him in my discussion, but due to my viewing the social space of Facebook as a meta-physical place, in the analysis my focus – and the concepts I use – are mainly those from the works of Foucault himself. Koopman creates a new, but no less Foucauldian, concept of power emphasising the unique power flows in play in the digital age and spaces, while I use pre-existing Foucauldian concepts. I do this to underscore my epistemological view that there is no inherent difference between one and the other: For my purposes, bio-power is bio-power, whether the body be digital or not. The two views are not incommensurable, but they do point to differences in perspective, object, and intention.

In her book, *If...Then: Algorithmic Power and Politics*, Tania Bucher (2018) has a '... premise that life is not merely infused with media but increasingly takes place in and through an algorithmic media landscape'. I share this view, but go a step further to ultimately state that not only do digital subjects live through this mediated world, they exist on it, internally as well as externally. On the meta-physical, digital plane, then, one can occupy different and differentiated spaces at the same time. Furthermore, one – or one's data double – can engage in social activity even without one's agency or explicit knowledge, the digital (part of the) body acting on behalf of the psychological persona in telling others what one likes (or "liked" at a given time), redisplaying past utterances, and telling where one plans to go next Thursday (regardless of whether one goes or not). The social actions of these zombie doubles might be just as meaningful to other actors, as the ones actively taken – and they might lead to other (inter-)actions. As such, the zombies can be seen as a part of the (social) subject, a view I will explore much further in Chapter 8. It can be argued that this is a natural progression from / evolution of the spoken, rumoured, written, and printed word, but the more the process is automated, the less the computer becomes merely a medium. Where, then, does the human end and the computer begin? Once again, this empirical question is part of the side-stepped ontology. What matters is not whether we can meaningfully draw a line where the fleshy automaton that controls the keyboard clearly separates from the human being constituting itself and others in the digital realm. The

point is not the apparent similarities or differences between social life in the cyberspace of Lessig (2006) or the social world of Weber (1905). With Foucault, what physical and ontological differences there may be shift out of focus, and what becomes important is instead the structures and techniques that shape subjects – what happens, what they do. In a sense, more directly empirical, while at the same time focussed on something entirely situated, relative, and discursively bound (Flyvbjerg, 1998). Where the human subject is realised as human, there the human subject is. That which does the self-subjection and in turn is subjected by the government(ality) of others, that is the human subject, at least doubly so. A point I will return to in Chapter 8.

In this chapter, I have introduced Foucault and some of the theory and concepts related to Foucauldian “science”, taking the first steps towards establishing my theoretical frame. This has also introduced themes which I will explore further when I look at the emergence and proliferation of the collection of techniques called state in Chapter 4. In this exploration, I note among other central concepts how Foucault’s theories revolve around subjection and power-knowledge. Power is inseparable from subjection and a central concept in the Foucauldian thought for which I have now laid the foundation. To move forward, let us consider relations of power.

3 POWER AND SUBJECTION

In chapter 2 I have laid out a Foucauldian framework and considered what it means to perform a Foucauldian study in the digital age. I have presented a position which resists simplification and universalisation and focuses instead on the situated relations of power-knowledge and truth of itself and that which it studies. This leads to a particularist position with an emancipatory, yet self-consciously un-normative aim which ultimately seeks to enable resistance to power. This is done through the uncovering of relations of subjection, something which I will do in the Foucauldian tradition of genealogy and discourse analysis. Other Foucauldian concepts such as archaeology have also been presented to help situate the approach and this study. In considering the implications for this study, I have argued that virtual social reality can be seen as equivalent to its offline counterparts. The main assertion is that the focus should be not the physical form and location of the structures and institutions (digital or abstract) from whence power can be said to flow, nor the humans enmeshed in them. This is to say that the purpose here is to uncover the governmentality of the digital state and not to analyse a given entity or institution which we might call “a state”. The physical form and location of said technology – or connection of technologies – is relevant to consider (and I will do so in Chapter 4), but the main focus is on how subjects are constituted, the techniques through which subjects are made subjects, and the way in which power acts on, with, and through these subjects. The next step, then, is to consider that seemingly clear concept which so eludes definition. Let us talk about power.

Power, like the state, is an essentially contested concept (Lukes, 2005, p. 30; Gallie, 1955). It is an abstract that at first glance seems meaningful, but whose meaning becomes increasingly blurred, the more specifically we treat it. Different theorists of philosophy, state, politics, and societies have operationalised and treated power differently, and if we have learnt one thing by the many definitions – and discussions – of power that have been presented over the years, it is that a clear conception of power is central to “good social science”. The different theories of power are intimately connected with politics, philosophy, and ethics, and span widely. Exploring the cyber policies that shape digital subjects, the Foucauldian concepts

of power/knowledge is implicit in this thesis. But that is not to say that other conceptions of power or other theories around power cannot be helpful and add salience to arguments to follow.

3.1 The power of Foucault

Power in a Foucauldian framework is enmeshed in all relations between self and others. It is embedded in the inter-subject relations; it works on, even through, the subjects. It constitutes the subjects, and it allows them to produce themselves and others. Does that mean that the subjects are power-less? By no means. Rather the opposite, as power works through, within, and without each subject. Essentially, the only way a human subject can be free of the structures and effects of power is if that subject has ceased to exist and is forgotten to boot. It is important to note that according to Foucault a relation of power is not necessarily negative in the colloquial sense. Foucault claims that there is power in any and all human relations – even to oneself – and emphasises that power is productive as well as restrictive (Foucault, 1984B, p. 61).

An exploration of Foucauldian power would be incomplete without reference to the modern state. A large part of Foucault's work was namely concerned with the state in various relations. Foucault's subject was the human subject, to be sure, but the techniques and structures of power he traced as pervading the construction of self and others before, during, and after the alleged modernity of his time were inextricably and increasingly linked to the state. Thus, a main theme of his revisiting of his grander project mentioned above, aptly titled *The Subject and Power* was the 'pastoral power' of the modern state (Foucault, 1982). 'Pastoral power' is expunged in *Omnes et Singulatim*² (Foucault, 1979A). It refers to 'power techniques oriented towards individuals and intended to rule them in a continuous and permanent way' (Foucault, 1979A, p. 227). An 'individualising power ... whose role is to constantly ensure, sustain, and improve the lives of each and every one.' (ibid. p. 227-235):

² Also known as 'the Tanner Lectures'.

Christian pastorship implies a peculiar type of knowledge between the pastor and each of his sheep. This knowledge is particular. It individualizes. It isn't enough to know the state of the flock. That of each sheep must also be known (ibid. p. 237).

The pastor must know 1) the material needs of each individual member of his flock, as well as his 2) public sins – and 3) private (secret) sins (ibid. p. 238). This knowledge enables said pastor to better guide his 'sheep' towards (post life) salvation. In that regard, it is important to note that there is no immediate end-goal to this praxis – guiding and being guided is a goal in itself, and the faithful should aim to follow guidance unquestioningly (ibid. p. 238). Through Christianity, Foucault claims, obedience became a virtue – an aim in itself – rather than a means to an end, which it was under the Greeks (ibid. p. 237). Foucault goes on to show how, though the ecclesiastical (church) organisations have waned while the (modern) state has waxed, pastoral power has by no means disappeared. Rather, it has been adopted in the techniques of subjection of the state. The pastoral power of the modern state, then, works in much the same ways as does the original pastoral power of the ecclesiastics. A key difference is, however, that where the pastoral power of the church had as its ultimate aim the salvation of the subjects' immortal souls, the modern state seeks to provide salvation in this mortal world of the flesh (Foucault, 1982). What this salvation might be then becomes the point of political struggle featuring statistics and economics (Foucault, 2006 [1979]).

Though this second form of pastoral power is presented as particularly prevalent in the construction of subjects by and under the modern state, it is not the only one. Indeed, different forms, types, and techniques of power may be observed in the same place, at the same time. To structure the way of thinking about these different forms of power embedded in various discursive constructs or aspects of the same Foucault coined the term governmentality, which can be said to describe the mind-set according to which a given locus of power – such as a (modern) government or state – governs. Inherent in a given technique of governance (subjection) there is a mentality, a way in which subjects are implicitly constituted. In pastoral power, for instance, the subjects to be governed are to be saved – in some cases perhaps even whether they want it or not. They are to be understood and constructed both individually and collectively,

policed according to whatever leads to the ends of their salvation, as defined by the regime of truth in/with/by which this power operates.

Another important concept when understanding the Foucauldian relations of power and the state is sovereign power, which Foucault developed in *Discipline and Punish – the Birth of the Prison* (1995 [1975]). Closely related to disciplinary power and other techniques of bio-power, sovereign power is the ultimate power over life, death, and truth of the subjects. It is the power to make any decision with impunity, since 'Before the justice of the sovereign, all voices must be still.' (Foucault, 1995 [1975], p. 36). The sovereign power is related to the pre-modern (monarchic) state, but still possible to find in governmentalities existing today. It is felt rather than seen and especially manifested through the gaze with which a literal sovereign views in particular subjects standing on display for a parade or to be tried in a court (ibid. p. 48, 188). It is a power that can be delegated, but not transferred (ibid. p. 53). It is in principle all-seeing and all-knowing, and connoted to the disciplinary power of the panopticon thought out by Jeremy Bentham (ibid. p. 200; Dean & Villadsen, 2016, p. 107).

Disciplinary power, mostly developed in *Discipline and Punish – The Birth of the Prison*, and later subjugated as one form of bio-power (Foucault, 1978 [1976], p. 140), refers to technologies of power employed to discipline the body of the (political) subject, in order to mould it ever more towards the ideal shape of its function according to the authority effecting the shaping:

Thus discipline produces subjected and practised bodies, 'docile' bodies. Discipline increases the forces of the body (in economic terms of utility) and diminishes these same forces (in political terms of obedience). In short, it dissociates power from the body; on the one hand, it turns it into an 'aptitude', a 'capacity', which it seeks to increase; on the other hand, it reverses the course of the energy, the power that might result from it, and turns it into a relation of strict subjection. If economic exploitation separates the force and the product of labour, let us say that disciplinary coercion establishes in the body the constricting link between an increased aptitude and an increased domination.

(Foucault, 1995 [1975], p. 138, citation marks in original).

The mentioned concept of bio-power overlaps with disciplinary power, but also entails the policing (in the broad, classical sense) of populations – the techniques of statistics, demographics and (macro-)economics emerging in the eighteenth century:

Power would no longer be dealing simply with legal subjects over whom the ultimate dominion was death, but with living beings, and the mastery it would be able to exercise over them would have to be applied at the level of life itself; it was the taking charge of life, more than the threat of death, that gave power its access even to the body.

(Foucault, 1978 [1976], pp. 142-143)

Putting these concepts together, one can see how the techniques of the modern state, with the governmentality of the second form of pastoral power, will inherently justify exerting sovereign power to effect the disciplining of its subjects through disciplinary power and bio-power. A policy is enacted and in it the universal, modern state is doubly constituted as the sovereign that sends children to school, because it is good for them, individually and collectively.

Foucault's work on power, discourse, and knowledge is manifestly connected with any and all notions of the state. The disciplining taking place in schools and armies is ultimately under heavy influence from wherever power is concentrated in the social structures they are embedded in. Truth is often defined or licensed by and according to official bureaucrats and governors of apparatuses of state, and tracking the discursive shifts in what is authoritatively defined as a sexuality, a sickness, or a crime must include an analysis of what has been enshrined in law and politics. In this view, the state can be seen less as a thing unto itself, but as a specific technology/technique of power, similar to the Hobbesian king before it. Or, more precisely, as a collection of such techniques. The state is a universal referent, a "Big Other" which discursively represents such disparate things as the organ formulating the (legitimate) will of the sovereign, the static or at least slow-to-change institutions of state, and the (sometimes sovereign) collective that is being governed. I will return to the state in the next chapter. For now, I emphasise that when considering

these various concepts, it is important to remember that they are constructed for analysis and not for classification. That means that they are to be added to our vocabulary, as we consider and try to understand the operations of the digital state, but we cannot use them to define what the digital state is (and is not) using techniques of deduction, induction, or abduction (Guthrie, 2010). These Foucauldian conceptions are not to be misunderstood as ideal-types against which to measure a more or less observable reality. This can be done, as for instance a materialist scholar might deduct from Foucault and operationalised typology to be employed in the dialectic search for answers, but such an approach would not fit the Foucauldian frame.

Foucault is by no means the only theorist of power. As meaningful as it is to define a thing in positive terms, it can be helpful to delineate what it is not. This can also help justify whether the theory laid out here is indeed the best for the task at hand or whether other conceptions should have been adopted instead (Popper, 2008 [1963]).

3.2 The power of others

It appears an almost obvious truth when scholars and activists like Shoshanna Zuboff and Rebecca MacKinnon talk about the power wielded by “tech” companies like Facebook (Zuboff, 2019; MacKinnon, 2012). If one pauses, however, to consider what that means – what power is, it quickly becomes clear just how complex and unclear a concept it is. In the Foucauldian view presented above, it is a relative feature of all social action and interaction. But in a certain sense that brings us no closer to what power is; what the word really means. To uncover the governmentality of the digital state I will need to explore the power relations on and encoded by Facebook. To better articulate what that means, and in an attempt to preempt any theoretical tunnel vision due to an all-encompassing, radical, theoretical framework like the Foucauldian one I have adopted, I will also explore power through the eyes of others.

3.2.1 Lukes, Bachrach, Baratz & Dahl

A classical conception of power within political science and sociology is the three faces (dimensions, in Lukes’ narrative) of power. The first two were described by Bachrach & Baratz in 1962, assigning the first

face to Dahl, and the third was added by Lukes in 1974 (Bachrach & Baratz, 1962; Lukes, 2005). The first face of power is relatively straight-forward and speaks to most people's intuitive understanding of the word. The first face of '... power is exercised when A participates in the making of decisions that affect B.' (Bachrach & Baratz, 1962, p. 948; Lukes, 2005, p. 19). Or, as it was originally formulated: 'A has power over B to the extent that he can get B to do something that B would otherwise not do' (Dahl, 1957, quoted in Lukes, 2005, p. 60). The second face of power is often called the 'agenda-setting power': when an actor, A, is '... creating or reinforcing social and political values and institutional practices...' after her own mind, which crowds out issues that might have been raised by B - especially those that would have been less in A's interest, so that these cannot come on the agenda (Bachrach & Baratz, 1962, p. 948; Lukes, 2005, pp. 6, 20). It is noteworthy that, empirically, Bachrach & Baratz' second face of power demands observable (overt or covert) conflict (Lukes, 2005, p. 7). A two-dimensional analysis of power, then, should incorporate both decision-making processes (1st face of power) and nondecision-making processes (2nd face of power) (ibid. p. 22). In the first dimension, the observer can observe issues taken up within the political system, being put on the agenda and decisions being made by whomever holds the power to do so. In the second dimension, the focus is on observing groups or individuals outside the established political system seeking to have their issue(s) taken in and put on the agenda (ibid. p.24). The third dimension, looking at the third face of power, is formulated by Lukes in response to the two above. In this he is focused on 'the power 'to prevent people, to whatever degree, from having grievances by shaping their perceptions, cognitions and preferences in such a way that they accept their role in the existing order of things'' (Lukes, 2005, p. 11, quoting a later section of the same book). It is explicitly related to the Marxist thoughts of Antonio Gramsci (Lukes, 2005, p. 49). Uncovering Lukes' third dimension relies less on observable actions, and allows for the researcher identifying perpetuation of social structures or other actions - deliberate or not – and assigning 'real' interests for subjects, even if they do not see these interests as theirs (Lukes, 2005, pp. 28, 109).

Power then, according to Lukes' perspective, is a capacity. He asserts that often it is, by 'behavioural political scientists' (sic) (Lukes, 2005, p. 70) as Dahl, confused with the vehicle, or exercise of said capacity. When one makes a decision and it is followed by a group, one exercises power, when one assumes a given mantle of leadership, one enters a vehicle of power. But power in itself is a capacity, not its vehicle, action,

or effect (Lukes, 2005, pp. 70, 109). Lukes proceeds to develop a typology of power, aimed at grading and comparing the power (capacity) of different social actors. He underlines that such analyses necessarily imply value judgments, and presents a case for a system essentially focused on how much given actors can affect the central or basic interests of others (defined according to the given operationalisation) (Lukes, 2005, p. 80).

In the added chapters of his revised edition of this classic work, Lukes shifts his focus slightly, to 'power as domination.' (Lukes, 2005, p. 108), and reformulates his third dimension of power to be about actors 'securing the consent to domination of willing subjects' (ibid. p. 109). In this he sees domination as a limiting, restrictive, form of power, and states that the original formulation – dealing only with domination – is blind to the normatively neutral or positive forms of power (ibid.). Methodologically, Lukes insists that observations (of power) must rest on 'empirically supportable and refutable hypotheses (ibid. p. 29). Lukes develops his typology further and assigns a focus on each dimension of power to a type of researcher. (1) The liberal researcher who takes people's interests and political wants at face value, as expressed in the political system. (2) The reformist who is a version of the same, still looking only at what interests people themselves express, but also as expressed outside the political system. (3) The radical researcher, Lukes himself, who looks at ideal interests – asserting that people's views can be a product of their system and against their actual interests (Lukes, 2005, pp. 37-38). This ladder position has prompted some criticism, as it requires the researcher to assign preferences to subjects that they do not themselves realise, based on the researcher's own assumptions. As Lukes points out, however, this is essentially comparable to even the simplest conception of one-dimensional power analysis: A given instance where power is exercised (similarly) only makes analytical sense assuming a counter-factual. In assuming that B would not have acted in a given fashion had not A imposed his will on her, the researcher is indeed assigning counter-factual unrealised wants, desires, and actions to the subject at hand (Lukes, 2005, pp. 40-43). The evidence for such wants can be harder to find and substantiate in the third dimension, but the epistemological standpoint is essentially the same, not least since Lukes insists on 'empirically supportable and refutable hypotheses', showing a clear allegiance to the critical rationalism best known from Karl Popper (2008 [1963]). Lukes affirms that since the concept of power is, and concepts around power are, contested, it is

not possible to lay down an uncontested definition of power, much less the research of it (Lukes, 2005, pp. 108, 113). Still, he returns time and again to an ontological position of objective truth, re-affirming that subjects (who are not slaves or prisoners) can be more or less free, and imbued with an individual 'nature' (ibid. pp. 114, 118). This should be tempered, however, by the fact that he holds such objectivity to be relative to the explanatory purpose of the researcher (ibid. p. 148). It is an external (epistemological) standpoint, the objectivity only blending into the ontology of a given project, not a position of belief necessarily held or promulgated by Lukes himself (ibid. p. 146).

3.2.1.1 Habermas and the public sphere

As an avowed Neo-Gramscian, Lukes can be said to be working from a materialist (Young Hegelian) perspective, a wider tradition largely popularised by, and highly influenced by Marx (& Engels). Another important thinker in this tradition is Habermas. Though not a power theorist per se, Habermas' work based on his analytical concept of 'the Public Sphere' has been widely used for the study and critique of social media and is relevant to mention here as a related avenue of research in the wider tradition where Lukes can also be placed (Habermas, 2009; Fuchs C. , 2014). According to Fuchs (2014) Habermas' concept has been updated and enhanced by answers to various points of critique over the years. Fuchs explains how much of the critique of "the public sphere" stems from a misunderstanding of what the concept is and is supposed to do for the researcher. First of all, it is important to understand that the concept is an analytical construct akin to a Weberian ideal type. It is derived from narratives of a purportedly existing public sphere of contemporary, capitalist-liberal society/societies, and its main function is to allow the researcher / critic to illustrate how the empirically found reality does not correspond these idealised narratives, thus exposing in a dialectical critique the mismatch between rhetoric and reality in an otherwise supposedly free society (ibid.). This is a concrete and usable strategy to identify the differences between an ideal (and openly stated) objectively desirable state of affairs and the realities experienced by the suppressed individuals living under the given conditions. As such, the power frame laid out by Lukes could be meaningfully combined with this analytical concept of Habermas' to analytically (through dialectics) identify the ideological and material mismatch between the ideal and factual state of affairs. This further allows the normative, critical scholar to chart a course forward, leading the oppressed towards a better

social position (see Chapter 2). Utilising the materialist approach in general, and this concept in particular, Fuchs and others have been able to define elaborate and sophisticated categories for different quasi-material abstracts (e.g. 'Capitalist Media', 'Public Service Media', and 'Civil Society Media' (Fuchs C. , 2014, p. 68)). These sophisticated operationalisations enable equally sophisticated analysis, ultimately aimed at unmasking injustice and making the world a better place. This, of course, is ethically similar to the intent of Foucauldian approaches – but ultimately so different in its assumptions as to be incommensurable with a Foucauldian frame (Flyvbjerg, 1998). The similarities between the traditions aside, thinkers across this fence have been eager to understand and learn from each other. As a theorist of power, Lukes also took up Foucault, and has shared his reading of this different theory. A perspective that might be helpful for scholars from the same or similar traditions in order to better understand Foucauldian theory on its own terms.

3.2.1.2 Lukes on Foucault

In the revised 2005 edition of his classical book, *Power: A Radical View* (1974), Lukes explicitly addresses the Foucauldian take on power, as he sees it, related to his typology. His treatment of Foucault is at the same time insightful and expresses some differences to at least my own view and operationalisation of Foucault. For this reason, and to invite and enable further criticism of my own approach I will take a somewhat critical stance to this accounting by Lukes.

Lukes alludes to how Foucault's approach 'has been said to reveal a 'fourth dimension of power'' (Lukes, 2005, p. 88, referencing Digesser, 1992) and proceeds to show how, in contrast to Lukes and his colleagues, Foucault focused not on specific actors or institutions with power, but rather on the power relations embedded in all social relations – the structures rather than the structured – the techniques and paradigms of knowledge-power rather than singular individuals said to wield power. In Lukes' explanation of governmentality he identifies four key things the concept references to: 1) 'rationalities of rule', 2) 'conceptions of the person that they seek to inculcate' (the subject), 3) 'Technologies of the self', and 4) 'the ways in which these elements are aligned with one another' (Lukes, 2005, p. 96).

In a mild critique of Lukes' well-researched, thorough, and eminent representation of Foucault it could seem that one finesse of the words and theories he quotes eludes him: The subject is constituted, wholly and completely, by the technologies of power, the rationalities, that permeate it. This does not mean that the subject is not just that – a subject – and it does not render the subject inconsequential. It does, however, render the subject a secondary source, at best, for the subject of research – the regimes of truth and power-knowledge (the two are, to Foucault, mutually constitutive). The subject of power is created by, imbued by, and carries around said regimes – but they, not the person-subject, is the subject of research. This may reflect Lukes' embeddedness in the materialist-ideological tradition, as exemplified by Habermas (and Fuchs). Lukes takes from Foucault a focus on how people are sometimes 'believing themselves, sometimes falsely, to be free of power' (Lukes, 2005, p. 123). From a Foucauldian perspective, the 'sometimes' is misleading at best. A core and much-repeated tenet in this tradition is that there is nothing outside the discourse (e.g. Laclau & Mouffe, 1985). There is no subject without power relations, without technologies of power within and without. Without subjectification in the double sense there can be no subject. This does not stand in opposition to people being "free", rather it twists the argument, showing that the very idea of a free subject is a falsism, a utopian dream. At the same time, the free subject does exist within its episteme, its paradigm, or that of a researcher. Thinking on whether subjects are "actually" free and being able to assign them objectively truer needs and wants than they themselves see, is a classically materialist (Marxist) position. Lukes believes (and is surely right, within his paradigm) that he can, as a researcher, assess whether subjects are more or less free in their choices, more or less powerful. In the Foucauldian framework we essentially cannot know. There is no objectivity, and we cannot judge subjects as more or less free (Lukes, 2005, p. 123), in the same way that we cannot authoritatively define what something is and is not. It is all discursive and particular. In the end, even the highest king is constrained by the rationalities and knowledge-power structures embedded in him, as we are constrained by our own, internal structures of power-knowledge.

Moving from this, Lukes sets up a dichotomy that either we "buy" the Foucauldian view, as he sees it – or we reject all the thoughts and work of Spinoza and others, dealing with subjects and freedom. He supposes that with Foucault 'power cannot be based on rational consent' (Lukes, 2005, p. 107). Such a dichotomy

simply does not exist outside of his text. The Foucauldian point is that rationality is, indeed, context-dependant. The researcher has to make a choice as to what to believe, making an aim, though not a claim, to objectivity – or at least scientific rigour. We have to start somewhere and must simply aim to be explicit about the choices we've made, and rigorous in our pursuit of truth. But it is not objective, it cannot be, and we are always engaging in a dialogue of power. In Lukes' terms, widened to a Foucauldian scope, we are indeed exercising power, as through our actions of knowledge/truth creation we reinforce and influence structures of power-knowledge. What Lukes struggles with, to my mind, is not the theoretical-philosophical aspect of the Foucauldian theory he lays out so masterfully. What he fails to fully present is the ontological implications of said theory. He seems unable to accept a completely relativist, social-constructivist ontology where all truth is particular, if not necessarily relative, coupled with a conscious choice to work epistemologically on discursive networks of power and influence, rather than those subjects that carry, create, shape, and are shaped by these seemingly infinite structures of power. The focus is on the discursive structures, the technologies that make people subjects, not the subjects/actors themselves – the very network which I deem indispensable to the appreciation of the technologies and effects of the digital state. This focus appears to Lukes intriguing and inspiring, but ultimately oxymoronic. "Why do research, when there is no objective truth to seek?" he might ask. The point is that there is. Spinoza, Lukes himself, all of the truths they and others have found remain as important and valuable as ever. The Foucauldian perspective does not stand in opposition to his, it simply looks at it from another angle, another dimension to stay in his thematic jargon. A dimension Lukes presents well, but doesn't seem to fully recognise, since his own research and thinking remains materialist and agent-centred rather than systemic. In Foucault, power can indeed be 'based on rational consent' – but all rationalities, and all power-knowledge is bound and enveloped in the paradigmatic structures of their position. The same structures that Foucault strives to lay bare for all to see, all the while refusing to pass authoritative judgment on them (at least explicitly). To this end, in fact, Foucault worked to uncover structures of power-knowledge, so that subjects are made able to "see" them and choose for themselves whether to perpetuate or change them. Though he did so in an explicitly and for some, among them Habermas, frustratingly un-normative way (Visker, 1995; Flyvbjerg, 1998).

3.2.2 Digital power in Luhmannic light

Not all theorists of power are agent-centric. An important theorist when talking about media and social systems, if not power directly, is Niklas Luhmann. Luhmann is best known for his overarching systems theory, which centres around self-observing and self-referential social systems systems/organisations. What others may perceive as a change in a given system, Luhmann sees as a new system in and of itself (*sui generis*), evolved from the old one (Tække & Paulsen, 2010, p. 6). Luhmann's grand theory on organisations talks of communication, as a type of occurrence that is repeated, with reference to itself (its former occurrence) (Luhmann, 2006, p. 50), and in being so, (re-)produces the system (Luhmann, 2006, p. 47). In Luhmann's vision, humans are carriers – vessels – of societal systems. He conceives of systems viewed in and of themselves, mediated by communication, and in principle without any direct focus on human actors at all (Fuchs C. , 2008, p. 36). Luhmann sees modern society as functionally differentiated where '[i]ts subsystems are operationally closed networks of communications' (Fuchs C. , 2008, p. 37). These systems are embedded with binary codes of communication – for instance the legal system essentially handles the binary of legal/illegal (*ibid.*). Furthermore, each system is facilitated by its own embedded media – in the case of the legal system, the medium of laws (Tække & Paulsen, 2010, p. 3).

For Luhmann, communication is a result of three selections: information, message (*Mitteilung*) and understanding (*Verstehen*). Communication only constitutes itself as a fact if all three selections are made. Information is the selection of something in the world that can be uttered in some way. It is the meaning-construction of something that potentially can serve as a message. It actualises something from the infinite latency of human existence. Rasmussen (2014) explains how, in Luhmann's view, communication is less about how apt a given sender of communication is to get her point across, and more about how it is received:

Next, a message must be selected from the information and formed as a message. ... Information must be given comprehensible form. An utterance is interpretable as a selection. Only when a message is produced does the third selection – understanding – come into play. Understanding

refers to the change of the state of the one who receives the utterance. Understanding is a selection based upon a distinction between information and message.

(Rasmussen, 2014, p. 75)

In this, it is important to remember that the subjects are only relevant as “carriers” – perpetrators – of the structures in focus. In a Luhmannesque light, then, a study of Facebook would focus on the various communications systems surrounding, and perpetuated by the users, but without looking at the users themselves.

The main contrast to a Foucauldian view, then, is that the Foucauldian subject cannot be taken out of a relation where, essentially, there is nothing outside the structures of knowledge and power. These structures are within and without the subject, and always in interaction with each other. Where Luhmann’s structures are essentially isolated, variable, and cannot meaningfully connect, Foucauldian structures are inherently connected and variable. Luhmann’s theory is elegant in its logical clarity and a valuable addition to the social media theory toolbox, but it is not the right fit for the tasks set out in this study, regarding the shaping of subjects, by holders of power-knowledge. Luhmann’s theories are highly applicable to social media interaction and the analysis of the communication and social networks thereon. It focuses on information systems, but appears blind to the individuals populating the system, and how these individuals are changed by the systems and change them in return. Furthermore, it focuses on how changes in a system happens “organically”, as opposed to any overt or covert intents of powerful system agents. Some scholars, like Fuchs, are highly critical of Luhmann, most especially the latter’s strictly positivist ontology which holds that, within the theory, any and all systems and values are relative – only value-laden within the given (sub-)system but without an outside given objective value (Fuchs C. , 2008, pp. 37-39). Others, like Tække & Paulsen, see Luhmann as the ideal theory for understanding modern social media, such as Facebook (Tække & Paulsen, 2010). In any case, Luhmann’s theories clearly emerge as less fit for my purposes than Foucault’s.

3.2.3 Stray, but never falter

In an effort to broaden the understanding and scope of the concept of power, and in order to show how and why the Foucauldian framework of this thesis is indeed the apt choice, I have explored and contrasted some other major theories of power. I have put special emphasis on those seen by myself and/or others as potentially relevant to the project, and this should not be seen as a judgment upon those who have not been included. In a world of facets, we must pick our focus and accept the shortcomings of that to which we will remain blind. These other theories of power lend concepts to express and thoughts to contrast the Foucauldian view outlined at the onset of this chapter, yet are not to be included in the foundation for this thesis. Not just the language and concepts used in setting up my study, but the epistemology they imply and reinforce inexorably makes this a Foucauldian project and text, with all the challenges, caveats and benefits this implies. The aim here is not to define a clear unidirectional power relation (1st face/dimension of power), nor to ascertain what person or entity has the power to set the agenda (2nd face/dimension of power), the answer to which in this case would likely be “algorithms” and not take the analysis much further. I do not aim to describe the institutional arbiters of truth which act on and through the platform to shape the preferences of individuals (3rd face of power), perhaps malignly so, though such a view could meaningfully be employed to analyse some media actors and certain politicians. Indeed it could be the foundation of a proper analysis of Facebook as a state, something which I can spare only passing attention to (see Chapter 4). As such, I have no need for a materialist analytical concept, such as Habermas’ public sphere nor the dialectical approach it implies. While these, and also Luhmann’s, theories can and have been employed in salient analyses of social media, they are not ideal to engage with the techniques and structures of power-knowledge in play in the social space in question, in all its complex, interconnected glory. All these theories are important and could meaningfully be wielded for a salient analysis, but they would not help in this endeavour. Thus, this almost critical rationalist falsification of the theory of choice makes no dent in the assumptions and epistemology of the thesis. This is, of course, expected, since it was based on the circular logic of commonplace academic writing: The theories were presented to contrast and showcase, rather than truly attempt to supplant the choices already made. Indeed, at times this chapter appears almost dialectical, if not positively rhetorical. The implication of my epistemology is a degree of

self-reflection that once again questions the inherent validity and scientificity of the steps taken to prove the same. The theories serve to make clear why the very nature of this (Foucauldian) project would have made using any of the other theories not just illogical, but counter-productive to finding the answers I seek – at least in the form they are stated.

Thus, in the forum of theorists, we have heard what others had to add, only to emerge with a stronger assertion of the theoretical footing already proposed. But what does that mean for the users – the subjects caught in this Foucauldian web of power-knowledge?

3.3 Subject(s) and freedom

The human subject is at the very core of a Foucauldian framework. In one of his most explicit (and accessible) texts about his ideas, his approach, and his aims, *The Subject and Power* (1982), Foucault writes about his work, as he saw it:

[T]he goal of my work ... has been to create a history of the different modes by which, in our culture, human beings are made subjects. My work has dealt with three modes of objectification which transform human beings into subjects.

The first is the modes of inquiry which try to give themselves the status of sciences ... the objectivizing of the productive subject ... in the analysis of wealth and economics. Or ... the objectivizing of the sheer fact of being alive in natural history or biology.

... [Second], objectivizing the subject in what I ... call “dividing practices.” The subject is either divided inside himself or divided from others. ... Examples are the mad and the sane, the sick and the healthy, the criminals and the “good boys.”

Finally ... the way a human being turns himself into a subject. For example ... how men have learned to recognize themselves as subjects of “sexuality.”

(Foucault, 1982, pp. 777-778, quotation marks in original)

Foucault goes on to exemplify relations where human subjects (in his time) are resisting various types of what we might call institutionalised power structures. He notes how the examples he chooses are 'immediate' and 'anarchistic': These are instances of resistance not to one identified 'enemy', but rather against the structure of subjection itself and/or the assigned position of the subject in it. Struggles that question '... the way in which knowledge circulates and functions, its relation to power. In short, the *regime du savoir*'. These overlapping regimes/structures of knowledge which identify and determine who and what 'one is' (ibid. p. 781, italics in original):

To sum up, the main objective of these struggles is to attack not so much such or such an institution of power, or group, or elite, or class, but rather a technique, a form of power.

This form of power applies itself to immediate everyday life which categorizes the individual, marks him by his own individuality, attaches him to his own identity, imposes a law of truth on him which he must recognize and which others have to recognize in him. It is a form of power which makes individuals subjects. There are two meanings of the word "subject": subject to someone by control and dependence; and tied to his own identity by a conscience or self-knowledge. Both meanings suggest a form of power which subjugates and makes subject to.

(Ibid. citation marks in original)

This famous Foucauldian double subjection is at the heart of the view outlined here. Foucault speaks to the context of a technology called 'state', but neither this technique nor the double subjection embedded in it is bound to exist only in the physical and temporal places where he experienced them and laid them bare. The attentive reader – even if new to Foucault – has already noted here just how eminently relevant such a double subjection is to the study of a coded social space, such as the one on Facebook – even barring my claim to come, that the collective techniques of subjection on Facebook can be analysed as governmentality of a (digital) state. To exist on Facebook one must subject oneself to the terms and conditions – including the policing of them – and constitute oneself as a subject, according to the structures afforded by the site. To exist on the site is to have a priori constituted oneself as a double subject.

Acknowledging social materialism (i.e. Marxism) as dissimilar from his own, but still a valuable standpoint to do such enquiries from, Foucault emphasises how (at least to his point of view) the ‘mechanisms of exploitation and domination ... entertain complex and circular relations with other forms [of subjectivity]’ (ibid. p. 782). This leads into his description of the new form of political power that he sees developing from the sixteenth century onwards and becoming part of the emerging state. The (modern) state is

... both an individualising and a totalizing form of power. ... [T]he modern Western state (sic) has integrated in a new political shape an old power technique which originated in Christian institutions. ... [T]he pastoral power. ... I don’t think that we should consider the “modern state” as an entity which was developed above individuals, ignoring what they are and even their very existence, but, on the contrary, as a very sophisticated structure, in which individuals can be integrated, under one condition: that this individuality would be shaped in a new form and submitted to a set of very specific patterns. ... In a way, we can see the state as a modern matrix of individualization or a new form of pastoral power.

(ibid. p. 782-784, quotes in original).

This then leads into what some might term the more normative or even activist part of Foucault’s work. He details how the collective ‘we’ of his – and perhaps our – time struggle not to be free of the state, but to free ourselves from the ‘type of individualization which is linked to the state’ (Ibid. p. 785). For my purposes, that raises the question of whether – if the subjections on Facebook can indeed be analysed as a technology of state, and if we are indeed doubly subjected by it in a Foucauldian sense – we then should enable a struggle to be free from this subjection? But before we can even contemplate this, we must first see what subjections we are indeed subject to by, in, and on Facebook – and whether a struggle is even possible. And to move further towards that goal, we must return now to explore the concept of governmentality.

3.4 Governmentality

Earlier in this chapter, I summarised governmentality as a concept which describes the mind-set according to which a given locus of power – such as a (modern) government or the state – governs (Foucault, 1984A, p. 338; Dean & Villadsen, 2016, p. 10). In this conception, it refers simply to a philosophy – or mentality – embedded in a given strategy of governance (Henman, 2011; Dean, 2009). This is a common description, but as is so often the case, there is more to the story. As introduced by Foucault (2006 [1979]), governmentality was not a general concept, but referred to a specific mentality which ‘had become the common ground of all modern forms of political thought and action’ (Rose, O'Malley, & Valverde, 2009, p. 6). Later authors have then expanded and adapted the concept to enable analysis of different governmentalities (Dean & Villadsen, 2016). It is an important concept, as Foucault and others inspired by him have used it extensively to explore how certain ways of thinking are intricate part of certain technologies of power – in Foucault’s case, those which he himself traced up through that loosely defined period called modernity.

When we speak of technologies of power, it generally refers to what might also be named policies, strategies, or institutions (such as the state). Whenever a discursive entity exercises coercion in active or passive ways to influence or steer – govern – the actions of others, the way in which this is done implies something about how one must think of the subjects and the actions taken to exercise power in this way, how the subjects are constituted. This is the governmentality, an inherent quality of a given way of exercising power, and that way – that type of exerting influence or control – is a technology of power (Sawyer, 2015). It is the often explicitly formulated “rationality” behind techniques of subjection, embedded in structures of power-knowledge. Similar to other Foucauldian concepts, governmentality is best understood as part of the wider framework. In his eponymous essay about governmentality, Foucault (2006 [1979]) starts out by asserting how the governance he talks about is not (just) governance in the narrow sense of sovereign(s) governing political subjects. He speaks of a general blossoming of ideas and technologies of governance emerging in sixteenth century Europe: governance of the self, governance of others, and governance of children. The questions guiding these ideas come from two processes: The

formation of the pre-modern state, and the religio-philosophical aspects of the reformation and the counter-reformation:

There is a double movement, then, of state centralization on the one hand and of dispersion and religious dissidence on the other: it is, I believe, at the intersection of these two tendencies that the problem comes to pose itself with this peculiar intensity, of how to be ruled, how strictly, by whom, to what end, by what methods, etc. There is a problematic of government in general.

(Foucault, 2006 [1979], p. 132)

In their review of the concept and its use in the English-speaking world, Rose, O'Malley, and Valverde (2009, pp. 2-3) recollect how Foucault traced different arts of governing, paying special attention to the particular 'reason of state' of the early eighteenth century, the emerging sciences of state, and the emergence and links with liberalism. It is important in that regard to note that Foucault paid distinct attention to the emergence and development of liberalism in his own formulation of the concept. Liberalism, here, is seen not as a 'doctrine of how to govern. Rather ... a search for a technology of government that can address the recurrent complaint that authorities are governing too much' (ibid.). Critique of Liberalism, and the later version(s) of it called Neo-Liberalism – 'a principle according to which interventions by the state should generally be limited' (Foucault, 2008, p. 81) has emerged as an important part of Foucault's work on governmentality. In fact, as per Foucault's own definition of the concept, governmentality is conceptualised in a clearly situated and explicit context. In Foucault's understanding governmentality means three things:

1. The ensemble formed by the institutions, procedures, analyses and reflections, the calculations and tactics that allow the exercise of this very specific albeit complex form of power, which has as its target population, as its principal form of knowledge political economy, and as its essential technical means apparatuses of security.
2. The tendency which, over a long period and throughout the West, has steadily led towards the pre-eminence over all other forms (sovereignty, discipline, etc.) of this type of power which may

be termed government, resulting, on the one hand, in the formation of a whole series of specific governmental apparatuses, and, on the other, in the development of a whole complex of savoirs.

3. The process, or rather the result of the process, through which the state of justice of the Middle Ages, transformed into the administrative state during the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries, gradually becomes 'governmentalized'.

(Foucault, 2006 [1979], p. 142)

To Foucault, then, as he espoused the concept, governmentality was very specifically bound to the technologies of government that he traced, leading up to and during the Liberal era he considered himself to be in. That is not to say that governmentality in the wider post-Foucauldian sense, mainly linked to the first definition he lays out, could not exist independent of Foucault's work. As is generally the case with abstract concepts, it could be applied elsewhere, given the appropriate contextualisation of both concept and object. One could imagine a historical genealogy tracing the "governmentality" of the bygone Byzantines/Romans or other societies of humans. It would, however, behove such an analysis to include an explicit reckoning with Foucault's more narrow definition. Rose, O'Malley, & Valverde outline a general definition of a Foucauldian analysis of governmentalities:

This [Foucauldian] perspective views ... power as always operating in terms of specific rationalizations and directed toward certain ends that arise within them. An analysis of governmentalities then, is one that seeks to identify these different styles of thought, their conditions of formation, the principles and knowledges that they borrow from and generate, the practices that they consist of, how they are carried out, their contestations and alliances with other arts of governing. From such a perspective, it becomes apparent that each formulation of an art of governing embodies, explicitly or implicitly, an answer to the following questions: Who or what is to be governed? Why should they be governed? How should they be governed? To what ends should they be governed? Thus, the governed are, variously, members of a flock to be nurtured or culled, juridical subjects whose conduct is to be limited by law, individuals to be disciplined, or,

indeed, people to be freed. Further, instead of seeing any single body---such as the state---as responsible for managing the conduct of citizens, this perspective recognizes that a whole variety of authorities govern in different sites, in relation to different objectives. Hence, a second set of questions emerges: Who governs what? According to what logics? With what techniques? Toward what ends? As an analytical perspective, then, governmentality is far from a theory of power, authority, or even of governance.

(Rose, O'Malley, & Valverde, 2009, p. 3)

They move on to review 'governmentality studies' which they articulate as an English, Foucauldian tradition, juxtaposed to what they consider an American (read: US) interpretation of Foucault, employing discourse analysis in a narrower understanding of Foucault than the one they themselves feel they represent. In their review, they show how the part of the governmentality tradition in their focus adhere to Foucault's above definition, without explicitly referring to it. Thus, though they define governmentality in a more general way, the field as they present it does not seem in discord with Foucault's own definition. They seem to focus on the first definition, leaving the second and third to fade into the background, as a setting for the concept rather than part of the concept itself. This is consistent with my operationalisation and utilisation of the concept here. While I consider the concept origins important, my focus is on governmentality as what it has become, not as it was originally formulated. Still, it is important to remember that as abstract and generalised as the concept has now become, it carries with it this explicit legacy. In analysing governmentality, I am not trying to explicitly do what Foucault did, looking to describe the modern or Liberal 'art of government', understood both narrowly and broadly, nor 'the introduction of economy into political practice' (Foucault, 2006 [1979], p. 135). All the while, I am attentive to the implication of the history of the concept. In short, I employ governmentality in a general sense, while conscious that in using it, I am implying certain connections within and without that which I seek to capture.

In presenting the Foucauldian concepts related to power I have returned repeatedly to the state. Both the pre-modern or modern state treated by Foucault and the digital state, which I will explore on Facebook. The main points to carry forward is the interconnectedness of subject, power, and state. As the subject is

inherent in the theories of power laid out above, the last object to be brought to the fore, before moving towards an analysis, is the state.

4. THE DIGITAL STATE

The goal of this thesis is to explore the governmentalities of the digital state, through a discourse analysis of the digital state of Facebook. To build such an analysis demands qualification and explication of the concepts. In the preceding chapters I have introduced social media and teased the idea of the digital state – and Facebook as a place of digital state power. I then moved on to present Foucauldian theory as the main theoretical foundation of this thesis, explaining the form and role of discourse analysis and genealogy in general, and for this thesis in particular. I moved on to a review of Foucault’s concepts of power and subjection, leading into the central concept of governmentality. In this review, other theorists of power were explored and contrasted to Foucault.

To complete the foundation of the thesis, I move now to present the last piece of my stated puzzle: The digital state. I first review the concept of the state, exploring its definitions and narrowing into the Foucauldian view of the state and the governmentality of the modern state. The operationalisation of the state preceding the Foucauldian angle invites further consideration as to what a state “is” and whether a corporation can be seen as such. Though a tangent to the overall thesis, it is a tangent worth exploring and I will make the case that Facebook can indeed be seen as “a state”. Following this, I return to the Foucauldian frame with its focus on what a technology (of state) does rather than what it is (or is not), and introduce the state of digital modernity.

4.1 The concept of state

Like power, the state is an essentially contested concept (Gallie, 1955; Anderson, 2006 [1983]; Lukes, 2005); the modern nation state in particular (Willoughby, 1896). The word “state” has come into our modern languages via Latin, originally denoting “status” – the state of things – “State” (French: Etat, German: Staat). Related back to the city state in ancient Greece (the *polis*) the state has become mainly a

descriptor for autonomous³ political units, and/or their leadership (chosen democratically or by other means).

4.1.1 Defining a state

As a type, the modern – or contemporary – state is often said to have been founded in the Westphalian peace of 1648 (Cerf, 2018). It is generally asserted that until this time, geographical and political state borders (if one applies our concept to the political units of the time and insofar as it can serve as a descriptor) were fluid and prone to change, as allegiances of higher or lesser nobles switched back and forth, and ever-returning border skirmishes and wars reshaped kingdoms and redrew maps of allegiances and lands time and again. The political unions of this, in terms of a modern conception, pre-state time were large and small, and though one could be king of France it was not always clear where exactly that realm ended and who it entailed. One could be king of Navarre or even holy emperor of the Romans to boot, but this was always enmeshed in overlapping systems of varying authorities and geographical areas. The focus was on each political unit's own borders, and ideally other lands only mattered to a ruler if they could be put under one's own flag or threatened to do the same to you. If the ruler was weak (or not about), one might march through and trade or fight with the inhabitants of a given area without necessarily facing consequences, since it might not be a violation of any agreed upon treaty, or since said treaty could not be enforced. Importantly, sovereignty was at this point conceived as being over land, rather than subjects. A ruler was not (necessarily) responsible for the actions or well-being of those inhabiting his land (Cerf, 2018; Foucault, 2006 [1979]). With the peace of Westphalia that largely ended for European states. As a response to the zero-sum prisoner's dilemma of warring monarchs, the European lords of the day set down an agreement that was to become historical in its simplicity: They agreed to recognise each other as rulers of their respective sovereign kingdoms. This is not to say that there would not still be wars of conquest or for other reasons, but it did mean the possibility of peaceful resolution to disputes, and (most importantly) a

³ At least in recent history. States can choose to bind together and in the current political world supra-state units such as the EU and the UN exist and can be said to limit said autonomy.

mutual recognition of unitary states, and their borders. It is commonly argued that the peace of Westphalia laid the conceptual and legal groundwork for what became the United Nations (Weiss, 2016).

In his widely acclaimed book on *Imagined Communities*, Anderson (2006) explains how the areas and peoples that were to become states and nations were influenced by the languages of the printing presses, by efforts to unify schooling, and were linguistically shaped by increasingly centralised bureaucracy imposing one or few languages as the literal language of governance, the “Language-of-state”. If one wanted to put a case before the eyes of a magistrate in 19th century Ireland, English was the language one had to do it in, although the everyday language of the Irish subjects was mainly Gaelic (Anderson, 2006 [1983], p. 78). Through these varied processes linguistic and (at least to some extent) cultural communities came to be and increasingly they corresponded with political areas – in mainland Europe perhaps culminating in the creation of the unified German state in 1871. Meanwhile, the idea of “peoples” of different kinds came to correspond more and more with these groups, fitting various racist and proto-nationalist narratives and fuelled and reimagined by both science and art. From such communities and the stories told in and about them is derived Anderson’s definition of a nation:

[I]t is an imagined political community – and imagined as both inherently limited and sovereign. It is imagined because the members of even the smallest nation will never know most of their fellow-members, meet them, or even hear of them, yet in the minds of each lives the image of their communion.

(Anderson, 2006 [1983], p. 6)

As science, art, and sovereign power increasingly came together to create narratives of culturally and often, in the narrative of the time, “racially” homogenous peoples and nations, the nation states became (imagined) reality. Whether by centralised schooling programmes and compulsory military service (France), or by finally appending a state to an area of duchies increasingly experienced as inhabited by culturally similar people (Germany), the borders between different sovereign kingdoms and republics increasingly signified a change from one imagined community to another, each with their specific and increasingly

homogenised language, values, and culture. As the borders began to correspond with the human communities separated by them, and the stories surrounding them came to correspond these formalised divisions, the nation states were born. Concurrent with this process came the rise of the state apparatus and bureaucracy similar to how we know it today. First came the various discussions of constitution – in terms of both treaty and formation – of various states, then came the shifting state rationalities (governmentalities) towards a, perhaps, more reflective or even scientific approach to governing – one that can be linked to the rise of positivist science á la Hume and Darwin or, as Foucault does, to economist ways of thinking (Foucault, 2008, p. 27ff.).

It appears the modern state is a nation state; on the one hand an imagined community (a nation), on the other hand a state. As an imagined community it is a more or less empty signifier which is also a common signifier allowing a principally unlimited number of subjects to consider themselves part of one common unit, as illustrated by Hobbes' leviathan (Hobbes, 1651). Second, it is the sum of the institutions of state to which these subjects refer (and subject) themselves (OED, 2017). Taken together, these institutions which in their infancy represented the sovereign monarch⁴ of the proto-nation state political units becomes the singular unit of the mass noun 'states' – a particular type of institution. According to a dictionary definition, a (political) state is:

2 A nation or territory considered as an organized political community under one government.

2.1 An organized political community or area forming part of a federal republic.

(OED, 2017)

We can add to this, Max Weber's classic definition:

The state is the human community which, within a particular area, (successfully) claims for itself the monopoly on legitimate physical violence. Because the specific of the present is: that the right

⁴ Though the monarchic naming practice of institutions remain in certain European states, such as the UK, this is considered here a question of aesthetic rather than form.

to exercise physical violence is only ascribed to groups or individuals, in terms of what the state, from its side, allows: It counts as singular source of “Right” of violence.

(Weber, 1919, my translation)

This meaning of the state is thus two-fold. First, it is a spatial entity, which can be seen as a ‘community under one government’; second, it is the governing entity itself and all of its representations, assuming that the entity who governs is the same as the one who has the monopoly on legitimate violence.

A state (and perhaps Facebook) might be seen as these things – an imagined community, a state actor, and the sum of the institutions of state, which the right of legitimate exercise of violence. But the concept can also be seen in a different light, as a collection of techniques of governance. Let us consider what that means.

4.1.2 The Foucauldian state

As pre-empted above, the state has varied over time and place, both as concept and institution. Foucault’s treatment and conception of (the) state was rooted in this but went besides and beyond it (Dean & Villadsen, 2016; Foucault, 2006 [1979]; Kendall & Wickham, 1999). As Rose, O’Malley, & Valverde put it, Foucault’s studies of state ‘... undermined the conventional view of the state as the origin, animator, beneficiary, or terminal point of power.’ (2009, p. 5). In the main, Foucault treated the state not as an entity or even an institution, but rather as a technology/technique of government – and/or a collection of such techniques. Thus, when we talk of “the state” in this way, it is not any or all specific instances of state that are in focus. Rather, the abstract concept – the shaping discourses and techniques, the web of power-knowledge that doubly subjects and empowers. The state in this specific abstract is intrinsically linked to the concept of governmentality (Rose, O’Malley, & Valverde, 2009).

Foucault dealt with the state as something both larger and more complex than did most other theorists, while at the same time rejecting the analytical focus on the state as a clearly defined and delimited entity with clear characteristics. From this follows that in a Foucauldian framework it would be oxymoronic to attempt a definitive answer as to whether this or that “is” a state. Rather, we must content ourselves with

suggesting that something – in this case Facebook – can be *seen as* “a state”, even as we hold firm to this being a relational if not wholly empty signifier. There is no attempt here at a positivist claim to truth nor an empiricist claim to the definite nature of things, but rather an assertion that the pervasive techniques of subjection collectively called state can be observed in certain sites which we may call institutions, and that Facebook is such a site. A site especially suited to observe the workings of the digital state.

Foucault’s relational, particular abstract(s) of “state” mirrors his treatment of other, related concepts, such as medicine, sexuality, normalcy and truth. After all, if each subject in and of herself is pervaded and constructed by contradicting structures of power-knowledge, then the institutions built by such subjects cannot help but be increasingly complex. In a clear critique of what can be seen as a gross oversimplification of what a state is, does, even “thinks”, Foucault famously called for theorists to cut off the head of the king in theory, as it had long been cut off in practice (Sawyer, 2015; Neal, 2004; Foucault, 1979B). Foucault critiques common theories of state as he sees them re-imposing the idea of feudal sovereignty upon the field. He warns that such a view might miss how a state, though powerful and pervading, is not all-powerful and all-pervading:

The State is superstructural ... to a whole series of power networks that invest the body, sexuality, the family, kinship, knowledge, technology and so forth. ... [B]ut this meta-power with its prohibitions can only take hold and secure its footing where it is rooted in a whole series of multiple and indefinite power relations that supply the necessary basis for the great negative forms of power. I would say that the State consists in the codification of a whole number of power relations which render its functioning possible...

(Foucault, 1979B)

So, the state, in Foucault’s view, is not unimportant or non-existing. It is a technology rather than an entity, but it remains complex and multifaceted. Rather than attempt to look theoretically at the state as a whole, Foucault focused on tracing those power relations individually and collectively, sometimes letting the state

– or an idea of a state – pop up, but never losing sight of a sometimes bigger, sometimes smaller and always more specific picture.

Tracing the emergence and development of the modern state and state rationalities – governmentalities – is a key part of Foucault's most impactful writing. Indeed, some of his work is still directly employed in critique of current-day policies and practices (Neal, 2004; Amoore, 2018). Foucault's conceptions of power mentioned in Chapter 3 all come into play as Foucault describes how modern nation states constitute their subjects. The modern state (as phenomenon, but also as a concrete instance of the type) seeks to know all of each individual subject, and govern it accordingly, but it also seeks to govern the collective. A main difference in the way the modern state constitutes its subjects to how earlier sovereigns had done so is that rather than simply hold the power to grant life or inflict physical pain and death, the sovereign head of state and her advisors now took it upon themselves to govern intimately the everyday life of each subject, whilst knowing the statistics of their state. Both in terms of organising the masses according to various logics and rationalities, but knowing, recognising, caring for, and shaping – taking responsibility for – each subject:

If one can apply the term bio-history to the pressures through which the movements of life and the processes of history interfere with one another, one would have to speak of biopower to designate what brought life and its mechanisms into the realm of explicit calculations and made knowledge-power an agent of transformation of human life. It is not that life has been totally integrated into techniques that govern and administer it; it constantly escapes them. Outside the Western world, famine exists, on a greater scale than ever; and the biological risks confronting the species are perhaps greater, and certainly more serious, than before the birth of microbiology. But what might be called a society's "threshold of modernity" has been reached when the life of the species is wagered on its own political strategies. For millennia, man remained what he was for Aristotle: a living animal with the additional capacity for a political existence; modern man is an animal whose politics places his existence as a living being in question.

(Foucault, 1978 [1976], pp. 142-143, citations in original)

Foucault describes how this 'science of state' and 'science of policing' became more and more embedded in the rationalities of modern nation states (Foucault, 1979A, p. 242). In his own words, he examined the relations between 'experiences ..., knowledge ..., and power' (Foucault, 1984B, p. 239), trying to uncover and understand the structures of power-knowledge of modern state(s), through the history leading up to it. He tells of the rise of the 'governmentality' (Foucault, 1984, p. 338) of the modern state, which he sees as historically unique in that it is 'both individualising and totalitarian' (Foucault, 1984, p. 254), wielding and employing both 'pastoral' (individualising) and political power (ibid. pp. 227, 235). The modern state, then, is an amorphous and changeable entity, but it is enveloped in techniques of governance and power embedded with governmentalities of disciplinary, pastoral, sovereign, and bio-power (see chapter 2).

In his eponymous outline of the concept of governmentality, which I explored in the preceding chapter, Foucault (2006 [1979]) traced how the political rationalities of sovereigns shifted from the government of territory to the government of people and things. From a restrictive sovereign who delimits, bans, and punishes the emerging reason of state articulated to guide the rulers of lands and peoples into employing the figure of the benevolent father and shepherd: a ruler who has (and should have) inherently benevolent aims for her subjects and takes action to achieve them. With the early enlightenment emerges statistics – ledgers that 'realise the population as individual nodes and thus enables population as individuals as the object of governance rather than the families' (Foucault, 2006 [1979], p. 137). This process of individualisation and individual subjection to the state means that the feudal system hierarchies with families as the base unit shifted towards an ideal of individual subjects related to an individual sovereign. Thus, 'the family becomes an instrument rather than a model: the privileged instrument for the government of the population and not the chimerical model of good government' (ibid.).

In this new rationality of state, the sovereign ruler is (still) conceived as a benign parent. But rather a parent to individual and collective statistical subjects than simply a restrictive head of a clan of families. This new model of ruler should do more than define right from wrong and punish transgressions. The sovereign super-parent at the verge of modernity had under its responsibility and purview not just the wicked to be

punished, but all subjects. And with this positive responsibility of nurture as well as torture came the need to formulate practices and techniques to achieve benevolent aims.

Rather than simply setting the frame for behaviour with laws, as did the princes before them, the emerging pre-modern state employs tactics – policies – with specific aims and designs upon behaviour. Thus, rather than constrain and limit particular unwanted behaviour, power was wielded with the intent to produce wanted behaviour and practice. To the governor at the service of the household, rather than the household at the service of the governor.

(Foucault, 2006 [1979], p. 138)

In this Foucault finds an emergence of what we might call “statecraft” as a separate field of rationality – a rationality intrinsic to the here ‘pre-modern’ state, which ‘cannot be derived solely from natural or divine laws or the principles of wisdom and prudence’ (ibid.). Rather than simply deriving principles with which to guide the ruler from laws and tenets from other areas of life, philosophy, and nature this new state rationality is bound primarily and exclusively to the science of state. In a predominantly means-ends ethical framework, with the ultimate aim of subjection being the increasingly measurable salvation of double subjects in whatever way that salvation appears to the statistical eyes of the state:

[T]he state, like nature, has its own proper form of rationality, albeit of a different sort. Conversely, the art of government, instead of seeking to found itself in transcendental rules, a cosmological model or a philosophico-moral ideal, must find the principles of its rationality in that which constitutes the specific reality of the state. ... In other words, the transition which takes place in the eighteenth century from an art of government to a political science, from a regime dominated by structures of sovereignty to one ruled by techniques of government, turns on the theme of population and hence also on the birth of political economy.

(Foucault, 2006 [1979], pp. 138-141)

What Foucault is describing here is the emergence of the pastoral power of the modern state introduced above. From this point onwards the pre-modern and later modern state grows along with the governmentality of modernity into the form we know today. The state of today is articulated as universal in many respects. It is eternal, rational, and in direct relation to all subjects, human or otherwise. This abstract sovereign, now many steps removed from individual Cæsars, bishops, and kings, is personal and universal. It demands subjection in the double sense with every legal subject being required to subject themselves to the rules and norms of the state as well as realise herself as that which she is in the state ledger. The latter, of course, can often be identified as one of the sites of resistance described by Foucault as guiding his studies – not least of sexuality (Foucault, 1982; Foucault, 1978 [1976]).

It is important to re-emphasise here that the state treated by Foucault is a particular technique/technology. It is a historically and discursively bound abstract intrinsically connected with the many concepts outlined in the preceding chapters. The state talked about in this context is not a political entity. It is not a nation state, nor a territorial state – rather it is the idea of “the state”. The universal referent, the commonly recognised sovereign other, which “modern” subjects constitute themselves and others according to and in relation to. This concept is very much related to the wider idea of government and governmentality. In Foucault, the idea of the state goes hand in hand with the idea that subjects should be governed. All are bound as subjects of the (universal) state, and the state is bound to its subjects to seek for them the earthly salvation and govern them towards this hallowed ground.

When these concepts are connected especially to the era of Foucault’s modernity, the claim is not that these techniques and forms of power, knowledge, and practice have never existed before nor that they could not exist in other times and places. The point is that it is this particular conception and form of state that is at issue here. Thus, the Foucauldian state emerges – as does so many of his concepts introduced above – as particular, relative, and fluent. It is the modern state with its triangle of ‘sovereignty-discipline-government, which has as its primary target the population and as its essential mechanism the apparatuses of security’ (Foucault, 2006 [1979], p. 142) (see also Chapter 2). It is historically, geographically, and culturally situated in the last few centuries of especially European history, and some see it as spread across

the world in various forms and iterations (e.g. Grigat, 2014). This state carries and is carried by a certain operational logic – rationality of state – called governmentality. I introduced the concept of governmentality in the preceding chapter. I will now further sharpen this concept to describe the specific governmentality particularly treated by Foucault, the governmentality of the modern state.

4.1.3 Governmentality of the modern state

I have introduced governmentality both as a specific concept, as used by Foucault himself, and as an abstract inspired by this (especially his first definition), then expanded and used in more general terms by Foucauldians and others. In the view originally outlined by Foucault, the governmentality concept was directly linked to the modern state (Foucault, 2006 [1979]). It can be said, then, that talking specifically of a governmentality of the modern state implies a non-existing or at least problematic assertion of a dichotomy which clearly diverges from how Foucault himself envisioned and employed the concept. On the other hand, for some scholars, governmentality has emerged as an increasingly abstract concept, referring to rationality of (a) government in the complete abstract as much as a rationality of (the) government in the concrete sense of the modern state as a collection of techniques (Dean & Villadsen, 2016). Others have used governmentality as a typology, identifying ‘... different historical models of governmentality, [such as] reason of state, classical liberalism, contemporary neoliberalism ...’ (Vicencio, 2014, p. 283). I have stated that though I employ the term more generally than did Foucault himself, I do so on the foundation of his work. When I talk of the governmentality of the digital state, I attempt to treat this digital state similar to how the modern state of his time was treated by Foucault. Though I propose the digital state as a separate concept from the modern state that is not to say that the digital state is not modern, nor that digital and modern cannot coincide. This is also not meant to set up a typology for the comparison of various configurations of state and power. Indeed, to some degree and in some modalities the digital state will appear as little more than the modern state, online. For this reason, before turning to this digital state, I will introduce the governmentality of the modern state.

I have shown how the state can be seen as varied and changing as the humans, times, and societies of the pre-modern and modern age are changing. Still, as Weber and others have shown us, ideal types are often

helpful for an analysis in setting up a figurative multi-dimensional scale against which to measure a certain phenomenon (Beck, 2005; Weber, 2002[1922]). It is also important to remember that Foucauldian concepts are not mutually exclusive and often overlapping (Koopman, 2019). This, then, is not an attempt to reflect on an existing and constant entity, but rather to pose a discursively situated flash of something alike to the thing to be looked for in the (digital) state of Facebook.

At its broadest, the modern state is a collection of techniques of subjection and government. It is not limited to formal institutions and officials, though it does not preclude them either. It is a state (of governance) that seeks to envelop and colonise all aspects and facets of conscious life (Foucault, 1979A). Even as the govern-mentality of the state warps institutions and shifts power away from sovereign persons to abstract sovereign institutions, and then from those institutions towards “private” companies and markets (Vicencio, 2014), still it continues to pervade the societies and subjects of modernity. The state is best seen in those specific techniques and institutions of sovereignty, discipline, and government which we can see working on a broader scale, and which are embraced by the majority of modern subjects: the (state) school, the (state) army, the (state) bureaucracy, and the codified laws of the nation states (Foucault, 2008; Dean & Villadsen, 2016; Kendall & Wickham, 1999). The modern state as an ideal-typical entity is sovereign in that it represents the highest and most legitimate authority – before its words ‘... all voices must be still’ (Foucault, 1995 [1975], p. 36). The state “speaks” the highest truth and as such is ultimately vested with the highest power to define truth; power-knowledge. It is the collection of techniques that discipline subjects through themselves and others. The discourses it defines are embedded with the truths it speaks, and those who stray from these truths are disciplined by themselves and others. Thus, the subjects of state are normalised and always subjecting themselves more, becoming increasingly docile and productive vessels of state. Finally, the state institutions define and constitute the government. When the sovereign, modern state expresses its incontestable truth (whether spoken by a doctor, a schoolteacher, or a judge), it implicitly and explicitly shapes and governs subjects. The subjects of the modern state are subjected and governed by themselves and others according to those rationalities of state that are expressed with inexorable truth when the sovereign speaks:

In any case, I wanted to demonstrate the deep historical link between the movement that overturns the constants of sovereignty in consequence of the problem of choices of government, the movement that brings about the emergence of population as a datum, as a field of intervention and as an objective of governmental techniques, and the process which isolates the economy as a specific sector of reality, and political economy as the science and the technique of intervention of the government in that field of reality.

(Foucault, 2006 [1979], p. 142)

In the perhaps too narrow sense of state as the specific institutions governing a polity, this modern state is infused with the logics and narratives outlined above. It is infused within and without with governmentality, as proposed by Foucault. If we were to isolate this narrow state apparatus theoretically, the governmentality of said apparatus would at the same time be defined and employed within this bureaucratic apparatus, but also without and around it. We would see in the broader state surrounding the state institutions critiques and discussions arising employing, influencing, and asserting truths of government to be and being embedded in the same governmentality. The struggle becomes to define – according to this wider governmentality of the modern state – what is the best, most worthy goal of state rationality, and how to achieve it; what ends are the closest to earthly salvation and the duty of post-Christian pastorship, and what techniques, what policies should be employed to best achieve them for the singular and collective subjects.

We live in the era of a 'governmentality' first discovered in the eighteenth century. This governmentalization of the state is a singularly paradoxical phenomenon, since if in fact the problems of governmentality and the techniques of government have become the only political issue, the only real space for political struggle and contestation, this is because the governmentalization of the state is at the same time what has permitted the state to survive, and it is possible to suppose that if the state is what it is today, this is so precisely thanks to this governmentality, which is at once internal and external to the state, since it is the tactics of government which make possible the continual definition and redefinition of what is within the

competence of the state and what is not, the public versus the private, and so on; thus the state can only be understood in its survival and its limits on the basis of the general tactics of governmentality.

(Foucault, 2006 [1979], pp. 142-143)

Finally, this modern state governmentality carries with it a legacy of power structures from the cultures and histories from whence it came. First, it is a part of a 'society of laws', written and unwritten, which establishes boundaries for subject behaviour and a framework (or more) in which to contest and renegotiate those boundaries through asserting them broken (or not) (Foucault, 2006 [1979], p. 143). These norms and laws establish basic obligations, positive and negative rights, and one or more arenas and ways in which to contest or renegotiate these laws. Second, the modern state carries and is carried by 'the administrative state' whose emergence I have treated above. This administrative apparatus – the state bureaucracy – formalises and enforces the formalised, universal laws and the processes through which they can be individually or collectively challenged or changed. It further polices the state subjects and thus enforces the sovereign will of the governmentalised state, disciplining subjects inside and outside the state apparatus. Indeed, one can see in the narratives of the "responsibility to protect" and the liberal institutions instituted to organise and police the world an implicit ethos of responsibility and thus implied sovereignty to police towards all potential subjects (Grigat, 2014). Third, the governmentality of the modern state is unbound by the territory/territories that birthed it. Rather than geography it deals with and is defined by the statistics of state – the population, products, and resources: the abstract capital to be individualised, collated, and totalised rather than the physical roots it – or at least its concept – originally represents.

This state of government which bears essentially on population and both refers itself to and makes use of the instrumentation of economic *savoir* could be seen as corresponding to a type of society controlled by apparatuses of security.

(Foucault, 2006 [1979], p. 143, italics in original)

The modern state moves toward abstractly knowing all its subjects individually and collectively (pastoral power) and would – it if could – know the name, address, sex, gender, sexuality, medical records and all other individually differentiated and quantified information about each subject whilst also knowing the collective state of what groupings can be made in that society. The state plays a key role in setting the boundaries for disciplining its subjects, be it through schools, civil service regulation, laws or authoritative works of knowledge-power. With these techniques it seeks to shape subjects – exercise bio-power – and have them function ever more according to the prevailing rationalities of state. While it is true that where there is power, there is resistance, and the individual subjects shape and change the structure as much as it shapes and changes them (ultimately the structure exists only in the collective knowledge of the subjects), the structure can at times seem as unmalleable as a block-chain calculation, and bad calculations that do not correspond to the distributed ledger will be discarded without further ado. The governmentalities of the modern state march on in their inexorable drive to colonise and subjectivise other rationalities and subjects.

These abstract, discursive constructions have real-world implications. On the one hand, the state institutions know more and do more on and with subjects – on the other hand other actors employ the rationalities and techniques of (modern) state. Indeed, as some so-called neo-liberal policies from the last decades of the former millennia onwards have moved to in some senses retract the state from civil society (Beck, 2005), this by no means mean the end of state power: If and when organisations and companies not formally proclaimed as state institutions exercise pastoral, disciplinary, and bio- power, in order to shape subjects into docile bodies – if and when they govern the subjects in any meaningful sense of the word – well, then in this radical conception they are part of the loci of power that in other theories might include only the institutions formally titled “state”, and they can and should be included in the story of government of the digital subject. Indeed, I will argue that “private” companies can be seen as states of their digital realms. This statement, however, should not be taken lightly and merits further exploration (see 4.2, below). For now, it should be asserted that while the above might imply a critical standpoint, my aim is to see what is, rather than to criticise it in the negative sense of the word. Whatever else they are, the power structures that organise and subjectivise the subjects of the modern state are productive. The salvation

defined and sought by the governmentality of the modern state is also one of freedom and productivity for its subjects in personal and economic terms. Realising subjects as datafied nodes to be optimised makes possible governance for the calculated and perceived greater good. The governmentality of the modern state is one that subjectivises and makes docile its human subjects – but in realising these subjects as objects to be governed towards neo-pastoral salvation it also makes these subjects live longer, healthier, and more care-free lives. In the governmentality of the modern state we see yet another example of how power is always productive as well as delimiting. As is code (Winner, 1980).

4.1.4 Questions of state and power

The exploration of the concept of state above mirrors the earlier exploration of theories of power in its abstraction. In both cases, the concepts of power, and the state, become increasingly intangible, as we climb the typological ladder from the two faces of power to the purported third and Foucauldian fourth dimension of power. The more abstract notions of power that arise as the theory progresses may seem similar compared to the more “realist” first and second faces, but as Lukes explains in proposing Foucault’s theory as a fourth dimension to complement the two that went before and his Gramscian third, in truth, they are not. So, too, the concept of the state. From concrete to abstract, we have now arrived at the Foucauldian notion of the state. Not an actor nor even an entity; not a typology nor an operationalised concept for dialectic analysis. It is a collection of those techniques that turn subjects into subjects, an exploration of what they are, of what operational logics are embedded in them. A web of power-knowledge that constitutes – creates – subjects and allows them to constitute themselves in reference to the subjecting technique. A linkage of abstract truths that contain and constitute the self and the universal other called state. State, in this structure, is the universal other which the subjects consider the sovereign, universal other. Indeed, whether these subjects call this other “state”, or “nation”, or the “General Congress” is unimportant. The point is that there has emerged a universally recognised structure of governance and political struggle is not about whether this big other should govern, but how it should govern, with what means, towards what ends (Foucault, 2006 [1979]).

In this framework we cannot even know a state by its given name, since the point is not to identify quasi-material institutional archetypes at all, but rather the structures of governance. Cutting loose the material plane can be daunting. What of subjects living in places where so-called “weak states” supposedly govern and get to define the names on our maps? What if the political subjects in those areas are mainly governed by corporate rules set up around the institutions of mining operations? What of those living wild or remote, in blissful ignorance of any universal big other claiming to be a state and claiming them as its subjects? Am I claiming that for the former, the mining corporation rather than the remote institutions of the formal state, is the actual state? Am I claiming that the latter has no state – or that they perhaps have their own tiny state of tribe or community? Again here, the answer is neither yes nor no. These materialist concerns of definition are worthy and important, but they are not the focus of this research. In both cases, I would try to discern however I could what structures of subjection envelop and constitute the subjects, and how they work. But, a materialist might ask, how can I know what governance is happening, if I do not know who or what governs? The answer is that it is a question of methodology, but more specifically one of epistemology. To answer this, and to better understand my approach, we might reverse the question: How can I know who or what governs, if I do not know what governance is happening? Hopefully this illustrates the circular tautology of both questions. If we assert that something governs in a certain way, we are implicitly saying that it is – at least *prima facie* – an institution that can and does govern. If we assert that something is an institution that can and does govern, then we are implicitly saying – at least *prima facie* – that it governs in a certain way⁵.

In recognising the circular epistemology to arise from our ontological assumptions, we also arrive at the realisation that there is no a priori primacy to either formulation of the question. At the end of the day, none of the strategies is inherently “better”. They are simply different and lead to different methodologies. We have to start somewhere, and that means constituting one theoretically in order to explore the other empirically. In doing so, we must be faithful and upright to our readers, and allow them to pass judgment

⁵ I am leaning heavily on Foucault’s essay *The Subject and Power* (1982) for this point, indeed this section.

on our approach. If they find the theory wanting, then perhaps the purposed empirical findings are of less value – or at least less or different impact than the theory claims. So be it. From this standpoint – my standpoint – this is essentially true for all scholarship, whether purportedly “scientific” or not.

My focus is not on who or what governs, but rather on how subjects are being turned into subjects; how they are governed and according to what logics, towards what more or less defined ends. This means that rather than trying to define where power is materially situated (a fruitless task in any case, in a Foucauldian framework), I can focus on the structures of power-knowledge. I aim to explore empirically the coded meta-structures that restrict, allow, and produce social actions and subjects and the rules that govern them. When I try to ascertain the rationalities and ends being embedded into the techniques that govern – what subjects are allowed and supposed to be, and to what end – it is essentially unimportant if the given norms and rules ascertained in the framework are quasi-materially situated in Facebook Inc. in the US, in the EU, or in some other more or less clearly defined institution. The point here is to figure out where best to explore the governmentality of the universal other called state, on and of Facebook. In the questions about governance of the subjects on Facebook, the main question is about the governmentality of the state of Facebook. Whether Facebook(.com) or Facebook Inc. in and of itself can be called “a state” is a secondary question. But it is worthy of consideration. In an un-operationalised manner I at the very least treat Facebook as a social space where subjects are constituted. If not, there would be no state operations to analyse on Facebook. Further, whether methodologically relevant to the wider study or not, the question about whether Facebook Inc. can be seen as a state is an interesting one, and answering it would help further situate the site of study and the analysis. This can also serve as a theoretical footing to support a further claim that there can be such a thing as a state of Facebook – whether that state then be situated inside or outside the platform and the corporation or not. As such, before we continue the main narrative, let us consider in earnest whether Facebook Inc. can be seen as a state.

4.2 Facebook as a state

I have claimed that I can analyse the techniques of subjection of digital subjects, in the digital, as operations of digital state. I have claimed that Facebook is a good place to do so, the best for my purposes, even. But

what does this mean? While I have carefully steered clear (read: edited out) rogue allusions to Facebook, the platform and/or Facebook Inc. being in and of themselves “a state”, my choices and my approach does imply this. To claim that a corporation can be seen as a state is no trivial matter. If carried forward, this mixing of institutional typologies has implications far beyond this thesis. A burden I should accept and try to bear, at least briefly, before returning to the safety of my Foucauldian confines.

So far, I have argued my case in positive terms. I have explained the reasoning behind my choices and presented why I consider it meaningful to apply Foucault to the questions of the digital state – a collection of techniques for which Facebook appears the ideal and thus chosen site of analysis. In this section, I explore whether and how Facebook can be considered a state. When, in this regard, I am talking about Facebook, I am referring to the online platform, which is inextricably linked to the company which, for these purposes, I designate Facebook Inc. I follow the same logic of the abstractions of power and the ontologies of state I have treated above. That means that I start from a base conception of a state, moving on to more complex formulations, starting with arguments from a “realist” perspective, moving on to an institutional, constructivist view, and then finally into a Foucauldian view. I will start by looking into the idea of a corporation as a state and then move on to apply the same thinking to Facebook Inc. Doing so must be accompanied by a caveat. A clear theoretical implication of the thesis so far is that we should treat an abstract like “the state” as a non-entity. In the Foucauldian framework, the state can only be an abstract, but never a concrete “thing”, as Foucault explicitly sees his own approach in opposition to the ideas of other critical theorists (Habermas in particular) since his ‘analytics of power ... can be constituted only if it frees itself completely from [this] representation of power that I would term ... “juridico-discursive” ... a certain image of power-law, of power-sovereignty’ (Foucault, quoted in Flyvbjerg, 1998, citation marks in original). As such, in this framework it is ideally beside the point to discuss whether the Paris Commune, the various European Commonwealths with their East India companies, or Facebook is “a state”. The question can neither be answered in the positive nor the negative. In the extreme, it would be the equivalent of asking whether your local school, whatever the name of that particular school is “a pastoral power”. Since this concrete school is not an abstract, it can of course not be said to be “a pastoral power”, but it might very well be a site where one can *observe* the workings of pastoral power. Indeed, it might

very well be a fruitful place to watch “the state” as emerged in and of that school (Kendall & Wickham, 1999). This does not mean that the school is now “a state” (nor the opposite). In fact that question is immaterial to the focus and intent of the Foucauldian approach. On the other hand, when I announce that I can and will analyse the digital state of Facebook, I am clearly implying that there is something there, in the digital, which is at least like a state. The direction of my thinking, as well as the methodological choices I have made in order to analyse the digital state of Facebook clearly implicates that at least in a certain sense I understand and treat Facebook as a polity – a political community – and Facebook Inc. as an institution comparable to the government of that country. Further, Foucault – and others working within his framework – can and do talk about particular institutions of state, and at the very least hints at states as entities, if not actors. Foucault openly talks about France, Germany, and England! When I talk about Facebook in the same way as he talked about these commonly recognised nation states, I am discursively, reflexively implying that they are of a similar nature. Confusing as this may seem, the point is, I believe, that Foucault does not deny (nor confirm) the existence of particular states as discursive entities. Rather, he asserts that we must not – especially in theory – treat these discursive entities as if they were individuals, as if they were actors. As such, Foucault’s framework does not merely imply a rejection or inversion of the materialist and realist, later neo-realist, notions of state which have come to define how much of social science constitute the state in theory and practice. It implies a disregard for those precepts, but not a denial of them. It is not discussed whether this or that state – indeed, the state – does or does not exist, it is true, but the institutions of state which he treat are commonly recognised as such. With Facebook this is not so.

The strongest part of my argument should remain theoretical, and based on the Foucauldian frame. But to situate this, to put weight behind the assumptions, I must start at the beginning. I must take seriously the question of state-hood. And so I shall. Before we turn to Facebook Inc., let us first consider the wider frame.

Can we compare corporations to states at all?

4.2.1 States, corporations, and other institutions

As we have seen, what exactly constitutes a state is by no means a stable measure. The same can be said for corporations. Especially in an historical perspective, states and corporations both cover wildly differing

entities (Miller, 1960). The signifiers are flowing especially because they cover a large, heterogeneous set of institutions (an even more open signifier than the two we started with, perhaps). It stands to reason that some of the examples of one and the other can overlap. Especially when the focus is less one of trying to define one or the other (and their differences and commonalities), but to judge a given feature relevant to both, such as power. In such a case, Doris Fuchs (2013), referencing Ferguson and Mansbach (1999), looks at the economic resources of global companies and argues that in this context

... one may juxtapose comparisons of resources between global companies and other actors, in particular countries with small economies. There, one may see that today's largest global companies each have annual sales revenues greater than the GNP of a substantial number of countries... .

(Fuchs D. , 2013, p. 79)

Fuchs further notes how the political class ostensibly leading states overlaps with representatives of business to the extent where states seem to act on behalf of business (ibid.). While this does not make the businesses into states in and of themselves, states acting on behalf of singular or collective businesses does undermine the idea that one and the other can be seen as separate entities. Indeed, a state can be seen simply as the executive branch of the broadly conceptualised nation state, whose collective interests in some cases are seen to be equal to the interests of those running businesses formally based in said state (Miller, 1960). By definition, corporations are not states. But in a de-regulated world where companies have become much less regulated and unbound by norms than the family dynasties before them that came to define so many states, they can be seen as similar (Garrett, 2008). Nouveau riche colonialists from the Americas never did establish formal hereditary titles to match those of the very late quasi-Roman heritage titles of Western Europe. As such, they cannot be said to be aristocrats (regardless of any connection to the Aristocats). At the same time, there is a reason why books, films, series, and documentaries depicting the US American upper class often features references to someone being “a Kennedy”, “a Rodham”, or (now, perhaps infamously) (a) “Trump”.

On the one hand, businesses can be seen as a “new breed” of institution seemingly poised to challenge states for supremacy as scattered universal referents for mediation of the good life for the citizen-consumers, something which could perhaps be likened to what the state was and is in relation to the family. On the other, as we have seen above, the state as we know it now is not necessarily much older, and at least some international companies can be seen as comparable to colonial state institutions and vice versa for small states acting in relation to large companies (Miller, 1960; Fuchs D. , 2013; Garrett, 2008). It behoves us to remember that neither “Cæsar” nor “Augustus” were titles before the first emperor, Cæsar Augustus, had been in power long enough to lend untold new symbolic power to the family names of himself and of his adoptive father, and the honorific associated with the office he came to institute. Similarly, what historians have come to call the Roman Empire, supposedly birthed by the same emperor (a title that translates to various renditions of “Cæsar” in many languages (Kaiser, Kejsler, Zar, ...)), seems to still have been considered a republic to its contemporaries (Pierson, 2015). Such is the fleeting and mutable nature of signs and signifiers (and signified) (Saussure, 2011 [1916]). Given this, it should come as no surprise that the connections, differences, and similarities of corporations and states have been up for debate for some time.

At our current point in time, it seems implausible that “the company” should come to replace “the state” as the name given to the latter is considered to refer the nexus and primary arena of political power. On the other hand, the de facto distinction between states and companies can be strenuous, and some have argued that international corporations should at the least be viewed as stand-alone actors on the international stage (Fuchs D. , 2013), or as a ‘private government’ of the states from whence they hail (Miller, 1960). The question can also be posed as one of organisation. One can adopt a highly state-centric view of the US society and conceptualise corporations as simply agents of the US state (in broad terms), if not of the US government (Miller, 1960). This follows the logic of privatisation of state operations and public-private partnerships (PPPs). In that view, the services provided by the various corporations are simply operations of the US state, by private (government) actors (ibid.). But there must be a tipping point. If one organisation – say, Amazon – should happen to effectively take over the political, monetary, and decision-making power over per instance the digital infrastructure of the US state, then at some point that

entity (a sub-division of Amazon) would de facto become the government agency responsible for digital infrastructure. Reminding us again of the Roman Byzantine revolving titles and honours, this state agency may still go by the name of “Amazon Cloud Services”, but it could no longer meaningfully be categorised as an independent operator on a capitalist market. Conversely, if a state decides to keep the control of a given area “in-house”, then the organisation built up within the bureaucracy of the state will be comparable to the aforementioned organisation built up within the bureaucracy of the private company (and intermeshed with the rest of the public and private laws and institutions of the state in any case). I will return to and expand on this point about private corporations as state agencies when I turn to the state of Facebook. But first, let us return to the corporations and consider further their relation to states.

4.2.2 Garrett and the corporation as a sovereign

One key feature of a state is its status as a sovereign entity within its territory. Allison D. Garrett has comprehensively explored *The Corporation as a sovereign* (2008), and she minces no words:

In the past two hundred years, sovereignty devolved from the monarch to the people in many countries; in our lifetimes, it has devolved in several significant ways from the people to the corporation. We are witnesses to the erosion of traditional Westphalian concepts of sovereignty.

(Garrett, 2008, p. 130)

Garrett argues that globalisation and communication technologies have ‘made the nation state ... far less significant’ (ibid. p.131), while the influence of corporations continue to grow. This has led to corporations taking over some of the ‘duties of sovereign nations’, and that ‘their similarities to sovereign states increase’ (ibid.). She moves on to list various, often overlapping authoritative definitions of state, nation, and nation state, citing in particular:

... the 1933 Montevideo Convention on the Rights and Duties of States. That document provides that “[t]he State as a person of international law should possess the following qualifications: (a) a permanent population; (b) a defined territory; (c) government; and (d) capacity to enter into relations with other States.”

(Garrett, 2008, p. 140)

Based on this she explores in what way and to what degree corporations vis-à-vis states can be said to fulfil these qualifications. In relation to **(a)** a permanent population, she finds that nation states have increasingly un-permanent and diverse populations who do not necessarily identify as mainly a citizen of this or that nation state. She emphasises a rising trans-nationalism and cosmopolitanism and considers workers connection to their employer – their ‘corporate citizenship’ – to sometimes be more salient than that to their place of birth (ibid. p. 143). She further compares cultures of different corporations to cultures of different countries and notes how the rising power of corporations may lead to the elite politics of corporations accruing an increasing importance compared to the elite politics of states. In relation to **(b)** the control of a defined territory, she writes that

... land, as one of the means of production, is less significant now than ever before. This decrease in significance is the result of information, which has taken its place with land, labor, and capital as a means of production.

(Garrett, 2008, p. 146)

She further argues that the size of territory is ‘irrelevant to the issue of statehood’, and that geographic borders have lost significance ‘... as capital, people, and information cross borders with ease’ (ibid.). In other words, she is posing that in a globalised economy, ownership of information and (portable) capital are to be seen as increasingly important compared to the sovereign control of land. She is not claiming that corporations have started amassing control of a defined territory. Instead, she suggests that what corporations control is to be seen – at least in an economic sense – as waning in value as a material base of power and sovereignty. In relation to **(c)** government, she explores the economic power of corporations. Echoing Doris Fuchs (2013), Garrett finds that various companies do indeed hold much economic sway, especially compared to small states. As for **(d)** the capacity to enter into relations with other States, Garrett shows how corporations are eager participants in international diplomacy, influencing local and global governance, with a particular investment in trade policies, including ‘environmental, labor, consumer

protection, and other concerns' (Garrett, 2008, p. 150). She adds to this, the particular ability of large corporations to negotiate their taxation.

Having addressed the Montevideo qualifications, Garrett moves on to explore internal and external security (read: policing and legislative) operations. She notices how 'corporations [establish private security forces and] routinely exercise police powers' but re-iterates that we are unlikely to see 'corporate armies comparable in size to that of the East India Company' (Garrett, 2008, p. 152). She also cites cases of corporations funding or arming national police or security forces in order to further their own political and material goals, as well as the privatisation of prisons. She also considers both the internal legislation and policing operations of corporations, as well as how '... in recent decades, corporations have also partially supplanted legislative bodies, the [state] police function, and the courts' (ibid. p. 153-154, italics in original). Rather than trust to national or international state courts, corporations increasingly favour privately established international arbitration. The same type of courts in which Ulrich Beck have noted how states are reduced to an equal participant (Beck, 2005). Of particular note to us is that 'companies are increasingly utilizing "machine rule" as a means of partially replacing enforcement of contracts by the courts' (Garrett, 2008, p. 155, citation marks in original). By this she means particularly software code embedded with an automatic termination date of services unless a license is renewed periodically. While recognising the efficiency of this type of automated settlement of potential disputes ("computer says no"), she notes how this 'devolution of contract enforcement mechanisms to private enterprise raises important questions about the nature of contracts themselves' (ibid.). As this automated ruling effectively pre-empts any intervention or recognition by (state) law, she considers whether such a rule is then itself law, and whether it can even be considered a contract⁶. Similarly, she notes how a large corporation like Wal-Mart is able to 'create private international law' (ibid. p. 156 and corporations' ability to 'pre-empt governmental regulation' (ibid. p. 157).

⁶ See also Zuboff (2019) and her extensive treatment of automated contract, leading her to the concept of the 'uncontract'.

In relation to monetary policy, Garrett considers mintage and seignorage – ‘[t]he amount of real purchasing power that [a] government can extract from the public by printing money.’ (Cukierman, quoted in Garrett, 2008, p. 159). She notes in that regard the various ways in which corporate entities can expand or inflate currency, otherwise influence monetary policy, as well as undermine state income through their quasi-currencies, noting the advent of ‘electronic transactions, such as PayPal ...’ (ibid. p. 160).

Finally, in regards to public welfare she notes how, historically (pre-Friedman), corporations have not necessarily considered profit for shareholders their primary reason for being, but have indeed featured discourses we might compare to those surrounding the institutions of the Foucauldian (pastoral) state. Similarly, she considers “corporate social responsibility” (CSR), and how private corporations have, with varying success, built infrastructure in developing countries, and participated in disaster relief. She concludes that there is a general wax of the corporation and wane of the nation state.

In some places, Garrett’s otherwise excellent analysis appears somewhat Western-centric, if not positively US-centric and naïve. She mentions in passing that corporations tend to be meritocracies, and that an (apparently universal) ‘characteristic of ... the nation-state is that citizens of the state have the right of suffrage’ (ibid. pp. 143-144). Similarly, she simplifies greatly (and thus misrepresents) the EU rules on local, national, and supra-national suffrage. With these caveats in mind, Garrett presents a well-put and well-sourced argument. She lists many of the functions, responsibilities, conceptions, and powers of nation states, and proceeds to show how corporations can increasingly be seen to wield the same or similar powers. She shows, on the one hand, how powers of jurisdiction and legality – at least when corporations are concerned – have become detached from the state (and supra-state) apparatuses. At the same time, she shows how various powers and responsibilities formally assigned to the state have increasingly been taken over or imitated by corporations. This includes, but is not limited to, wielding economic power and setting or influencing monetary policy, protecting and providing for society and building and maintaining infrastructure, policing internally and aiding or even carrying out military operations, and engaging in foreign relations. Garrett also briefly treats the issue of sovereignty over land and population. In that regard she emphasises how land – mostly governed by states – has waned in importance related to information –

governed by corporations. Particularly in this regard, I believe the digital modernity can add fuel to her fire. While it may be hard to argue that one can live on – or in – information, as one can on land, the digital offers more nuance to this picture (Lessig, 2006). So let us carry this on to Facebook. First, as a classic state.

4.2.3 The classic state of Facebook

Earlier in this chapter I derived from Weber, Anderson, and the OED that the most basic meaning of “a state” is two-fold. It is, first, the collective socio-spatial entity of the whole community of the state, second, the institutions and/or entities who govern and legitimately exercise violence on behalf of the state.

From the outset, this double definition could seem applicable to a private company or a private home in most contemporary societies. But in both these cases the owner of the property – even if she should give the place a name and its own set of rules – is still subject to the laws of the state on or in which the residence is placed, and the representatives of the state (e.g. the Police) have a monopoly on legitimate violence; an external onus of power that the person and her property is subject to. A private person does not have monopoly on legitimate violence and defining rules in her personal space. She can police it to some degree, hire a private security force and so forth – but they are still subject to state law. Thus, the state is generally considered the main locus of ultimate power and human co-ordination in modern societies, although some argue that this is changing (Garrett, 2008).

I might make all the rules I want within my home, and I might demand my guests follow these rules, but ultimately the rules of the sovereign state on whose land my residence abides bind me, and the representatives of state retain the monopoly on legitimate violence within my home. I may have some limited authority to ask others to dress according to my whims or even ask them to leave, but I am not allowed to use violence and what rights I do have are given to me by law and charter of said state – not by virtue of my own sovereign ownership of my abode (whether I am a renter or owner of my home). For me to truly be the sovereign of my own house, it would need everyone inside the house to agree that we are a nation of House and that I am the ruler of said nation invested with the power of legitimate violence. But this is still not enough, because what happens when the neighbours come knocking and are admitted, but appear hesitant to supplicate and prostrate themselves before my royal person? The state around my

house might frown upon any action I should have to take to get them with the program and ultimately intervene if I incarcerate or attempt other correctional activities on them. Clearly, internal agreement is not enough, and I need other states to recognise my statehood and sovereignty as well (Fuchs, D., 2013). This is where the principles related to the peace of Westphalia comes in. In the example I made up, the people on the area of my state (e.g. the Kingdom of France) and/or the people who are members of the nation I govern (the subjects of France / the French) recognise my sovereignty. But also, the people outside my purview, most notably those with similar claims to sovereignty politically, spiritually, or geographically adjacent to mine, must recognise my right of ultimate rule. Only then can I be the sovereign of a nation, only then can I be the sovereign of the nation of House. In an empiricist (positivist) view, then, to accept something a state, we would require it to be delimited spatially and/or ethnographically, to be organised as a community under one government, and that this governing entity has an internally and externally recognised monopoly on violence within the state and on behalf of the state. In other words, we arrive at the qualifications put forth in the 1933 Montevideo Convention on the Rights and Duties of States: "... a permanent population; (b) a defined territory; (c) government; and (d) capacity to enter into relations with other States" (The Convention, cited in Garrett, 2008, p. 140). Note that (d) has recognition by said states as a logical prerequisite. It does not necessarily follow, however, that said states must recognise said entity as a state.

If we turn this thinking to the digital in general and Facebook in particular, the results are curious, but unclear. It would seem that there are similarities, but also differences. The primary difficulty is the empirical contention that the digital is not actually a place. If the territory – the physical land – is indeed of importance, then the digital fails the test of statehood before even starting, since it arguably has no physical land to speak of. But then again, what of the servers? What of the infrastructure and the uncountable electrons dancing to the tune of the dominant actors online? All of this is different from the territory of a nation state to be sure, but it does exist, and given the private property rights of the US and other countries an argument can be made for sovereignty of and within the physical infrastructure, albeit bound by (inter)national law. Also, let us remember Garrett's point above about information as a means of production to be potentially equated with land (Garrett, 2008). The information stored on these servers is

indisputably owned by Facebook Inc. This information – this code – is what builds the meta-physical space of social interaction. Even if one rejects the meta-physicality of the Facebook platform itself, then this code stored in binary is a physical manifestation of those abstracts we see on screen. In retaining the legal ownership of the information stored on any given instance of the hard drives and random access memory (RAM) modules Facebook Inc. is in control of the physical manifestation of the abstract “place” where people around the globe “go” on a daily basis. In this, we might picture a development of the nature and value of land different than that proposed by Garrett. We might say that as human society became ever more complex, ever more infused with ever denser and more extensive social structures, so too did the construction of land and the real capital it supported and contained. We might even propose a path of economic development looking at how the relative value of land (and other capital) has become ever less about quantity and ever more about quality. We might see how, over a long period, the economic yield of land was increasingly connected to maximising its theoretical-capitalist value to a maximised number of people. Building ever higher in urban areas, digging ever deeper in mining regions, building ever more complex machinery and other developments. We might consider how “real” value was increasingly replaced by ideas of future value, of potential and current trade value. In such a light, the storage units of the Facebook servers – as well as the other tech giants – can perhaps be seen as a temporary endpoint, the furthest the scale has gone as of yet. The connection to physical size, the quantity, has been decoupled, and only the encoding, the quality, of the capital units which are arguably too small to be considered ‘land’, matters. In an increasing layer of abstractions, where now human life and interaction itself has been moved to and mediated by those abstract structures which in turn shape and record them, the physical manifestation of the land of Facebook is quantitatively negligible – but qualitatively immense. A few cubic centimetres of commonplace hard disks in a certain binary configuration not visible to the human eye, worth millions. If we carry this thought experiment to the modern nation states described by Anderson and picked up by the recount of Foucault, then we see that there is a shift from the governance of (people on) a given territory into the governance of particular people (of a “nation”). If we apply this to the digital, and remembering the imagined community, then the important point to consider is whether a given community of people consider themselves to be collectively subject to a given sovereign person or

institution. In this regard, a digital community is almost determinative of community membership in this most basic sense, since the human-computer-code interaction effectively defines a conceptual frame prior to any reflection of the subject. If one goes to Facebook.com and especially if one creates a user there, then one has necessarily joined an imagined community and subjected oneself to Facebook as a sovereign. Rendered as graphics on a computer screen, this imagined community of Facebook-users seems all but tangible. But it is imagined all the same, mediated as it is by keys, screens, and cables. The physicality aside, a member of Facebook is a member of an imagined community. In becoming such a member, she also proclaims to have read and agreed to the terms and conditions of the community and adhere to its rules, as stipulated by, and subject to change by, the company who rules the site. Rules adjudicated by machine law and corporate guidelines, which seldom come under the purview of any state outside Facebook Inc. (Garrett, 2008). In being there, on Facebook, and interacting under the governing codes, the user-citizen implicitly as well as explicitly agrees that the exercise of what meta-physical violence can happen in this milieu is legitimate. Indeed, for most actions performed as a community member, she has no choice, as the actions possible are afforded by the computer code – a step beyond the productive power of pre-digital law (Lessig, 2006). All in all, it appears that in all but the strictest sense, in a classic view Facebook can be said to have both a territory and a population. And Facebook – the compilation of codes rendering and governing the site – together with Facebook Inc. – the company – are recognised by community members as the legal sovereigns of this territory, complete with judicial powers of legislation and a monopoly on legal violence, although the extent and object of this violence is limited by what actions can be defined as violence to the digital subject in an online milieu.

But what of the neighbours? As we have seen, to be considered a state, the automated governance of the code on Facebook and/or the company of Facebook Inc. ruling the site would need to be recognised as sovereign from outside its digital territory. Not just by the members of the imagined community of Facebook, but also by other sovereigns bordering the community in various ways. Starting at the Montevideo qualifications, where recognition is first defined as simply a matter of being able to have relations with (other) entities already defined as states, it is hard to argue against. If we look at how Facebook and Alphabet (Google) in particular are de facto treated by political institutions like the EU, the

US Congress, and nation states like Denmark, these relations certainly appear more like mutually recognised international relations than dictates from state(s) over subject(s) (Garrett, 2008; Wichowski, 2021). Indeed, Denmark has literally sent an ambassador to the tech industry in Silicon Valley (Office of Denmark's Tech Ambassador, 2019), an example other countries have since followed (Wichowski, 2021).

In the online realm, the lines are more blurred than in the physical states mentioned above (Floridi, 2020). Certainly, the servers and programmers working on and in the digital spaces they govern are situated in the physical world. But the virtual spaces created for social and meta-physical actions, such as “waving”, “clapping”, “sharing”, “liking”, and commenting, are located somewhere else: on the Internet, in cyberspace – not to mention, arguably, in people’s minds (Lessig, 2006). A place where, increasingly, modern states (viewed as actors) are seeking influence. But, as is evident by how they do so, still a place they consider outside of their direct control. In the end, modern nation states are neither policing nor defining these spaces – the “companies” that build and continuously re-build them, Facebook Inc. among them – are. Generally, offline states neither dictate, define, nor police the actions taken by users in the online milieu. They do, however, police the companies themselves, and they are empowered by said companies to aid in or dictate terms for the policing of the digital realm by taking actions in the physical. In this we may simply see a pendant to how states deal with other states whose policies they disagree with – not by actively taking part in their internal affairs (discounting for argument’s sake declared wars and covert military action), but by putting restraints on the country’s ability to trade freely with other entities (Fuchs D. , 2013). On the other hand, nation states can regulate the wider legal framework the platforms operate in, and in recent years, they are increasingly doing so. In 2017 a milestone was passed when Germany passed a law making failure of a social network company to react swiftly to reported hate crimes or similar offences punishable by German law (Bundesrepublik Deutschland, 2017). In the following year, especially Facebook faced growing critique and scandals such as the uncovered Russian tampering with the 2016 US presidential and other elections, the company Cambridge Analytica’s involvement in the so-called Brexit referendum, and the problem of targeted and/or ‘false’ news and ads in general (Koopman, 2019). This has led to hearings and interventions from the EU, the US, and various smaller political entities, such as the UK. I have elsewhere noted how the EU has sought to ‘soft govern’ hate speech filters and the likes

through round-table discussions (Brønholt, 2017; 2020). The most significant and most recent governance acts in relation to Facebook is arguably the EU's 2018 GDPR Regulation, and their 2020 White Paper on AI with more to follow in 2021 and beyond. The General Data Protection Regulation framework sets strong limits to the data public or private companies and institutions can hold on EU citizens, and how. The white paper seeks to coordinate, control, and strengthen the development of algorithmic technologies within the EU. This increasing political attention and growing will to regulate can at least in part be seen as an attempt to assert control over influential entities who are seen to wield immense social and institutional power. "Tech" companies in general and social media companies in particular are increasingly seen to host massive spurious and unpredictable effects to societies and democracy such as the ones just noted. As a result of this, they are targets of criticism and debate, and their representatives have been brought to testify before parliaments across the democracies of the world and accept responsibility for any and all potentially damaging effects enabled by their technologies. Even still, much of the critique has called for accountability and has asserted the companies' obligation to self-governance on their platforms. Indeed, much of the regulation in place asserts and re-affirms the web site owners' (sole) authority to govern and police their sites internally whilst only demanding compliance as to how the front- and back-ends of this governance and policing is handled. Regulation such as the GDPR does not seek to overstep the boundaries into the digital, it simply constrains the real-world frames encasing it.

All in all, as with the corporations treated by Doris Fuchs and Garrett above, the picture is not clear. On the one hand, states and the EU supra-state seem to clearly assert their sovereignty over Facebook Inc. and its operations. On the other hand, the way in which they do so tends to reinforce rather than delimit the company's sovereignty on their platform. To my knowledge, no state entities have taken steps to conduct policing operations on Facebook themselves. This would be technically possible. As would dictating and changing the particular rules of service and any other coded or uncoded rules. In this regard state and supra-state lawmakers seem content to treat Facebook as a sovereign state, interacting only with the corporate heads of said state and staying out of the minutiae of their internal affairs. This appears consistent with the general trend identified by scholars comparing corporations and states (Beck, 2005; Garrett, 2008; Fuchs D. , 2013). The significance of Facebook, then, lies not in the corporation being treated

as a quasi-sovereign, but rather in this treatment combined with the governance of a meta-physical space of human being. In treating Facebook Inc. like a mega-corporation, which is to treat it like a quasi-sovereign of its own affairs, the state representatives – not to mention representatives of the fourth estate and other private critics – are reiterating Facebook’s right and duty not just to rule, but to police and discipline its users, in its online milieu. In other words, they are recognised within and without, as the arbiter of legal violence, in their part of the digital. Albeit a constrained such.

It appears that at least some arguments can be made for Facebook as a state, according to a classical view of the state, and the Montevideo qualifications. Let us explore further, following the categories laid out by Garrett, and take a look at the economic power and control of monetary policy exercised by and on Facebook.

4.2.4 The economic and monetary power of Facebook

Comparing the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (based on purchasing power parity) of a country to the revenue of a corporation is a flawed exercise. They measure different things, for different entities. Even so, though qualitatively different, they do say something about the size, reach, and impact of the different entities’ economic operations (Garrett, 2008). In 2008, the time of Garret’s writing, the largest company revenue of the Fortune 500 is that of Wal-Mart which was at that time \$315.6 billion (ibid.). Wal-Mart’s revenue for 2020 was \$559.2 billion (Miscellaneous, 2021A). This is over 6 times the \$85.965 million (≈ 86.0 billion) for Facebook Inc. in the same year (Facebook, 2021A). The other tech giants of Amazon, Apple, Alphabet (Google), and Microsoft are all on the top 50 of the Fortune 500 list, with a reported revenue (in billions) of \$386.0, \$274.5, \$182.5 and \$143.0, respectively (Miscellaneous, 2021A). Facebook Inc. ranks as number 144 on the list (Fortune, 2021). Facebook Inc. is thus economically smaller than other large corporations, but its reported revenue of \$85.965 million for 2020 is still slightly higher than the GDP (PPP) of Slovenia, the projected 97th largest world economy in 2021 (Miscellaneous, 2021B). This means that Facebook Inc.’s revenue for last year is higher than this year’s estimated GDP (PPP) for 99 of the 195 countries on that list. While less ‘staggering’ than the discrepancies analysed by Garret (2008, p. 147), Facebook Inc. does have some economic muscle. A decision by the company to invest or divest in a given

country could have tremendous effects on that country's economy – not least given the relative fluidity and geographical elasticity of the internet-based operations, compared to the geographically bound countries. Further, due to the particular nature of Facebook's services, the platform itself has the potential to indirectly influence politics and policies of most nations. There is no immediate reason to assume that Facebook Inc. is anything but sincere in their stated desire to mediate truth and opinions with as little editorial intervention as possible, even trying to counter filter bubble effects and other unwanted detriments to free debate (Bakshy, Messing, & Adamic, 2015) (see Chapters 6 & 7). Even so, the potential alone cannot be discounted – something that could be linked to the well-known *Soft Power* of Joseph Nye (Nye, 1990), and related to the agenda-setting power of Bachrach & Baratz (1962) from Chapter 3. Also, the connections Facebook mediate between businesses and consumers (not to mention politicians and voters) impact both individuals and the economies in which they reside. Simply put, changes to the Facebook infrastructure can have significant economic effects to advertisers, buyers, sellers, and through them to the wider economy (Facebook, 2019G).

A large infrastructural change spearheaded by Facebook and bound to impact the economies of several countries has been in the works for some time, is the Diem framework. Under its former name (Libra) the Diem was conceptualised as an online currency which was to be integrated in the services of Facebook and those of other virtual and/or financial sites and services (Diem Association, 2020). Implementing the Diem on the various apps of Facebook and their partners should '... enable financial inclusion, broad competition, and responsible innovation and thus facilitate the creation of services for the unbanked and underbanked' (ibid. p. 2). Something which on the one hand seemed a laudable goal for those target consumer-users, on the other a sound business case, potentially undercutting existing money transfer companies, and providing further income-generating services for new customers. Upon announcement in June 2019, the project seemed poised for instant success, listing prominent experts in financial transaction, such as Visa, PayPal, MasterCard, and eBay amongst its partners (Brühl, 2020; Browne, 2021A). The Libra project got caught up with the rest of Facebook Inc. in the heavy critique of the time and faced strong political opposition (Browne, 2021A). This led the aforementioned partners, and others to withdraw support, and Facebook, together with the rest of the association took steps to change the scope and nature of the

project. Now, in 2021, what is currently proposed is a pilot featuring a stablecoin pegged to the US dollar, coupled with a system that allows for financial transactions in the US area, rather than a stand-alone currency (i.e. the Libra) (Browne, 2021B). At the time of writing, though, the Libra (sic) is still featured in the White Paper as a single-currency stablecoin, to be used in 'countries that do not have a single-currency stablecoin on the Libra network' (Diem Association, 2020, p. 11).

Overarching, the Diem is now mainly conceptualised as a framework for the electronic exchange of existing currencies, with 100% financial backing (a massive percentage, compared to banks and other financial institutions) (Diem Association, 2020). This differs from the original Libra concept, which intended to use Libra as a currency across countries and regions and could be said to more closely mimic that of a nation state currency. It was to have been a stand-alone currency, held up by various assets, including other currencies and state bonds (Brühl, 2020). In the original conception, the sovereign currency of Facebook, pre-approved and to be implemented as a usable currency by the largest handlers of fiscal transactions in the world would have been easy to compare to a currency of a (rather large) state. With the resources of the Facebook company alone – and especially with the resources of the whole of the original Libra group behind it as well – this currency would have been significantly trusted and likely had become an instantly stable (and valuable) currency. Still, the curtailed version of the framework without the universal implementation of the coin, the Diem, can have remarkable effects. Should Facebook and the rest of the Diem Association finally succeed in rolling it out internationally (which I remain convinced that they eventually will), the consequences could well be staggering. The simple effects of further entrenching the Facebook apps as an integral part of people's lives would exacerbate the colonisation of and influence on people's lives. Further, allowing some currencies and not others to be traded instantly via the framework could drastically undermine some and strengthen others. While the implementation in the US is unlikely to have much of a dollarization effect, the formerly unbanked people and communities, as well as those whose transaction costs for international transfers will drop drastically might very well prefer to start trading in US dollars or Euros (or Libras), rather than unstable local currencies. Even as Facebook Inc. is institutionally separated from the Diem, the network would be a great boon to their apps, and the company. Though they would not directly benefit from the seignorage boost to the US possibly arising from

the implementation of a diem-based exchange of US Dollars, a side effect of providing the framework for an increasingly important medium of exchange and distribution of the currency is – at least theoretically – that Facebook might take over a role akin to that of a second (independent) central bank of multiple countries. The current, curtailed version of the framework, with full backing and a commitment to only creating 1:1 copies of existing currencies means that the Diem framework will not be able to freely “print money”. As such, they will on the offset be more akin to a large bank (or a credit card / financial transaction company), and much more curtailed due to the 1:1 backing percentage, than to a central bank. In the current version of the Diem White Paper, however, there is an invitation for central banks to ‘be directly integrated into the Libra network’, when they develop central bank digital currencies (CBDCs) (Diem Association, 2020, p. 11). In effect this would enable national currency money to be created directly on the network. Although I am still stretching the similarities somewhat, this can be seen as similar to having the Diem association take over the printing and distribution of said currencies. The Diem is shuttered from direct contact with Facebook Inc. and is otherwise intentionally limited in scope. The consortium’s white paper considers and addresses many of the worries spurred by the original Libra proposal, attempting to allay many fears through a commitment to non-interference with monetary and fiscal policy, and dedication to collaboration with central banks, states, and other stakeholders (Diem Association, 2020). To further curtail their potential powers, the association has also devolved the power of currency conversion, ensuring that ‘... any such exchange functionality would be conducted by third-party financial service providers’ (Diem Association, 2020, p. 11).

The original plans for the Libra did in many ways look as if Facebook was making a bid for statehood, empire, or something akin to such sovereign political entities. The Diem, and the rhetoric around it seems humbler in comparison, at least for now, and is not yet a reality. Though the IT infrastructure is ready to go, the launch has been delayed time and again, in its comparatively slow crawl toward implementation (Browne, 2019; 2021A; 2021B). Comparatively slow, given that we are talking about a contemporary tech solution to a perceived market (or problem, depending on definition) (Zuboff, 2019; Morozov, 2013). Still, the infrastructure will come, and the effects should not be taken lightly. No matter the words of assurance, and no matter the institutional and procedural knee taken to the nation states of the Bretton Woods

system, the US state chief among them, the Diem framework will and must cause effects to monetary and fiscal policies near and far. The repeated promises not to cause disruptions, the efforts to make the association independent, transparent, and separate from Facebook and the promises not to wield the potential power the control of such a system all speak to the potential of their opposites. I would argue that the original plans for the Libra could have very much been likened to a fledgling nation state establishing a somewhat independent central bank to mint their independent currency. An economically strong state at that, and a strong currency to boot, backed in potential, options, and opportunities, rather than simply the faded gold of an old world. The Diem is less than that. But even kept institutionally separate from Facebook, and even though it promises to mainly distribute digital copies of (fully backed) existing currencies rather than its own, the implementation of such a network on Facebook's services does mean at the very least one thing: Facebook will become the authority that defines the legal subjects in relation to payment and bank operations across the globe. As a partner of Diem, Facebook Inc. will continue to play a major role in defining the rules surrounding those third-party partners and institutions allowed to trade, and to define who can trade on the platform. One of those partners will be Facebook Inc. themselves. Even assuming the most benevolent of purposes, when Facebook Inc. becomes the entity that enables and governs the transfer of wealth, it becomes yet more a crucial institution in the lives of its user-citizens. And it certainly becomes more than just another corporation. Meanwhile, the Diem Association may not coin their own currency at face value – but the creation and distribution of digital meta-currencies will inevitably mean a degree of control with the trading and distribution of those currencies. Even if the intent and effect would be benevolent and/or conservatory in relation to existing inequalities, it is hard to imagine a world with and without this network being the same in terms of trading value and seignorage connected to nation states. Especially weaker ones. Once everyone gets access to real-time transfer and usage of stable, international currencies such as the US dollar, the Euro, the Remnibi, or the Libra (or at least their digital counterparts), it is hard to imagine that usage and seignorage of weak, local currencies are long for this world. A boon for those hurt by the volatility of those currencies, perhaps, but hardly without consequences for the nation states that print them – or for the networks that distribute them.

All in all, the Diem is not quite as revolutionary as the Libra might have looked for a time. It is institutionally separate from Facebook, and it is not yet implemented. At the same time, the short story of the Diem so far seems yet another foreshadowing of a corporation outgrowing a state (Garrett, 2008). It might be slow in coming and it might first, even mainly, act as a vessel for neo-imperial power of the global north, but it will also shift powers and authorities into the digital, onto the Facebook platform. The plans to institute a currency standard, and a cross-national, standardised means of trade speaks of an institutional, political power in relation to fiscal and monetary policies and more, at least resembling that of a state – if not a supra-state, or an empire.

It is worthy of note how the narrative around the Diem (and the Libra) clearly emphasises a benevolent intent for the user-citizens. Most especially the ‘... large global underbanked and unbanked population ...’, and of course ‘... innovation [and] software developers’ (Diem Association, 2020, p. 19). In her assessment of corporate vis-à-vis state power, the final factor considered by Garrett is public welfare. Let us consider Facebook in that light.

4.2.5 The public welfare of Facebook

The original intent of Facebook, according to its own marketing material is: ‘... to help people stay connected and bring us closer together with the people that matter to us’ (Zuckerberg, 2018C). While this might well be easily discounted in a Marxist analysis, ultimately exposing the capitalist intent to exhort and maximise profit (Morozov, 2019), the assertion should not be fully ignored. Even viewed most cynically, a connection created for profit could at least theoretically provide some good for the ones being connected, and as such could point to a benign intent at least being part of the reasoning behind one or more decisions made. The analysis of the governmentality of the digital state of Facebook is yet to come, but even at this pre-analytical point the repeated assertions of the company in general, and Mark Zuckerberg in particular about the benevolent intent for “their” user-citizens should be highlighted (e.g. Zuckerberg, 2018C) (see Chapters 6, 7, and 8).

Garrett emphasises how in recent history the US has utilised corporations as means to achieve public goods and utilities (Garrett, 2008, pp. 161-162). Quoting Hammill (1999), she emphasises that chartered

corporations were 'granted privileges in the form of monopolies or franchises' (as cited in Garrett, 2008, p. 162), to incentivise through rentability the private investment in infrastructure developments. Though the Facebook network and the Facebook site were not planned by a nation state government, the de facto state of affairs surrounding Facebook Inc. does resemble such a setup. Taken together, the services offered by Facebook, can be seen as an enhanced version of what was offered by first the telegraph and later the telephone companies (Schiller, 2020). Whether the Internet is the cables, the electricity, or just the poles in this analogy (with the social network underneath the site GUI then being the critical infrastructure resembling the telephones, the operator, or the cables), is beside the larger point: Whatever it has been, and whatever we can compare it to, the Facebook service can be seen as a de facto public utility (Schiller, 2020).

Apart from the general utility of the service(s) the Facebook platform provides and the (at least rhetorically) benevolent intent towards the users, Facebook Inc. also actively supports and launches initiatives aimed at improving the public welfare of people on and off their platform. Following the Marxist critique mentioned, I acknowledge that these might also be seen as simple marketing ploys or even "whitewashing". With this caveat, however, I note that Facebook has built a dedicated sub-platform for 'social impact', with guides and features aimed at 'empowering people to make the world a better place through tools that have positive real-world impact (Facebook, 2021B)', as well as how they utilise for example the 2021 Ramadan to promote a 'month of good' (Facebook, 2021C). Still, the potential public good of these things – as well as aiding efforts to hold free and fair elections in Africa (Gyekye, 2020), 'keeping children safe' (Facebook, 2018), or '[driving] innovation in energy-efficient technology' (Facebook Research, 2021) must be weighed against the criticism Facebook has faced for the damages caused, by their "real-name" policies (MacKinnon, 2012), by the recorded efforts to 'dupe' children to spend money from their parents' credit card (Halverson, 2019), and the inaction in response to and subsequent firing of a data scientist frustrated that Facebook was not doing all they could to prevent political crimes, and had 'blood on their hands' (Ortutay, 2021). All in all, for whatever reasons, Facebook has arguably engaged in activity aimed to improve the public welfare. They may have done so only as marketing stunts, as excuses not to do more, or reluctantly, but something has been done. There may be inherent problems with letting

a formally “private” company take responsibility for action dealing with such complex issues, but then the issue here is one of statehood, not actual benevolence. I will not go further into the numerous examples of the cases where some argue that Facebook should have done more or different – or the cases where they present the work they have done to – at least at face value – improve the world one way or the other. What we can take from those discussions is a confirmation of my earlier assertion: people, press, and politicians apparently expect and demand that Facebook Inc. be the entity that polices political and military operations on or via the Facebook platform. We can add to that, that whether they also do ill, whether they do enough, and whether, in an idealised world, they are the ones we would want to attempt doing good, Facebook is doing more than nothing for the public welfare in the offline world. In other words, we can confirm that Facebook provides – indeed is – a public good, that the management of Facebook Inc. appears – at least in some degree, and in some cases – to be intent toward public good in their policing of users, and that they do launch and support initiatives with benevolent purposes for people and communities across the world.

Some arguments are beginning to appear. But to make a case, we must also allow for objections. Let us consider some points to the contrary. Let us hear why Facebook should not be seen as a state.

4.2.6 Wider theoretical considerations

In a Critical Rationalist view, claiming Facebook as a state might be considered at best a weak theory, at worst a non-falsifiable circular claim (Popper, 2008 [1963]). Rather than skirt this objection, I will consider various ways of making sense of Facebook Inc. as a state and see if there are arguments to falsify (or strengthen) the idea.

I have argued that from an epistemological view, it is both meaningful and fruitful to view certain online platforms as states. While I recognise the ontological difference between a digital and an offline state, I thus assert that the empirical reality of the state-like mechanics and effects of such states, as well as the gains in sophistication in the analyses made possible by this view, supersedes what realist quibbles we might have about what is, in some sense of the word, “real”. A staunch realist might reject the notion that a state without geographical territory (apart from some servers) can be “a state”. But I remind that a state

is an inherently abstract concept no less rooted in observable object realities than is truth, deities, or love. If one acknowledges that virtual spaces are subjectively real to subjects, then an entity such as Facebook easily fits the first descriptors of a state. The users see themselves as part of a community, and there are those who can exercise legitimate violence over those users within that community (Weber, 2002[1922]; Anderson, 2006). Some of them – users and exercisers of violence – are human, some machine. According to a broad, classical view of what constitutes a state all that is needed for Facebook to be seen as such is the acceptance that virtual space is as real to subjects of an imagined community as the abstract spaces only seen on maps. Facebook, then, might be seen as a state, even in the broader sense.

Viewing globalised corporations as state-like actors – or at least actors of a similar strength and scope – is not a novel idea (Beck, 2005; Fuchs D. , 2013; Miller, 1960). The argument here, however, is slightly different from those put forward by Beck and others in his wake. In a classical-realist view, I would emphasise the meta-physical territory owned and governed by digital states. My claim concerns corporations who attain de facto ownership and/or governance of physical or digital spaces inhabited by people – such as we have historically seen with the various East India Companies, a comparison which is not unheard of in the literature (Zuboff, 2019; Couldry & Mejias, 2019). These are the cases where it is commonly accepted that companies have become de facto states, and this is the notion I compare to the social space in the digital, governed by Facebook Inc. This notion of statehood has, of course, also been (in-)famously noted by the president of Facebook, Mark Zuckerberg (Kirkpatrick, 2011, p. 254).

It follows from this view, and the recognition explored above that various theories of International Relations (IR) are applicable to these companies in general and Facebook in particular. In a realist framework, Facebook Inc. is ever amassing more (virtual) territory, subjects, and resources; in a neo-realist framework, the company is seeking hegemony in its sphere; in an institutionalist perspective, Facebook Inc.'s steps to establish an independent institution of its own design, population, and making to oversee the policies of itself and others seem eerily similar to narratives about 'soft power' (Nye, 1990) and mirrors efforts to maintain a liberal world order according to US doctrines through international institutions even after the downfall of its military dominance. These assertions invite further questions. Even accepting

digital spaces as subjectively “real”, can moderators be considered a police force? – can a state be operated from inside a different state? – can a state exist without an army (or, analogue to the question about the police force, can privately owned cybercrime units be considered as armed forces)? But the answers to these and similar critiques are implicitly answered by the methodological and paradigmatic choices outlined above: If we accept Facebook as a state, which I argue we should – at least could – then an affirmative answer to all of these follow. Not least given that (offline) nation states increasingly deploy military and police resources in the digital realm (Klimburg, 2011).

It seems that – at least for now – the idea of Facebook Inc. as a state stands. It is important to remind at this point that my focus is on the digital state as a collection of techniques, not as an entity. Facebook is treated as a proxy for the emerging institutions and techniques of the digital state. Facebook-as-a-state is thus not the object of inquiry in this thesis, but Facebook is the site where this specific inquiry must be situated. In treating governance of Facebook users as subjects of the digital state, I am at the very least implying a state-like power to flow through Facebook. The platform is coded, maintained, steered and ruled first and foremost by Facebook Inc. Establishing the corporation as something we could call a state situates the analysis of the digital state, and lends power to the insights they afford. Let us turn towards an answer.

4.2.7 Facebook is a state (of sorts)

Putting together what we have learned, the answer seems clear: Facebook Inc. is a state. While it is not the same as a concurrent nation state, and while it cannot quite be compared to a strong, contemporary Western state in all the ways in which we might assess and bestow the nomenclature, Facebook Inc. can be said to meet the qualifications of statehood. Many of the arguments behind this assertion grow directly from work by other scholars, most particularly Garrett, arguing that big, multi-national corporations in general can be seen as states. The abstract features of the state-like companies she identifies in theory all seem to appear in the concrete case of Facebook Inc. To this we can add the particular nature of Facebook, the platform. While many consumers might enter a Wal-Mart and be more or less willingly nudged and guided toward purchasing decisions, the citizen-users of Facebook are indefinitely influenced in potentially all social actions they take on and off the platform. Add to this the imminent roll-out of the Diem network,

and the real-world effects of administration of justice on the platform. While nation states may be waning, and corporations may be waxing, Facebook as policy and platform, together with Facebook Inc. as sovereign seems much further progressed along most of these measures than even the largest non-tech corporation.

Table 1: Categories of State - Nation state, corporation, and Facebook

State responsibilities	Nation state	Corporation	Facebook
Permanent Population & Defined Territory	Yes (waning)	No	Yes (waxing)
Economic Power	Yes (waning)	Some (waxing)	Some (waxing)
Capacity to Engage in Foreign Relations	Yes	Yes	Yes
Protection of Society	Yes	Some (waxing)	Yes, internally
Administration of Justice	Yes (waning)	Some (waxing)	Yes, internally
Monetary Policy	Yes (waning)	Some (waxing)	Some (waxing)
Public Welfare	Yes (waning)	Some (waxing)	Yes, internally

**Categories and categorisation of Nation state and Corporation based on Garrett (2008).*

I have explored the case for Facebook Inc. as a state, and found the evidence in support rich and the objections unconvincing. Indeed, it seems to me that all successful falsifications of a hypothesis proposing Facebook as a state would inadvertently necessitate that we equally deny statehood to many existing nation states. A list of states would normally feature countries such as the Vatican State, Somalia, and Yemen, but if we set up limitations to statehood in order to rule out Facebook, many such small or “weak” states would also not make the cut.

I would not argue that Facebook Inc. is a comparable state to that of a larger, stable country, like the US, or even a supra-state like the EU – but I find that it most certainly can be seen as a state, and (perhaps more importantly) that it has features and powers at the very least matching those of various states, and in some cases reminiscing supra-states or even nascent empires. An overarching consideration to note is that as the various institutions in the concrete and abstract change – along with the societies they are in and of – so do the concepts of “state”, “corporation”, and “platform”. In the rest of this thesis I avoid getting bogged down further in these considerations of what exactly does constitute an X, and whether Y is one of those. Another, somewhat similar, way to consider these changes, is to look at them from a societal point of view, considering the emerging ‘platform societies’ of our age (van Dijck, Poell, & de Waal,

2018). I should add that had this project been about Amazon or Google (Alphabet), this particular case might have been stronger and clearer, yet. Both companies are significantly bigger, economically, than Facebook, and the nature of their services are potentially, in each their way, even more potent in terms of a similar case about statehood (Moore & Tambini, 2018). Arguably, the Alexa and Google Assistant's services are as intimately integrated into the life of data subjects as any services Facebook provides. Meanwhile Google, at least to the same degree as Facebook, has the power to issue what we might call a "digital passport" – a confirmed identity with which the user can authenticate herself across the services of countless sites and apps (Google, 2021) and Amazon, which is firmly rooted in the connection between the digital and the physical, differentiates prices according to murky calculations (Calvano, Calzolari, Denicolò, & Pastorello, 2019) – something which could potentially be likened to a state erecting internal and external customs barriers, not to mention the "tax" Amazon takes for providing the infrastructure that connects buyer and seller. For my purposes, however, these two companies are much more murky in the ways in which they interconnect the physical and the digital, compared to Facebook. The goal remains to ascertain the governmentality of the digital state. To this end, Facebook is simply better suited for analysis. The state power that operates through the platform is more readily available and is mediated almost exclusively in the digital. A study involving physical artefacts, material things, and their interconnections with the user-subjects is surely an intriguing proposal. But it would be another study – and likely one more suited to a different theoretical frame, such as the materialist tradition of Habermas and others, or the Actor-Network-Theory of Bruno Latour (Latour, 2005). For this Foucauldian study Facebook remains the site of study best suited to ascertain the governmentality of the digital state.

I have shown how the case can be made for viewing Facebook as a state. A sometimes strong, sometimes weak state, perhaps a sometimes dominated state, but a state none-the-less. What is important is the assertion that the technologies of digital state operate on Facebook, and as such that the governmentalities of digital state can be understood through analyses relating to the site. With this, I move now back to the main narrative. Before this section I explored the type and governmentality of the modern state as analysed by Foucault. Now, I turn fully to the matter at hand, and propose – within this framework – the digital state. This newest iteration of state is in part to be seen as the modern state in the era and arena of the digital

but is presented first as a novel (ideal-)type of state (technology) to follow the modern state like it itself followed the sovereign state.

4.3 The state of digital modernity

I have established Facebook as a state. We have seen that corporations and states overlap increasingly in some of their functions, and that some particular corporations can be said to have more state powers and functions than some particular states. We have also heard arguments supporting the idea that nation states are an increasingly passé and passing mode of human organisation, poised to be eclipsed by corporations. When looked at from a de-materialist ontology, however, it is of less importance what exactly the state *is*, and we should rather focus on what the state / government *does*. Returning now to the re-enforced Foucauldian frame, I will develop the theory of the digital state whose governmentality I seek to understand.

4.3.1 A digital place for the digital state

The modern state is a defining feature of the era – or eras – of modernity and beyond. Whether it be understood as entity, phenomenon, or as a collection of techniques of subjection, it appears to us as something not before seen. The late modern, second modern or even post-modern time of post-industrialist societies has yet to see a halt to the immense changes in physical, social, and individual conditions which some trace to the industrial era, some further back. Indeed, some see these changes as having sped up their cadence (Harari, 2015). An important change of the latter years is the increasing digitalisation of human economic, social, and political life. Whether one ascribes these changes to the emergence of the Internet, or rather to tendencies preceding and surrounding it (Koopman, 2019), the change itself is hard to dispute. As such, one might say we live in the age of digital modernity (O'Hara, 2020).

As humans (of the sapiens race, I should add, given the reference to Harari) were connected digitally, there emerged new abstract places and spaces for social and individual play and inter-play (Žižek, 1998; Lessig, 2006; Pariser, 2011; Sunstein, 2007; Snowden, 2019; Clarke, 1994). These spaces were built by code –

written instructions codified and systematised to enable the creation of especially graphic representations of abstract interactive meta-physical creations. It seems all but “natural” to us now but consider explaining computer programming – or even just Facebook – to anyone born before the 19th century. For that matter, consider explaining it to yourself in a meaningful way, without any inside point of reference. There is a reason some refer to this as “the digital revolution”, complete with declarations of independence, such as the perhaps most famous one by John Perry Barlow (1996). Humans entering the digital can perhaps be likened to those engaged in the Republic of Letters or the use of the Gutenberg printing press. But in other ways it resembles just as much how we might imagine the before and after of invention and spread of writing or language itself. A process that took hundreds, if not thousands of years, depending on your operationalisation of the question (Harari, 2015). I view this process as similar to those surrounding other techniques and entities of history described by Foucault and outlined in the chapters to come. Just as material and conceptual developments lead from the sovereign state to the emergence of the modern state, the material and conceptual changes surrounding subjecthood and power as modernity has switched to digital modernity and brought forth a new modality of state, one that I call the digital state. In the same way that modern humans came to increasingly accept and internalise nationalism to the extent that they would consider nationhood (and subjecthood to the sovereign nation state) a basic, universal fact of life, the humans of digital modernity have come to see themselves as existing in the digital - as being (in part) our data (Koopman, 2019). Now, the wider digital space we live in seems nigh as natural as the physical bodies the timeless We seem always to have inhabited.

The currently most visible and consciously known part of the web of information surrounding us emerged in the early 21st century and was later dubbed Social Media. The by all accounts most successful and widespread of these undertakings in facilitation of social interaction between individuals, groups, and societies (with both human and non-human entities) is Facebook (Kirkpatrick, 2011). Due to its emergence and primary existence in the digital, Facebook – to the extent that the object can be treated as an instance of that abstract called state – is inherently digital in nature: if it be a state, it is a digital state. This is not to say that digital statedom is exclusive to Facebook, nor to entities that have emerged or operate primarily in the digital realm. Nation states have digitised or informationalised their subjects, and as masterfully

shown by Koopman (2019), this process predates the emergence of the Internet, and is ongoing (Clarke, 2014). Thus, when talking about a digital state – and the governmentality of such – one could also look at nation states operating on and through that which we call digital. From the Scottish state offering a voluntary digital ID with various benefits, over the Danish state increasingly seeking ways to govern subjects (and facilitate the self-governance of subjects) through digital techniques, to the Chinese Social Credit System, which is perhaps mirrored by, worse than or less randomly unfair than the corporate US surveillant assemblage employed when determining insurance and credit scores (Zuboff, 2019; Haggerty & Ericson, 2000; Scottish Government, 2019; Clarke, 2014). Nation states of modernity having gone digital in various ways and forms, however, is still intertwined with everything else they are and do. The digital part of what a concrete modern nation state apparatus does is relevant and might be expected to mirror and influence the implications of the findings here, but of particular interest here is the abstract state operating in and through the digital plane. As such, Facebook appears as the obvious choice for my research site, the closest to the purest type of the digital state (technology) as we might get. Whether or not the corporation Facebook Inc. can be named “a state”, which I have argued above that it can, the platform Facebook is a site for digital state power and subjection.

Further and equally important for my purposes, whatever critiques have been levied against Facebook as an entity, a site, a company, and a state, it is very visible and accessible to a researcher. First, the digital platform itself – the meta-physical place where subjection and governance originally and perhaps mainly take place – is accessible to anyone willing, with a click, to lie about having read and understood the terms and conditions. Second, the many considerations and decisions about governance and power made by Facebook Inc. tend to have been publicly visible, and associated with press statements, reports, blogs and various content from especially CEO and would-be ‘leviathan’ Mark Zuckerberg (Pontin, 2012; Harari, 2017). Third, said decisions have been debated and scrutinised widely by both politicians, press, and academia. In the process of these discussions, various internal documents have been leaked, making the governing logics of Facebook yet more visible. Indeed, contemporary social scientists might lament the attention the governance of our digital selves currently receive, compared to the political structures we

are governed by in many other aspects of our daily lives. This, too makes Facebook a strong choice as my site of study.

As we have seen above, the virtual spaces we see in Facebook can be said to fit the definitions of a state. But the only real issue at stake here is whether a collection of techniques of subjection we might call state operate on and via Facebook. Within its metaphysical frame, Facebook is an organised community under one government – and this government (whether “it” be headed by Facebook Inc. by nation states, or by something else entirely) has a monopoly on (meta-)physical, legitimate violence. It can incarcerate data doubles, it can restrict (social) actions proactively and retrospectively, and it defines the rules according to which this happens. By its very definition a totalitarian state, albeit it one in which you can arguably choose to no longer exist (or at least relinquish control of your data double). All of this makes the object and digital space of Facebook an immensely suitable site for the investigation of the digital state.

4.3.2 Cyber policy

I have established the digital state as a Foucauldian technology akin to and overlapping with preceding Foucauldian concepts such as the modern state and the sovereign state. Both as concepts and as concrete instances of state, an integral part of the various types of state (technology) is the techniques to govern subjects. As we have seen in the review of the work of Foucault and others, these techniques have shifted and changed over time, being sometimes replaced by others in new state modalities, at other times continued as practices of state and governance persist across paradigms and techniques of state and governmentality.

A central feature of state is the policing of subjects (Foucault, 1979A). In studies of the modern state the specific initiatives and tactics explicitly employed in the governance of subjects are termed policies. Following the idea of modern state governmentality as coupled with a quest to “mathesise” subjects, policies are articulated as formal strategies intended to create desired outcomes in the form of re-formations of the objectified political subjects, individually and collectively (Foucault, 2006 [1979]). In mathesised terms, the political subjects of the modern state are seen as changeable constants (s) who – through policies (p) can be changed to a state closer to the individual and collective salvation which is the

ultimate end of the new pastoral power (Foucault, 1982): $p(s) = s^1$, where s^1 is the desired future state of the subjects individually and collectively. Expressing the techniques of formation of subjects as ciphers in this mathematical way quickly puts one in the mind of formalised “social sciences”, such as Economics and (Quantitative) Political Science. Indeed, these disciplines are to be seen as a part of the governmentality “package” rather than something external to and independent from it (Foucault, 1989 [1966]). I should further note that many governmentality analyses and this thesis among them can be discursively placed within the stated fields of social science and as such parts of the struggle to define the means and ends of power. The reason I bring attention to this formulation of a policy as a mathematised ideal – a formula describing a policy as a controlled intervention with mathematical precision and effect – is its resemblance to computer code. With some few exceptions, computer code is built up using binary logic. Essentially that means that whatever the code handles and is supposed to do, the output is some version and instance of 1 or 0 (in this simplified view, “error” or “null” are simply 1’s or 0’s to a binary statement somewhere in the extended code hierarchy). Thus, another way of describing a policy could be, as a function in the programming language Python:

```
Subject1 = Subject.policy
```

This example is simply a rewrite of the above statement. It states that an elsewhere defined policy mitigates the global Subject and the result is Subject1. This could mean a change of one of the global subjects projected or its real-time attributes. Depending on the scope and design of said policy, the subject can be programmed to probabilistically live longer, become healthier, be terminated, or be imprisoned (Amoore, 2011). Apart from the visual representation of what contemporary readers might recognise as formalised computer code, this way of constituting and working upon political subjects does not differ from that described by Foucault (Foucault, 2006 [1979]). In other words, policies are to be seen as yet another instance of that which Foucault terms ‘techniques of government’ (ibid. p. 143). In this light, the codes that define the actions and interactions possible in the digital social spaces on Facebook are to be seen as digital pendants to the rules that govern social behaviour and spaces in the offline world. There is a difference, however: in defining how the spaces and subjects are to be constituted and reflected, these constitutions

and reflections instantly becomes reality. As the word of the Judaic God, when the code speaks it creates and vice versa. This makes the coded policy into more than simply a digital representation of a policy by the modern state in the pre-digital. This cyber policy also shapes and re-forms the cyber-space it acts within and upon. It is implicit in this cyber policy that code cannot act without treating that upon which it acts as objects. Here again, the features of the digital state resemble those of the modern state described by Foucault, but emerges something slightly different, something more than just a re-emergence of the same state governmentality in the digital. Something we must explore further.

This marks the end of the theoretical foundation for this thesis. My goal in this thesis is to perform a discourse analysis of the governmentalities of the digital state, as seen on Facebook. In the preceding chapters, I have presented my thinking, my assumptions, and my frame. I have noted how social media has emerged and grown as a phenomenon, pointing out how even at a cursory glance the largest company in this field acts similarly to that which we call a state. I have contended that this development can and should be analysed not as a singular company amassing market power – or a singular state acquiring influence and territory – but as an abstract phenomenon called digital state. I have recounted the concepts and theories of Foucault, leading into the theoretical assertions of epistemological sameness of social actions in the offline and online life-worlds of subjects. This was followed by an exploration of power in a Foucauldian view, recounting and contrasting other theorists of power. I then moved from what could be said, and how to say it onto what I will be talking about. In this chapter, I have developed the concept of the digital state, as a continuation of the modern state treated by Foucault. Along the way I substantiated the contention that Facebook can indeed bear the name of state, especially a digital such. Ultimately, I have asserted that the technologies of subjection called digital can be observed and researched on Facebook.

Having established these building blocks, the focus changes. I have outlined what I am researching and how to describe it, nested in how to think about it. Now I will move to the practical application of these theories. I will describe how I conducted a discourse analysis of the governmentality of the digital state, as seen on Facebook. The time has come to start building a framework for the genealogical analysis to come. The time has come to talk about methods.

5. CASTING WEBS ON THE NET

In the preceding chapters I have laid out the theoretical frame of the thesis. I have presented Foucault and discussed power in his shadow; I have presented the state as a collection of techniques of subjection of self and others; I have presented the digital state as a new form of the technique called state, as phenomenon if not necessarily as entity, and I have proposed Facebook as a fruitful object and site of research into the governmentality of the digital state. Governmentality and other relevant concepts have been introduced, as have some elaborations – and alternatives – to Foucault.

I have stated my goal to uncover and describe the governmentalities of Facebook. Governmentality has been introduced along with other, connected concepts, and it has been shown how Facebook is treated as a proxy and site for the digital state. What still lacks is a clear definition of what that means in practical terms – how I approach(ed) the object of analysis. In this chapter I clarify what I planned to do, how I did it, and why; how I sought the answers to my question about the governmentality of the digital state. In other, perhaps colder, words, I will describe my methodology. I will relate this study to others and outline my approach, which I term digital genealogy. To begin with, I introduce some of the shoulders I stand upon.

5.1 The ones who came before

This is a Foucauldian study of governmentality and state. The theoretical and empirical foundation for the thesis is to be found in the preceding chapters. At the same time, however, it is a study of digital techniques of governance as they appear on the social media platform of Facebook. To understand these techniques of subjection and the governmentality of the digital state, as seen through these observations, an understanding of the digital state is not enough. We need a deeper understanding of the site of research, the digital through which this new web of power flows. We need to situate our understanding of the digital state of Facebook in and relate it to the realisations of scholars of socio-digital life, media, and platforms.

Important work on the theoretical side has been made in identity formation and performance of social relations in the digital realm. In these studies, Foucault and other theorists have been applied to better understand what the enveloping digital overlay and mutual colonisation of the social realm means to users

(Couldry & Mejias, 2019; Zuboff, 2019; Sujon & Dyer, 2020). The common denominator argued missing here is, of course, what this study aims to do: Apply Foucauldian theory to research and understand the structures and techniques of power in play on digital platforms. This shift from user to technique – and at the same time from structure to the power relations building and embedded in that structure – is inherently Foucauldian and in that sense can be seen as a continuation of the studies of Foucault and others. My study is novel in the way I propose to perform a digital genealogy, as well as my application of these concepts and techniques to digital platforms in general and to Facebook in particular, and in my assertion of the digital state as a new modality of state. But it is by no means the first of its kind.

5.1.1 Studies of homo digitalis

There is no clear line demarcating the study of humans, of structures or techniques of governance, and of machines and artefacts. As objects, society, and humanity move forward through time the lines between them become increasingly blurred. Indeed, later in this thesis I will argue that, increasingly, not all of that same “I” is rooted in physical, human bodies. In that case, and assuming a continuation of that tendency, the future subject might as well root its history in the birth of what became machines – one early form being humans.

I am not the first to enter the fray at the potential cusp of the proposed singularity. Others have asked what it means for the human subject to move attention and existence into a coded world of 1’s and 0’s (soon to be re-defined and potentially rendered obsolete, as quantum computing rises). First and foremost, I should mention Shoshana Zuboff and her most recent book, *Surveillance Capitalism* (2019). In this book Zuboff follows a classical sociological approach akin to Durkheim and Weber, inspired by Marx and others. She develops and presents a theory of surveillance capitalism which convincingly explains the abstract socio-economical workings of the current milieu of online commerce and existence. In short, Zuboff proposes that the data sweat of users is now gathered up and used, not just to enhance online services, but to drive a connected system of prediction and control aimed at steering behaviour (i.e. getting users to buy things). Zuboff is explicitly normative and in this, she considers the optimisation of services a worthy use of said data sweat, while the distillation of it for increased profit is considered an infringement of what

she claims should be a (human) 'right to a future tense' (Zuboff, 2019, p. 331). Zuboff traces and describes how these techniques of exploitation and control have developed and spread. She then links this to what she calls 'instrumentarian power' – a contrast to totalitarian power. The concept of instrumentarian power can be linked to the 'data derivatives' proposed by Louise Amoore (2011). When a human and its actions is sufficiently quantified, it can be probabilistically predicted what it will do next if presented with certain options. Though no prediction will ever be certain – especially since life and the world is inherently too rich in variables to allow all to be included. Predictions are fixed to subjects and the reality of their lives – the means of subjection and self-subjection – are adapted accordingly. Treating humans in an instrumentarian fashion means treating them as objects rather than subjects: instruments to set and employ according to the definitions of whoever controls the ignition key. The contrast to totalitarianism is that while a totalitarian power might seek to dominate individuals through control of the inside – the truths running through their minds, instrumentarian power seeks to dominate not what people are, but what they do. Like rats in a maze, the instrumentarian simply places individuals in conditions and options that have them moving towards the exit, oblivious to and not caring what the rats are thinking on their way there. Thus, not just the current, but also the future truth is affixed to the subject without the possibility of choice. This lack of realistic choice leads Zuboff to present her concept of the 'un-contract' which denotes not just the lack of, but the reversal of a contractual agreement between the actor and the governing structure (Zuboff, 2019, p. 217). Ultimately, Zuboff echoes and expands on Amoore in problematising this and demanding the aforementioned 'right to the future tense' for subjects (Zuboff, 2019, p. 331). Zuboff's main point here is not that the predictions always carry a possibility for misalignment with empirical reality (for more on that, see Amoore, 2018 on 'doubtful algorithms'). Her point is that whether or not the predictions might (not) be right, humans (should) have a right to decide for themselves what future(s) they wish to pursue and in how far statistical math should be allowed a say in this. This point about rights links to earlier internet scholars, such as MacKinnon (2012). Speaking from an avowed liberal-humanist position, she reminds us that the need to define rights only appear as said a priori right is being treathened. MacKinnon deserves a particularly honourable mention here, since her assertion of 'Facebookistan' and 'Googledom' as state actors served as original inspiration for this thesis (MacKinnon, 2012, p. 145).

Speaking of rights compels me to include legal scholars such as Lawrence Lessig and Cass R. Sunstein. Lessig (2006) and his concept of 'code as law', as well as his operationalisation of 'cyberspace', is an important pre-cursor to my conception of the coded subject and state. Sunstein (2007) is famous in the field for introducing and warning of the virtual 'echo chambers' online subjects might find themselves in, hearing only echoes of their own (policital) attitudes when they speak into the perceived public of the internet they see. This, of course brings us around again to the un-consented behaviouralistic control, in the perhaps somewhat lighter assertion of the 'filter bubbles', proposed by Eli Pariser (2011). Pariser has later delved deeper into solving the problems he set out to explore, and in doing so has moved towards conceptually treating digital spaces as analogue to physical spaces – specifically cities (Pariser, 2019). This points back to a seminal text from the early days of digital studies, where Langdon Winner asked 'Do Artifacts Have Politics?' (Winner, 1980) and proceeded to show that artefacts can certainly be designed to serve and enact political ends on subjects. Others, such as Bossetta (2018), have furthered these studies of digital infrastructures as metaphysical places and how they might influence subject behaviour. Finally, rounding off with another cornerstone of my inspiration, I will mention *How We Became Our Data* by Colin Koopman (2019). In an exemplary employment of Foucauldian genealogy, Koopman (2019) takes the reader through the formation of data as (self-)identifiers leading towards the concurrent understanding of ourselves as data subjects. Koopman does this in part by tracing the development, if not evolution, of 'human bookkeeping', examining the rise and standardisation of birth certificates as authoritative and important identity documents in the United States. In doing so, he examines changing contemporary accounts and debates shaping structures, tools, and policies as well as the physical certificates themselves, as they change over time. I shall revisit Koopman and draw out further some of his concepts some chapters hence.

Though I see my approach as aligned with these theoretical, philosophical or even sociological studies, there are others to whom I would speak. As I move towards situating the digital state, viewed through the analysis of Facebook, I should start with an understanding of this representational object as it is more commonly seen: a social media platform.

5.1.2 Studies of social media and digital platforms

As the prevalence and importance of Facebook and its likes has risen, so has academic interest in it. Some of this interest has, like this thesis, been rooted in Foucauldian theory, often looking at how such platforms facilitate technologies of self (van Doorn, 2010), or panoptic surveillance and is part of the discursive patterns of power-knowledge of state institutions, such as the NSA (Meldgaard, 2014). Some have utilised aspects of Foucault in discussions of ‘mobile health’ (M-health) and the possible benefits of internet technologies to enable (beneficial) technologies of the self (Bull & Ezeanochie, 2016).

Over time, the object – the digital platform – has changed, and so have the tactics and objectives employed to understand it (Gillespie, 2010; Helmond, 2015; Eriksson, Fleischer, Johansson, Snickars, & Vonderau, 2019; Postill & Pink, 2012)⁷⁸. More often than not researchers and theorists – not to mention writers of science fiction – have pre-empted the societal changes the new digital technologies would foster (Clarke, 2014). At the time of writing, digital platforms are increasingly at the heart of both theoretical and practical social science, as evidenced by the increasing propensity of creating university departments, political institutions and NGOs with the digital as their main area of interest, not to mention the popularity of books and TED talks on the subject. The study of digital platforms and social media in particular can be roughly divided into two, inter-weaving streams (allowing for overlaps): one lead by theory and philosophy and one lead by practice.

On the theory side many have applied thinkers such as Foucault, Luhmann, Habermas, and others to theorise about the sociological, social, and psychological impact of digital practices (Tække & Paulsen, 2010; Henman, 2010; Žižek, 1998; Fuchs C. , 2014). Some, such as Sunstein (2007) and Pariser (2011), have tracked the development of current trends and fostered more testable hypotheses about what we are seeing and what impact can be expected because of it. Others, such as Lessig (2006) and MacKinnon (2012), have focused on a legalistic struggle intermingled with theories of freedom of speech, liberty and justice.

⁷ For an exploration on the emergence and meaning of the term “platform” for itself, see Gillespie (2010).

⁸ For an updated critique of the ‘platform’ term and its implications, see Eriksson, Fleischer, Johansson, Snickars, & Vonderau (2019).

More recent examples tend to draw on most or all elements of this stream (Clarke, 2014). Yet other scholars have employed Habermas' notion of the public sphere (see Chapter 3). Christian Fuchs explain how they (and he among them) have focussed 'on the necessary material resource base for any public sphere' (Garnham 1992, quoted in Fuchs, C., 2008, p. 58), finding that:

[S]ocial media has a potential to be a public sphere and lifeworld of communicative action, but .. this sphere is limited by the steering media of political power and money so that corporations own and control and the state monitors users' data on social media.'

(Fuchs C. , 2014, p. 89)

The practice-oriented stream is perhaps linked more to political science in the quantitative, positivistic sense, to anthropology, and to data analytics and statistics in general. In this area we see a wide variety of techniques, often featuring Boolean statistics and various degrees of Skinnerean behavioural psychology, employed to trace and understand the digital human, both singular and plural. This area and its methods are interconnected with the products and services of digital platforms, as they themselves employ techniques to better understand, anticipate, and steer the behaviour of users (Anderson, Huttenlocher, Kleinberg, & Leskovec, 2013; Hansen, Saridakis, & Vladlena Benson, 2018; Wu, et al., 2019). Here we also find those who have empirically tested the aforementioned theoretical claims of Sunstein, Pariser, and others (Williams, McMurray, Kurz, & Lambert, 2015; Bessi, 2016; O'Hara & Stevens, 2015; Flaxman, Goel, & Rao, 2016). Presumably the most technologically sophisticated (if not necessarily advanced) research in this latter area is being done by the companies behind digital platforms themselves (Hilbert, Ahmed, Cho, Liu, & Luu, 2018). While it seems quite unlikely that the companies would publish their most insightful and important results they do interact with academia and publish papers on some of the progress they have made (Taylor, 2019; Johnston, 2019; Warlop, Lazaric, & Mary, 2018)⁹. This reluctance to interact fully with the public seems in part due to concerns about maintaining their competitive edge, in part a safety measure

⁹ See <https://research.fb.com/> and <https://ai.google/research>.

to avoid public backlash over ethical concerns, such as what Facebook and Cornell researchers experienced after their now infamous 2012 collaboration paper on emotional contagion on digital platforms (Meyer, 2014). In this article the authors handled empirical evidence from a Facebook experiment on users where the “News Feed” (see below) was tweaked differently for two different user groups to see whether the sorting algorithm could negatively impact the emotional state of users. It demonstrably could, and thus, some users were left experimented on and slightly worse off than the control group, without having ever received any notification other than agreeing to ‘Terms & Conditions’ (T&C) upon registering on the platform, ipso facto showing that Facebook explicitly experimented on subjects and wilfully made some of them relatively worse off. Something which they did without giving prior notice to the subjects, apart from their having clicked acceptance and knowledge of the terms and conditions (Meyer, 2014).

In addition to these more common threads, others before me have applied Foucauldian theories to social networking sites, such as Facebook (Owen, 2014; Geiger, 2015; Howlett, 2016; Meldgaard, 2014). Most of these researchers tend to envision ‘Social Networking Sites’ (SNS’s) and Facebook in particular, as “spaces” for self-realisation and performative identity assertion and proceed to focus on the implications this structure has for subjects, rather than on the structure itself. Though this structure is seen as permeated by discourses of power, and though some studies do mention and cast a cursory glance at the management governing these sites, and their governmentality, few are focused on these. Geiger (2015) is an exemption. In an interesting idea paper, he proposes a brief argument for focusing on the governmentalities of social sites in general, and Facebook in particular (Geiger, 2015, p. 3ff.). He raises some interesting points, connected to the thinking behind this thesis, but the argument in this concept paper appears preliminary, perhaps argumentative rather than empirically founded and yet undeveloped, albeit promising and interesting.

Clearly, I am not the first to try my hand at bringing Foucault online, certainly not the first to research Facebook or even social media in general, nor am I the first to see the state in the machine. In the dichotomy I set out above, this thesis is an attempt to synthesise an approach that speaks to both the theory and the practice side. The thesis has emerged heavy on theory, but it turns to and around an analysis

of practice by and on Facebook. The further question, then, is how to do the concrete analysis, which seeks to straddle theory and practice. Again, I start with a view of what others have done.

5.1.3 Scraping and other mathesis of code

While academic literature on digital platforms and other later-to-be-dubbed social media has been fairly comprehensive, the knowledge built in and around these themes has been dominated by quantitative methodologies, methods, and epistemologies (Brønholt, 2017). This might in part be traced to the prevalence of engineers and computer scientist interested in that field (Pariser, 2011), but also to a coded field built and run on binary computers and powered in its operations by Boolean statistics which simply lends itself well to quantitative study. In a digital milieu all subjects, objects, and areas of interest already exist in a (binary) quantitative state. Research can then be seen simply as a matter of fitting them to the method (a devout positivist might argue that this is true for everything there is – or at least everything worth involving in scientific inquiry). As is the general norm for quantitative studies, this type of research has largely focused on testing hypotheses within the social space, as coded. Thus, theses largely related to the function of the structure of the media, such as Sunstein’s theory of online echo chambers, and Pariser’s theory of filter bubbles have been tested, but tested quantitatively (Brønholt, 2017 being an exception). This research has been aimed at the directly measurable causal relationship between structural features of social media and its users. How subjects act in their environments, perhaps even touching on how subjects act because of their environment (Bessi, 2016) – but not how the environments act upon, without, and within them. The latter is what I seek to remedy in this thesis. I will not be employing such digital mathesis (Foucault, 1989 [1966]). Partly because this work has already and is continually being done, but more importantly because it is not apt to inform the answer to the abstract question I have put forward. It would not help me bring Foucault into the digital; it would not help me explore the governmentalities of the digital state.

Important and relevant as all such studies of digital platforms are, they are not what I am attempting to emulate here. To my theoretical view, studying such autonomous agents of a comparable and clearly demarcated nature echoes the studies of states so taunted by Foucault (Sawyer, 2015). While I refrain from

advocating the cutting off of anyone's head, the avowed aim here is to analyse techniques and discourses – structures of power-truth – rather than more or less clearly defined entities. This is a study of the digital state. This digital state is seen as a technique / collection of techniques of governance, and observed in, by and of Facebook. That means I have to, in some sense, observe what happens on Facebook, what the concrete state of Facebook does in relation to its subjects, as well as find contextual artefacts through which I can further my understanding of the cyber policies acting upon the digital social space. With Amoore and Koopman as the notable exceptions, the recounted scholars all operate in different frameworks than the Foucauldian one I adopt. Still, each in their own way, they serve as both inspiration and foundation for my discussion. Without the thoughts, theories, and findings of those that went before, my task would have been all but surmountable. Other scholars, historians, philosophers and scientists could be included here, but I have emphasised those who have inspired my thinking and whom I actively include in my discussion to come.

Before the discussion must come the analysis. As I progress towards my own asserted approach, I start with the general and steer to the specific, as I reflect upon the methodologies steering my methodology.

5.2 Foucault of the machine

Having considered research done in and on the digital by others, I turn now to develop and describe my Foucauldian approach to the social dynamics online. In this section I lay out the methodological theory, birthed by the thesis so far. Once this frame within a frame has been set, I turn in Section 5.3 to a more detailed description of what I analysed and how.

I am inspired by other Foucauldians, most especially those already working on the digital, and the related work of Shoshanna Zuboff. Louise Amoore works within an explicitly Foucauldian framework (Amoore, 2011; 2018). Rather than studying technology as such, she explores the human in technology and technology as a mediator, carrier, and shaper of humanity. Her format is self-consciously narrative and not structured according to more narrow ideas of scientific or academic writing. Though this thesis has in the end been re-worked into a format more resembling a common structure for scientific writing, this is the

result of conscious choices, rather than adoption of implicitly or explicitly prescribed rules of scientific narration. On the one hand, Amoore employs Foucault directly to these themes of the apparent third modernity (Zuboff, 2019; O'Hara, 2020); on the other, she brings in various theorists, empirical evidence, and philosophies, when they are relevant to the discussion, object, or point she is making. Though not working in a Foucauldian framework, Zuboff (2019), does the same. She, too, has served and serves as inspiration for this study. Though somewhat reined in over the drafts, I reference broadly, and employ theories, arguments, and concepts outside and beyond the Foucauldian, while remaining in the larger paradigm, reminiscent of her style. Finally, I have already mentioned Colin Koopman's *How we Became our Data* (2019). In this book, Koopman introduces the new Foucauldian conception of 'infopower' to the field. In doing so, he creates a Foucauldian offshoot that is explicitly usable and illuminating to the logics and connections of the datafied human in the digital. Koopman's methodological framework and his rigid and coherent approach to the genealogical method is my most direct inspiration for this thesis.

5.2.1 Studying digital subjects

How, then, to study these 'modes by which ... human beings are made subjects' (Foucault, 1982) in the online realm? If one is to derive from Foucault (1982) an approach to digital states such as Facebook, the immediate idea might be to identify those struggles against forms of subjection taking place on and by Facebook and derive from them the techniques of subjection and their governmentalities. But given the definitional, coded nature of the arena of play, how humans are made subjects, is, in the first instance, an empirical question of how the digital subject is constituted. Thus, due to the material-physical differences of the online realm compared to that of the offline social world, first and foremost the sheer physics will need to be described. In this particular form of physicality these virtual structures are intertwined with the techniques of subjection in a similar fashion to Foucault's description of buildings infused with subjectivising governmentalities, most famously the proposed panopticon of Bentham – something which, with Winner (1980), we may link to the study of coded structures. Identifying the structures of subjection and dominance then allows for the identification of possible struggles. These struggles do not imply a singular, clear source, of course. Where the pastoral power of state Foucault describes has emerged and encroached upon and within a physicality, a sociality, and a society already existing, the digital state is

concomitantly created and governed. Though the platform has undergone many changes, the inherent subjectivity of code demands that there ever be definition, subjectification, and control (Lessig, 2006). Like the panopticon, these very structures of code tell a tale of subjection. And the changes they have undergone over time enriches the story with a counter-story of the struggles they have changed in response to.

Much like monarchies that have adopted constitutions, even parliament and democracy to continue their existence in some form, rather than cease existing as the losers of a historical struggle, the structures and techniques of subjection on the platform has shifted over time, becoming what they are now. Though what they are changes by the day, the individual, and the device subjected to Facebook. Following this, a full-fledged archaeology of knowledge of Facebook might have dealt primarily with the ways in which subjects, subjections, and truths have been defined and changed over time in the milieu that is constructed by and on Facebook. But this is conceptualised as a study of the digital state of Facebook that *is*, rather than the Facebook that *was*. Though the history of Facebook and other platforms is an important part of the puzzle and is both drawn in and referenced, it is not the true object here. The object is not to study Facebook as a thing of itself and unto itself. It is to study the digital state, as a collection of techniques of governance and subjection. Thus, the situation and exploration of the concept of state above is more important than a detailed archaeology of Facebook itself. The goal is to study the governmentality embedded in the digital state techniques. A study of how the specific state apparatus of France was conceived as a concrete entity, was never the focus of Foucault's genealogy. He studied the modern state as an abstract rather than concrete *thing*. In the same way, I intend to study the digital state. I look for it in Facebook for the reasons outlined above, but the goal is not really to understand Facebook, but the digital state that flows through it. For this reason, the above part of the narrative has dealt more with the state, subjection, and power, and less with Facebook as concrete entity (or "a state"). The site and conditions of the study must be situated, and Facebook is introduced and treated as a quasi-entity – but it is always to be seen as a proxy: an example of and site for the digital state, whose governmentalities are the true objects of interest and research here.

5.2.2 Analysing Facebook

In this study, I perform a genealogical tracing of the power techniques in this digital realm. When I employ the term 'genealogy' it means that I trace the techniques of power in play on Facebook as it appears from my particular point of view (see Chapter 2). While doing so, I am aware of my own position in relation to that which I observe only in reflection, as it is in many ways internal to me, as much as I am to it (as a subject and a researcher, as it were).

In the coming analysis, I detail, first, the meta-physical landscape of the platform in order to separate the parts in a meaningful sense. This enables me to explore what codes, and what algorithms are in place to govern subjects in each corner of the vast social space that is Facebook and how (Seaver, 2017). This exploration is what I especially model on the genealogical approach. I trace how each part – each function – came to be and how it came to be what it is. This is situated in a wider history of online platforms, as well as in historical engineering of the Internet, and social science dealing with various forms and iterations of the datafied and digital human citizen. Along the way, I recall and integrate narratives of the governmentality and technologies of self and biopower of the modern nation state, as analysed and detailed by Foucault. Using this as a point of reference, I explore to what extent the digital polity of Facebook is embedded with sometimes similar *modus operandii*, and similar structures of power-knowledge. But first, I build a tale of the site – the polity – in itself and of itself, only later turning to this comparative twist. The data is dependent on the step. See in this a pendant to someone starting an analysis of a nation state by describing the emergence and status of its codified laws and customs, its clothes and the culture, and its buildings and administration.

In a sense, genealogy is a far cry from some common conceptions of (social) science and is as much a historical as a "scientific" method. At the same time, however, there is little denying the profound social scientific gains and implications of the work of Foucault and others. Koopman (2019) is an example of this, having used this approach to better understand the datafication of humans and the everyday human life through an exploration of its roots. My research can be argued as being too contemporary for a meaningful historical analysis, but though genealogy has strong ties to historical/historicist traditions, the crux of the

approach is not in the temporal separation from the present, but rather in the uncovering of how contemporary discourses and truths came to be in order to understand what they are. My research begins with conceptions about what states are and do, re-visiting Foucault's own work mentioned above, tracing that development into our current age, if a different age it is. It is a matter of choice, and of that choice being meaningful in a narrative and a conceptual sense. Ideas and discourses of personhood, datafication, power, the state, individualism and being human are important pieces of the puzzle I am trying to assemble. Digital platforms and chat forums are likewise important and parts of the frame, but they are not the subject to be placed in the golden ratio axis of the emerging motif. What I wanted to uncover was the governmentalities of the (coded) techniques of subjection, as they appear on Facebook, as seen from my computer during my time of writing. That is not to say that it is static. Indeed, several changes and shifts have happened during the span of my project so far, and two years into my process, Facebook announced that they might all but remove the "like" count from their platforms (Constine, 2019) – a change which could be significant in terms of subjection / subjectification and self-constitution on the platform. To establish a description of the metaphysical reality of the space in question, I have looked at how the platform is in the fleeting temporal place of today. To see what objects are constructed for the subjects of various kinds (user, moderator, advertiser, governor), the direct source is to log in, observe what is, and describe it. Due to the platform's adaptive nature, this must be done in rather general terms, and be informed by other research and sources of knowledge, academic and otherwise.

This description of the metaphysical space and its coded rules serves as the basis for the further analysis. Following this, the focus turns to the governmentality of the aforementioned cyber policies. This part of the analysis is based on a discourse analysis of press releases, of the help section of Facebook, of internal documents leaked wittingly or unwittingly, and of public messages by the would-be leviathan of said state of Facebook, Mark Zuckerberg. From this literature describing the policies, goals, and thoughts behind them, come the data salient enough to identify the governmentalities of the techniques of bio-power and self, employed on the platform; the digital state.

In short, to analyse the world online, first and foremost, I need to log on. But to a modern human that is akin to saying that to analyse a societal phenomenon I need first to be human. A bit more is needed. Having reflected on the studies I use as my base and inspiration, I now present the methodological wrappings of my empirical research, ending in a concrete description of what I have done and how.

5.3 Methods

As explored at length in Chapter 2, a Foucauldian approach necessitates a fair degree of epistemological, ontological, and methodological consideration. There is a wide field – are wide fields, even – of Foucauldian research spanning all manner of adaptation and emulation of techniques of discourse analysis, governmentality studies, and genealogy. Rather than committing explicitly to this or that particular anachronism, I have opted to honour all of these legacies as best I can, and explain myself not in opposition to them, but rather building on the tradition, as I apply my understanding of the wider field for my own knowledge-building. It is in relation rather than opposition to these that I explain what I mean by naming my approach a digital genealogy rather than a discourse analysis or another more common term. In this section I move from theory to practice to explain what that means for this project.

5.3.1 Discourse analysis

One of the things touched upon in Chapter 2 is the complicated relationship between Foucauldians, discourse analysis, and genealogy. Though I term “my method” as ‘digital genealogy’, I could also have termed it a ‘discourse analysis’ (not to mention, a ‘governmentality study’). This is because of the simple truth that in what I do, I am analysing discourses to understand governmentalities.

In my approach, I am not focussed exclusively on written (or transcribed) accounts narrowly sourced and analysed in colour codes in analogue or NVivo. Since I am inherently critical, albeit trying to be so in a somewhat satirical rather than explicit way, as per the points about the genealogical style above (Saar, 2002), it could be said to be a critical discourse analysis. But this, if seen as a proper name, signifies a theoretical distinction pointing rather towards Marxist (or) Gramscian approaches, such as the one exemplified by Lukes above – or the Frankfurt School with Habermas arguably chief among the

foundational theoreticians. All in all, I believe calling my method a (critical) discourse analysis would muddy the narrative waters rather than clear them, and so I steer away from the name, if not the critical stance, and assert 'digital genealogy' as the tool I employ in this endeavour.

I also avoid terming my over-all approach a discourse analysis because of the largely textual – indeed, grammatical – focus this name might imply. The discourses in the written artefacts – documents – are an important and vital source of “data” for my research. But of at least equal importance is the simple fact of *being* on Facebook to observe the built structures and cyber policies in action. I will be enveloping myself – with a critical eye – in the space I purport to analyse. But how? What am I actually looking at?

5.3.2 Data sources

The work done here, using the approach that I call digital genealogy can be seen as a mix of what Lupton (2013) terms 'Sociological analyses of digital media use' and 'Critical digital sociology'. From the onset, one of the big questions of this project has been around the source and type of data. While a case can be made that “more is more”, adding both type and amount of content also widens the scope and complexity, potentially hampering deeper insights.

In what we might cautiously term my “data collection strategy”, I have looked at many, varied sources. First of all, I have looked at structures and texts created by representatives of Facebook Inc.: I have looked at the Facebook GUI (Graphic User Interface), help articles from Facebook Help, various material from the Facebook Press Room, Research papers and explainers from Facebook Research, patents related to Facebook, and released documents from court cases, including internal e-mails. For discovering and identifying many of the concrete documents, I have been guided by journalists and scholars. My awareness of the relevant news and scholarly articles, as well as loose comments about things worth looking at, I owe in no small extent to the sorting algorithms of Twitter, Facebook, and my personalised Google Search. This is not as a result of a conscious strategy, nor is it pure serendipity. It is the direct result of how I – as a digital subject (and scholar) – set out to learn all I could about how subjects of Facebook are constituted and governed. This process naturally started with reading through relevant papers and books from news and academia, thus finding interesting scholars and journalists and following them. In these digital communities

of shared interests and collective understanding sharing is caring, and tweets from scholars and activists such as Mar Hicks and Wolfie Christl, but also from the Facebook Newsroom¹⁰ and everything in between allow for the identification of an immense amount of potential data sources. Add to this the insights and references to be found in the scholarly work, the most relevant of which I have mentioned above or in the narrative, and what I have found simply by translating thoughts into series of queries and allow Google to do the rest. It is no exaggeration to say that the research and data collection for a non-digital genealogy of the same scope would have taken years. This is inherently an argument of quantity rather than quality, however, and there are significant trade-offs to my approach, which I will explore further in Section 5.4. I have summarised my data sources for the individual sections of the analysis and discussion in Table 2. All textual sources are referenced using the CTR (Harvard) system (in the same way I reference scholarly articles, books etcetera), and I have included screenshots of relevant functions on the site(s), as viewed through my Google Chrome browser, when logged into facebook.com, with descriptive captions.

Table 2: Data sources (analysis)

Section	Main object of research and/or discussion	Main data source	Found via
6.1	The meta-physical structures of Facebook	User GUI on Facebook.com	Viewed as a private user (my profile) in Google Chrome on PC
6.2	What is allowed and disallowed on Facebook, and how	The explicitly defined rules and policies in effect in that digital space	As accessible via Facebook Help
7.1 & 7.3	The governmentality of the digital state – how the user / subject is seen and managed.	Studies about and documents showcasing how coders in general and those working at Facebook in particular construct /constitute / seek to subject / understand the user	Found through literature review, library searches, references from colleagues etc. often picked up from my echo chambers on Twitter & Facebook

¹⁰ <https://twitter.com/histoftech>, <https://twitter.com/WolfieChristl> and <https://twitter.com/fbnewsroom>

7.2	The ethos of engineering	Studies about the mindset of engineers, and documents by Facebook coders / engineers	Found on Facebook's pages – Facebook Research, Facebook Press Room, Facebook itself (posts by Mark Zuckerberg), as well as public sources (patents and court cases). Often picked up from my echo chamber on Twitter & Facebook
-----	--------------------------	--	---

Far from all that I have come across has been included in my analysis. As mentioned, the goal was never to analyse Facebook Inc. as a company (apart from Chapter 4), or Mark Zuckerberg as a person, though both are related and relevant. With the help of my supervisors, I have sorted my observations (and drafts) to focus on that which has helped towards an understanding of the digital state of Facebook, and cut out documents and sections that do not aid me in this overall effort. In the same light, I should mention that if I had at any point found the publicity of documents or other content I inadvertently accessed to be of dubious legality, I have exempted it from the project – at least until such a time as it would be released by a legal source.

While I employ all of the various sources throughout the rest of the thesis, there is a difference, related to the development of the narrative. Roughly put, the sources I mentioned can be placed under the headings of Theory, Empirical Evidence, and Data. In a general – perhaps somewhat positivistic – idea of doing research, we tend to ask for theory to support the theoretical-methodological frame, ratified empirical evidence from other studies to setup and situate the work, and data (often freshly collected) to perform the new analysis, adding to the sum of knowledge summarised by the former two. This analysis is then set in relation to both theory, empirics, and rhetoric (logic) in a discussion. This produces some findings, which can then be concluded and commented upon (Yin, 2009). In the tradition / paradigm of this thesis, however, such rigid separations of sections can be hard. The preceding chapters are definitely more theoretical, and more based on the research of other scholars, and the formal analysis does set off from original data, but the lines are fussy. In particular, I do not aim to draw a hard line between analysis and discussion, though there is a narrative progression from one to the other. This means that while the beginning of the analysis can be fairly clearly defined as Chapter 6, the transition into discussion and

theoretical considerations and implications is gradual. Along the way, the narrative becomes almost purely theoretical, but then recedes back into what I believe is a less unwieldy conclusion of the analysis in Chapter 9. For the theoretical discussion parts, I mainly use the sources introduced above – especially Foucault. The analysis, however, is situated in the all but meta-materialistically real objects that I can observe on my screen, and enriched by the research and/or claims of others, both scholars, journalists, and practitioners (often meaning people who work for Facebook Inc.). I could have retro-actively labelled my “data collection strategy” as a ‘hermeneutic approach’, or perhaps even an attempt at ‘grounded theory’ (Rennie, 2000, p. 483), but such an after-rationalisation would perhaps imply that my approach – in a positivist way – was defined as such and followed particular rules and precepts in my quest to understand. The theoretical framework, as it grew, also grew into an understanding that defining such a strategy would mean having to formulate a theory; an idea about what that data is, says, and does – indeed, what it can be, what it can say, what it can do and what it cannot (Foucault, 1982). Something I, following Foucault, would not do. All the while, as I struggled towards my understanding of what my Foucauldian framework for this study should and would be, I also gathered the data detailed above and tabled below.

I have pointed out above, how coded structures are inherently inseparable from the laws that govern them. Remember that, as a general rule, the wide majority of users can do only that which they are supposed to do in a coded environment. How users are policed on Facebook is an important second step in the analysis. With a less complex (and less protected) code, we might be able to simply read it and see what affordances are available to users and not. However, first, a platform like Facebook does not run much code on the client side (on my computer), and, second, the code which displays a current-day site like Facebook is an output – a result of those more complex computations taking place on the server side (their big data centre computers). That means that while reading through the html “source code” in my browser¹¹ can give me a

¹¹ You can see yours by clicking (or typing in) this url: <view-source:https://www.facebook.com/>. This will show you the (mainly) HTML output that your browser translates to the graphic interface you see on the web page.

basic idea of what simple actions and interactions I can trigger on the particular page of the site I am currently on, it does not really tell me much of substance:

Figure 1: Screenshot of Facebook.com source code, viewed in Google Chrome

The code does provide a bit of an “under the hood” view, as it calls various functions with or without active user participation and interaction, and it can also tell me something about how the functional layers are prioritised and interact. Still, all of this would only really be relevant if I wanted to understand and interact with particular, separate functions of the code. In terms of understanding the larger aims (and affordances) in the coded reality, I do not actually learn much here. Indeed, in terms of how the user is constituted as a subject and enabled to constitute herself as a subject, it is much easier and meaningful to “read” the actual, normal browser window. The GUI on facebook.com is intuitive and as a long-time user, I know what the various graphic cues symbolise – what actions are afforded, and what the results of those actions is supposed to be. This is the information I really need. This is what I need to analyse in order to move towards and understanding of the governmentality of the digital state of Facebook. Even if I did have access to the whole code hierarchy and all the databases, even if I was able to read and understand all of it, this would still be less helpful towards my aims. Perhaps akin to how the specifics of the biological anatomy of the human eye is less relevant to a governmentality of the modern state than the expert, medical, or sovereign

gaze and how it constructs and divides the human beings turned into subjects (Foucault, 2003 [1963]; 1995 [1975]).

5.3.3 Digital Genealogy

The method I adopt is a genealogy of the digital spaces and techniques (of governance) of and on Facebook, employing discourse analysis of meta-physical (coded) structure (read: features and apps on the site), as well as text in documents and on sites, including help pages, Zuckerberg's posts, and press releases (political / governance speech), but also terms & conditions (laws), and internal and external working documents (bureaucracy). Through a digital genealogy of these sources, I can create an image of the governmentality of the digital state. In reading this, one might ask why I do not include political entities outside of the digital state. To be sure, the discourses and governmentalities vis-à-vis the company Facebook as a subject of governance by the US, the EU and others are relevant to the story of Facebook. But again here, that is not the story I hope to tell. Likewise, the lives led by subjects subjected by Facebook – the user-citizens – are relevant to consider (Bucher, 2018). But to understand the governmentalities behind the conduct of their conduct, the users are second-hand sources. Indeed, only one user account is needed to observe the concrete instances of the cyber policies of the abstract digital state, and that is mine.

In my approach, I start with the site itself, as seen when I log into it from this computer. From this angle, I first build up a critical description of the meta-physical structures on the platform. This allows me to further pre-empt some of the insights to come in the (discourse) analysis and discussion to follow. Not to mention setting up the wider (techno-)philosophical considerations, some of which have already been pre-empted along the way. The data I use for my digital genealogy is heterogeneous in format, authors, and intent. The way I select my data – including the type of data – in no way follows a formalised attempt to randomise or formally systematise my encounter of said data. There is no attempt at a simple, random selection in order to make claims about external validity and statistical significance. Rather the opposite. Critique of the idea that a computer or a given formalised random selection criteria should be a priori less biased than the conscientious scholar is implicit in this thesis. As such, a data selection strategy based on a methodology

asserting primacy to formalised techniques of objectification would be at best ironic, at worst undermine the foundation of the project.

I have picked and kept the most relevant sources for analysis through what I describe as a (digital) genealogical approach. Something which might also be likened to a historical approach. Since I make no claim to objectivity, positivistic strategies to counter subjective bias are rendered moot. This goes particularly for concerns about (inadvertently) selecting data fitting a desired dependent variable. The framework employed here is not concerned with formalised causalities, but rather with understanding the governmentalities of the digital state. In this, I as a researcher present myself as the subjective and discursively situated individual that I am. This particular individual – I – have a profile on Facebook, which allows me to observe first-hand the structures and effects of the meta-physical manifestations of the cyber policies to be analysed. I also have access to both scholarly and journalistic articles, journals, and books about Facebook – material which often share or make possible the search of their sources from within and without Facebook. Further, through conferences, collegial chats online and offline, as well as my (heavily echo chambered) feeds on Twitter and Facebook, I have been led to even more sources in one form or the other. Finally, serendipity plays its part as reflections by myself or others have led me to google for patents and scholarly articles authored by people working for Facebook. It might be said that such a strategy is not methodological. But in another view the strategy can be seen as an attempt to find as much relevant material as possible and using the most sophisticated computational device for this task yet known – the human brain – to select among the possible sources identified. In this, I follow Foucault whose sources were selected for relevance, rather than randomness. Foucault famously spent months and years in archives and libraries before emerging with the insights and references which should prove so influential. The reason I call my approach a digital genealogy is simply because I have found and accessed all the material referenced here through the internet, mediated and aided by digital means. I will admit to having printed some resources, and to having bought or borrowed paper versions of the academic references, but those artefacts which I refer to as the main data for my analysis are all found and accessed digitally. For this simple reason, I name it a digital genealogy. This digital genealogy, however, along with the rest of this

“method” is by no means above reproach. Perhaps I have sinned against the precepts of science? With such vague and fluffy formulations, is this even science?

5.4 Sins and penitence

This thesis features various implicit and explicit jabs at various scientific assumptions, practices, and paradigms, and the narrative has a tendency towards attempted levity when it comes to “defend” the choices made against would-be “attackers”. That levity in tone is not to be confused for a disregard for the points raised, however. In the main it is simply the result of my personal version of a Foucauldian writing style (cf. section 2.1 and Saar, 2002).

Above, I have described, first, the work of others, then attempted to bring Foucault into the digital, and described my approach – my method, if you will – digital genealogy. Now, perhaps owing to a tradition of critical dialectics of the thesis-antithesis variety, or to the aforementioned falsification notions of Popper and others, I aim to pre-empt yet again some critique that might be reasonably levelled against my approach. This performative critique will of course be met with equally perfunctory replies as to why my approach truly is the best it could be – but this is rooted in honest considerations and efforts towards scholarly rigour. Tradition and critics have demanded that I partake in this ritual and present various related themes as if it was an honest attempt to test my assumptions and pre-empt criticism, and I agree with the practice, while remaining somewhat less committed to the performative honesty of the format. In any case, I agree with would-be critics that relating theory, objects, and assumptions to alternative ideas and approaches is a good way towards a deeper understanding, refinement, and explanation of one’s assumptions and their implications. I believe self-critique is beneficial for both the readers who might agree with either the critique or that which is being critiqued, and (perhaps especially) for the scholar critiquing herself. To my mind such critique cannot be a true test between purportedly even competitors, but it is worthwhile. The competitors can never be even, as any competitor put into these Foucauldian waters would be like a mock trial of a land fowl’s ability to swim faster, deeper, or just plain better than a fish. In these waters, the fish will always emerge “better”, but that does not mean it is of an inherently higher order. The comparisons should serve to illustrate what the fish is and can do, rather than what the land

fowl is not and cannot. With this caveat in mind, let us consider honestly some of the considerable shortcomings of my methodology.

5.4.1 Shedding a positivist light on things

While not explicitly stated before this point, the attentive reader will have noticed that I do not consider myself and much less this thesis to be “anti-positivist”. Both in my review of the above, and in the analysis and discussion chapters to come, I am prone to reference what theoretical and empirical studies I find most relevant (and salient), rather than those who share to some extent my own methods or paradigms. However, while not against it, the foundation of the thesis itself is a far cry from positivism indeed, and many critiques could be levelled against it from this side.

Much of the post-Enlightenment scientific tradition involves various forms of what can broadly be called falsification (Popper, 2008 [1963]). Rigorous critique of a given theory or approach will allow us to test its mettle and it emerges either hardened as accepted truth, disproven, in order to arise as a phoenix from the ashes, with some amendments, or discarded, to be replaced by a newer theory which then undergoes the same treatment. This overall approach has paved the way for many important scientific discoveries and scholarly insights. I believe it has also fed a wider, implicit assumption that to be strong and valuable, a given scientific theory, method, or approach need to be performatively tested and emerge victorious from a field of mock battle with its competitors. Much could be written about this with references to various liberal traditions and thinkers of the last hundred years, and the valorisation of competition above all. I might even suggest this could be led back to *The order[ing] of things* explored by Foucault (Foucault, 1989 [1966]). I will not pretend to answer here from whence comes the idea that everything can (and should) be ordinally (and if possible, cardinally) scaled, but I will comment on the idea that this also goes for scientific theory and methodology. To be unequivocally clear: I do not believe this work, nor even the work of Foucault himself is inherently “better” than that of other scholars. I admire Foucault’s work, and I honestly believe that I have approached this thesis in the best way possible for me, for my object, and for my project – but I have plenty of admiration left for other scholars of various other paradigms, and I will not pretend that assigning value to what I do and have done here suggests other work to be of less value.

Implicit in this assertion is an immanent critique of and disregard for many assumptions connected with positivism and the “unitary method of science”, but that does not mean that I scorn nor would attempt to disprove either. Indeed, I hold those assumptions to be equally true, each in their element.

The first point of critique from a positivist camp might very well be the recently mentioned trust put in the researcher for the data selection, rather than a devolved, formalised system of random (and/or exhaustively defined) selection of data. In a paradigm often connoted with Locke’s ‘tabula rasa’ (Duignan, 2020) and the mistrust of the unsupervised human mind, my data selection described above amounts to a clear admission of “selection bias” – “cherry-picking,” perhaps even. On the other hand, if the cherries are ripe, perhaps they are the right ones to pick. In a complex reality, dealing with a complex problem, a mathematically randomised selection method can hinder more than help. Defining rigid definitions of what data to include and what to exclude involves an a priori operationalisation – a theory of that which the data should help describe. A more open approach to data collection is not inherently better than the opposite – but it is also not inherently worse, as with most methodological considerations the real test is whether it is fit for purpose; whether it works well with the paradigm, the assumptions, and the methods. My approach fits my project, and I have described it in such detail as to allow any critic the opportunity to disagree.

The problem of recursive tautology and confirmation biases remain, of course. Seen through the language of positivism in particular and scientific or even logical thinking in general, I can easily be accused of having had a hypothesis – perhaps even one that could be stated as a question – and proceeded to select data that confirmed my a priori assumptions. To some extent this is, quite simply, inescapably true. The Foucauldian framework is a bit of a minefield of linguistic beating around the bush. Rejecting the search for causal claims is all good and well but brought to its logical conclusion it potentially makes scholarship itself a wan and meaningless effort. After all, why study a thing if we a priori assume we cannot understand how it relates to everything else – what it does – apart from that which we already felt to be true? I would argue, however, that this extreme interpretation of the theoretical frame is a misunderstanding. There are no formalised, simple hypotheses to be tested here, but in a wider sense there is an implicit claim about

causal structures: The governmentality of the digital state, for example, can be said to have causal effects on how subjects of said state can be and will be constituted by themselves and others. The problem with this (causal) formulation is that it potentially leads towards several misunderstandings. First, said causal relations are multi-directional and principally endless. In focusing on one or a hundred, these would be given undue weight in comparison with the whole. It would be akin to a net thrown to gather up and research the sea, ocean currents and all. Second, it would open up the same concerns raised in relation to Lukes some chapters hence, about alternative realities and the all-knowing researcher. If we formulate a theory of what is but might as well not have been, of what is not but should have been, or even what is but should not have been, we are ontologically and epistemologically treating flights of fancy as if positively existing alongside observable phenomena. If we could truly don a methodological veil of ignorance, carrying with us an omniscient collection of theories of what might be, and then write on that tabula rasa all these options, then to test reality against them with perfect measures then arguably all research and scholarship should be done according to these principles. But in a complex reality featuring multi-faceted and –directional theories of dubiously definable causalities and imperfect measures some room must be left for doubt as to the universal applicability of the sometimes proposed universal method of Science, writ large. In this particular case, and following Foucault, the goal was never to formulate a theory of what “a state” is and test this or that entity against the theory (a deductive approach) – nor did I attempt to ascertain what Facebook is to see whether that might fit the definitions of a state (an inductive approach). I did not even attempt to – perhaps dialectically – test the veracity of various purported bits and pieces of one or the other in order to land at a relative understanding of the hypotheto-material reality of one or the other (an abductive approach), although this latter proposition can be seen as ideally if not materially closer to the mark than the two former. And so, I follow Alice down the rabbit hole, dodging queens, guards, and watches, trying to keep my head. Sadly, claiming what something is not and replying simply “Foucauldian” as to what it is, does not alleviate all doubt. From this side as well, critique can be found.

5.4.2 Who framed the Foucauldian rabbit?

The Foucauldian frame, as I have developed it, follows Foucault's arguments in his essay *The Subject & Power* (Foucault, 1982). Discussing how the general theme of his research is the subject, and not power, he writes:

Do we need a theory of power? Since a theory assumes a prior objectification, it cannot be asserted as a basis for analytical work. But this analytical work cannot proceed without an ongoing conceptualization. And this conceptualization implies critical thought – a constant checking.

The first thing to check is what I shall call the “conceptual needs.” I mean that the conceptualization should not be founded on a theory of the object – the conceptualized object is not the single criterion of a good conceptualization. We have to know the historical conditions which motivate our conceptualization. We need a historical awareness of our present circumstance.

(Foucault, 1982, p. 778, quotes in original)

Clearly, hen and egg problems abound. Foucault goes on to consider the role of philosophy and political rationality and the Enlightenment, mentioning the approach of ‘some of the members of the Frankfurt School’ (likely Habermas among them), while distancing himself from it. His intent, as he says,

... is not to start a discussion of their works, although they are most important and valuable. Rather, I would suggest another way of investigating the links between rationalization and power. ... [N]ot to take as a whole the rationalization of society or of culture but to analyze such a process in several fields, each with reference to a fundamental experience: madness, illness, death, crime, sexuality, and so forth.

(Foucault, 1982, p. 779)

“But wait!” you might say. “What such field is this thesis then supposed to cover?” And as you find yourself intrigued by these snippets, you might read said essay for yourself and discover how Foucault goes on to

suggest that for our analysis we take ‘the forms of resistance against different forms of power as a starting point’ (ibid. p. 780). Clearly, this differs from the strategy laid out above, and unfolded below. In response to this I can only say that I believe my approach to be pertinent to the object of my research. I have found no better way to articulate the historical conditions surrounding the digital state. I do not take my reference point in concrete forms of resistance (though I do mention several as I attempt to describe said historical conditions), but rather I explore the means and objects of subjectification and consider the ever-dwindling possibilities of un-subjectivising resistance they afford. I see in this an effort to identify potential points of resistance, but it is hardly the same. My objective is to continue the ‘history of the different modes by which, in our culture, human beings are made subjects’ (Foucault, 1982, p. 777), but the analysis strategy is adapted to the concrete site of analysis and the narrative reflects an attempt to carry the reader along a Foucauldian understanding of the meta-physical living spaces of the digital subjects of the digital state. This may not be what Foucault would have done, but I remain convinced he would approve.

In the same vein, some have asked me to explain clearly precisely what works of Foucault I am attempting to emulate here. Am I most concerned with the sovereign power of “the earlier Foucault” or with the disciplinary power, bio-power, and governmentality of “the later Foucault”? In response, I resist the desire to repeat what I believe would be Foucault’s own answer to this (but see section 2.1), and attempt an honest and direct answer: Succinctly put, I have made no attempt to distil this or that essential Foucault, and I have not attempted to emulate any Foucauldian work in particular. During my project my understanding of both Foucault, Foucauldian scholarship, and almost everything about this thesis – frame, object, subject and all – has changed. What has emerged is an understanding of the Foucauldian foundation, as I understand it, and as I see it fitting for this project, and a methodological structure built on this foundation and aimed mainly at achieving the overall goal of performing a (Foucauldian) analysis of the digital state. I see this work as an attempt to continue the work of Foucault, bringing it into the digital modernity, and as such it can certainly be said that I try to carry forward more from his later work (especially on governmentality and bio-politics) than his earlier. But I strongly feel it would be disingenuous to pretend that I explicitly modelled my approach on this or that book, work, even more so this or that Foucault. Clearly, the work around governmentality is more important to me than that of sovereign power

– but without the latter, the former appears hollow. And what is the power-knowledge structure of a state without relations of sovereignty and subjection?

I have attempted to understand and explain in clear(-ish) terms how I understand a Foucauldian approach towards analysing the governmentality of the digital state. In doing so, I have referenced the works of Foucault and others that I find relevant to situate and understand the theory, object, and methodology of this thesis and critically judge it. It might very well be judged wanting, and some would perhaps argue that I could –and should – have shielded myself from such judgments. I respectfully disagree. I have done my utmost to enable and invite criticism from any and all corners. I have done all I can to provide transparency and an honest account. And I maintain that this is a Foucauldian work of which I myself am satisfied with the rigour and value. That does not set it above reproach, nor should it. But it is my hope that it is worth reading and can provide some insights, allow us to edge the field forward, as they say. Whatever field that may be. Another critique to be levelled against this work is the very late (post submission) realisation of how important a chosen silo of knowledge is. Not just to those tasked with judging veracity and rigour, but also to the reader in general. When push comes to shove, I believe this should be called mainly a work of political theory. I admire Foucault’s ability to seemingly resist being enveloped in various boxes and labels, but I am less convinced now than ever if it should be an ideal to aspire to. So, let me content myself with having writ a work of Political Theory, which I hope has some relevance for those eminent scholars working within Sociology, Social theory, Political Science, Philosophy, Media Studies, International Relations, and perhaps even Phenomenology. It is my hope that especially this final edition of the thesis contains enough relative explanations to make it accessible to a wider audience than simply Foucauldian political theorists.

Ultimately, my main “defence” in this dialectic court seems to be that this is a Foucauldian thesis, and a presentation of what that means to me. If I came across a bricklayer who had built a foundation for a square-shaped house, gathered up considerable piles of red bricks, and had started on the basis of the outer walls, then I would find it odd to question her proposition to proceed with building the rest of the square-shaped, red brick house, as intended. And I would certainly not spend much time arguing that he should really have built a wooden shed or a concrete skyscraper instead. All of these have their uses, but

he is building a red brick house. I would hope he had considered his options, however, and if it turned out he was building a proper house simply to store a spade and a bucket, I should politely inform him that there might be a better solution to his problem. Critique based on the assumption that he should really have built a different structure, since I would myself prefer building such a structure is essentially non-sensical, unless supported by some evidence that such a structure is indeed what was rather needed. I thus implore my reader to test the frames and prod the foundation, judge the masonry and the thatch – but please stand upon the foundation when doing so. Judging something from afar and dismiss it because it uses different building materials from one’s preferred is of little substantial value.

I have established the theoretical foundation for the thesis, explored and discussed the methodological considerations this leads to, and presented and discussed the methods used. Now, following Foucault – or rather dragging him into the digital sphere – I will first describe and situate the digital world built to facilitate, police, and govern user behaviour. I will then analyse the governing discourses, informed by the documents and other recorded “speech” of, by and about Facebook to ascertain the governmentalities embedded in these cyber policies – these digital techniques of algorithmic power. From this, I will build a discussion of what is, touching on what could be. I move now to the analysis, the digital genealogy. I move now to describe the coded structures of subjection on Facebook.

6. THE STRUCTURE OF FACEBOOK

Until this point this thesis has been largely abstract and pre-emptive. The study has been established as a Foucauldian work, employing digital genealogy – an exploration of documents and spaces in, around, and about the coded social environment of Facebook, with a particular eye on those that might illuminate the governmentalities of the digital state. From this presentation of the thoughts and assumptions that have been, I move now to a description of what is – as seen through these lenses.

Describing Facebook in this day and age can seem as would one explain the concept of clothes or humans talking. Especially among those who would be reading this thesis, Facebook can be assumed to be well known. But as common-day as it is, it is not static. It has changed over time, and it is increasingly adapted collectively and individually to fit each user, taking into account from where she logs on, at what time of day, from what device and so forth. Facebook, as so many things, is never and yet always the same. Still, though the ordering and structure of the content varies according to time, place, and person, since the last major change to the platform – the introduction of the News Feed in 2012 – the meta-physical structures are largely the same. This is what I will describe here. In this chapter, I outline this virtual polity from the inside out: First detailing the productive construction of a digital persona, then the construction of community and other interaction with fellow digital subjects, and finally, the cyber policies seeking to govern pastorally how and what is done by the subjects of this metaphysicality. Or, in fewer words, I will describe the structure that structures the digital subject.

6.1 The digital constitution of self

When it first launched, TheFacebook was little more than a digitised version of the paper face book – yearbook – of the founder’s university (McGirt, 2007; Kirkpatrick, 2011). Where the nascent forum (later to be redubbed social networking) sites thus far had enabled users to customise a digital persona very loosely related to their offline selves, thefacebook.com was of a different breed. It was designed to mirror reality. It was a place for digital doubles of the offline self, not for construction of yet another avatar, and users needed to use – and prove – their real name to get in (MacKinnon, 2012; Kirkpatrick, 2011). Leaving aside for now the many other features that have since been added, this mirroring of offline selves is still at

the heart of the self one can constitute on the site. While the imagined true self is increasingly as much digital as offline in nature, Facebook profiles still reflect this idea of one, true person, across platforms and realities per human (ibid.). That being said, in recent years, Facebook can be seen as growing an understanding of the multifaceted nature of said human self, as they adapt content according to time of day, device, and other variable metrics (Warlop, Lazaric, & Mary, 2018).

6.1.1 Facebook profile

To become a user-citizen of the site – to doubly subject oneself to Facebook in the Foucauldian vernacular – one starts by creating a “profile”. While this profile will appear as a blank ready to be filled by the user, it should be noted that Facebook, along with various other arbiters of personal data, make extensive use of web trackers and cookies. Thus, even if one has not (yet) actively registered and thus self-subjected oneself to Facebook, one is already subjected in the first sense, as Facebook (along with Google and others) have long since constructed one as a more or less clearly defined subject-object of governance (Zuboff, 2019). To register a profile, then, is the first step for the user to actively subject oneself to Facebook – it is not the first step through which the user is subjected.

Once the user-citizen has given and proven her name, and performatively agreed to the terms of service, she is able to populate her profile. Digital spaces and entities are inherently quantitative, and the Facebook profile no less so. Some content can be filled with free text, but most drops down a closed set of options to more or less predefined categories. While the free-text enables not already defined options for self-subjection and representation, whatever one types in is parsed in an advanced quantified manner, using so-called artificial intelligence (AI). In this way, all that is entered is rendered quantitative and computable. An example of such a category is what one is ‘interested in’, the choice at this time of writing being a binary dichotomy where one can report to be interested in either one of, none of, or both of women and men (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Researcher's 'Basic Information' (Facebook), March 2019

In the earlier instances of the platform, filling out this data was at the heart of what users would be encouraged and expected to do – now, most such data is already held by this and other companies and simply correlated to the profile (Barocas & Nissenbaum, 2014). Importantly, non-human entities – commercial or otherwise – can also create profile pages akin to, but simpler and presented differently from, the profile one can create as a user.

To get started with constructing oneself as a digital subject on Facebook, one chooses a profile picture and a “cover photo” relating to the notion that one’s extended profile includes one or more photo albums performatively portraying one’s life and identity. The profile was originally supposed to be, literally, a picture of one’s face, though over time, the site policy has gone a more loose avataresque way, as the algorithmic knowledge of the individual has grown. These pictures, along with the name, are the basis of the visual representation of the I that is portrayed, when in this digital social space someone does the computer equivalent of focusing their eyes on you and point their mouse to your (profile) name or picture. This preview also includes current work and study occupation, if any, as well as former such experiences (Figure 3).

Personal details withheld.

Figure 3: Researcher's Facebook profile preview, September 2020

One can continue to fill out basic info, but what really populates the knowable digital subject is activity. Every action – even a potential consideration of an action (the hovering of a mouse, a pause in scrolling) is logged and fed back to the machine learning algorithms designed to determine ones interests and feed content (and ads) accordingly. Not all of this populates the overt profile, but much does, and can be seen and edited through the subject’s GUI (Figure 4). It can also be seen by various other “visitors” to the profile, as defined by the user in terms of visibility of individual or grouped parts of the profile.

Figure 4: Researcher's Facebook activity log as seen by user, March 2019.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

These activities by no means encompass all that is registered. After the advent of smartphones, Facebook services have been heavily integrated into them (Valentino-DeVries, Singer, Krolik, & Keller, 2018). The company Facebook has also enhanced their “Messenger” service – developed from their more industry standard on-platform chat system to a stand-alone communication app across devices – to include text messages (Messenger, 2016; Miscellaneous, 2019A). In the year of writing (2020), the same app is projected, along with various other functions, to be integrated with similar parts of Instagram and WhatsApp (Zuckerberg, 2019A). As Nieborg and Helmond (2018, pp. 2-3) point out, Messenger ‘displays Facebook’s ambitions to, in the words of Facebook CEO Mark Zuckerberg, position its ‘family of apps’ as ‘ubiquitous utilities’’. According to them, the company ultimately seeks to monopolise the digital mediation of social interaction, a point which I will return to. Here, the take-away is first that all of Facebook’s apps on all devices that have them installed is set to register and return any and all data about the users, registering them to their profile. Second, some – but by no means all – of the data gathered is rendered visible to the user. This asymmetry of knowledge and control is important. The human user-citizen is presented with what appears to be complete control – complete with the ability to delete or hide things from the log – but cannot in the same way access all the data gathered and correlated to her profile (though the EU has ensured some avenues for further transparency for EU users). It is generally argued that most users are unaware of signing away their consent for this information asymmetry, while others are aware of it, but accept it as an uncomfortable trade-off (Kempa, 2015).

6.1.2 Facebook status and Photos

Once the profile is established, one can perform various mainly social actions on Facebook. Main among these – at least in the current iteration of the site – is posting status updates and photos. Status updates are small blogs – bits of text, often including links to other sites, such as news providers or commercial sites inside or outside the Facebook ecosystem. The status updates sometimes come with one or more photos or videos appended. Once created, the status updates appear in the News Feeds of other users, as per individual preferences, connections and (assigned) settings. I return to the News Feed below (Section 6.1.4). Unless chosen otherwise by the user, uploaded photos will be shared in the News Feed as well as on the profile – and will appear in a dedicated sub-page of the profile.

Figure 5: Researcher's Photos tab on Facebook (contacts anonymised), July 2020.

The user can exercise extended control as to which other users are able to see content shared in this way. For each post or photo individually or for all collectively, the user can choose various degrees of visibility to specific groups of people with or without exceptions. The user cannot, however, opt out of (all) photos and posts being available for research and moderation by Facebook employees. Further, unless the singular user has explicitly and arduously opted out of it, the photos of all Facebook profiles are parsed by face-recognition algorithms in order to enable an automatic linkage in the form of “tagging”:

Face recognition is used to analyze the photos and videos we think you're in on Facebook, such as your profile picture and photos and videos that you've been tagged in, to make a unique number for you, called a template. When you turn your face recognition setting on, we create your template and use it to compare to other photos, videos and other places where the camera is used (like live video) to recognize if you appear in that content. Keep in mind, we don't share your template with anyone.

(Facebook, 2020A)

This is how the site can “recognise” the photos above as being “of me” – I have been “tagged” by myself, others, or algorithms in them. This tagging enables the automatic data handlers to run the pictures through an algorithm which is then able to predictively suggest a further tag to me and my Facebook contacts if and when something resembling my face appears in a new photo (Facebook, 2020B). What exact programs and algorithms are run “behind the scenes” is not public knowledge, but it is noteworthy that Facebook researchers have patented a way for such systems to recognise different pictures that are taken by the same camera, regardless of user and motif:

Images uploaded by users of a social networking system are analyzed to determine signatures of cameras used to capture the images. A camera signature comprises features extracted from images that characterize the camera used for capturing the image, for example, faulty pixel positions in the camera and metadata available in files storing the images. Associations between users and cameras are inferred based on actions relating users with the cameras, for example, users uploading images, users being tagged in images captured with a camera, and the like. Associations between users of the social networking system related via cameras are inferred. These associations are used beneficially for the social networking system, for example, for recommending potential connections to a user, recommending events and groups to users, identifying multiple user accounts created by the same user, detecting fraudulent accounts, and determining affinity between users.

(Muriello, Heise, & Chen, 2015)

Same as the profile, this part of the larger structure is embodied with an information asymmetry. While some features are presented to the user, and explained in greater detail if that user visits the help section, the whole of the operations taking place “behind the scenes” are not mentioned. This is not surprising, as attempting to lay out all the functions and algorithms handling the user data in a pedagogical manner would be all but absurd. Algorithms of today have generally grown too complex for one single human to

understand any one of them without specialised training and the aid of code translation software, which in turn has to be built into the systems that train and build said algorithms. Few car users are interested, even if capable, of understanding all the intricacies of modern engines, as long as the car does what it is supposed to. In the same way, users of Facebook will rarely want to look for a thorough explanation of every detail of every code that conducts their conduct online. Note also how the patent summary focuses on the productive power of the patented code. With the implementation of this, the (inner workings of) the site will be able to recommend potentially interesting objects for the users to interact with, as well as enhance their protection from undesired objects such as fraudulent accounts.

6.1.3 (Facebook) Messenger

It is interesting to note that among people socialising via the internet of the early 2000s “Messenger” as a proper noun generally referred to MSN Messenger, the then industry standard (Corden, 2021). As mentioned above, sites that featured chat or discussion forums also routinely had a subpage dedicated to “private” messaging between users. Now, such a sub-page is often referred to as an “app” – short for application and related to the platformisation of (some) web sites (Helmond, 2015). The early web sites had different (static) pages, whereas a platform allows packages of code – programs / applications – to be run, engaging with both the user, the user’s data, and other apps. Some of the first such apps were chat pages, producing nothing more and nothing less than the ability for users to write messages to each other individually and collectively. These site pages dedicated to text communication enabled programmer-users and companies to develop stand-alone programmes (aka. executables or applications) for their computer’s operating system (Linux/Unix, Windows, Mac OS) designed to connect solely with those chat sub-functions of the sites. Facebook, which was originally constructed for socialising in the narrow terms of ‘friending’, ‘unfriending’, ‘poking’ and writing on a person’s ‘wall’, introduced a chat function similar to that of (other) forum sites in 2008, updated it in 2010, and finally released a stand-alone messaging application in 2011 (Miscellaneous, 2019A). As the name changed from Facebook Chat to Facebook Messenger, while MSN Messenger had been renamed Windows Live Messenger and then finally subsumed into Skype, the users waned while Facebook user counts continued to rise, the name of the Facebook app was changed to Messenger, tout court, in what appears a blatant step to position the app as the standard, not just in the

industry, but conceptually in the minds of the users (Nieborg & Helmond, 2018; Corden, 2021). An aside to this is that though by all accounts reaching into the same user database, the Messenger applications, the web browser GUI and the applications for Facebook as a whole, are now so conceptually separate as to spur user questions about whether they are connected at all (Quora, 2017).

Figure 6: Researcher's Facebook Messenger (contacts anonymised), September 2019.

On this (Facebook) Messenger, users can interact socially in a mediated social milieu which could be said to emulate a conversation between people standing physically in the same room – facial expressions, body language and all. Messenger could be loosely grouped with a telephone of yore, handling voice calls, as well as more recent iterations enabling users to send Short Message Service (SMS) texts to each other. Indeed, the Messenger app for smartphones also handles SMS texts, if set up to do so by the user, when prompted (Facebook, 2019E). In Messenger, the main function is that the user can send text messages with or without emojis – modern hieroglyphs that need no further introduction, originally derived from keystroke symbols vaguely resembling facial expressions, such as the ‘smiley’: :-) – to one or more other users. She can also initiate a voice or video call with one or more other users. In the current iteration, many other actions are made possible. for instance, a given message sent by a user – be it a voicemail, a video call, text, emoji’s or a GIF (a short, soundless video clip, often with text overlay) – can be ‘reacted’ to,

appending emojis to a message post (see Figure 9). This allows the user to add various layers and nuances to interactions, making the potential means of expression more complex and nuanced than a simple textual or telephonic conversation (though, to be fair, both allow for great variance in tone, demeanour and style). Three things are notable. One is that while a conversation partner looking at a given conversation can see if and when one is typing, they cannot see what is being typed, until/unless it is sent. Second, the user can see if and when a conversation partner has seen a given message. Third, a user can delete messages – including ones they have sent themselves – from their own presentation of a conversation, but the message will still appear on every other screen – once sent, it is outside the user’s control in everyone’s eyes but hers. I highlight these, since they represent specific choices made – in each case the programmers could have made the rules and features of the function differently, and some have indeed changed over time.

Figure 7: ‘Remove’ dialogue from researcher’s Facebook Messenger, September 2019

These choices create a distributed asymmetry of both information and control between the users. These asymmetries are productive, as it gives the user not just a sense of control, but actual control. At the same time, however, this control is reversed once the message is sent, emphasising that the user’s control only extends to what the user can themselves see and are in the process of creating. Similarly, a user can choose to turn off notifications for messages from a given conversation, but not see if another user has done the same. Finally, while other users cannot see that which is being typed, the Facebook site admins and background programs potentially can, as is evident in a 2013 paper from Facebook Research:

For our purposes, we operationalize “self-censorship” as any non-trivial content that users began to write on Facebook but ultimately did not post.

(Das & Kramer, 2013, italics in original, emphasis added)

6.1.4 News Feed

The main page on Facebook and the first thing one sees when logging into facebook.com is the News Feed. Launched in 2006, it is a staple and centrepiece of the platform, showing content that is algorithmically deemed interesting to the user. Originally, the News Feed basically listed social events as reported on the platform, such as changes in marital status, (performative) assertions of preference, and messages left for others to see on their previously static 'wall' (Facebook, 2006A). This means that when the News Feed was launched in 2012, messages left on other users' 'walls' prior to this change were suddenly recast as news about social activity and highlighted as such, especially to mutual friends. This sparked much controversy from the users, prompting Facebook to implement a privacy filter for users to control what would be shared, and who could see it (Facebook, 2006B; Kirkpatrick, 2011). Later, as the complexity and connectivity of social interaction on and with Facebook has grown, the content possibly included in the feed ranges from meta-data from users or entities (e.g. "Thorsten Brønholt is interested in <event name>"; "Danish Parliament posted an update..."; "Thorsten Brønholt checked into The Bottom of the Sea") to posts typed in by the offline bodies of such profiles, either in full or in preview, and with or without links to other web sites or Facebook sub-pages and media, including advertisements. In this development it is important to note how the "news" shared with other users are no longer just communicative user to user actions repurposed as news to other users about those same communicative actions, but also automatically registered actions of the online or offline human subject. More or less conscious and self-reflective subject actions are thus repurposed into inter-subjective communication. When I "like" something, it is not simply a preference I state for myself, perhaps adding some form of support to the author of the entity or item that I click on, it becomes a piece of news where the digital action is reshaped into an act of informing particular people that "Thorsten likes <object>". Perhaps insinuating that they should too. What started as a widening of the audience for an originally communicative action has thus expanded to re-purpose potentially any action into a communicative action. In this radical view, any- and everything a user-subject can be registered to do is of potential interest to other user-subjects. And even more so to the algorithms governing the sorting and distribution of those news. As the information flow expands proportionally, so does – for simple, practical reasons – the information asymmetry. All actions are rendered potentially social

and their registration or inference thus desirable to the mediating machine, powering it to ever more efficient adaptation of the structure and experience of its user-subjects.

Figure 8: Researcher's Facebook News Feed (contacts anonymised), September 2019

While the page content in the margins, as seen above, is static for each session (but, like everything else on the site, variable for separate sessions and connecting units), the News Feed itself is scrollable and continues on ad infinitum, more content being formatted for representation every time the user nears the bottom of the page or starts over by refreshing the page or reopening the app. Each presented item can be interacted with socially: it can be shared further, commented on, or 'reacted' to (with one of the 6 predefined emoticons seen in Figure 9). This 'reaction' is a 2016 update or 'extension' of the former binary 'Like'-function introduced in 2009 (Facebook, 2009; Facebook, 2019C). In April, 2020 a seventh reaction was added in wake of the Covid-19 pandemic, though it is not yet clear whether this will be rolled back at a later time and so it is not depicted here (Voica, 2020).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 9: 'Reactions' to content, September, 2019 (Facebook, 2019C).

This information feed became the centre of Facebook's activity and, importantly, their business model. Profile owners can buy their way into users' personalised News Feeds directly or indirectly. If they pay Facebook in cash, the otherwise apparently neutral algorithmically determined spreading of content will be tweaked and their content views boosted. One can also pay in time and attention: The more a profile interacts with other profiles – and/or other profiles interact with it – the more likely it is to be shown to ever more profiles. These two ways of paying – with labour or capital, as a Marxist might put it – can of course reinforce one another. After increasing scrutiny and negative stories about Facebook in the press, the News Feed was changed significantly in 2019, tuning up the number of posts from or related to 'friends', and tuning down the posts from non-human entity profiles, such as businesses (Facebook, 2019B). The stated aim to this particular change was to move away from the increasingly criticised commitment to tweaking the news feed towards maximising the time users spent on it – and the amount of ads they would see and click on (more on this below), and towards maximising people's well-being (Zuckerberg, 2018A; Mosseri, 2018). In 2020 the News Feed has been the target of yet more criticism, first, due to its decision to continually allow political advertisements on the site, and second due to a decision to not take down a controversial statement by the incumbent president of the US in relation to the Black Lives Matter (BLM) movement (Hsu, 2020). It is noticeable how the sorting and adaption of the news feed according to strategies and aims set by the company officials is not being criticised. The critique revolves around what those aims and strategies should be, while ultimately asserting that the company, Facebook, are the ones who should make these decisions. In this, I see a pendant to the development described by Foucault where the over-powering discourse of the governmentalised state does not allow for questions as to *whether* the state should govern each and every subject, but only *how* the state should conduct this governance (Foucault, 2006 [1979]). By right of history, creation, and conquest the digital state of Facebook must and should govern its user-citizen subjects. The only question left is how.

6.1.5 Other places and pages

Apart from the profile, Messenger, and the News Feed, the Facebook site features pages for Events, Groups, Videos, Causes, Marketplace, and Settings – not to mention Fundraisers, Weather, and Games – the latter a once main part of the site’s attraction to users, notably featuring games such as FarmVille (Miscellaneous, 2019B). In concert, these pages exemplify the extensive colonisation of any aspect of the daily lives of human subjects (Couldry & Mejias, 2019). In the Marketplace, subjects are invited to perform their daily economic activity on the site, in Events, they can – and do – co-ordinate collective action of all manner and type, colourfully themed by the pre-made template pictures. Watching videos on a personal device is re-cast as a social action where the aforementioned digitised social actions of other users are layered onto the video viewed, all of it happening in “real time”. Causes, like events, enable any and all things that could fall under that category and finally, in Settings, the user who really wants to can exert direct and fairly detailed control over what she sees and what she shares, how, with whom, and under what conditions. This control, of course, is limited to what she has to be offered due to external regulation, such as the GDPR, and what it has been deemed necessary to offer from the side of the governance team of Facebook. In this section I should also mention the WhatsApp and Instagram apps. The former is roughly equivalent to the Messenger app detailed above – the latter, to the News Feed. WhatsApp and Instagram were both developed as stand-alone applications with no relation to Facebook, by independent companies, later to be bought by Facebook. For this reason they originally had a different user-base and marketing profile than the similar apps under the Facebook brand, widening the corporations reach in terms of user-citizens, and breadth in terms of control with the digitised part of these user-citizens’ daily lives.

While these are all relevant and popular parts of the social space for the digital state power I analyse, I will not go into further detail about each, as they are of importance, not as particular, singular sites, but rather as per their role in the interconnected social weave mediated mainly (but not exclusively) by the News Feed and Messenger functions and their underlying logics. For many users, Facebook is not just under your skin, it is your skin, through which you touch the world. But that point is to be left until we have explored the rules at play in these structures built for digital subjects to play and live in.

6.2 Laws, policing and ethereal governance

As all societies and most social spaces, Facebook has rules that are structurally enshrined. Rules that are set down by virtual law and serve as the legal basis for the virtual policing taking place, and context-dependant and ever-shifting social rules established between social subjects.

Embedded in all of the functions on the site – and indeed computer code in general – are limitations (Lessig, 2006). If I define five possible user actions in a given function then, by definition, the user is limited to those five actions. Thus, reacting socially to a post before the 2016 introduction of ‘reactions’, I could either ‘like’ it, comment on it, share it or ignore it. After the function was changed, the hitherto binary of ‘liking’ (or not) was expanded to allow me to express one of the six emotions depicted in Figure 9. Emotions that were later animated, not to mention picked up and copied by LinkedIn (Hutchinson, 2019; Chen, 2019). The changes Facebook have seen over time have generally been in the direction of increased complexity, allowing for ever more advanced social interaction. Inside platforms and media, across the mediated sociality as a whole, and concurrent with this development of technical possibilities, social structures have come into being and spread around and into this social space. These social structures and their rules are not *sui generis*. They are an extension and adaptation of the pre-existing offline structures of power and knowledge, implemented according to the rules, technical possibilities and precepts in place. The (social) rules on a site such as Facebook – as in an offline polity – are in part coded: What actions are possible are almost always limited to the ones made possible by the structure. In fringe cases, a particularly gifted hacker might circumvent the code of the site and perform (social) actions outside the scope of what the code is meant to allow, but this is an outlier and of little relevance to the large majority of subjects interacting in the space. Some other actions are meta-physically possible, but not allowed. The digital state entity, invoking its right to define the rules of the social space it governs, asserts the right to ban(ish) or quarantine any and all profiles that, in the estimation of their moderators, human or algorithmic AI, violate the uncoded rules of conduct.

6.2.1 Inappropriate or abusive things

A common example of breaking the rules of Facebook is to write messages to other users that can be considered offensive, either in public (Post or Comment on News Feed content), or private (Private Message on Facebook Messenger). While this might sound simple enough to identify in theory, how to rule whether a person has indeed transgressed is difficult in practice and becomes even more so, the more significant the given social space is to the actors, and the more varied the microspaces within the larger whole has become. Adding to the heuristic complexity, is the problem of volume, which for the company Facebook Inc. translates to time and other resources. In declaring that human moderators trained and paid by Facebook Inc. inform and guide, if not always make, most moderating decisions, the company has created for themselves a monumental task to be solved daily by its nigh on 52.000 employees and growing (Facebook, 2020D). But the paid content reviewers of Facebook and their subsidiaries are not alone. Within the delimited spaces on the sites, such as 'Groups' and 'Events', some users are 'administrators' or 'hosts' as a consequence of their having created the space or having been uplifted to this status by another administrator/host. These users can act as moderators and govern this micro-space according to their own rules (and whims). Their power is limited to banning other users from and deleting content posted within this "smaller" sub-space, as well as change the name and nature of the page or event (up to deleting it from the front end of Facebook). Their possible meta-physical policing actions are limited to those made possible and allowed by the code and status affording to them, but within these limits, they are as sovereign as the feudal lords of old, and can act with impunity.

If a user wishes to report content, such as a news feed post or a message in a conversation (or the entirety of it) to a policing authority a menu allows her to 'Find support or report post' (News Feed) or report that 'Something's wrong' (Messenger) respectively. In either case, a dialogue opens with categories under which to file the report. Choosing some of these, prompts further options to be filled. If for instance a Messenger contact is 'Sharing inappropriate things', the user gets to pick these as being either 'Nudity', 'Pornography' (these two constituting an interesting dichotomy in and of itself), or 'Violent or graphic content'. Once a report is filed, it enters a black boxed process where it is reviewed by someone (human) or something (AI) at some point and ruled upon (Brunk, Mattern, & Riehle, 2019). While it would be all but

impossible to account for the many possible differences in this process, based on the apparent geographical location of the user's device (as determined by meta data), some specific differences between identified EU users and other – especially North American or Oceanian – users have been reported, due to GDPR. For users accessing the platform from various countries outside the EU, Facebook refers identified divergent users directly from algorithmic to human scrutiny and further to outside entities, such as a suicide prevention hotline or the police. In the EU, all that can be done in terms of transferring the user to offline state authorities is to generally highlight the message that '... if someone is in immediate danger, call your local emergency services. Don't wait.' (Goggin, 2019). The first instance enables the user to have the surveillanced subject further subjectivised for disciplining (or empowered to specific actions of self-subjectivisation and -discipline) by an outside actor, the second enforces a discursive assertion openly imposing norms on the user. In both cases, the governmentality embedded is one of both users (the one seeing something to report and the one being seen and possibly reported) as subjects capable of bounded rationality who should perform – or not perform – certain actions as prompted and defined by the designers of this elaborate technique of bio-power. The avowed aim of this technique is benevolent: the digital sovereign seeks to save lives by preventing suicides and reporting criminals. Representatives of Facebook Inc. openly state the enhanced surveillance and subjectivisation – potential subversion of agency, one might say – as a calculus they have weighed in consultancy with medical professionals and found acceptable in the pursuit of their benevolent goal (Card, 2018; Singer, 2018).

Whether it has been thus “flagged” by users or algorithms, reported content is currently (2020) reviewed by human moderators. These moderators then choose an appropriate reaction to either dismiss the report or discipline the user-citizen. In earlier instances moderators had to make a solely binary choice of whether to delete or not, without much further recourse for involved users (Common, 2019). This has increasingly become a more complex question, as the importance of online speech acts to people and politics are becoming ever more salient (Zuckerberg, 2019B; 2019C). At the time of writing Facebook is setting up an ‘Independent Oversight Board’ to act as an ‘appeals court’ for the decisions made by Facebook’s moderators (Harris, 2019). This board is to be independent from Facebook Inc. though set up and funded by the corporation via a trust which is also tasked with the election of board members. The board is

endowed with the power to change not only individual moderation decisions, but also the community guidelines on which such decisions are founded (Zuckerberg, 2019D).

In all of this we can see the concrete workings of the abstract digital state in the concrete examples from Facebook. The rules and rationales evident in this governance of subjects separates itself from the neo-pastoral power of the modern state only insofar as the subjects are reached through the digitised social (Foucault, 1979A). Indeed the subjects' offline bodies themselves are rendered governable by proxy, as the digital state realises how their conduct of conduct in the digital can spill over to save the life of their subjects. This salvation, of course, is contingent upon the subjection of self to the subjecting entity (the digital state).

6.2.2 Independent oversight, self-subjection, and constitutional monarchy

In 2019 Facebook Inc. announced the establishment of an Independent Oversight Committee (later renamed the Independent Oversight Board). Having faced and addressed with varying success the aforementioned critique of latter years, the management team has struggled to define clear rules of conduct for both employers and algorithms, which satisfy inside and outside actors, and now moves to establish an external appeal institution. This approach is explicitly informed by the constitutional courts of the US and other constitutional democracies (Zuckerberg, 2019F). Once established, this external review board will supposedly act as a check to the moderation power of Facebook's content moderation team. Going forward, user-citizens who disagree with the moderation decisions made by Facebook Inc. will be able to first petition the decision to an internal appeal authority – and if they remain unhappy with a decision made there, they will be able to submit the decision to the Oversight Committee for review (Facebook, 2019F). The oversight committee is to be defined, founded, and funded by Facebook, but otherwise be independent. It will have powers to:

1. *Request* information from Facebook ...;
2. *Interpret* Facebook's Community Standards and other relevant policies ... in light of Facebook's articulated values;
3. *Instruct* Facebook to allow or remove content;
4. *Instruct* Facebook to uphold or reverse a designation that led to an enforcement outcome;
5. *Issue* prompt, written explanations of the board's decisions. In addition,

the board can provide policy guidance, specific to a case decision or upon Facebook Inc.'s request, on Facebook's content policies. The board will have no authority or powers beyond those expressly defined by this charter.

(ibid. italics in original)

The company rhetoric around this initiative is benevolent, while from a tactical point of view it is hard not to notice that by establishing oversight power to an institution defined by themselves, Facebook Inc. is seemingly pre-empting initiatives from offline political institutions to set up independent oversight authorities after their own definitions and tastes. Much as an offline nation state seeking to evade outside or public interference in its internal policies, Facebook Inc. meets the criticism by establishing, if not democratic, then formally egalitarian, legalistic structures of their own design and making to which they are willing subjects.

In this development we can see a pendant to the process of self-recognition and assertion of that sprawling behemoth which came to call itself a state in the offline world (Foucault, 2006 [1979]). The realisation from within and without of the digital state as the governing entity leads to internal and external processes of producing and structuring knowledge according to these precepts. By acting as "the state", by being seen as "the state" by those acting within, without, and in relation to it, the digital state of Facebook becomes ever more a discursive structure akin to what we call a state. Universal in its inevitability, it cannot be questioned whether it is to govern. It must. Because not to do so would mean the destruction of the territories and subjects it is duty-bound to save and perhaps serve. The question remaining, then, can be only one of how it is to govern. Once again pointing us back to the development of the governmentality of the modern state, as laid out by Foucault (Foucault, 2006 [1979]).

6.2.3 The medium of least resistance

On Facebook, you can be whatever you want to be. If the suggested answers to definitions of sexuality, religion, or other markers according to which subjects differentiate themselves does not suit, you can write new ones on the fly.

Figure 10: Editing dialogue for 'basic info' on Facebook, step one, September 2020

Basic info

Custom ▼

Female

Male

Custom ✓

Male: "Wish him a happy birthday!" ▼

Figure 11: Editing dialogue for 'basic info' on Facebook, step two, September 2020

Basic info

Custom ▼

Gender

Attack Helicopter|

The radical individualisation made possible in a milieu that is wholly restructured according to the assigned-perceived preferences of each individual subject opens up for a subversion of resistance into expression without recipient. Like a child screaming at the roaring sea, or like the silent internal scream of dread as a nightmarish ride is about to end, resistance can always be alleviated with a sign-posted way out of the subjection as it seems, into a self-subjection which is the same by another face. By allowing ever more open-ended possibilities of alternative self-subjection, resistance itself becomes mediated into subjection. Thus, rather than resisting by ceasing to exist as a subject – the radical resistance seldom (but sometimes) seen by human subjects of offline states, but still relatively common among online dissidents – resistance might come in the form of creating Facebook groups petitioning (or demanding) change of the Facebook sovereign (Kirkpatrick, 2011). By opening up further the way in which subjects can assign themselves subjective formats, such as sexualities, the platform gains both greater finesse and precision in its pastoral, individualising strategies, and circumvents resistance to the subjectification of each binary choice.

Effectively turning the answer to Foucault's central question which 'all ... present struggles revolve around ...: Who are we?' into another form of subjection (Foucault, 1982, p. 781).

In a similar note, the long-standing option to 'like' something (or not) was continually petitioned by user-citizens to be enhanced with an option to 'unlike' things – a feature found for instance on YouTube. This debate was eventually solved by the company neither denying nor acquiescing. In the end, the sovereign institution opted to expand the positive choice of liking something with several other positive emotive assertions (see above) and is now considering either removing it altogether or at least curbing the social effects and visibilities of the 'like' (Constine, 2019). The option to acquiesce to the resisting users remains unaddressed. See in this not a point about Facebook Inc. (even as "a state"), but about the governmentality of the digital state which we analyse via the techniques of subjection on Facebook. Further, the design of preference selection dialogues is written in a way as to make possible whatever option is deemed more desirable, whilst "nudging" the user-citizen towards compliance with preferred policies. In an example of this, a recent Facebook session of mine was interrupted by a user dialogue steeped in 'dark patterns' (Waldman, 2019) poised to make me activate the 'face recognition' feature mentioned above, which I had long ago opted out of. I was able to opt out again, though the design was such that each step demanded increasing focus to arrive at opting out rather than in – hence a 'dark pattern'. I and other users will most likely be able to opt out in the future as well, but only until we submit to the desired policy. After all, as I am given to understand, my opting in would be an aid to people with visual impairments. Remaining opted out is thus an implicit slight to those fellow subjects of mine, whom I implicitly owe inclusion. Resistance is always possible, but infinitely futile, as the site will keep asking until I give the correct answer.

This form of mediating resistance into different type(s) of subjection can on the one hand be seen as a tactic to ultimately make resistance impossible. If there is no resistance it is not power, but violence that flows in that technique (Foucault, 1982). On the other hand, it can be viewed as a way of making said resistance (productively) possible within the social environment at hand. In this dual view, then, it is a concurrent making possible and impossible the resistance, by allowing it to manifest as a non-conforming action in the digital space. In this case, then, it is a matter of perspective. If one adopts the view that the

governmentality is tending towards techniques where, ultimately, all resistance is attritioned into compliance, then that is an ultimately violent governmentality that would make subjects unfree, chained without possibility for resistance. If, on the other hand, one views the digital space as similar to the social space existing (also) elsewhere, then this non-acquiescence to conformity made possibly speaks of a governmentality of power, yes, but also of a productive freedom in the digital. Perhaps not the freedom envisioned by Barlow (1996) and experienced in the early digital days by Clarke (1994) and Snowden (2019), but a freedom none-the-less. The subject can be whatever she wants to be – or in other terms, she can define what subject she is, according to the categories provided – as long as she subjects herself to the radically visible digital state of being. That being said, her subjection is (at least formally) contingent on her linking that subjectivity to the identity she has in relation to her offline nation state. Thus, the digital state enacted through algorithms knows both what she is in her own mind, and in the collective mind of her offline political entities, as well as what she is according to the statistical collective she is part of. This brings us back to the pastoral power of the modern state. Knowing ‘omnes et singulatim’ – all in the collective and each in the individual sense – the state power is able to carry definitions of the earthly salvation of each and every-one, which is its goal (Foucault, 1979A; Foucault, 2006 [1979]). In these operations, the digital state not only constitutes the user-citizen as a double digital subject, it also measures said subject individually and collectively.

The basic operations and techniques of this digital state, then, emerge as eerily similar to the pastoral power operations and the governmentality described by Foucault. What is not clear, however, is how salvation is defined. The salvation for subjects of the modern state of Foucault changed over time, but moved increasingly towards ensuring health and longevity, as measured by medical and social sciences and objectifications. Guided by increasingly sophisticated measurements and computations, the discipline and spread of statistics enabled seemingly rational ends to be defined, from whence to derive the means of ideal government (Foucault, 2006 [1979]). But what defines the ends towards which these seemingly similar digital techniques are steering?

Having sketched out the meta-physicality, and quasi-legal rules and structure of the Facebook subject, I have shown how the modes of individualisation and structures of governance found in this digital milieu resemble those explored by Foucault, as he described the governmentality of the modern state: A pastoral power seeking to lead the user-citizens towards utility-maximised salvation. This raises the question, however, what that salvation is to be. Where are those subjects to be governed and guided to? To approach an answer, I turn now away from the structure and further into the techniques themselves. I come, finally, to look more directly at the governmentality of, on, and in the digital state of Facebook.

7. THE GOVERNMENTALITY OF THE DIGITAL STATE

In the preceding chapter, I outlined the meta-physical structure of the coded social space of Facebook, as well as the quasi-legal paradigm outlined to enshrine the prevailing norms in law. In this we saw how the meta-physical structure surrounding the Facebook subject is laden with inequalities in information and control, producing a high degree of control to the visual representation of user-subject's self-subjection, while rendering that same subject radically visible and governable to the cyber policies of the site. We further saw how the complex interplay of knowledge-power inside and outside its sphere of direct domination, the digital state of Facebook has been and is still being transformed ever more into a state-like universal referent in its milieu. Finally, it appeared how this duty to govern by virtue of having to govern in order to create implies and indeed demands ever more complex techniques of subjection.

Now, I move on to focus on the discourses embedded in those meta-physical and legal structures that conduct the conduct of user-citizens, to better understand the governmentalities at play. I will analyse the prevailing discourses of the cyber policies on Facebook, as seen through the indirect lens of text about, with, and by those who write the code that constitute and govern this digital space. What we might consider the representatives of this iteration of the digital state while noting that the employees of Facebook Inc. are subjects of the digital state to at least the same degree as any other user. In considering the programmers of Facebook in particular, and engineers more broadly, I will generalise about a large, heterogeneous group. That is not to be confused with a positive claim as to the traits, hopes, or dreams of the actual singular and collective people now coding for Facebook. Rather, the aim here is to dig out the governing discourses of the governmentality at play, regardless of any causal claims about who or what embedded these discourses, when, where, how, or why. I am simply looking to see what is there, much in the same way as I might analyse the writings of any number of nation state bureaucrats to investigate the governmentality of the nation state – whatever nation state(s) and other bureaucrats they may materially represent. Though discourse analysis as a term is founded in linguistics, it has been deployed to analyse pictures, video, sound, and stand-up performances (Silveira, 2016; Quinn & Silveira, 2018). Here, I will deploy it to understand the governmentalities embedded in this structured environment built by code. I

begin with a look on the construction of “the user”, leading into an exploration of the ‘engineering ethos’ identified as a guiding principle for those who are writing the digital world (Pariser, 2011; Snowden, 2019; Coleman, 2013).

7.1 Hacking the user

The quasi-physicality of abstract places “in” Cyberspace has from the beginning been mirrored in the terms used to describe it. In a sense it can be hard to see the difference from a structure, created in the mind of a reader – as Foucault and others do so eminently – and a structure written out in code and presented by the flickering light on a screen. The difference, of course, is just that – the parsed representation, the product coming out of the black box. As probably all who have printed out some form of ‘hello, World’ have experienced, there is something uniquely satisfying about commanding an action in abstract language and having a device translate it into a product – even if this product is virtual and the printout is on that same screen that shows the code above (Snowden, 2019, p. 30). It is your will made manifest, your commands taking on a life of their own. It is no wonder that many early programmers have likened themselves to gods – after all, they build entire worlds with tips of their fingers (Barlow, 1996).

But even in these magic world, there are gremlins (if not devils). Whether tech supporter, programmer, or something in between, most who have dealt with computer users from a service point of view have experienced a piece of software or hardware reported not functioning according to expectation or design being due to “PEBCAK” (Problem Existing Between Chair And Keyboard): User error. User error is a term used to describe how the cause of something experienced and reported as a problem by a user is, in essence, a misunderstanding. Either due to misalignment of expectation, understanding, skill or a combination of these. The user tries to get the machine to perform some task she expects it to be capable of, with no success. While the dichotomous and somewhat adversarial understanding of “users” and “programmers” has arguably waned in a time where everyone is a user and where programmers have long since learnt that usability is a key design feature, it is still the case that those who design a physical or meta-physical environment have the ability to structure and enable – or disable – user behaviours (Winner, 1980; Bossetta, 2018). Further, even if programmers (and their bosses) increasingly see themselves as

paternalistic guides and caretakers, rather than misunderstood and antagonistic geniuses (Little & Winch, 2017), they are no less imbued with and aware of their power to shape the behavioural paths and patterns of their users.

Figure 12: Illustration of ‘How users see programmers’ and vice versa (Vas, 2013)

Seemingly an afterthought of the adaptation of, and to, digital technologies, in the second decade of the third millennia of our somewhat arbitrary counting, citizens and politicians have become increasingly aware of the implications of choices made by programmers. This thesis, of course, is a product and part of that reckoning. The literature and press coverage of technology is ripe with expressions and aphorisms, as the ones mentioned above. Two concepts worth mentioning here are ‘hacking the user’ and ‘dark patterns’. Hacking is a term used amongst many who consider themselves tech-savvy to describe fiddling with something – especially something mechanical or digital – normally in order to make it work better, or serve

an entirely different purpose than intended by its designer(s). It is often connected to a common ethos seen among engineers and programmers (Coleman, 2013; Pariser, 2011; Snowden, 2019). In the common vernacular hacking has increasingly been associated with what those same people might term “black hat hacking”, meaning a malevolent actor employing computer code to perform unauthorised operations on/in IT systems not belonging to herself. Whether hacking the user is understood as employing the word in a somewhat benevolent version of the first sense, or the second, the term implies tinkering with the user to make “it” (an subject-object) behave in a desired fashion. This can be done using what some (e.g. Waldman (2019)) have taken to somewhat ominously calling ‘dark patterns’. The current day users of sites and apps have been socialised into certain visual and graphic cues of desired human-computer interaction. If most users are assumed (or desired) to want to accept, say, cookies, without spending too much time on reading background information, a small font text, perhaps on a blurry background might state that ‘By clicking or navigating the site, you agree to allow our collection of information on and off Facebook through cookies.’ (Facebook, 2019D). Sometimes text like this is accompanied by an inviting, brightly coloured OK-button. The upshot is that most users will do as asked, and click the button that will let them move on or forward with whatever it is they were doing, before this interruption, this hindrance, was inserted to block their path. The learned or intuited codes of human-machine conduct that informs many user actions exacerbate the comfort and usability of using web based services, but it also opens up for suggestive pathways to get users to perform actions they might not have agreed to, had they been asked about their acceptance in more neutral terms (or had been asked to make a principal decision, affecting a standard answer to all web sites without renewed obstructive interference in each singular session). Using such cues to have users behave in ways that are potentially not in their best interest, as objectively observed by the (Gramscian) observer, is what is termed as employing dark patterns.

As I am working from a Foucauldian perspective, I will not go so far as to assert given ideal interests for users. Rather, my interest is that the existence and academic discussion of dark patterns further underlines the tendency to constitute user-citizens as subject-objects to be steered towards desired ends. These ends might be digital at first – the user-citizen needs to tacitly accept the terms and conditions without balking – but as Zuboff (2019) emphasises, the current and future user-citizen to be controlled, very much includes

the consumer in her offline as well as online capacity. We see, then, a governmentality which views all and everything as constructs to be fit into object-oriented programming, parsed and sorted into the packages that will operate as designed (or close enough to). In a reversal of Kant, the user-citizen is constructed as a subject-object to be programmed, her behaviour to be engineered. Like a small human child who has learnt to respond to a smile with a grin, without grasping the intricacies of social signals possible between humans and how humans might through these influence each other's behaviour, the human user responds as taught without much thought as to why they are lead to this junction and having it presented in such a way. To be sure, everything else would be even more tiresome, but the result remains that the interaction between user and program remains unequal. As unequal as that between an adult and a child. And in this case, the adult acts according to precepts set by the programmer, the engineer. Precepts that are now becoming fluent, as we rely increasingly on algorithms to define not just means, but ends.

7.2 Trust me, I'm an engineer

It is an obvious truth that the digital milieus we interact with and within are coded. It has been coded by many hands and commands, but among those who have defined coding as it grew exponentially, there is a decided prevalence of certain discourses, both in the chat rooms and the code itself (Coleman, 2013). The formally or informally trained engineers and computer scientists who create the structuring code of meta-physicality are far from a heterogeneous group. Still, as with most abstract groupings, it has been found meaningful to look at "them" as a group with somewhat collective tendencies, structures, and norms (Coleman, 2013; 2014; Pariser, 2011). Thus, scholars like Coleman (2013; 2014), Zuboff (2019) and Lessig (2006), as well as commentators such as Pariser (2011) have been able to sketch with broad strokes some of the values and assumptions encoded in these digital structures.

Facebook, seen as a coded artefact, is originally conceptualised and coded by Mark Zuckerberg and like-minded predominantly white, heterosexual cis-men from "Ivy League" universities in the US, and or Silicon Valley (or Palo Alto) (Kirkpatrick, 2011). Mark Zuckerberg retains leadership of Facebook to this day, having more or less successfully positioned himself as synonymous with the company in terms of Public Relations (Little & Winch, 2017). While both the person, persona, and Cæsarian tendencies of Mark Zuckerberg are

interesting, they are not the focus here. Rather, the point is the simple fact that he, being a “tech bro” retains a guiding influence of what is coded, why, and how. For these reasons, and because computer scientists and engineers are the ones doing the actual coding, it is relevant to explore the discourses of the engineering ethos in general and of Facebook in particular.

The section title “trust me, I’m an engineer” refers to a popular meme on the Internet. As much humour online – and especially that which is addressed to coders – the comedic effect is sarcastic in that it plays on a post facto self-reflection about a solution that favours function over form and efficiency over quality. It is often accompanied by pictures of less-than-ideal, but workable (and often inherently amusing) solutions to practical problems.

Figure 13: Trust me, I'm an engineer (Google Image Search)

While the meme displays a self-critical and –reflective consideration of an engineer, it also implies that such reflection and critique comes after the solution has been built and implemented. The engineering

ethos values problem-solving, efficiency, and speed. Considerations, as a rule, come after. This relates to the pragmatism of modern “science” touched upon in the earliest chapters of the thesis. Rather than spend time debating the constitution and possible hidden problems and potentials of a given thing, the archetypical engineer quickly asserts what the problem appears to be, how it can be solved (as fast and/or as efficient as possible), and proceeds to implement the first workable solution that comes to mind.

7.2.1 Move fast and break things

This meme points towards what Evgeny Morozov (2013, p. 19), borrowing a ‘pejorative’ (sic) term from architectural studies, terms ‘solutionism’: an ideology that implies viewing any potential challenge as a Gordian knot to be cut by the sword of Internet-era technology. He emphasises how his point is less a re-formulation of the old adage that ‘... for someone with a hammer, everything looks like a nail’ (ibid. p. 20), and more focused on how this ideology implies treating any and every challenge as a simple problem, to be treated in similar fashion to a coding problem. This type of problem-framing and –solving he connects in particular to Silicon Valley start-ups and internet-related technologies.

This same way of thinking is evident in the way Facebook is originally described by its creators (Zuckerberg, Bosworth, Cox, Sanghvi, and Cahill) in 2006:

A system and method provides dynamically selected media content to someone using an electronic device in a social network environment. Items of media content are selected for the user based on his or her relationships with one or more other users. ... The user's interactions with media content available in the social network environment are monitored, and those interactions are used to select additional items of media content for the user.

(United States of America Patent No. 8171128).

While this is intrinsic to the patent format, even the notion that a (coded) connection of human users is to be defined as a technology to be described in the same terms as once captured the plans behind the cogs and wheels of industry underpins the inherently instrumentarian logic embedded in these techniques (Zuboff, 2019. See also explanation of Zuboff’s ‘instrumentarian power’ in Chapter 5). For Facebook, this

way of thinking has been openly embraced and fuelled from the get-go in the former internal motto of the company, 'Move fast and break things' (Miscellaneous, 2020B).

Figure 14: Move fast and break things (Deerkoski, 2014)

If, under this governmentality, a problem is encountered – or better said, if something appears to be a problem, then the response is immediate. The problem must be quantified, computed, and the solution as logically determined should be implemented immediately. In this view, interference in any of these steps is unproductive and unhelpful at best, disruptive and damaging at worst. Thus, when encountered by the criticism of how their platform creates echo chambers and filter bubbles, the response by a team of Facebook engineers was essentially “it’s not a bug, it’s a feature” (Bakshy, Messing, & Adamic, 2015). Having utilised their exclusive (and virtually un-restricted) access to user data on Facebook, the engineers determined that while the algorithms did indeed lead to the creation of echo chambers and filter bubbles, this was due to ostensibly objectively determined user preferences and choices (Bakshy, Messing, &

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Adamic, 2015; Tüfekçi, 2015). In the end, all the News Feed algorithms did was organise content according to the user's (intrinsic) wishes, as deduced by their behaviour.

The main creative force behind the company that became a digital state, Mark Zuckerberg, who instituted said motto, similarly shows ample evidence of Facebook Inc. being infused with this logic. As the main shareholder of Facebook, he is perhaps more autocrat than spokesperson for Facebook Inc. and while the public speech of a politician is not to be confused with the in-house speak of the ultimate head of development, the rhetoric in these performative acts is telling. His is a rhetoric of identifying the solvable problem in a given challenge and then proceeding to a solution. The most pertinent perhaps being the AI-powered censorship system set to policing each user:

... we have a plan to further reduce the amount of harmful content. Our AI systems already proactively identify about 90% of hate speech [which] we remove before anyone even reports it.

(Zuckerberg, 2020B)

This particular cyber policy which he also mentions in his interview with Zittrain (Zuckerberg, 2019B) conducts the conduct of the user-citizen in a way never before possible. In encountering the challenge of unwanted behaviour made possible by the productive power of code, further code is added to censor and discipline the subjects who perform such unwanted versions of the allowed behaviour. Similarly, faced with climate change, Zuckerberg-Facebook reacts by devoting some of their resources into re-shaping the knowledge and conduct of their user-subjects:

Today we're launching the Climate Science Information Center ... The Climate Science Information Center will include factual resources from trusted organizations and, most critically, it will include actionable steps you can take in your everyday life to combat climate change. ...

(Zuckerberg, 2020A)

Again, Zuckerberg-Facebook exhibits openly benevolent aims. In assuming responsibility for solving this issue in general, and by actively aiming to govern individual and collective user-citizens in particular, he

exhibits a state governmentality aimed at putting all economies of power and knowledge under its purview (Foucault, 2006 [1979]).

A leader who reacts with ideas and efforts to benevolently solve problems as they are put in front of him is not a damning feature. Perhaps it is even a redeeming one. What might gnaw at the critical observer is the very idea that these problems are Facebook's to solve. To this, of course, Zuckerberg has a solution:

... I understand people are concerned that we have so much control over how they communicate on our services. ... That's why we're establishing an independent Oversight Board for people to appeal our content decisions.

(Zuckerberg, 2019G)

In other words, the problem of the power of the digital state of Facebook lies not in the structure, but simply in who governs that structure, according to what logics. Similarly, when presented with the potential challenges from AI-powered surveillance systems to human agency (by Yuwal Noah Harari), Zuckerberg means to continue the development of the tools and solve potential problems with a framework of control:

"... It's not clear that a democratic process alone solves it, but I do think that it is mostly a policy question, right."

(Zuckerberg, 2019E)

A second gnawing to the same observer, and more important here, is the way in which the user-subjects are consistently treated as nodes and objects to be governed instrumentally. They are to be led towards desired outcomes. Facebook Inc. has changed its motto, and updated their rhetoric about, and approach to many of the perceived challenges and critiques they are faced with. But the way they approach whatever is perceived as a problem tends to fall back into the same instrumentalist logic. It carries an imperative to never go backward, never abandon a technology or technique, but rather adapt, amend, or add to it.

7.2.2 Moving forward, pushing through

In a 2018 study, Facebook engineers determined that emotions could indeed be transferred from user to algorithm and from algorithm to user in an automated recommendation environment online (Hilbert, Ahmed, Cho, Liu, & Luu, 2018). This led them to conclude that there should be implemented (more) quantified measures of emotional content in algorithmic recommendations, to allow for 'more socially responsible algorithms' (sic) (ibid. p. 2). The same way of thinking is also evident in a conference paper from the same year, where Warlop, Lazaric, and Mary (2018) of Facebook explores how to more efficiently prevent users from getting bored while inside their digital space.

In many ways the technologies and theories collectively called AI (Artificial Intelligence) – whether a misnomer for what is essentially a collection of “IF, THEN” statements or not – can be seen as a model instance of this engineering technique of power-knowledge. Following Morozov’s point, whatever problem may occur the solution is apt to be a relatively narrow definition of the problem, some measurements of a solution, and an AI to compute a link from A to B through regression analysis. With the AI of today, this goes a step further than applying immediate, obvious solutions to a narrowly defined problem. A current-day AI can be fed with increasingly abstract and vague problem definitions – e.g. “Find similarity patterns in this dataset, to positively determine subject sexuality (operationalised as a binary, a scale, or...), based on profile picture.” As is often the case, the ultimate instance of this approach can be found in various places in popular culture, for instance in the form of a super-computer tasked with creating peace on Earth (West World season 3) or just the ultimate joke, which determines the extinction of humankind to be the most efficient means towards that end, immediately launching all the nuclear weapons in the world (South Park S2E15, “Funnybot”). A problem of unclear definition, to be sure, but also illustrative of the inherent problem with outsourcing cognitive functions to non-biological machines. If the prevailing logic is instrumentarian, and the governmentality (mainly) constructs problems and tasks as solved by achieving particular measurable ends, then the user clearly emerges as a subject-object to be governed towards defined ends. An industrial lamb to be herded to the fold for safety – or for slaughter, if that be its computed salvation.

The user-subject conceived as an object to be optimised is also comprehensively evident in the meta-physical structures of Facebook laid out in chapter 5. Across the functions and features, the user-subject is met with suggestions and suggestive imperatives, enticing her to lend her human weight to the socially productive force of the algorithms. Suggested friends, suggested conversation partners, suggested activities and fundraisers; every possibly action – all of which already socialised whether inherently social in nature or not – is optimised to birth as much further social interaction as possible. The logic is simple: more is more. As Zuboff has shown, how the ideal surveillance capitalist sees the digital subject can easily be compared to how the industrial capitalist sees the factory worker: A subject-object to be governed and disciplined with increasing efficiency in order to maximise the productive output of the subject. The focus here is on the discursive structure and not the actors, but the ideational construct is illustrative of the optimising part of the governmentality of the digital state. The meta-structure is infused with reflections of a subject constituted as an optimisable producer and consumer of resources where economics of scale point towards more being better, and forward to another click being an end unto itself.

7.2.3 The governmentality of Facebook Inc.

While these examples serve to show how Facebook engineers follow the above logic in application of their skills, the same operational logic is evident in other dealings of the digital state of Facebook. Perhaps as a consequence of the ‘move fast and break things’ way of thinking, Facebook has been embroiled in various lawsuits, investigations, and general instances of scrutiny. Documents from several of these cases are publicly available due to various and recurring leaks (Campbell, 2019; Sanders, 2020), something we, with Foucault, might recognise as resistance which should pique our scholarly attention. From such documents (and the investigative articles surrounding them), we know among other things that Facebook used their access to users’ smartphones to surveil behaviour outside and unrelated to their usage of the Facebook app (Gross & Klein, 2018). An access level they shared with developers (Dance, LaForgia, & Confessore., 2018). Presumably, this was done in order to optimise their ability to find possible ‘Facebook friends’ to suggest for users, and to measure the usage of then-competing apps, such as WhatsApp. Similarly, while Facebook has made a data download tool available to users in response to the GDPR, this tool limits the data dump to that data which ‘they consider relevant and interesting for the user’ (Schrems vs. Facebook,

2020, my translation). Other cases point to similar behaviour where infringements or violations are either considered expendable in a risk-reward estimation – or have simply not been considered at all (Kelly, 2018; Gold, 2018; Frenkel, Confessore, Kang, Rosenberg, & Nicas, 2018; Halverson, 2019). In this behaviour as well we see the engineering ethos mirrored, as solution is favoured over consideration.

The over-arching ends – the salvation towards which these actions lead – seem to be knowledge, growth, and dominance. First, the digital state seeks to know all about each subject, individually and collectively. This quest for knowledge does not start or stop with the subject actively using the services provided by the state, as any- and everyone that can be surveilled is surveilled, before, after, or whether they were ever active users. Second, the digital state encroaches upon, colonises, and attempts to become the dominant part of any and all functions and institutions it can, embroiling everything in its web of power. In this we see the echo of the Foucauldian state which seeks to enter and govern all walks of life. A logic which can perhaps not be fully separated from what one would expect from a capitalist company seeking market dominance, but one does not discount the other (Morozov, 2019). Following EU's Vestager and Zuboff we might concede that Facebook, along with Google, Apple, Microsoft, and Amazon, are simply acting out their roles as capitalist companies unhinged from constraint and creating such market-destroying monopolies as warned about by economists of all stripes and colours. But in the Foucauldian framework the logics and workings of state are not contingent on whether they are bound in entities formally named "states" or "companies". If pursued further, this line of thought might lead to a wider consideration of the connections between capitalism, Enlightenment, and governmentality, but that would also lead us further away from the case at hand. Suffice to say that the digital state is steered towards growth, dominance, and ever-increasing ways and angles through which to surveil and subject its subjects. Even if Facebook's engineers are no longer moving quite as fast and have backed somewhat away from breaking things, wherever one looks Facebook Inc. is still applying the same logic to the problems they perceive. From the speeches, the public posts, and the interviews of Mark Zuckerberg, over the documents leaked and published about internal operations as court cases and media scandals have continued to roll over these last years, to the structure of the digital space laid out above, the engineering ethos, and the instrumental discourse appears steady over time.

In this broader, more abstract turn, I have established the digital user-citizen of Facebook as a subject-object to be controlled towards increasingly abstractly defined ends (defined by algorithms tasked with converting abstract goals into specific salvation-ends). I have shown the engineering ethos prevalent at Facebook Inc. and evident in their internal and external discourses and workings. In all of this, we see a strong resemblance to the governmentality of the modern state, as described by Foucault (2006 [1979]). One that is on the one hand more abstract, dealing with subjects through code, power defined by algorithms and mediated through electric lights in silicon cables, on the other hand more brutally direct, as there is no veneer to mask the structure of control and governance. It has to be as it is, otherwise it could not be – the very nature of code demands it (much as the very nature of social relations demands power relations between subjects). These insights in hand, I move now back to the actual entity at hand, to look more concretely at the digital state of Facebook, and how its subjects are governed.

7.3 Governing the Facebook subject

The meta-structure of Facebook has undergone many major and minor changes over the years. In chapter 5 I outlined some of these changes, to contextualise this discursive analysis dealing with Facebook as it currently is. I turn back to the built reality of Facebook here, not to look again at the meta-physical structures, but more to consider the structures of more abstract subjection, the cyber policies enacted to govern the user-citizens; the techniques of the digital state.

7.3.1 Self-subjectivisation and conduct of self

A main theme recurring in Facebook's history, functions, and rhetoric is one of self-expression and – representation. The site was conceptualised and created as and remains a site for mediated social representation as well as, increasing over time, mediated social connection and communication. To this end, the governing techniques enshrined in code are productive, enabling and encouraging social actions and interactions in relation to almost all content seen on the site. Many actions, such as writing a 'Post' (also known as a 'Status Update') or a 'Story' are inherently social, sending out communiqués to be read, seen, or heard and perhaps responded or performatively reacted to by other social actors. Further, establishing connections, such as 'like'-ing something, sharing a location or action, expressing interest in

an event, or becoming a 'fan' of or 'friend' of a person or other entity, is recast as meta-social actions and mediated to those deemed to find it of interest. In other words, all conceivable social actions are enabled, and all (not inherently social) actions are socialised (as well as monetised cf. Zuboff, 2019). This means that a subject performing subjecthood through and on Facebook is an inherently more fully social – and surveillanced – subject than her pre-digital equivalent. If every step I take, every move I make, is being reported to my 'friends' and 'followers', the visibility and spread only limited by individualised-individualising algorithms which I cannot control, and privacy filters which I seldom reflect on or change, it is, at least possibly, being seen. Meanwhile, all of these actions are covertly seen and parsed – conducted, acted upon – by the governing algorithms. As Foucault has shown us, letting us know that we are always potentially being seen is a powerful technique for governing the conduct of others and inducing disciplining of self (Foucault, 1995 [1975]). Further, the inherent sociality of all experienced content in the digital milieu doubly underscores that actions performed in this space are re-iterated as social. Whatever content one encounters, it can be commented on or shared (with some few exceptions), but also reported to the digital authorities, as well as to the personalised-personalising algorithm governing one's own view of the social world mediated through Facebook.

Whereas the coded rules are all but unbreakable, and the written laws are bureaucratically, if imperfectly, policed, the social rules in a digital space are fluid and context-dependent. Similarly to how humans act differently in different offline environments, they also adapt and edit behaviour according to differing digital socialities (Goffman, 2012 [1959]; Meyrowitz, 1986). Not only is there a difference between how one might act in a private message (Messenger) or in a public comment (News Feed), but in the layered social spaces with varying degrees of visibility to heterogeneous audiences and participants the social rules can be as common – and as different – as among the social groups of partners, families, friends, school, work, the pub, the opera (Meyrowitz, 1986). In these spaces, individually and as a whole, the social rules are constantly under negotiation with some social actions (particularly what we might call speech actions) being 'submitted for review' to the digital police. These social rules, however, are also heavily influenced by the algorithms embedded in the (meta-)physical structure of the reality. Not only does the adaptive code of Facebook steer what one can do and be but, crucially, it governs what one can see. To consciously

act upon something, one must first see it, and so in filtering not only type of content and users, but also (types of) comments for each, these algorithms decide what is made knowable and thus possible to be acted upon by each subject. In this way, two users might see the same content, but in a frame or with an accompanying text tailored not just to their personal interests, as judged by what they and meta-dataly similar users have interacted with in the past, but to an operationalisation of what, in Zuckerberg's words, is more 'valuable' to them (Zuckerberg, 2018A). The subject made possible and encouraged here is an inherently hyper-social subject. It is on the one hand a voyeur who is told where interests, entities, and contacts go and why, whom or what they interact with and what they say, what they like and dislike, what they (say they) think, and how they look or what they are (performatively) sharing a view of. On the other hand, the subject is a constant performer, obliged to offer opinions and share experiences related to any and all aspects of life – whether situated in the digital or physical sphere of self. This simultaneously surveillanced and surveillancing subject is continually prompted to actively perform more of one or both of these social actions, and passively have algorithms perform them on her behalf. The Facebook user-citizen, then, is first and foremost constituted as a surveillanced-surveillancing mediated social subject. Every part element of the actions made possible in the space is imbued with sociality.

Compared to other social media sites of its time (or before), the early Facebook was often noted for its comparative restrictiveness towards users (Kirkpatrick, 2011; MacKinnon, 2012). In its current iteration(s), however, it is in many ways more open. Creating an account is no longer restricted to those affiliated with specific institutions, and is not always subject to scrutiny of proof of legal (offline) identity (Facebook, 2021D). Further, the actions made possible on the site or made possible to re-constitute as mediated social actions during or after the performance of said action in a given different setting (the offline world, a computer game, a different social platform) are ever-expanding in type and form. The story of Facebook's development can be cast in many lights, and one of them would be one of adding social options for users, assigning to or increasing sociality of already existing actions performed on/through the platform, and connecting action performed elsewhere, constituting it as a mediated social object in this space (see in this a pendant to the 'platformization' explored by Helmond (2015)). The imbued governance logic of socialisation leads the digital state of Facebook (as a collection of techniques) to always seek to constitute more

users as social objects to be assigned and related to the existing subjects, chief among them the user-citizens. This drive towards socialisation leads to what has also been termed colonisation of aspects or avenues of human life not themselves taking place on Facebook (Couldry & Mejias, 2019). This is, of course, reminiscent of Foucault's finding that the modern state apparatus inherently seeks to subjectify and govern every aspect of life (Foucault, 1979A), not to mention studies of the ethos (and governmentality) of (neo-liberal) capitalism which have shown how all aspects of human and social life are increasingly infused with transactional logics (Beck, 2005).

7.3.2 Cyber panopticon

The user-citizen of the digital state is doubly subjected by meta-physical, meta-legal, and normative techniques all directed towards realising her as a surveillanced-surveillancing subject or, more polemically put, a voyeur-exhibitionist (or a 'prosumer' cf. Alvin Toffler, *The Third Wave* (1980)). The responsive, personalised web 2.0 design of the site communicates to the user that she is always seen, even as it sees more than she might imagine, when also scrolling speed and pauses are recorded as data markers for algorithmic optimisation, and behind-the-scenes interaction with her extended digital self (something which will lead me to develop the concept of a third subjection in chapter 8). This always seen and always seeing subject can always see and show more, and so should always see and show more. As all actions are rendered social, they are also recast as performative and communicative. Like a patient whose blood pressure is measured or a spy under a polygraph, all vestiges of existence – not least the data sweat left behind by her data doubles – the subject must now place her actions under (potential) scrutiny by others, and thus by herself. At the same time, she is invited to engage in the scrutiny of others, feeding back – or forward – social cues in the various formats made possible.

Further, due to the performativity of the self inherent in the medialisation of the social, the desire to be seen, be recognised by others (cf. Honneth, 1995), there arises a normative imperative to react. An imperative that is embedded in the algorithms that govern what is shown to the individual subject. Indeed, the more likely user-citizens are (statistically) to interact with a given item, the more likely they are to be shown something similar to that item. This specific technique has also become the site of considerable

resistance to this power. Much of the criticism social media companies in general and Facebook in particular have faced these past years has revolved around the distribution of news and opinions. It has been pointed out and explored extensively how the, at least to a self-reflected sense (see Bakshy, Messing, & Adamic, 2015), agnostic and objective distribution based mainly on likelihood to interact as a proxy for interest, can potentially reinforce held opinions and biases (Sunstein, 2007; Pariser, 2011; Brønholt, 2020). Further, the targeted advertising made possible by the extensive data profiling of users continue to spark debate, especially in relation to political advertisement before elections (Associated Press, 2020). This is relevant here, as this resistance has shaped the governmentality of the technique, embedding it with ever more (pastoral, patriarchal) responsibility towards user-citizens. Thus, the governance technique is not – perhaps no longer – simply geared to make subjects into voyeur-fetishists, but also aimed at promoting their individual and collective (mental) health, as measured by (quantitative) psychological and sociological techniques of reflexive measurement of well-being. Something which reminds us yet again of the governmentalised state and its pastoral power, as described by Foucault (Foucault, 2006 [1979]; 1979A).

7.3.3 The digital pastorate

Not only does the digital state of Facebook in many and increasing ways embody the techniques and rationalities of state in a Foucauldian sense. The governmentalities of the techniques of subjection and power operating in this digital space – a space which connects to and influences the lifeworlds of both humans and things, across different realms of physicality – are strikingly similar to specifically those of the modern state treated by Foucault. They are pastoral in the Foucauldian sense, governing subjects individually and collectively with intimate knowledge and (social) objectification of each and any action performed by those subjects. Techniques through which minute ideal objects are determined and presented for each user, as she is steered towards her personal salvation, as statistically determined. To even exist on, with, and through Facebook demands and carries with it the double subjectification of the Foucauldian state (Foucault, 1982), and the aim to improve and better the lives of subjects, as statistically determined (Foucault, 1979A).

Koopman (2019, p. 155) underlines how constantly having to actively perform our informational selves in preformatted forms in turn shapes our perception of ourselves. By constantly having to tick a box reifying “race” as a meaningful indicator for who I am, it in turn becomes part of the assemblage I consider socially significant in differentiating myself from others – it becomes part of my description of who I “am”. As the algorithms take over, I am increasingly spared checking the boxes. Cookies and cross-referencing databases keep track of my informational self and its differentiation is increasingly performed without my active participation. My activities input into what is algorithmically assigned as meaningful for me, in terms of interests (again, particularly ads, but also web search results and cultural artefacts) – but my offline self does not have to perform it (ibid. 165). In this way, the further shaping of my perception of self is less and less influenced by crude techniques asking me to reflect and interpret my own data points. In a sense quite emancipatory. But, on the other hand, the shaping is performed more subtly when I am increasingly walled into this outside reflection of meaningful data points. I no longer have to state that I am whatever race and gender – but the social and informational world I encounter is shaped according to these and other data points considered meaningful for me. In this skewed mirror, I am shaped – lulled – into an image of normalcy where the world appears as made for me. In this *gated community of the digitised mind* I might be radicalised in the eyes of my offline political community as an effect of being normalised according to my ever-adapting algorithmically assigned preferences (Brønholt, 2017).

The ideal of objectivity demands scepticism towards the human’s ability to perceive what is best for her – her salvation – and much more so towards her ability to properly communicate such interests as she might perceive herself to have (Foucault, 2002 [1972]). But in knowing all and everyone, the state – now in its digital form – can finally answer the riddle of paradise (Foucault, 1979A). In the radically de-ontological utilitarianism of objective market forces, we can see what the subjects “truly” want (Friedman, 1953), and now, finally, is emerging the means through which to optimise connections between buyer and seller to give them all measurable increase in happiness we could ever think of.

Foucault told us how the new political economy of the governmentalised state would continue to apply objectification, subjection, tallying, statistics and economics to both determine and pursue the new

pastoral salvation. But there was perhaps an inherent problem with this, in the pre-digital state operations: After all, the search was for objective measures and operations, and though infused with governmentality, mathesis, and positivism, the operators of state remained as human as their fellow, double subjects. No more. Though the techniques and tools of governance are similar to the state that came before, the carriers, and operators of them – the “arms” of the law – of the digital state are different. Where the Weberian and Foucauldian state apparatuses had police, Facebook has algorithms. Where the states of the offline world have buildings, roads, and traffic signals, the digital state has coded, abstract, and changeable meta-physical structures. The subjects, originally, remain the same as they are mostly human and other legal entities of the offline world – but these subjects are enhanced and stretched by more than ledgers, as their digital selves interact independently of their human originators. This core difference has implications, not just for digital humanity, but for post-human sociality (or post-human humanity, if you will), and for post-human society. In the age of digital modernity humanity and subjecthood itself has changed, at least discursively. Because now, so it seems, all has finally been rendered computable, and so not just the “what” of the subjects, but the “how” of the operations of governmentality are being handed over to algorithms, precluding the question of “why” – a question that was always too big for human minds to handle anyway, and impossible to truly answer without a God or a Deep Thought to refer to for eschatological, pure truth. With these increasingly powerful systems of computation set free to define salvation according to whatever “objectivity” they are embedded with, the inter-subjectivity of those governed changes. When algorithms determine not just the measures or even the means, but the ends as well, the digital subject becomes truly governed by algorithms.

I have explored the discourses in, around, and by Facebook, determining a governmentality of the digital state which doubly subjects users in a virtual replay of the modern state described by Foucault. It is a governmentality that constructs the user-citizen as objects to be pastorally governed individually and collectively towards salvation. Though what that salvation looks like is less fixed than ever. Indeed, it depends on the constitution of the individual and collective digital subject. A subject which I now turn to.

8. THE DIGITAL SUBJECT

I have explored the construction of the digital environs and the user-subjects governed inside it. The prevailing focus on the structure and the structuring leaves us the wiser as to the workings of power and subjection in the digital state, but it also begs the question: What about the subject? To approach an answer to this, I will twist the Rubik's cube yet again. The user-citizen of and on Facebook, the digital state, is still the human subject, seeping, bleeding and sweating into the digital. As clear as the digital subjection might seem in the analogue above, as unclear the self-subjection becomes, the more we stare into a mirror darkly. First, the analogue human stepped onto the platform and enacted sociality through and via the digital. Now, as the subject is itself increasingly digital, the question of self-subjection becomes increasingly muddled.

The digital human subject comes into existence once subjectified in relation to its corresponding offline human. On Facebook and in the normal case this will follow the process described above where a user adheres to the discipline of the sign-up flow and populates a node with what data is needed to make a digital subject. The most significant part of the creation of a digital I is perhaps the strictly unceremonious ceremony where the human falsely attest to having read and accepts untold lines of legal text, designed to ensure that all rights possible to imagine in an Anglo-Saxon judicial system are reserved by the sovereign. Having thus formally created the digital subject and subjected it to the sovereign, the Facebook persona comes into existence. It should be noted, though, that also a digitised/digital entity that has not yet consciously subjected itself to the digital state (of Facebook or other sites of digital state power) will already exist as a "ghost subject". An echo of all steps trod online is stored and bartered by Facebook and others, and though one has not yet a profile on the site, an entity does still exist. If as nothing else, the digital subject exists as an empty point of reference – pictures stored in hex-code identified to depict the same human which is not yet actively known as a self-realised subject. Purchases and visits, browser data and habits – all of these might be logged and are simply awaiting linking to a self-submitting profile. Perhaps similar to an apartment, a social number, and a credit card registered as belonging to a subject of the pre-

digital modern state who has not yet herself contacted the authorities, but who is already passively known in the protocols and rows, only awaiting a print and a header for the file.

The meta-entity incepted by signing up as an active subject of the digital state immediately starts interacting with other entities. Data is shared across sites, platforms, and apps, and the subject is placed in relation to other digital entities – human and otherwise. The quantitatively richer the life of the digital subject, the more it can interact socially with or without the offline part of the human actively pursuing social action. The governing algorithms use the relational data of the subject both as means and ends to decide what objects to put in relative proximity and when. The digital subject might recommend to strangers a book she read, an event she will go to. She might, as part of an anonymised yet identifiable A/B group act as legislator and jury, informing or inadvertently deciding ongoing small changes to the formal structures that further subjectifies and shapes herself and others (Eriksson, Fleischer, Johansson, Snickars, & Vonderau, 2019). Apart from the social existence disconnected from the active participation of the offline human, the subject actions can also originate in the flesh. In this case, the subject interacts mainly with other similarly human-machine hybrid subjects, blending the social interaction instigated and performed in the digital and analogue spaces both.

8.1 The re-enchantment of life and the world

This social interaction is by no means restricted to the Facebook web site or app. Enmeshed in the whole of the digital eco-system, encompassing digital mirrors of all that is deemed either directly or indirectly worthy of digital existence, the digital persona interacts across time and space, its behaviour a trace of, but not determined by the actions instigated by the physical human it tethers its existence to, still. In this relational mirroring of the offline world objects too become reified with sociality and the world reinvested with something akin to the mystic science of pre-modern times.

In *The Order of Things* (1989 [1966]), Foucault tells of a science of times past where all things were more than they seemed. The digitised existence promises a return to this enchanted time where all was more than it seemed, and the world was not yet 'disenchanted' (Weber, 1919, p. 488). In the emerging

augmented reality, fantasy and other associative thinking becomes subject to control and formulation embedded not just in the structures of knowledge we carry in this human flesh, but also, perhaps rather, to associations indirectly programmed by others. As we visit galleries and assistants – both or either being mainly of the digital or of the mundane – tell us what to look for, what to see, and what to interpret in the arts and artefacts of times gone by. So the world becomes enchanted once again, as it is increasingly layered with digital structures of meaning. Already now, if we see a statue in a remote corner of a strange city, we might want to know more than our mortal gaze can see and turn to our phone for further information (or a Pokémon). In the near future, this information might be preloaded in the digital part of our selves, and reflected to us, once we pass by that statue and do indeed dwell our eyes on its chiselled features. Like the passive memory of a pre-digital self – surfacing and offering bits of learned history and art to better understand that which we see, the digital self will be informed instantaneously from the collective memory gathered in a server. Further, in this commonly accessible augmented reality of the near future, the statue might well come alive before our very eyes, pre-empting any internal fantasy. It might twirl and bow, as music plays, enticing children and adults alike to hear its story – perhaps interspersed with a slight narrative nod to the friendly sponsor of this free service, the hot dog vendor across the street. The story and even the statue might vary according to who is listening and watching. Algorithmically re-fashioned as each interactional subject and life itself is refashioned in each individual's experience thereof, the ambiguities of the collective recollection is condensed into one story for each subject – or one for the collective present, taking in their preferences, but adapting to fit them all and allow them to experience the same or close enough to. Perhaps the only individuality left will be in the sponsor mentioned, as the odd vegan out is prompted to try the bagel shop rather than the hotdog stand (or, perhaps more likely, vice versa for odd carnivore of the future). Thus, the increasingly mediated life-experience of the digital subject allows for re-enchantment and escape into an assigned dream to supplant the inner, dominated fantasy.

8.1.1 Re-animated flesh of concrete, steel, and dead fur

In the digitised life-world, then, not just the human subjects are (or, to a perhaps more cynical, perhaps just more empiricist view, seem as) social actors akin to those related to the offline humans at play. As

objects are actively and passively anthropomorphised and as the informational layers of meaning built upon all that is constituted as a subject of social code make the link to the physical world less and less relevant; as our social existence goes the way of work and value in a hyper-capitalist economy and becomes increasingly abstract, all but disconnected from its existence in an objective world (if ever anything did exist outside the ideational reflection), what objects we interact with – virtual or otherwise physical – become ever more salient social actors akin to those based on our own existence. As human subjects become increasingly digital and objectivised, the digital and digitised objects become increasingly human and subjectivised, and the lines are blurred ever more. Already now, sociality is increasingly mediated, carrying with it a digitalisation of parts of the subjects so that parts of the social part of each subject exist digitally – a sub-dividual unto itself, and no less a part of the whole than those parts which reside in her skull. The (in part virtually rendered) teddy bear finally comes truly alive and both child and parent can hear the answers to the questions posed in play. Perhaps the answers are not the same to each ear, and perhaps they are, due to laws defined by the automated sovereigns that govern those rules of interaction. Perhaps the dialogue is scrutinised and transcribed, all safeties taken to ensure that no harm comes to the child. Perhaps the talking teddy bear leads the game, as it is deemed safer than what the child's own mind might conceive. Its dance moves never suggestive, its jokes never too dirty for a young mind about to be disciplined into a perfectly docile existence, born to be saved. And perhaps in the brave new world to come, all children interacted with in this way are recorded and correlated, and the future play-things enact policies built to ensure that behaviour correlated with the children growing up to become undesirables is subverted and reprogrammed before the fact. Perhaps, when the pastoral power of the algorithmic state reaches its zenith, bordering on totality, humans will have arrived in a world free from worries as well as crime. A world of freedom and magic, even if it be resting on a physical world as seen through the lens of Hollywood dystopia in "The Matrix" – or perhaps just "Ready Player One".

8.1.2 Digitised humanity

Even before Turingian questions of sentience rear their heads to ask uncomfortable questions about the enslavement of those virtual entities, whether bound by mechanical flesh or simply related from a mythical cloud in an Icelandic cellar, the ethics and social reality of digital humanity becomes muddled. As the meta-

physical objects existing in the social world of digital humanity are infused with sociality of the same kind that connect the digital humans, the differences start to lose their meaning. We have seen – not just in films, but in news of some repute – humans profess love to and marry toys, quadruped animals, and digital personas (BBC, 2019). We have seen adult humans refusing to harm a robot they know not to be sentient (Darling, 2018). What, then of the Facebook user-citizens of tomorrow, friends and advertisements always present through the Oculus and the shifting network of social connection the digital parts of their selves are always engaged in? We can see these developments in two lights. One is that digital entities are increasingly socialised and personalised in a double sense. They are both becoming more personal, but also more like a person. The digital devices and applications increasingly mimic a subject position in their interaction with humans. ‘Good morning, Thorsten’ one app writes out – or even speaks – as I open it on my way to work. ‘What’s on your mind, Thorsten?’ the Facebook page asks me, inviting me to actively engage with the social world I am already passively engaged in behind my screen.

Humans are blending over more and spreading out across the digital, the sociality of our existence maintained increasingly on servers, as well as in our minds. At the same time as other entities on those servers interact with the digital parts of ourselves, they point to front-end interfaces that interact with the human part. In this two-pronged way, human-machine sociality is blended, and we are homogenised and individualised ever further, through individualising techniques set according to limited patterns – and those digital entities are homogenised along with us. Not only are our bodies becoming digital – enhanced by those cybertronic devices that allow us to move, think, and calculate with inhuman speed and surety – but also our unconscious minds are spreading outside that flesh which we call ours. Colonising and being colonised in turn by the digital subjects that are as much us as the feelings we experience when our human bodies shake someone’s hand.

This view of the human as exceeding the bounds of her mortal form, of course, does not limit itself to the digitised person of today. Mediated sociality has existed and does exist in many forms, and personhood has been enacted and stretched across time, space and materiality for all those we narrate about as “human”. Humanity, personhood, and existence can be mediated as feeling and thought – as memory and

writing. We still interact with thinkers like Foucault, though his physical form has expired, and we might do so again, in more meaningful terms when all of his works are fed into an AI tasked to create an interactable version of him, as fantasised of in the movie “her”. Often enough, we, as scholars of thinkers gone before and besides us, act as mediums in our own right, trying to convey our situated understanding of what that person would have thought of a student’s question. But there are differences, and critiques can certainly be raised of this view of humans as ephemeral existences spread out across all vessels that may carry a glimpse of nested truth about their individual being in the common consciousness.

In another and perhaps more clear sense, the digitised subject can be seen as akin to a formalised sovereign of old: The queen as a concept, as a technique. The queen might enact Her will through Her ministers (without constant, prior consultancy), She might become friends with one other monarch, enemies with another, mediated by diplomats, officers, and bureaucrats (Foucault, 1995 [1975], p. 28). Her will is done in courts across Her lands, and justice served in Her name. Today, of course, “the queen” has been more or less replaced by “the state”, but still Her (the state’s) will is served and the narrative continued by practitioners and researchers alike (as famously pointed out by Foucault

... [T]he institution of monarchy ... developed during the Middle Ages against the backdrop of the previously endemic struggles between feudal power agencies. The monarchy presented itself as a referee, a power capable of putting an end to war, violence and pillage and saying no to these struggles and private feuds. It made itself acceptable by allocating itself a juridical and negative function, albeit one whose limits it naturally began at once to overstep. Sovereign, law and prohibition formed a system of representation of power which was extended during the subsequent era by the theories of right: political theory has never ceased to be obsessed with the person of the sovereign. Such theories still continue today to busy themselves with the problem of sovereignty. What we need, however, is a political philosophy that isn't erected around the problem of sovereignty, nor therefore around the problems of law and prohibition. We need to cut off the King's head: in political theory that has still to be done.

(Foucault, 1979B, p. 121)

In a smaller, but similar sense, we see the barrister and the secretary, the hunting dog, and the 'please keep off my lawn' sign. All manner of ways in which we as individual subjects mediate ourselves and our interactions. The difference between the digital persona and at least some of these things I mention is, perhaps, what some would call "agency" or "autonomy". Signs and letters seldom perform other actions than exactly those they are prescribed to, the hunting dog seldom reports its orders to the God of Dogs¹², who then collect and correlate all dog-related data and feed it into a model suggesting what friends, family, and pizza to consume next in the social and physical milieu. While sociality and subjecthood might have been mediated in multiple ways in times gone by, never before has it in such profound and individualising-totalising ways been curated. Partly due to the unique nature of the digital, partly because of the governmentality of the digital state, the digital subject is re-constructed towards itself and others in disparate ways.

We have long had the possibility to stretch our sociality further than our own existence. But that was as static expressions of will and/or performed subjectivity. Now, as diplomats are to states, pastors to their God, each of us have social processes running in the digital, and those parts continually interact with those of other subjects, human and in-human alike. We are more than our bodies.

8.2 Triply subjected

We have seen how, on Facebook and beyond, the digital subject, spread across flesh and wire, is subjected in various ways and with various techniques (of self, of domination, of power-knowledge). Still, at a casual glance, there is talk of nothing more than a digitalisation of that which already is. Perhaps the digital is simply another arena for the relations of power and subjection we know so well, and so intricately described by Foucault to play out. I argue that it is indeed that but that it is also more.

¹² Let's call him Wroffer. Seems like that would be his name.

It is clear how the pastoral double subjection of individualisation and totalisation techniques is very much present in the governmentalities pervading the digital state, remember:

There are two meanings of the word “subject”: subject to someone by control and dependence; and tied to his own identity by a conscience or self-knowledge. Both meanings suggest a form of power which subjugates and makes subject to.

(Foucault, 1982, p. 781)

But that is not all, for the digital subject is triply subjected. First, to the digital sovereign who controls the social space she interacts in (Facebook), and on whom the very existence of her digital self depends; second, to her own subjection into the identifying categories supplied for the enactment of digital personhood; and, third, to the algorithms that surveil, control, and shape her, constantly changing not just what she sees, but what she is – the very subjecthood and sociality of her being.

In the classic formulation, the original Foucauldian subjection is best illustrated by the subject’s relation to an external and clearly defined hegemon – the sovereign (queen, state, digital state of Facebook). Figure 15 depicts a given subject (one of many who are identical in this relation of subjection) who is seen as a subject of the sovereign both by the sovereign and themselves.

Figure 15: Double subjection (self, sovereign)

In a more modern – and abstract – state, the subjection has shifted and happens according to and through techniques of subjection. As explored previously, such a technique implies a governmentality – a mode

according to which subjects are constituted for governance (note here especially the implications of Foucault’s own operationalisation of the term as discussed in chapter 3, subsection 4). This mode is part of the subjection of self and others, and dictates how subjects can be constituted as such, individually and collectively. While each subject is individually subjected by their internalised governmentality, as well as the collective governmentality, it is still a double subjection. Figure 16 illustrates this modality where the techniques of subjection (which are part of the super-structural technique called state) doubly subjects each subject in an individualising and totalising way. In this relation the subjects can realise – self-subject – themselves in different ways according to the configurations of power-knowledge. This modality still implies a double subjection, only different from the first illustration in that governmentality techniques have been introduced to the relations of power and subjection.

Figure 16: Relations of subjection to the modern state

In a digital version of this formulation (Figure 17), the functions and operations of power are influenced – aided – by algorithmic processing. Thus, the subjection is still (only) double, but it is transformed by a new factor with separate and different logics and influences. It is a double subjection like the ones that came before (sovereign, modern), but the internal operations of the techniques of power and subjection are being transformed. In this modality, (most) humans do not exist in the digital plane, but simply enact their symbolic and social existence through it. Though social interaction and cognitive existence is mediated by algorithms (and thus influenced – filtered and redefined), it is not governed by them separately. It is still a double subjection, though both the hegemonic subjection and the subjection of self are influenced – aided by algorithms. The only apparent difference to the modern state is that this state works in and through the

digital, which enables, enhances, and strengthens the possibilities of certain techniques of subjection already existing in the pre-digital, modern state.

Figure 17: Double subjection (self, sovereign), aided by algorithms

Finally we move to the digital modernity currently dawning, the age of the digital state caught in glimpses above. As humans are no longer merely projecting their existence onto the digital plane, but literally exist there as much as in their offline bodies, the algorithms take on a power of their own and enact a third subjection. Figure 18 illustrates how both the online and the offline part of the human is doubly subjected (something which could also have been seen as a separate, digital double subjection, making for a double, double subjection). But more importantly, in the interplay between human, technique of subjection, and algorithms, there is a misalignment of relations (of subjection), which births the truly separate third subjection I argue here.

Figure 18: Triple subjectation (self, sovereign, algorithms)

The user-citizen of the fully realised digital state exists as a hybrid-entity across digital and physical space. The parts of the subject immersed in the digital are doubly subjected there, while the offline parts are subjected in their plane. Both subjectations exist on both planes and interact, bleeding seamlessly across the imagined divide. But though the existence in both places are linked (linking parts of the same social entity, the same subject, and the same subjectation), the subjectation of the offline self to the digital structure is itself mediated. This formatting, as Koopman (2019) names it, is not neutral. In the digital state, it is an uneven subjectation, as it constitutes and populates the data double, which is then governed online – but the same technique that governs the online (part of the) subject, also governs the offline part of the self. In this way, the user-citizen is subjected by the self, the sovereign, and the algorithm both internal and external to her self, each with their separate modality.

In the early Internet – and perhaps the earliest versions of Facebook, the subjectation was merely double. It was digital, but it was double. Some social platforms allowed some particular forms of more or less performative self-subjection of identity. Others did not. Some had more rigid structures of possibilities, and/or demanded and enforced more adherence to clearly defined rules of play. Others didn't. The arbiters of digitised humans of today, Facebook or perhaps Google first among them, do more. They have algorithms take control of both the first and the second subjectation, and they go beyond them in a third

subjection which is governed by its own internal logics – logics which are not disclosed, nor even comprehensible to the human mind (at least in their coded form – abstractly understanding them arguably one of the primary points to this whole dissertation). Both the subject and the sovereign can feedback into this third subjection, but it is to be seen as a subjection unto itself. It could be argued that this, what I term a third Foucauldian subjection, is simply the mediated subjection to one-self, and to the sovereign by another name. I would argue that exactly this mixed and trans-human nature of the third subjection is what makes it different. It works on, through, and by the digital part of our self. For humanity, there is no equivalent to this shift, apart, perhaps, from that of the emergence of the pre-state sovereign, as detailed by Foucault. While humans in forms resembling their pre-digital ones might never truly enter the matrix, the digitised humans already exist and interact with each other, even as their mortal bodies rest AFK¹³.

Our selves and our sociality are stretched out and mixed across the various planes of our social and subjected existence. Both the selves and the subjectification, however, in part exist on the digital plane which is separately governed by algorithms. Due to the inherent changeability of domains under algorithmic control and surveillance, this part of the self and subjectivisation is in its own flux and never settled – even as all relations of subjectification and self in singular or in concert can be said to be in flux. In perhaps a more Luhmannic view, the self itself – part of it digital – is in its own flux, working and morphing according to internal forces and external pressures and feedbacks. As is both sovereign and algorithms, as well as the very techniques and nature of subjection pervading these – in this view – systems (or parts in one system). In the digital, as well as the mundane internal, the subjections and subjectivities of self are legion and never fixed; shifting faster than the flesh and blood subject of old could have followed. Triply subjected subjects that we now are, it concomitantly becomes ever harder and easier to know ourselves. We live in a world populated by not just mirrors and storefronts, but cameras, pictures, and textual representations to boot. At any time we can see – and often change – how we are presented to

¹³ AFK = Away From Keyboard – an abbreviation used in chatrooms and computer games to indicate the absence of human control with the avatar. The avatar might still be interacting with other players, steered by macros.

ourselves and others, as we consciously see them. Meanwhile that seeing itself is subject to the algorithmic morphing, enhancing one thing and highlighting another. Perhaps to one fellow user-subject, my picture is more important, another simply hears a read-out of my profile text and interests – or my work history, perhaps. I can see myself at any time, but the image on my screen has a new filter by the day and change of mood or light. I am subject, subjector, and subjected. I am viewed digitally, in mediated picture, and in person. I can reach out and see other subjects – indeed I must, as the digital part of my self might at this very moment be establishing a connection with a node of your being. Even as I was sleeping, a change might have occurred and the collated self-subjecting technique of the digital shifted to re-hash my interests and accordingly update the preference table for the suggestion of content, friends, and lovers. Triply subjected, we increasingly release the control with our selves, giving ourselves over to governmentality operations of the machine.

8.2.1 How best to train the digital subject

Going forward, Facebook Inc. aims to curb social behaviour on the Facebook platform tending towards an identified limit of unwantedness on a binary scale, by downgrading virality according to this measure. Content found to be crossing that same border will, as is customary, remain cause for censorship, sanctioning or deletion (Zuckerberg, 2019B). This is emblematic of the emerging governmentality of the digital state, as analysed above.

It has been suggested by Common (2019) that to delete a post hardly incentivises a change of (unwanted) behaviour. Such a view presupposes an adherence to the positive reinforcement logics embedded in a punitive penal technique (a parent sending you to your room without dinner/phone to consider what you've done) (Foucault, 1995 [1975]). But there are other ways to shape behaviour. Some acts deemed undesirable by a given authority performed by itself, by oneself, perhaps to oneself carries with it the immediate success of whatever was the point of the act (in eating a cookie before dinner, one immediately tastes the cookie) (Žižek, 1998). Other acts do not. If one leaves a note more or less politely requesting a sibling to exit the household permanently then whatever the more or less consciously desired reaction – picking a fight, the sibling actually leaving, receiving a note back – is similarly not achieved if a parent or

god simply removes the note before it is even seen, and never mentions it. In the same way, a digital speech act flagged for review by AI and suspended, then deleted by a moderator without notifying me will simply have no effect, consciously intended or not. If I shout something offensive in the forest and no-one reacts, am I likely to try again? In this light, it is interesting to hear the CEO of Facebook Inc. openly acknowledging that ‘... you want to be designing systems that just prevent like (sic) alarming or sensational content from going viral in the first place.’ (Zuckerberg, 2019B). Facebook Inc. has found that ‘... people will engage disproportionately with more sensationalist and provocative content ... [and] no matter where [we as moderators] draw the lines for what is allowed, as a piece of content gets close to that line, people will engage with it more on average.’ They seek to change this by ‘... penalizing borderline content so it gets less distribution and engagement’ (Zuckerberg, 2018B). Rather than delete content, and – in the stated view – infringing on the user’s ability to post whatever they wish, the digital state will be moving in the direction of curbing distribution of specific messages and content. The posts will not be deleted, they will just be (algorithmically) deemed more or less undesirable and their distribution curbed accordingly. The user can say what she wants, but the context of that speech might adversely affect who gets to hear it, if anyone. Another input into all three levels of subjection, as the dictate trickles down, first, the radically skewed subjection, second, the sovereign subjection, and, third, the subjection of self.

Subtle changes to the social dynamics such as this illustrates just how different the social space of the digital state, as seen on Facebook, is to one of the physical realm. In the public square of the digital state, Plato’s enlightened despot algorithm can simply tune down the volume of those voices whose opinions would harm the collective harmony (or perceived good) (Zuckerberg, 2019F). Subjects may still speak freely, but as free as their speech is and remains, if it is a priori deemed divisive no-one will hear it, whether they (would) want to or not. The question left standing is whether to tell the user that this is happening. A question which has been openly pondered by the Facebook Inc. CEO (Zuckerberg, 2019E). Actively informing the subject that their content distribution has been curbed might incentivise her to change future behaviour – but might also spark annoyance and contention. Not informing at all, however, once again opens the ever-present critique of opaque, closed black box governance. In the end, the digital governors might very well opt for passively making the information available (only) for the user who goes actively

looking. As we know, Facebook Inc.'s main reaction to the critique and anger stemming from the wider understanding among user-citizens and offline politicians of what micro-targeted marketing means and entails caused by the Cambridge Analytica scandal was to make available to its subjects a 'Why am I seeing this?' dialogue for each post on the News Feed (Browne, 2019). At the same time, however, they cycled the build-up of the code to prevent NGO's and organisations, such as Mozilla and ProPublica from (with active, informed consent from users) collecting and analysing this meta-data in correlated form (Merrill & Tobin, 2019). The upshot is that each individual Facebook user can see at least some reasons why a given ad was placed in their feed (the first I found scrolling down my feed just now "... is trying to reach males aged 18 to 44 [and] whose primary location is Copenhagen..."). Meanwhile a systematic collection and analysis of who is being targeted is being technically obfuscated – discouraged though not forbidden. Only the digital state is to have the total knowledge of the collective and the individual – even if the user consents to share that same knowledge with another entity, it is not made possible to do so. The pastoral power remains the prerogative of the algorithmic ruler to wield and the responsibility of power towards salvation necessitates maintaining the un-equal relations of knowledge and power.

This subtle sophistication allows the digital state of Facebook to divide, conquer, and rule its citizen-users in open and closed ways. By analysing content and giving it relative advantage in virality according to set preferences the algorithm actively engages in the direct shaping of subjects. It exacerbates the filter bubble effect on both the sending and receiving end of social interaction and in effect subjects are shaped internally and externally. When my contentious posts are graded down, compared to my pictures of kittens and sunsets, not only do I get enticed to share more of that which clearly gives me social success in the form of attention and recognition – but those who interact with me will see only this polished version of me – a digitally filtered and exclusively catered front stage persona with all the relatively perceived flaws glossed over or omitted (Clarke, 1994). Whether this is further developed into a pre-post check that after recognising supposedly adversarial language actively engages with and encourages the user to maybe change the tone slightly (akin to Microsoft Word's encoded dislike of long, passive sentences and other apparently universally unwanted stylistic choices), or just becomes yet another silent part of the mystical

inner workings of the news feed algorithms, it does mean pulling the levers of power. But since code, like all language, can only ever be productive and restrictive, what else can the coders do?

8.2.2 Nurture, nature, and randomised A/B

There are two main sources of governmentality transformation, in the sense of defining, informing, and adapting the techniques of subjectification in the cyber policies of the digital state of Facebook: The Sovereign and the Subject. The managers of the sovereign company Facebook Inc. come up with new 'products and features', which are then implemented according to the perceived preferences of the subjects, both human and commercial, on the platform. The subjects, however, are rarely asked, as that is considered an imperfect data source for the "true" wants and desires for the informational subject. The one time these particular user-subjects were asked to express their opinion democratically, they showed a profound lack of interest (Kirkpatrick, 2011). They might participate in virtual versions of disobedient practices – creating Facebook groups or virtually signing or sharing statements protesting changes to the structure or practice of their digital community – but as a group they have proven reluctant to participate in deliberative dialogue, and even more so to voting (ibid.). Even when the meta-physical structures of subjection are taken out of their dark patterns of persuasion and put front and centre in a democratic fashion, in order to produce a response, the user-citizens appear reluctant to pick. Apparently they do not want to be asked. Secondly, there are things that it would not make sense to vote about. Some things are simply inherent in the structure – the physicality of the platform. If, like children vigorously lamenting the need for sleep, the majority of user-citizens would want to banish ad sales on the platform, the managers' answer is simple: "Without ads, no Facebook. You are welcome to cancel your account, but we cannot and will not dismantle the possibility of existence for the collective because of your opinion", they might say. And so, some questions are not put to the subjects. The only questions that can be asked are those that already presuppose those things decided unquestionable, and those things decided by the sovereign designers. In broad reality, it boils down to one question: "Within these limitations, and as a subjected user-citizen, how do you want your personalised version of Facebook to look?" And the subjects are not trusted to answer truthfully if at all, and so an "objective" truth is searched for in their behaviour (Amoore, 2011; Zuboff, 2019).

Where questions of this nature in offline states is related to the complex interplay of political discourse, involving all those games of truth and power that might play out in all media and on all social stages, here, it is a much more individual experience. In a Foucauldian typology of power it is more pastoral than even the most modern of pre-digital states: The subject is indeed governed by algorithms.

8.2.3. Governed by algorithms

The existence of user-subjects on Facebook is at the same time complex and simple. It is complex in that the structural power of the ecology produces virtually endless opportunities for subjectification and representation (Kotliar, 2020). One can relate to any and all, one can engage in dialogue and actions performatively or privately, one is connected with all other entities, in ever entwined and overlapping ways. At the same time, it is simple. The design is intuitive and the users, having now been socialised into using not just this site, but personally adaptable sites more generally, see a simplified version of the world. They know experientially or implicitly where to look for that which they want to see, hear, or express; what they want to feel, even.

What is perhaps not clear in this “user experience” is how the content and possibilities presented to one is determined, not simply by ones existence in the space, but shaped and reformatted by who one is, as algorithmically determined and re-constituted. As the governmentality of the pastoral state of the offline sought to know all in the singular and the collective, the better to govern them to the benefit of one and all (*omnis et singulatim*), the techniques of confession and declaration have in the states of today – and in this digital iteration in particular – been replaced by techniques of inference (Foucault, 2006 [1979]). The shade of the virtual trees, the pixelated faces of other subjects encountered – they are all becoming algorithmically determined and adapted to ones needs, along with the advertisements passed along the way. You get to see what you want to see, according to how your seeing has been seen, correlated, and re-subjected. You get to be what you want to be, according to how your being has been thus seen. More than likely, you see exactly that which you would have wanted to see, if asked after the fact. But the choice was made for you – that which was warned of by Amoore (2011), and something which Zuboff strongly opposes as an infringement of the ‘right to a future tense’ she argues we are owed (2019, p. 331). The rationale

behind the ads being, of course, that the truly personally adapted and targeted ad is not an imposition, but a utilitarian plus-sum game of connecting the willing seller with the eager buyer, to the benefit of all. Rational subjects that buy are, by definition, happier than their pre-digital sisters who did not get to have their needs so determined and was offered no satisfaction and release. And so the governmentality of the digital state seeks to define the ultimate optimum and steer its users towards their ends.

In the narrated state of the digital state the sovereign subject rules supreme. In the Facebook version, rational users explicitly and implicitly adapt their News Feed to better maximise their utility of the service, and the collective informs the governing algorithms through correlation. The machines might not know you, nor even care to know you as a fellow human subject might, but given enough data points, they can show you your hearts truest desire, whether you knew such a thing to exist or not. This, of course, supposes an a priori existence of an as of yet unrealised or latent desire – or at least the creation of one that might fill that blank. In any case it assumes that the creation and subsequent fulfilment of said desire leaves the subject and its discursive other – the seller – better off. This, in turn, points back to the governmentalities embedded in the computational science of psychology as described by Koopman (2019): if given ‘traits’ are defined and the measurement of them found statistically significant in representative populations, then they are, if not exact descriptors of internal variables, then usable proxies for whatever processes do exist inside the human brain, and thus meaningful in and of themselves. When this way of thinking – this technique of constructing subjects (subjectification) – migrates into an environment which is inherently coded in clearly defined binaries, it is as if the world here is made for this construction of humanity. In this world, the codes of salvation are truly there to be discovered by those programs who have the skill – the knowledge, the power to do so.

The coded part of the subjects of the digital state may not (yet) be all that the human subject is – but it aims to mirror, cover, and infer the full of that human subject it is an extension of. As humanity, individually and collectively gets increasingly transformed and socialised into these states of being, they also become increasingly individualised and homogenised. Each life-world as mediated by personalised apps is principally unique – adapted to the inferred and reported preferences of each individual subject. The

minute parts of this individualisation technique, however, is happening according to defined standards set by programmer, machine, and both. Perhaps in a similar move to the dichotomous racialisation of humans (and sexualisation cf. Foucault; genderisation cf. Butler), dividing us all into overlapping “ethnic” groups, based on skin tone, “nationality” of various sorts according to geography, language, and other markers imagined meaningful (Anderson, 2006 [1983]). As we are individualised into open-ended, but limited categories of otherness, those degrees of otherness are collated and collapsed, uncovering underlying truths of similarity behind seemingly different names. This bounded otherness produces freedom of movement, but binds us to that movement which is possible in the lanes prescribed to us. And the lanes are ever moving towards convergence rather than diversion. The myriad pieces of the story we call identity are provided, enabling us to show and see ourselves as the subjects we dream ourselves to be, inside and outside – “This content is private – show this only to me”.

As the lifeworld of subjects becomes increasingly digital, so do the logics of perception, of being – both internal and external – become subject to algorithmic shaping. To talk of the analogue-digital divide is only meaningful inasmuch as it is meaningful to talk of the divide between how one performs oneself differently towards a friend or lover in the bedroom, in the living room, at work, in a restaurant, in a letter or a song. The telephone, the text message, the e-mail and the private message; the comment and the status update. These are different, to be sure, but not fundamentally so. To the human subject they are different types and paths of and to the same parts of the lived experience. Add to this how the performance – social or otherwise – of the digitised subject does not wholly originate in the human brain. Perhaps comparable to the family units of the pre-individual past: the mater familius can set up rules and lay down structures, but a wayward family member might still fall in love with the wrong neighbours’ daughter. The human brain formally creates and governs the minute parts that make up the digitised subject – but the algorithmic custodians then take over. As the hand moves towards the cup when I realise a desire for a sip, the body a slave of my master mind, the social interactions of my digital self act according to predetermined logics I neither understand nor control. As my watch reminds me that it is time for a run, I am left to wonder. In this hybrid self, spanning the physical-digital divide, where lives the master and where the slave (Hegel, 2004 [1807])?

I have discussed the digital(ised) subject, arguing that though double subjecthood spreads out onto the digital plane, that in itself is not necessarily different from the pre-digital version of the same. At the same time I argue that digital subjecthood as we see it today and in the future implies a third subjection. A construct which I present as an addition to the double subjection theory espoused by Foucault. Based on this empirically founded theoretical addition, I have discussed the implications for the user-citizen of, on and by the digital state in question here, that of Facebook. This discussion has led me to follow Zuboff, Amoore, Pariser, and others in problematising the algorithmically inferred worlds increasingly digital subjects are embedded in. I then turned to the part of us which is digital. I argued that – at least insofar as I operationalise (if not conceptualise, following Foucault (1982)) the human subject, it is no longer meaningful to draw a dividing line before or after the part of the self that has become digital. I argue that to encompass a digital subject – a human (mainly) of today – one has to recognise the digital part of the subject as part of the individual. One should consider the server operations of digital state of a similar nature to those neurons pre-consciously firing in the brain.

9. THE DIGITAL STATE

At the very beginning I stated that the objective of this study was to uncover the governmentality of the digital state. The digital state I presented as a new modality in a Foucauldian typology of state seen as a collection of techniques of governance. I then laid out the theory and praxis which serves as the foundation for this study, moving into a concrete methodology which I have termed digital genealogy. Through this digital genealogy I have analysed the digital state of Facebook and discussed the ramifications of my findings. This has led me to emphasise that the digital subjects of digital modernity are human-machine hybrids. To grapple with this, I have proposed a third subjection to be added to the double subjection of the pre-digital state described by Foucault. I have argued that this third subjection, unique to the digital state, has potentially profound effects on the digital subject. By appending the word “digital” to the concepts of state, subject and modernity, I do not mean to imply a radical otherness compared to un-digital versions of the same. Rather, I wish to imply that while each concept carries with it its conceptual and structural legacies and relations, my focus is on the concept as it can be seen and works through the digital.

Having explored the structure of Facebook, the governmentality of the digital state, and having realised the triply subjected digital user-citizen, I will now gather the threads. In this penultimate chapter I return the digital state for a final exploration of what I have found. I begin this chapter where I began this study, re-visiting governmentality in the digital sphere.

9.1 Digitised governmentality

In my analysis of the digital state of Facebook, I explored the meta-physical structures, as well as the political, legal, and academic-bureaucratic talk that mirrors and guides the creation of the cyber-policies in and around the area governed by the digital state. In this, I have found a consistent treatment of subjects as objects, a commitment to unequal relations of information and power, as well as myriad signs of the modern state governmentality recoded in the digital.

The unequal relations of information are encoded between different user-subjects, according to how they are constituted (e.g. differentiating between a Facebook Moderator and a User), but even more so

between users and the digital agents – the algorithms – executing the deduced will of the subject and the digital state. In all of these relations, if an ethical framework can be appended, it is one of consequence and utility. Put simply, each user is to be presented with that which she should most want to be presented with, as per her interests and those of paying customers. In earlier iterations of the services she was to be presented by that which she would most measurably want to see in the short term – what she would be most interested in here and now, according to her cookies. But as the pastoral responsibility of the sovereign is realised from within and without the cyber policies are increasingly moderated to downgrade some of those things most likely to catch measurable interest, and boost content determined to enhance the individual and collective utility of the subject and the service. In this shift we can perhaps see an example of the shift from utility to governance, akin to the (pre-modern) state's shift from providing relative protection from outside violence towards providing internal policing and moving towards pastoral guidance (Foucault, 1979A; 1979B).

In the radically uneven distribution of knowledge inherent in this structure, the individualising technique made possible by modern computation allows for each user to be met with a different state, reality, and self. The content, rhetoric, and truth of the services are all adapted both by the user herself, but especially by the always-responsive algorithms. In order to do so, the algorithms parse all potential content. In order to adapt the algorithms, the programmers, engineers, and researchers working on the algorithms working behind the scenes can perhaps access more, but they actively see very little, even as they themselves are subjected by the techniques of the digital state. The users are equally blinded, as they are led down their individualised paths to docility. The engineers can see and adapt all that is being seen, but both the seeing and adapting has long since grown too abstract for human minds, and the abstractions become rather like those orders sent out by dispatch from a far-away general, for officers and troops on the ground to hopefully follow, each according to their training and skills. Or, perhaps more fittingly, like the word of a biblical God, not concerned with the how of Her power, as she commands there to be light. In this increasing abstraction of construction and adaption of the techniques of subjection also the engineers are dragged down in an ever-widening gap of knowledge and control, user-subjects of the digital state alongside the rest of us. The algorithms are only subject in the singular sense of being subject to the

command of the engineers (and themselves, as defined by the engineers), and cannot be considered subjects in the meaningful sense of the word, which implies self-referential agency. But these algorithms emerge ever-more as the only part of the self that can touch and fashion the world lived in by the user and allegedly governed by the engineers. The engineers then become increasingly as the non-interfering God that so drastically started the world above, or the deceased sovereign who built her nation by the sword but now only exists as a concept. The algorithms are the encoded structure of power-knowledge in the digital state, more so by each passing day and upgrade. A digital bureaucracy of a digital state.

9.1.1 Shaping idea and matter

The unequal relations of power-knowledge enshrined in the cyber policies of the digital state are reminiscent of the modern Foucauldian state. Like its offline predecessor, the digital state renders its subjects into governable subject-objects to be lead towards secular salvation. This salvation is determined in a radically de-ontological fashion where not just the means and the collective ends, but also the individual ends are automatically rendered and re-rendered time and again. Where the techniques of the modern state allowed only for collective answers to the questions of power, the digital state can transcend and combine the collective with the digital in a fuller realisation of the second pastoral salvation than was ever before possible. On Facebook, in 2020, this means nothing more than the ability to connect with increasing accuracy willing sellers and buyers of goods, love, and social relations. This potential fulfilment of social and consumerist desires to the mutual enjoyment and utility of all seems less than ominous. But in understanding the modality of power-knowledge in this milieu, reasons for concern emerge. Because in this thesis Facebook is but a site of exploration of the digital state. The techniques of governance and subjection explored here are not unique to one social media platform.

As pointed out by Zuboff in other words, and following Amoore, a technique embedded with a governmentality that determines according to its own set objectivity the desirable outcomes for each subject-object and then asserts not just the right, but the duty to steer the subjects individually and collectively towards those ends, should give us pause. Transposing the modern state to the digital opens up untold possibilities of individual and collective subjection at scale. Even as the aim is and remains to

serve the user-citizens, the means through which the salvation is determined and realised implies a radical re-imagining of the human subject as governable both internally and externally. Zuboff has focused on the material ramifications of this, as the digital subjects to come are increasingly imagined to follow the paths laid out to them in behaviourist mazes. But whether philosophical primacy is laid in the material or the idea(l), the digital state ultimately shapes both¹⁴. As the outer is measured, and the inner is inferred, all avenues of resistance are rendered knowable and thus constituted as objects for the operations of power. Further, as the social functions of the extended human have migrated into the digital sphere, the total human is rendered yet more knowable and governable.

I re-emphasise here that the digital state as technique is in no way limited to that state of Facebook which I have analysed. The digital state is a theoretical construct. An adapted version of the modern state envisaged by Foucault. While I assert Facebook to be the most accessible and fruitful place to currently look for and analyse this digital state, it is not the only one. Offline states have long since digitised their citizens and though examples of algorithmic governance to anywhere near the scale and sophistication seen on Facebook are few and far between, some cases could be pointed out, such as the Danish 'Gladsaxe Model', where ...

The purpose was to trace children who were vulnerable due to social circumstances even before they showed actual symptoms of special needs. Based on previous use of statistics, the authorities decided to combine information about 'risk indicators'.

(Alfter, 2019)

While this particular initiative was discontinued due to massive protest, it illustrates how the governmentality of the digital state is gaining in influence and prevalence, both offline and online. It is also illustrative as an instance where the digital state might as well be seen as an example of the modern

¹⁴ This points towards the never-ending debate between young Hegelians such as Marx and other giants like Kant and Hegel himself, which I will not be getting further into here.

Foucauldian state. The digital state is not just the state of Facebook. It is the state of digital modernity – another abstract concept I append to something whose time has dawned.

9.1.2 Digital modernity

Depending on the conceptualisation of the abstract, there has been talk of up to three distinct modernities (Zuboff, 2019; O’Hara, 2020). I will not enter into a review or debate of this discussion here. Rather, I base the conception of digital modernity on a general notion of modernity as understood through the work of Foucault. I refer here to a modernity which features the governmentality of the modern state. It is a modernity not clearly demarcated by time nor place, but it is a modernity which Foucault has especially shown to emerge as European monarchical modes of governance turned into increasingly governmentalised states. It is modernity envisaged ‘... rather as an attitude than as a period of history’. (Foucault, 1984C, p. 39). In the same way as I reiterate Foucault’s modernity as a time-bound discursive assemblage – an attitude perhaps – rather than a historical period per se, I propose now such an attitude enveloping the trappings of the digital state which I, following O’Hara (2020), call digital modernity.

The reason I refrain from giving this attitude a name that is fully its own, such as “digitality” is that I wish to underscore that this is not a radical break from modernity. Digital modernity is simply modernity with an appendix. It is modernity re-configured by and in the digital age. In the digital modernity we see some of the powerfully productive strategies of subjection of the modern state re-imagined in the constitution and conduct of digital subjects. The digital state does not replace nor render obsolete the modern state. Rather, it enhances and endows its technologies with further tools, techniques and possibilities. Some of them allowing the realisation of degrees of sophistication which could only have been imagined before the advent of the microchip. In this, I argue a similar point to Morozov’s critique of Zuboff’s *Surveillance Capitalism* (Morozov, 2019). Morozov acknowledges the depth and worth of Zuboff’s work, but turns to criticise her for allegedly not recognising how much of that which she observes appears consistent with long-established social theory from Marx and onwards. He argues that the workings and effects of surveillance capitalism are different from capitalism per se only insofar as the surveillance part goes; the part enabled by the digital technologies and structures of digital modernity. What differences I

argue between modernity and its digital disruptor are only those afforded by the transposition (teleologically and otherwise) of the digital.

Whether the formal title and ownership of those techniques that I call the digital state remain connected with Facebook or other companies, or is reverted or subverted into other institutions such as nation states or supra-national institutions is irrelevant to my argumentation. Similar to how institutions and concrete technologies of the modern state sometimes act according to logics more related to the sovereign state, the digital state is an analytical construct which can intersect and operate atop a modern state. As with most Foucauldian concepts, they are not mutually exclusive – indeed, the more it overlaps, the more a state of sovereignty, modernity, and the digital realises and reinforces itself as a state. Both as concept and concrete entity. The digital state is the modern state of digital modernity. And we have seen its advent – its first, fumbling steps. But where do these steps lead?

9.2 The inevitability of subjection

We have seen that a key feature of the governmentality of the digital state is a focus on positive rather than negative solutions. If an obstacle is encountered between the A and B of a flowchart, ways are found through, below or around it, rather than turning back. A polemic analogy might be a builder of a petrol-powered car working to adapt it to Hydrogen or electricity rather than abandon the car altogether and just take the bicycle. As I have shown, the ethos of progress above all else enshrined in the ‘move fast and break things’ motto is visible in the speech acts and actions informing the techniques of the digital state, wherever one looks. This logic also plays out in the subversion of resistance into subjection. If the user-citizen shows signs of resisting the subjection offered, she is simply offered ways to resist on and through the platform. In that way, even resistance is turned into yet another subjection, and the user-object moves forward in the flowchart of control.

9.2.1 The acceleration of everything.

In his development of the concept of infopower, Koopman emphasises how the inherently political process of turning persons into specific ciphers involves the double fastening of pinning them down and speeding them up:

... at each moment of input, processing, and output, the work of information functions to pin down and speed up (or fasten) that which is being informationalized.

(Koopman, 2019, pp. 12-13)

Koopman shows with specific reference to Facebook (and academia.edu), how encoding someone means having them pinned to being what that code says they are – e.g. a gender. It also allows for the radical speeding up of operations upon the coded subject individually – e.g. by the number of proposed social interactions bleeping through the phone, and collectively – e.g. by the quick overview of how many ‘friends’ one has. This dynamic is true in general for everything that is encoded, and in particular for everything that is re-purposed to be socialised. A socialised business entity, per instance, might be nothing more than a human wearing a digital skin, but in relation it becomes a social actor on its own accord and reference. The digital part of digitised personhood is not limited to humans and whether born in code or with reference to the offline world, the referent objects become socialising subjects. “Digital assistants” such as Alexa, Siri, or Google Assistant, and children’s relation to them is an obvious illustrative example of this, as is bots. These programs explicitly created to mimic and partake in human interaction show clearly how the line between digitised persons based on humans and based on other entities (or just sui digitalis) is becoming increasingly blurred. I should note here that to a wide extent my view sees most digital assistants as less social subjects unto themselves and rather as part of the extended digitised human. The (chat and spam) bots are the stronger example of a-human relationally social subjects.

While we humans might realise in the day to day the obvious truth of Koopman’s argument, as the e-mails, text messages, and notifications tick in, the speeding up of informational and social operations of the digital state is far more radical than meets the eye. Consider the messages other social actors – bots, faraway

humans, or company profiles that are somewhere in between – have attempted to send you on a given platform. Consider all the possible socialised actions by nodes that are more or less potentially connected to yours of which you were not notified. The sorting of these, the decisions as to what should be presented to the offline part of the human involve is a social game at least as voluminous and complex in the possibilities and strategies as a parlour game between teenagers at their first real party. To the human eye it might seem dry in comparison, to be sure, but in order of magnitude the social cues sorted and reacted to, positively and negatively, is staggering. As much as we might feel the speeding up of sociality through that which is filtered through to us, the filtering itself is in itself a host of social actions as surely as is the lingering of a hand or a locked gaze across a crowded room. Determining who you might be interested in meeting on your app might be just as relevant a social function to you as was determining whom your parent should go sit down with at their first day of work, school or university. The difference is that the social cues they relied on to actively or passively decide were mostly in the human brains of themselves and others, while the social cues bringing someone to the front of your screen and mind are being computed far away from your skull. The digital social operations of the digitised subject are ever faster and more complex, and through the digital state techniques they affect the actions of the whole of the subject ever more (Zuboff, 2019; Amoore, 2011). A further talk of agency, perhaps in the Hegelian master-slave framework, is outside the scope of this thesis (Hegel, 2004 [1807]). Suffice to say that if a subject be seen as part active and part passively re-active, then both parts exist in both the offline and online parts of the subject.

This enhanced, expanded and accelerated subject is not just subjected from above and within in the double subjection demonstrated by Foucault. The digital part of the subject overlaps with both active and passive parts of this subjected self. In this digital part originates the third subjection unique to the digital state. As parts of the self are continually re-moulded according to self-referential and adaptive techniques a third subjection occurs. All these three subordinations are embedded with the governmentality of the digital state. A governmentality which follows the path of modernity's constitution of the self and the subject as objects of governance and subjects of power. These subjects are to be optimised – socialised – to their full potential. Each node; each user-citizen is to produce and accelerate the sociality of a social space where

more is better. More action, more interaction, and more re-action. This serves the dual purpose of transposing ever more of the subjects' lifeworlds into the digital, placing it under the purview and governance of the digital state, and making each subject ever more productive within the milieu, allowing for further domination and control. It moves, colonises, and dominates the structures that structure the subjects' lives, more so with each revolution of this wheel of power-knowledge.

9.2.2 Accelerated societies

It follows from the above that this acceleration of sociality influences not just the individual, but also the collective. Or, better said, through the individual this acceleration of social operations has profound effects on societies as one or more wholes. The scale and speed with which antagonising and homogenising operations of groups are possible through the technologies of the digital state are unlike anything seen by pre-digital subjects. Corporations, nationalism, and governmentality techniques across the board are perhaps similar in aim and effect, but the way in which the self-referent algorithmic-governed and -governing part of the self is in itself governed by digital governmentality means that a shift in that governmentality can have profound and immediate effects. The governmentality of the digital state – the techniques of governance and subjection of digital modernity which are to be found in all subjectivising connections to user-citizens – adapt automatically, as they algorithmically re-define the means, ends, and selves they govern. Facebook Inc. can change their settings and make groups of people slightly more or less depressed. Indeed they have done so (Meyer, 2014), and are by now considered obliged to do so, by themselves and others. While such experiments can appear shocking, at the same time they seem all but harmless – after all, they have allowed Facebook Inc. to focus on infusing the platform with cyber policies designed to make the user-citizens less depressed, rather than more (Zuckerberg, 2018A). But the sheer capabilities of these operations; the sheer potential of digital governmentality is easy grounds for more worry – or, perhaps, excitement – than your average amicable digital sovereign's algorithmically distributed anti-depressant. One need only look at governmentalised social movements of the past – nationalisation efforts, mandatory schooling, industrial warfare, genocide – and combine that knowledge with the nascent knowledge of the social impact and acceleration possible through the technologies of digital modernity. So far, studies dedicated to the seemingly separate phenomenon of “social media” have seen how this has

impacted and contorted events like the Arab Spring, the “Brexit” referendum, and the elections of US presidents Obama and Trump, respectively. But viewing digital governmentality as a mode and the digital state as a collection of techniques, we see that the scope of this discussion is and should be much broader. The overt and covert techniques of companies such as Amazon, Apple and Microsoft as well as states such as Denmark, the US, and Russia are increasingly infused with the governmentality of the digital state, allowing them to conduct the conduct of their user-citizens in new and never-heretofore-seen individualised and subjectivising ways.

We have already seen an increasing algorithmic governance of stock market transactions, as well as the social relations treated here. As technologies of the digital self are further developed and disseminated, there is no immediately visible end to the functions that can be re-rooted in the digital part of the subject. The lives and living spaces of future human-digital hybrids might be governed by algorithmically assigned, adaptable themes and tastes rather than decisions actively made by the offline self. Maybe the digital part buys and sells furniture, virtual and physical as life progresses, maybe it orders sustenance, and maybe it types out the paper the offline subject would have written. Maybe it does all of this, under the influence of whoever paid for the partitioned subjection of that particular subject. Maybe it handles voting to boot?

This leads me, finally, to some somewhat un-Foucauldian clear recommendation: transparency, meaningful consent, and participatory government. Put simply, to shape our future selves, we must transpose the ideals and ethics of liberal government into the digital sphere and fuse them into their governmentalities. We, too, must be able to see and demand changes to the codes that govern and shape us.

9.2.3 Resistance is futile

Even as Facebook is reined in by itself and others, even if Zuboff is finally heeded and commercial entities are not allowed to pursue the mechanics of surveillance capitalism, the digital state – like governmentality and modernity before it – will not disappear. The productive potential of the triply subjected digital subject will be realised. ‘Where there is power, there is resistance’, to be sure, but even as the odd teenager declares herself an anarcho-communist, the state and its governmentality continues to grow in abstract and concrete, even as its centres of power might shift across conceptual borders from institution to

institution. Likewise, the digital state. While scholarly work – this thesis included – bends critical, there is no denying the popularity of digital state operations. The myriad functions of outsourced techniques of self-governance – the active transposition of decision-making and social facilitation towards digital parts of the self – makes human life seem so much easier. I certainly am an avid user of Facebook, not just for research purposes. I communicate and share experiences and thoughts with friends and family; I get involved in political debates – sometimes with leading politicians from my duck-pond offline polity; and I plan social events. In the same way, I am an active user of the Danish borger.dk system. I log on to book a Covid-19 test and then the next day to see the result; I check my student loans and re-plan the re-payments on the fly; I order obscure books from a library across the country to be delivered to my home library. All of these things happen immediately and efficiently. More so even than had I had an offline, human assistant handling those same things for me in an offline world. While I am loath to let Gmail or Word tell me just what to write, I do accept some of their suggestions, and I appreciate having my typos pointed out to me. All this, even as I recognise the normalising and subjectivising effects of these operations. I understand that the digitised subject has the potential to be made infinitely more docile, to be normalised and subjectivised to a degree even Foucault might be mildly surprised by – and yet I consistently subject myself to the digital state, no less than I subject myself to the state that was already, before. There are personal and collective reasons why that is. But it is the case, regardless of normative position. The age of digital modernity has dawned and it will not be halted, whether one thinks it should be or not.

9.3 Rebooté la resistance

At the onset, being a digital subject, means nothing more than being a modern subject with digital tools at one's disposal. Early digital technologies simply extend the reach and productivity of the subject in ways similar to pre-digital products of industry. The way a Ford motorcar allows you to explore and experience vast and different areas of the world, you could have otherwise only read about or seen in pictures, is in essence much the same as when you enter the World of Warcraft on your computer: an extension of where the tool can carry you, the subject. Web 2.0, however, is different (van Dijck, *Engineering Sociality in a Culture of Connectivity*, 2013). In this paradigm the subject increasingly becomes digital as well as acts

through the digital. Ultimately, the subject comes to include also the motorcar, through the Internet of Things (IoT). This shift does more than simply transfer and extend the functions of governance, self and others into the digital. In the digital state self, subjecthood, subjection, and governmentality act and interact in new ways. The modern state shapes the conduct of conduct (subjection) of self and others. In extension, the digital state shapes not just the subjection of self and others, but also the internal operations of both the conducting and the self, in a way unique to this modality. This is more than a digital veneer for another story of the same state. Through the algorithmic coding of the coded part of the digital subject, a new, internal shaping occurs. This creates an asymmetry between the coded, self-referentially muting governmentality and the digitised subject: a third, Foucauldian subjection unique to the digital state.

This insight necessitates a critical reflection of the development observed. At the offset, this observed transformation of what it is and means to be a (human) subject, can easily lead to a panicked shriek and a demand of scaling back to a simpler mode. Indeed, such resistances are occurring, as people are quitting Facebook, going offline, re-focusing their governance of self and their children to enjoy nature more and screens less. But barring a religio-cultural revolution this development seems irresistible. After all, why would our future selves not want to be driven wherever they truly want to be driven without even having to reflect upon and phrase the question? Thus, if digital modernity is indeed as inevitable as it seems, then the question of whether this is “good” or “bad” becomes beside the point. When “whether” is rendered moot the question becomes instead one of “how”. How do we shape this change to include and incorporate the logics and modalities we would wish, curbing and resisting those we would fear? This ultimately takes me to the same issues explored by Zuboff, Amoore, and others. But rather than advocating resistance to “the Faceborg” (Frew, 2018), I acquiesce that resistance is indeed futile and recommend that we turn our attention to how we want to imagine and shape the compliance and integration into the digitised collective. In other words, while we might not all become subjects of Facebook and Google, we appear inexorably bound to become subjects of the digital state. And as such it is not a question of whether we are, but how we are to be governed by algorithms.

9.3.1 Let the voiceless speak

Concretely, I advocate for techniques of empowerment. Of users and of citizens. First, I suggest the development and proliferation of open source tools to decode algorithmic operations. Second, I suggest that a bit of that automated governance be put in the hands of the subjects themselves.

Artificial intelligence technologies – misnamed though they may be – can be built with the capability to feedback a simplified narrative explaining their decisions. This, of course, opens up an array of problems in terms of hypocritical pretensions and ludicrous misrepresentations. To be sure, the task is not easy – but as flawed as it may be, we ask even the professedly insane to account for themselves when in court or in office. The same questions must be posed to the algorithms that increasingly govern our lives and worlds. We – the digital subjects, as represented through political organs of the US or the EU – could make a demand for algorithmic translator modules into law. An alternative or compliment to such a legal or normative demand to include in a built-in self-explanatory module in each AI could be to implement standards according to which – through which – they can be scrutinised by external entities. Independently developed and expanded programmes could be the journalist equivalents to the digital sovereigns and their automated bureaucracies. In either of these or other solutions towards the same end, this would help not just legal squabbles over killing cars and hacked drones. It would help the digitised (human) subjects better understand and perhaps question and resist those parts of themselves that now lie hid between the lines and the printout. It would start the process of bringing the digital state away from asymmetrical autocracy and towards something resembling egalitarian democracy. Building and fostering an open source standard for sorting algorithms would allow insights and scrutiny, as well as a potential for further discussion, development, and adaptation of those murky techniques that govern us now.

Second, while we can hardly ask more of the offline parts of the user-citizens, we can empower them with (even more) digital tools. If combined with legislation, simple tools can be effective indeed. While the data policies of the EU are arguably on the positive side in this, other avenues are possible. Take cookies as an instance. The EU could enhance their requirements for the cookie policies of sites and pages, demanding that they adhere to an interoperable standard which plugs into a setting to be available in all web browsers.

The standard option would of course be minimum tracking. Something similar can be found for the diligent user, such as the Consent-O-Magic¹⁵ browser add-on developed and maintained by researchers at Aarhus University (Nouwens, Liccardi, Veale, Karger, & Kagal, 2020), but by enforcing this as a standard, the burden of the choice and effort can be taken away from the average user. If and when someone should actually want to change their generally stated level of desired surveillance and be tracked a bit more (again) they would simply have to change their browser settings one time.

We also ought to open up for resistance by dismantling and deconstructing the coded politics of necessity surrounding these issues. If nothing else, this thesis should make possible some resistance, at least in the short run. As for larger, political action, the more normative work of Zuboff and others speak much louder and clearly. I would, however, say this – to those in a position to impact those governmentalities of the digital (politicians, CEOs, coders, and others): I ask that you allow for those ephemeral agents that subjectivise to become subjects themselves. Or, in plain-speak: Make it a rule – a standard – that algorithms include a module which allows for an explanation. If a civil servant of flesh and bone sort my file into a given folder in front of my very eyes, I might ask “Why this folder?” “Why this file?” But if the same employee of the state gathers my data in a file and shuffles it according to opaque logics without my knowing, and without the possibility of knowing, the connotation is another entirely, for I cannot know how I exist. Without the possibility for resistance, it is violence. And so if AI are to remain non-violent in whatever techniques that subjectivise and govern us, and whether my assertion of subjecthood be accepted or not, then they should be endowed with the ability to speak. To explain their actions, and lay them out for all subjects to see. Further, if possible, please let users opt out of all of the various terms and conditions, in one central place. Standardise not just the cookies, but the various clauses in the terms and conditions which no-one reads (besides those doing research for a PhD, I suppose). Make functional layers to the sites and services and let the users decide on one central place what they will agree to and what not.

¹⁵ You can view the plugin and code on Github, here: <https://github.com/cavi-au/Consent-O-Matic>.

For some, this empowerment of users might be achieved simply by demanding that the code be public and open source. But as it is, even those engineers working at Facebook, handling the code, could not comprehend the code, even if they wanted to. Thus, either we need to further the development of tools to translate code into speech understandable by humans – programmes that deconstruct and perhaps interpret the speech of their counterparts, inhuman post-structuralists of the digital, as it were. Or we need there to be embedded in the AI's that build and re-build those codes a translator module, able to explain its actions to those human subjects, whether they be seen as master, slave, both or neither. And perhaps a standardised control panel to introduce something resembling meaningful consent. Perhaps we need both. Until then, all we have are human agents, through equally flawed methods and ill-fitting metaphors imperfectly seeking to ascertain and describe what governmentalities govern our digital selves. Having thus laid out the digital state, digital modernity, and my recommendations, I move to summarise and conclude.

10. IN THE LAND OF THE CODED, THE PROGRAM IS SOVEREIGN

Alas, all stories must come to a close, and so too this thesis. We are nearing the end, and as we move towards the exit, we might consider where we have travelled, and what we have learned. This thesis is as unapologetically human (and digital) as its author, and many things could (perhaps should) be criticised. Even so, I would lay claim to some gains and a hope that this work – my work – sparks thoughts to take forward, along with those equally valuable insights about how a future project like this could perhaps be done better. I have built my frame and performed my analysis and discussion of the digital state of Facebook. I have laid bare its governmentality, and I have given my thoughts about what it means for the triply subjected digital subjects we have become, and for digital modernity. Now, as we walk towards the rendered, rising sun I offer some final thoughts.

10.1 Dreams of digital domination

In this thesis, I set out to explore the governmentality of the digital state. I reasoned that a salient place to do so was a wholly digital space where the technologies of subjection unique to the digital sphere could be analysed with as little direct connection to the pre- and un-digital technologies of subjection which we know so well from the various iterations of the state analysed by Foucault and others. I identified Facebook as such a place. The main challenge to these choice is and remains the simple fact that Facebook Inc. is not the same as the state institutions of a nation state. In that light, a more robust choice might have been to analyse instead the digital operations of Denmark or Scotland, and the digitally mediated techniques of subjection and governance of their nation-state subjects. To further strengthen my choice, I considered why and how Facebook Inc. might indeed carry the label of state (see Chapter 4).

I have argued that the *sui digitalis* nature of the socio-political space of Facebook means that in that digital space we might see rather the techniques of the digital state, and not just the techniques of the late modern state, operating in the digital. To some extent, I was wrong. It appears that a fair bit of the techniques of governance I analysed was indeed similar to the state analysed by Foucault. On Facebook it appears that, to a large extent, the collection of techniques of governance I collectively call state construct

subjects and truth-power in a similar fashion as does those of the recent historical states analysed by Foucault. But I found something else as well. First, though similar in their logics and intents – in their governmentality – when these techniques are transposed to the digital and especially when they are working on subjects that are themselves part digital, some things do change. Second, the very nature of the digital social space (as it is currently constituted) enables and create a third form of subjection unique to digital modernity (a state where both the technology of subjection and (part of) the subjects exist in the digital). In the first case, the computational enhancement of techniques of subjection (e.g. policies) creates radical differences as to what is possible – what some might call the affordances of the techniques of subjection.

The sheer scale to which the ‘omnes et singulatim’ part of the pastoral power of the governmentalised state is possible in the digital is seemingly unparalleled in scale by that which came before (Foucault, 1979A; Harari, 2017). Add to that the second case, the third subjection where the subject is subjected by the self, the sovereign, and the algorithmic parts of both which continually reshape, restate, recompute, and reconstitute each other. In each their way, these two insights inform us of the governmentality of today and tomorrow. First, where the political economy and aims of the digital state might be similar to those described by Foucault in relation to the state of modernity, they are wed with the ability to radically individualise and subjectivise in the double sense, according to the governmentality of the pastoral state. Second, both this governmentality and the subjects governed by it is continually reshaped, meaning that not just the means, but also the ends for each increasingly individualised subject are continually redefined. This may not in itself be a problem. Power is productive, and the stories around the governmentalised subject feature plenty of evidence of those that, in the words of Radiohead, are ‘fitter, happier, [and] more productive’ (Radiohead, 1997). As the creation and mediation of structures of power-knowledge move into the digital, however, and come under the purview of the techniques of the third subjection, the opaqueness of those computations implies an increasingly inexorable drive towards paths of no resistance. In this, we should remember that possibility of resistance is the closest to freedom we might get in a Foucauldian conception of subjecthood.

This leads me from the abstract to my concrete key point applicable to the “real” world of politics (broadly defined). Those agent-less techniques – the increasingly abstract systemic logics of AI-powered technologies of subjection – are at danger of becoming de-humanised, de-centred, and un-personal mediations of tyranny. A tyranny without a tyrant, and a benevolent tyranny at that, but a tyranny none-the-less. This tyranny may truly save human (and other) subjects as they have never been saved before – but if in doing so it takes away the possibility of resistance, then perhaps even the most benevolent of aims put in as core protocol is not enough. As subjects, as societies, we need to be able to question and resist. At the very least, we need transparency (Wachter, Mittelstadt, & Russell, 2020).

10.1.1 Why Foucault?

Choosing Foucault for the frame has led to much speculation and explanation of what this means in general and especially to me, in this particular instance. In reading this, one might reasonably ask why I went to all this trouble. Clearly, I have been aware of different approaches to science, philosophy and (perhaps especially) methodology. So why invest so much effort into fully embracing this approach and attempting to make it work as an acceptable work of social science? What did I gain that I might not have found pre-packaged by other, more contemporary scholars?

First and foremost, the Foucauldian epistemology allows us to re-consider the very ways in which we construct knowledge. If we radically assert a pre-ontological or even a de-ontological approach to the analysis of social and historical contingencies, we may indeed be able to focus directly on those techniques that turn subjects into subjects (Foucault, 1982). If we further manage to free ourselves from the materialist and positivist aims of defining (ideally, universally) what something is we can focus instead on what it does. Better said, we can keep focus on what is done, whether an “it” can be defined as the one(s) doing it or not. This twist is what allows an analysis of the digital state without a prior objectification of what a state (or a corporation) “is”, and without much regard as to whether the place I go looking for it might fit such a definition. If I can constitute theoretically an analysis of techniques of subjection which I might collectively call “state”, then I can ascertain the governmentality of the digital state as it appears in this sphere, in this analysis. It is then for the reader to judge whether the constructions of truth and power-

knowledge I offer are to be accepted or resisted. This is a slippery slope, of course. Clear definitions and mathesised causal theories lend themselves well to dialectic consideration and critique. Abandoning both might lead to problems with that openly stated goal of enabled resistance. How is the reader to counter the claims made when the author refuses to commit to a (material) hill from whence these claims are made? It is indeed hard to shoot down an opponent who refuses to commit to a location. The answer here mirrors the methodological question just considered: as they say in Football: Focus on the ball and not the player. It follows from the emancipatory ethics of the framework that a Foucauldian player is duty-bound to provide as full and complete transparency as possible. For some readers this transparency might at times come off somewhat odd or even ironic, given the express aim to be suggestive and subtle rather than simplistic and definitional – multi-faceted rather than binary. This is also why, when attempting a work such as this, much explanation is needed. In part, it is needed to record and guide my own emerging understanding, but it is especially needed in order for the reader to understand, reflect upon, and possibly resist my ideas of what this project is and should be. Such resistance is not a defeat, it is another way in which I might be successful in helping the collective build a stronger understanding of ourselves and our world.

Another important feature of a Foucauldian frame is the assertion that freedom from subjection is impossible. While the empirical, material veracity of such a statement can be discussed, in a framework favouring discourses and relations of power-knowledge, this is necessarily true. A subject cannot exist without being subjected by the self and others. This assertion allows for the analytical focus to be on how subjects are subjected, rather than on the related questions about if, by whom, and whether this is a good thing. These questions of who or why are important, to be sure, but the Foucauldian frame allows us to focus, first, on that elusive how. It is my hope that I have provided a glimpse of that how and thus allowed other scholars to delve further into those other questions of materiality and norms, where, whom, and if this is as it should be.

The Foucauldian framework has allowed me to observe and analyse what the digital state does. The contingencies and limitations of my theory and methodology stand. While I did make something of a case

as to why the subjectivising operations taking place on Facebook can be seen as technologies of state (see Chapter 4), this may not be enough to convince. As such, future scholarship might do similar work on the digital technologies of institutions already assigned given states to identify by comparison in how far the operations of the digitised nation state match up with these findings. Some might also look into how the digital state fares when it leaves the digital and re-orders the material world in its image, as does Amazon, or when it even more explicitly instrumentalises and optimises human bodies through the bio-politics of subject actions, as does Amazon with its employees and Google with its user-citizens. Finally, in all this, critical theorists and ethicists might consider the relations of power in this brave new world and whether it matches the narratives and normative preferences of the digital subjects. Is this what we want? Is this what we should want? With Foucault, I have already stretched what answer I can provide here. But hopefully, I have helped enable some resistance, if deemed necessary.

10.2 Deus est machina ex machine

I have argued that the ways in which subjects are governed on Facebook can be seen as a collection of techniques called digital state. I have performed a digital genealogy to uncover its governmentality. The adherence and obedience to state is based on an abstract understanding and recognition of state's being and of the self existing in, and as a subject of, that state. The human actively attending the digital state of Facebook is partitioned out in instances of linear time, but the users exist as its subjects whether their human part is actively online or not, whether they have yet realised this governing other as their sovereign. The digital state is in cases radically different from other, somewhat historically removed, instances of state. But in other ways it is eerily similar. The bio-power it wields over the digitised subjects is as real as the power of any offline state its subjects may adhere to. The multi-layered, modern user-citizen is as much real in the state of Facebook, as in the UK, Scotland, the EU, the US or whatever other hegemony can actively or passively shape discourses and play games of surveillance, shaping, and power with the singular subjects of the post-modern age. Regardless what we might call it, and where we might see it, the digital state is here to stay.

Through exploring the structures and powers moving through and around the digital subjects it becomes clear how – not unlike the logics of modernity and neo-liberalism, as explicated by Foucault himself – the governmentalities of this old type of power in new and improved guise continue to shape subjects and through them societies of the digital age. The digital state treats pastoral governance as something best done by the machinated bureaucracy of algorithms. It sets precepts and goals, but the minute decisions made, the day-to-day governance, is made with inhuman subtlety and expertise, informed by the subjects themselves – ostensibly steered by them, in the form of their recorded behaviour – while the effect and impact of each setting they wilfully or behaviourally choose is weighed and decided with impunity by machine logics set and continually redefined by the sovereigns within the code, even as its precepts are shifted by those writing it and the results of its own computations. These cyber policies are embedded with logics of objectification and subjection of the user-citizen, objective overrulings to individual concerns, and an ethos of progress in any process, as an end unto itself. Thus, the governmentality the digital state of Facebook.

As the states before and besides it, the algorithms of the digital state govern its subjects with pastoral power, knowing all and each in her own singularity. These digital subjects are by nature self-reflective. The personalised apps and services actively and passively look to the user for settings, and through doing so shapes the world experienced through these apps. The more a social intermediary like Facebook adapts to users in this way, the more it shapes them in turn. For the digitised subject the promise of a constructed world beyond the theoretical arguments of constructivism becomes ever more salient. Users who see adapted version of themselves and others, citizens who engage only with that which is assumed to keep them happy – or compliant, even docile. They may not cause trouble, but the less room there is for resistance, the less room for power. Thus, the ultimately enveloped subject on the horizon is a subject of tangential violence and always closer to no power – but all stages on the way involve power (and resistance) indeed.

Each digitised human qua her data assemblage is allowing for the inference of personality traits, wants and desires, and is treated according to these mathematically assigned, “objective” values. This algorithmic

knowing of the self is the heir of the medical doctor described by Foucault (Foucault, 2003 [1963]), its objective, cold gaze strong with statistical determinism. Right now, this digital almost-intelligence is used mainly to determine the mediated lifeworlds of our social self, as well as our web searches, and whether in criminal court we should be recommended for early release. But it is poised to drive our cars, and deliver our goods, and already it prices our products, collaborating with its AI peers to set a more profitable price for its creators (Calvano, Calzolari, Denicolò, & Pastorello, 2019). Increasingly, Human in the collective and singular is governed by algorithms, and on Facebook we see a glimpse of what that might mean. Whether Facebook will change further and become more synonymous with the epithet of state in the offline sense as well, or whether those older nation states will further adopt the techniques of the digital state while Facebook fades, fails, or falls, time will tell. But the digital state and the digital subject are here to stay.

10.3 Digital modernity

In the digital modernity the coded, digital social spaces governed by algorithms – here exemplified by / on Facebook – are in many ways reminiscent of the state analysed by Foucault. The digital state is pervaded by similar logics of power – similar governmentalities – to the modern state. In this logic, one could see in the digital state a continuation of the process described by Foucault, of state and governmentality ever growing to encompass and dominate all economies of power and discourse. However, there are also differences between the two, which support the need for a conceptual differentiation between the (at least) two modernities. The primary difference is found inside the different states and in relation to the subjects governed in these epistemes. In digital modernity subjects are still doubly subjected, same as they were in Foucault's description. Each subject is subjected to the sovereign (which has become state) and to itself. Both subjections according to the precepts – the code, if you will – of the sovereign. As the subject – and sovereign – migrates and spreads into the realm of the digital, however, something changes. The self-referential algorithms that govern this space are rooted in, and similar to the governmentalities that went before them. But the shifting of discourse and power that defines the singular and collective subjects – both subjections and the struggle with and against them – increasingly takes place on the digital plane. In this space, though pervaded by the same governmentalities as the former subjections – indeed infused

with them by these subjections – the subjects, the subjections, and the governmentalities begin to shift in a way particular to the digital subject in the digital space. This is where the third subjection happens. A mutable subjection colonising and increasingly dominating both the subjection and the subject in a process of increasing digitalisation and dominance of the pre-digital parts of the hybrid subject.

10.4 To Utopia and beyond

The often linearly presented views of history as an unfolding story towards further grandeur and heaven-on-Earth that may or may not be “liberal”, “enlightened”, or “Marxist”, can also be recast as a story of homogenisation. Languages, cultures, humans, practices and animals become ever more in counted number, yet waning in difference. The emerged nation states are entrenched, if some more blurry than others, and prone to all manner of narratives fitting more or less constructed conceptions of what is the main features of what imagined community I choose to call “mine”. From the press, over national schools and curriculae, from the radio, over television, to automatically translated posts, all parsed through English by a code that always treats the same as the same and a nil as a zero. The homogenisation of humans is the other story of progress. From mantises to bees, perhaps. Or from dead tissue to living cells, binding ever more seamlessly together. Into this process the governing algorithms of our digital selves serve a dual purpose. On the one hand, each subject is treated as an individual and the unique combination of various correlationally defined signifiers makes for a treatment and a life-world that is, at least in a sense, unique. But this uniqueness is bounded by the coded rationalities actively and passively defined by governors, programmers, and the results of simulations as evaluated on and by whatever metrics are important in each iteration of change. Thus, there happens a concurrent homogenisation and a heterogenisation of the user-citizen: heterogenised into finite categories based on binary logics. The subjects become different only within the confines of the system – each free in their multi-coloured cell, as a polemic dystopian might put it. The human condition 2.0.

To answer whether this be power-knowledge or violence, we need only see if there is possibility for resistance. One can log out, one can cancel the service and delete one’s user – perhaps even permanently, if statements are to be trusted. But even as each individual logs out, even as, perhaps, Facebook in all its

glory and masks (Instagram, WhatsApp, Messenger...) will wane and disappear, the process seems inexorable. If not these companies (which I have argued as sites of digital state, such as they are right now, such as they govern subjects, and such as they act), then the older weary giants of flesh and steel will know their informational subjects and treat them according to ledgers, ends rather than means. Even if these new state-like corporations of the digital succumb and become nothing more than actors in a re-cast world, the states of old or other entities will partly or wholly transform and colonise themselves unto the digital and assimilate these techniques of individualisation, subjectification and discipline – many of which, to a view, appearing increasingly as digital heirs to the techniques of the past, and of the modern state, as described by Foucault. It has been argued that this has already happened. Indeed, there is a view that those companies doing the governance are no more and no less than agents – willing or unwilling – of offline states, populating the digital along with their subjects (Snowden, 2019; Atal, 2020). To the view laid out here, that is, to be blunt, irrelevant. Facebook, as seen here and now, is presented as a (more) digital instance of a collection of techniques and technologies called state. A place to research the specific sub-type of subject governance called digital state.

Whether futile or not, resistance still appears possible, and so these techniques of subjection and discipline are of power-knowledge, and not of violence pure. Yet, that is. Whether this is a transitory state of affairs is to be seen. On a larger, broader, and longer scale, it seems humanity is heading towards if not destined to increasing homogenisation in format, if not in cipher. '[W]hat does it do to human life and human agency?' Yuval Noah Harari has asked (quoted in Zuckerberg, 2019E, p. 9). And the answer that might emerge is one of less conflict, less measurable ill. Or at least of higher profits and maximised utility in a decidedly un-Milliean, relativist definition. The counterpoint is hard to defend. Who would be the advocate for suffering and uncertainty for their own sakes? For the human struggle exacerbated even unto fields of no discernible good? Why work hard rather than smart?

These answers are bigger than this project and this thesis. A stated subjective embedded herein would be that if we are to be governed, we ought to at least try to see according to what mentalities we are governed and allowed a say in governing them in turn. And if we are to exist in the digital modernity, we will be

governed indeed. Governed by logics and rationales within, without and all about ourselves and others. Humans have expanded beyond their worldly confines and are, both internally and externally, governed by algorithms. Perhaps we should start paying attention to what those algorithms are, perhaps we should demand that they explain themselves and submit to our judgment, as we submit to their decisions. For now, I have laid out my question, my inquiry and my answer. We have explored the governmentality of the digital state. We know now that we are triply subjected in the digital, and we have some idea what this entails for now and the future. We know that in digital modernity the digital state will be moving ever forward, colonising and subjecting ever more of the hybrid subjects we have become. Apart from abstractions as these, we cannot yet know what that means, but there are ways to learn if we demand them. We are governed by algorithms, but there is yet time to decide what that is to mean.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Alfter, B. (2019, January 29). *Report: Automating Society*. Retrieved from Algorithmwatch: <https://algorithmwatch.org/en/automating-society-denmark/>
- Amoore, L. (2011). Data Derivatives: On the Emergence of a Security Risk Calculus for Our Times. *Theory, Culture & Society*, 24-43.
- Amoore, L. (2018). Doubtful algorithms: of machine learning truths and partial accounts. *Theory, Culture & Society*.
- Anderson, B. (2006 [1983]). *Imagined Communities* (2nd ed.). London: Verso.
- Anderson, A., Huttenlocher, D., Kleinberg, J., & Leskovec, J. (2013). Steering user behavior with badges. *Proceedings of the 22nd international conference on World Wide Web* (pp. 95-106). Rio de Janeiro, Brazil: ACM New York.
- Arribas-Ayllon, M., & Walkerdine, V. (2011). Foucauldian Discourse Analysis. In C. Willig, & W. Stainton-Rogers (Eds.), *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Research in Psychology* (pp. 91-108). London: Sage.
- Associated Press. (2020, January 9). Facebook refuses to restrict untruthful political ads and micro-targeting. *The Guardian*. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2020/jan/09/facebook-political-ads-micro-targeting-us-election>
- Atal, M. R. (2020). The Janus faces of Silicon Valley. *International Political Economy*. doi:10.1080/09692290.2020.1830830
- Bachrach, P., & Baratz, M. S. (1962). Two Faces of Power. *The American Political Science Review*, 56(4), 947-952.
- Bakshy, E., Messing, S., & Adamic, L. A. (2015, June 5). Exposure to ideologically diverse news and opinion on Facebook. *Science*, 348(6239), pp. 1130-1132.
- Bangstad, S., & Nielsen, T. T. (2019, September 5). Thoughts on the planetary: An interview with Achille Mbembe. *New Frame*.
- Barlow, J. P. (1996). A Declaration of the Independence of Cyberspace. *The Humanist*, 18-19.
- Barocas, S., & Nissenbaum, H. (2014). Big Data's End Run around Anonymity and Consent. In J. Lane, V. Stodden, S. Bender, & H. Nissenbaum (Eds.), *Privacy, Big Data, and the Public Good: Frameworks for Engagement* (pp. 44-75). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- BBC. (2019, August 17). *Why I 'married' a cartoon character*. Retrieved from BBC News: <https://www.bbc.com/news/stories-49343280>
- Beck, U. (2005). *Power in the Global Age - A new global political economy*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Bessi, A. (2016, June 15). Personality Traits and Echo Chambers on Facebook. Elsevier.
- Bossetta, M. (2018). The Digital Architectures of Social Media. *Journalism and Mass Communication Quarterly*, 471-496.

- Browne, R. (2019, April 1). *Facebook has a new tool that explains why you're seeing certain posts on your News Feed*. Retrieved from CNBC: <https://www.cnn.com/2019/04/01/facebook-new-tool-explains-why-am-i-seeing-this-post-on-news-feed.html>
- Browne, R. (2021A, April 20). *Facebook-backed Diem aims to launch digital currency pilot later this year*. Retrieved from CNBC: <https://www.cnn.com/2021/04/20/facebook-backed-diem-aims-to-launch-digital-currency-pilot-in-2021.html>
- Browne, R. (2021B, May 12). *Facebook-backed crypto project Diem abandons Swiss license application, will move to the U.S.* Retrieved from CNBC: <https://www.cnn.com/2021/05/12/facebook-backed-diem-is-moving-from-switzerland-to-the-us.html>
- Brubaker, R. (1997). *Nationalism reframed : nationhood and the national question in the New Europe*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Brunk, J., Mattern, J., & Riehle, D. M. (2019). Effect of Transparency and Trust on Acceptance of Automatic Online Comment Moderation Systems. *IEEE 21st Conference on Business Informatics (CBI)* (pp. 429-435). Münster: University of Münster.
- Brühl, V. (2020). Libra — A Differentiated View on Facebook's Virtual Currency Project. *Intereconomics*, 54-61.
- Brønholt, T. (2017). *Gated Communities of the Digitised Mind*. København: Master's Thesis, Københavns Universitet.
- Brønholt, T. (2020). *Gated Communities of the Digitised Mind*. In K. Macnish, & J. Galliot (Eds.), *Big Data and Democracy* (pp. 104-118). Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.
- Bucher, T. (2017). The algorithmic imaginary: exploring the ordinary affects of Facebook algorithms. *Information, Communication & Society*, 30-44.
- Bucher, T. (2018). *If...Then: Algorithmic Power and Politics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Bull, S., & Ezeanochie, N. (2016). From Foucault to Freire Through Facebook: Toward an Integrated Theory of mHealth. *Health Education & Behavior*, 399-411.
- Bundesrepublik Deutschland. (2017, September 1). *Gesetz zur Verbesserung der Rechtsdurchsetzung in sozialen Netzwerken (Netzwerkdurchsetzungsgesetz - NetzDG)*. Retrieved from www.gesetze-im-internet.de: <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/netzdg/index.html>
- Calvano, E., Calzolari, G., Denicolò, V., & Pastorello, S. (2019, January 24). Artificial intelligence, Algorithmic Pricing and Collusion. *Discussion Paper DP13405*. London: Centre for Economic Policy Research.
- Campbell, D. (2019, November 6). *Facebook Leaks*. Retrieved from Duncan Campbell.org: <https://www.duncancampbell.org/facebookleaks>
- Capurro, R. (2017). *Homo Digitalis : Beiträge Zur Ontologie, Anthropologie und Ethik der Digitalen Technik*. Wiesbaden: Springer.
- Card, C. (2018, September 10). *How Facebook AI Helps Suicide Prevention*. Retrieved from Facebook Newsroom: <https://newsroom.fb.com/news/2018/09/inside-feed-suicide-prevention-and-ai/>
- Cerf, V. G. (1988). The Peace of Westphalia. *Communications of the ACM*, 6-6.

- Chen, C. (2019, April 11). *Introducing LinkedIn Reactions: More Ways to Express Yourself*. Retrieved from LinkedIn Official Blog: <https://blog.linkedin.com/2019/april-/11/introducing-linkedin-reactions-more-ways-to-express-yourself>
- Clarke, R. (1994). The digital persona and its application to data surveillance. *The Information Society* , 77-92. Retrieved from <http://www.rogerclarke.com/DV/DigPersona.html>
- Clarke, R. (2014). Persona missing, feared drowned: the digital persona concept, two decades later. *Information Technology & People*, 182-207. doi:10.1108/ITP-04-2013-0073
- Coleman, G. (2013). *Coding Freedom: The Ethics and Aesthetics of Hacking*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Coleman, G. (2014). *Hacker, Hoaxer, Whistleblower, Spy: The Many Faces of Anonymous*. London: Verso.
- Common, M. (2019, June 21). *Fear the Reaper: How Content Moderation Rules are Enforced on Social Media*. Retrieved from SSRN: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3405337
- ConnectWise. (2017, Jun 26). *Determine a static vs. dynamic IP address*. Retrieved from ConnectWise: https://docs.connectwise.com/ConnectWise_Control_Documentation/On-premises/Get_started_with_ConnectWise_Control_On-Premise/Determine_a_static_vs._dynamic_IP_address
- Constine, J. (2019, September 2). *Now Facebook says it may remove Like counts*. Retrieved from Techcrunch: <https://techcrunch.com/2019/09/02/facebook-hidden-likes/>
- Corden, J. (2021, March 23). *An homage to MSN Messenger, and simpler times*. Retrieved from Windows Central: <https://www.windowscentral.com/homage-msn-messenger-and-simpler-times>
- Couldry, N., & Mejias, U. A. (2019). *The Costs of Connection: How Data Is Colonizing Human Life and Appropriating It for Capitalism*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
- Dance, G. J., LaForgia, M., & Confessore., N. (2018, June 3). *Facebook Gave Device Makers Deep Access to Data on Users and Friends*. Retrieved from The New York Times: <https://www.nytimes.com/interactive/2018/06/03/technology/facebook-device-partners-users-friends-data.html>
- Darling, K. (2018, September). Why we have an emotional connection to robots. *TED Salon*. TED. Retrieved from https://www.ted.com/talks/kate_darling_why_we_have_an_emotional_connection_to_robots?
- Das, S., & Kramer, A. (2013, July 2). *Self-Censorship on Facebook*. Retrieved from Facebook Research: <https://research.fb.com/publications/self-censorship-on-facebook/>
- Davies, W. (2014). *The Limits of Neoliberalism : Authority, Sovereignty and the Logic of Competition*. ProQuest Ebook Central: SAGE Publications. Retrieved from <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/kbdk/detail.action?docID=1683733>
- Dean, M. (2009). Three conceptions of the Relationship between Power and Liberty. In S. R. Clegg, & M. H. (eds.), *The SAGE Handbook of Power* (pp. 177-194). London: SAGE Publications Inc.
- Dean, M., & Villadsen, K. (2016). *State Phobia and Civil Society: The political legacy of Michel Foucault*. Stanford, California: Stanford University Press.

- Deerkoski, M. (2014, April 30). *File:Move Fast and Break Things (14071866872).jpg*. Retrieved from Wikimedia Commons:
https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/b/b4/Move_Fast_and_Break_Things_%2814071866872%29.jpg
- Diem Association. (2020, April). *Diem White Paper*. Retrieved from diem.com:
<https://www.diem.com/en-us/white-paper/>
- Duignan, B. (2020, May 21). *Tabula rasa*. Retrieved from Encyclopedia Britannica:
<https://www.britannica.com/topic/tabula-rasa>
- Eriksson, M., Fleischer, R., Johansson, A., Snickars, P., & Vonderau, P. (2019). *Spotify Teardown: Inside the Black Box of Streaming Music*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press.
- Facebook. (2006A, September 5). *Facebook Gets a Facelift*. Retrieved from Facebook:
<https://www.facebook.com/notes/facebook/facebook-gets-a-facelift/2207967130>
- Facebook. (2006B, September 8). *Facebook Launches Additional Privacy Controls for News Feed and Mini-Feed*. Retrieved from facebook Newsroom: <https://newsroom.fb.com/news/2006/09/facebook-launches-additional-privacy-controls-for-news-feed-and-mini-feed/>
- Facebook. (2009, February 10). *"I like this"*. Retrieved from Facebook:
<https://www.facebook.com/notes/facebook/i-like-this/53024537130>
- Facebook. (2018, May 24). *Using Technical Solutions to Keep Children Safe*. Retrieved from Facebook Newsroom: <https://about.fb.com/news/2018/05/keeping-children-safe/>
- Facebook. (2019A, Jan 30). *Facebook Reports Fourth Quarter and Full Year 2018 Results*. Retrieved from Facebook Investor Relations: <https://investor.fb.com/investor-news/press-release-details/2019/Facebook-Reports-Fourth-Quarter-and-Full-Year-2018-Results/default.aspx>
- Facebook. (2019B, May 16). *Using Surveys to Make News Feed More Personal*. Retrieved from facebook Newsroom: <https://newsroom.fb.com/news/2019/05/more-personalized-experiences/>
- Facebook. (2019C). *Reactions*. Retrieved from Facebook Brand Resource Center:
<https://en.facebookbrand.com/assets/reactions/>
- Facebook. (2019D). *Cookie pop-up*. Retrieved December 6, 2019, from Facebook:
<https://www.facebook.com/>
- Facebook. (2019E). *Does it cost money to use Facebook? Is it true that Facebook is going to charge to use the site?* Retrieved from Facebook Help Centre:
<https://www.facebook.com/help/186556401394793>
- Facebook. (2019F, September 17). *Oversight Board Charter*. Retrieved from
<https://newsroom.fb.com/news/2019/09/oversight-board-structure/>
- Facebook. (2019G, August 16). *UK CMA: Online Platforms and Digital Advertising Market Study: Facebook's response to the CMA's invitation to comment*.
- Facebook. (2020A). *Tagging*. Retrieved from Facebook Help Centre:
<https://www.facebook.com/help/267689476916031>
- Facebook. (2020B). *What is the face recognition setting on Facebook and how does it work?* Retrieved from Facebook Help Centre: <https://www.facebook.com/help/122175507864081>

- Facebook. (2020C, April 29). *Facebook Reports First Quarter 2020 Results*. Retrieved from Facebook Investor Relations: <https://investor.fb.com/investor-news/press-release-details/2020/Facebook-Reports-First-Quarter-2020-Results/default.aspx>
- Facebook. (2020D). *Company Info*. Retrieved from facebook Newsroom: <https://newsroom.fb.com/company-info/>
- Facebook. (2021A, January 27). *Facebook Reports Fourth Quarter and Full Year 2020 Results*. Retrieved from Facebook Investor Relations: <https://investor.fb.com/investor-news/press-release-details/2021/Facebook-Reports-Fourth-Quarter-and-Full-Year-2020-Results/default.aspx>
- Facebook. (2021B). *Our Mission*. Retrieved from facebook social impact: <https://socialimpact.facebook.com/>
- Facebook. (2021C, April 6). *Celebrating the #MonthofGood*. Retrieved from Facebook Newsroom: <https://about.fb.com/news/2021/04/celebrating-ramadan-monthofgood/>
- Facebook. (2021D). *Creating an Account*. Retrieved from Facebook Help Centre: <https://www.facebook.com/help/570785306433644>
- Facebook Research. (2021, February 5). *How Facebook partners with academia to help drive innovation in energy-efficient technology*. Retrieved from Facebook Research: <https://research.fb.com/blog/2021/02/how-facebook-partners-with-academia-to-help-drive-innovation-in-energy-efficient-technology/>
- Farrell, H., Levi, M., & O'Reilly, T. (2018, April 10). *Mark Zuckerberg runs a nation-state, and he's the king*. Retrieved from Vox: <https://www.vox.com/the-big-idea/2018/4/9/17214752/zuckerberg-facebook-power-regulation-data-privacy-control-political-theory-data-breach-king>
- Flaxman, S., Goel, S., & Rao, J. M. (2016). Filter Bubbles, Echo Chambers and Online News Consumption. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 80, Special Issue, pp. 298–320.
- Floridi, L. (2020). The Fight for Digital Sovereignty: What It Is, and Why It Matters, Especially for the EU. *Philosophy & Technology*, 369–378.
- Flyvbjerg, B. (1998). Habermas and Foucault: Thinkers for civil society? *British Journal of Sociology*, 210-233.
- Fortune. (2021). *Facebook*. Retrieved from Fortune: <https://fortune.com/company/facebook/global500/>
- Foucault, M. (1969). Qu'est-ce qu'un auteur? *Bulletin de la Société française de philosophie*, (pp. 73-104). Retrieved from <http://1libertaire.free.fr/MFoucault349.html>
- Foucault, M. (1975). What Is an Author? *Partisan Review*, 603-614.
- Foucault, M. (1978 [1976]). *The History of Sexuality - Volume 1: The Will to Knowledge*. (I. Random House, Trans.) New York: Pantheon Books.
- Foucault, M. (1979A). Omnes et Singulatim: Toward a Critique of Political Reason. In *The Tanner Lectures on Human Values* (pp. 225-254). Stanford University.
- Foucault, M. (1979B). Truth and power: an interview with Michel Foucault. *Critique of Anthropology*, 131-137.
- Foucault, M. (1982). The Subject and Power. *Critical Inquiry*, 777-795.

- Foucault, M. (1984A). Preface to *The History of Sexuality, Volume II*. In M. Foucault, & P. (. Rabinow, *The Foucault reader* (1st ed.). New York: Pantheon Books.
- Foucault, M. (1984B). *The Foucault Reader* (1st ed.). (P. Rabinow, Ed.) New York: Pantheon Books.
- Foucault, M. (1984C). What is Enlightenment? In P. Rabinow (Ed.), *The Foucault Reader* (pp. 32-50). New York: Pantheon Books.
- Foucault, M. (1989 [1966]). *The Order of Things*. London: Routledge.
- Foucault, M. (1995 [1975]). *Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison* (2nd ed.). (A. Sheridan, Trans.) New York: Vintage Books.
- Foucault, M. (1997 [1978]). Security, Territory, and population. In M. Foucault, & P. Rabinow (Ed.), *Ethics, Subjectivity, and Truth: The Essential Works of Foucault, vol. 1* (pp. 67-71). New York: The New Press.
- Foucault, M. (2002 [1972]). *Archaeology of Knowledge*. New York: Routledge.
- Foucault, M. (2003 [1963]). *The Birth of the Clinic*. Taylor & Francis.
- Foucault, M. (2006 [1979]). Governmentality. In A. Sharma, & A. Gupta (Eds.), *The Anthropology of the State : A Reader* (pp. 131-143). John Wiley & Sons, Incorporated.
- Foucault, M. (2008). *The Birth of Biopolitics*. (M. Senellart, Trans.) New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Frenkel, S., Confessore, N., Kang, C., Rosenberg, M., & Nicas, J. (2018, November 14). *Delay, Deny and Deflect: How Facebook's Leaders Fought Through Crisis*. Retrieved from The New York Times: <https://www.nytimes.com/2018/11/14/technology/facebook-data-russia-election-racism.html>
- Frew, M. (2018). The Faceborg - resistance is futile. *Commentary discussion to the on-going research for this thesis*.
- Friedman, M. (1953). The Methodology of Positive Economics. In M. Friedman, *Essays in Positive Economics* (pp. 3-43). Chicago & London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Fuchs, C. (2008). *Internet and society: social theory in the Internet age*. New York: Routledge.
- Fuchs, C. (2014). Social Media and the Public Sphere. *Triple C*, 57-101.
- Fuchs, D. (2013). Theorizing the Power of Global Companies. In J. Mikler (Ed.), *The Handbook of Global Companies* (pp. 77-95). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.
- Gallie, W. B. (1955). Essentially Contested Concepts. *Proceedings of the Aristotelian Society*. 56, pp. 167–198. JSTOR. Retrieved from www.jstor.org/stable/4544562
- Garrett, A. D. (2008). The Corporation as Sovereign. *Maine Law Review*, 130-164. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.maine.edu/mlr/vol60/iss1/4>
- Gaunt, M. C. (2010, December 20). *Kommunen brugte 2.000 kr. pr. profil*. Retrieved from Berlingske: <https://www.berlingske.dk/samfund/kommunen-brugte-2.000-kr.-pr.-profil>
- Geiger, R. S. (2015, March 15). Does Facebook Have Civil Servants? On Governmentality and Computational Social Science. Berkeley, California, USA: UC-Berkeley School of Information.

- Gellner, E. (1983). *Nations and nationalism*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Gillespie, T. (2010). The politics of 'platforms'. *New Media & Society*.
- Goffman, E. (2012 [1959]). The presentation of self in everyday life. In C. Calhoun, J. Gerteis, J. Moody, S. Pfaff, & I. Virk (Eds.), *Contemporary Sociological Theory, 3rd Edition* (pp. 46-62). West Sussex: Blackwell Publishing Ltd.
- Goggin, B. (2019, January 6). Inside Facebook's suicide algorithm: Here's how the company uses artificial intelligence to predict your mental state from your posts. *Business Insider*. Retrieved from <https://www.businessinsider.com/facebook-is-using-ai-to-try-to-predict-if-youre-suicidal-2018-12>
- Gold, H. (2018, August 27). *Facebook bans Myanmar military chief and says it was 'too slow' to act*. Retrieved from CNN Business: <https://money.cnn.com/2018/08/27/technology/myanmar-army-facebook/index.html>
- Google. (2021, May 25). *Google Identity*. Retrieved from Google Developers: <https://developers.google.com/identity>
- Google Image Search. (n.d.). Trust Me, I'm an engineer. Retrieved June 23, 2020, from https://2.bp.blogspot.com/-OID1pmc9eSI/VrFUzPJ3yQI/AAAAAAAAFfw/1yiEDkHD_O4/s640/Trust%2Bme%2B%2527m%2Ban%2Bengineer.jpg
- Grant, J. (2010). Foucault and the logic of dialectics. *Contemporary Political Theory*, 220–238.
- Gregg, M. (2015). Inside the Data Spectacle. *Television & New Media*, 37-51.
- Grigat, S. (2014). Educating into liberal peace: the International Crisis Group's contribution to an emerging global governmentality. *Third World Quarterly*, 563–580.
- Gross, S. G., & Klein, B. H. (2018, 2 July). *DECLARATION OF DAVID S. GODKIN IN OPPOSITION TO DEFENDANTS' SPECIAL MOTIONS TO STRIKE (ANTI-SLAPP)*.
- Guthrie, G. (2010). *Basic research methods an entry to social science research*. London: SAGE.
- Gutting, G., & Oksala, J. (2018, May 22). *Michel Foucault*. Retrieved from Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy: <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/foucault/>
- Gyekye, A. (2020, October 22). *Supporting Elections Across Africa*. Retrieved from Facebook Newsroom: <https://about.fb.com/news/2020/10/supporting-elections-across-africa/>
- Habermas, J. (2009). The Public Sphere. In S. Thornham, C. Bassett, & P. Marris (Eds.), *Media Studies: A Reader* (pp. 45-51). Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.
- Haggerty, K. D., & Ericson, R. V. (2000). The surveillant assemblage. *British Journal of Sociology*, 605–622.
- Halverson, N. (2019, January 24). *Facebook knowingly duped game-playing kids and their parents out of money*. Retrieved from Reveal (The Center for Investigative Reporting): <https://www.revealnews.org/article/facebook-knowingly-duped-game-playing-kids-and-their-parents-out-of-money/>

- Hansen, J. M., Saridakis, G., & Vladlena Benson. (2018). Risk, trust, and the interaction of perceived ease of use and behavioral control in predicting consumers' use of social media for transactions. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 197-206.
- Harari, Y. N. (2015). *Sapiens: A Brief History of Humankind*. New York: Harper.
- Harari, Y. N. (2017, March 25). *Yuval Noah Harari challenges the future according to Facebook*. Retrieved from Financial Times: <https://www.ft.com/content/ac0e3b20-0d71-11e7-a88c-50ba212dce4d>
- Harris, B. (2019, September 17). *Establishing Structure and Governance for an Independent Oversight Board*. Retrieved from facebook Newsroom: <https://newsroom.fb.com/news/2019/09/oversight-board-structure/>
- Hegel, G. W. (2004 [1807]). *Phänomenologie des Geistes*. Project Gutenberg.
- Helmond, A. (2015). The Platformization of the Web: Making Web Data Platform Ready. *Social Media + Society*, 1-11.
- Henman, P. (2010). *Governing Electronically - E-Government and the Reconfiguration of Public Administration, Policy and Power*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Henman, P. (2011). Governmentality. In K. Dowding, *Encyclopedia of Power* (pp. 288-291). Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publications Inc.
- Hilbert, M., Ahmed, S., Cho, J., Liu, B., & Luu, J. (2018). Communicating with Algorithms: A Transfer Entropy Analysis of Emotions-based Escapes from Online Echo Chambers, Communication Methods and Measures. *Communication Methods and Measures*, 1–16.
- Hobbes, T. (1651). *Leviathan*. London: Andrew Crooke.
- Honneth, A. (1995). *The Struggle for Recognition: The Moral Grammar of Social Conflicts*. (J. Anderson, Trans.) Cambridge, England: Polity Press.
- Howlett, N. (2016). Making one's face appear in the other's presence: the governmentality of Facebook. Nick Howlett, School of Humanities, Language and Social Science, Griffith University.
- Hsu, T. (2020, June 23). Ad Boycott of Facebook Keeps Growing. *The New York Times*. Retrieved from <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/06/23/business/media/facebook-ad-boycott.html>
- Hugo, V. (1862). *Les Misérables*. Bruxelles: Albert Lacroix et Cie.
- Hutchinson, A. (2019, April 27). *Facebook is Testing New, More Animated, Reactions*. Retrieved from SocialMediaToday: <https://www.socialmediatoday.com/news/facebook-is-testing-new-more-animated-reactions/553595/>
- Johnston, N. (2019, February 6). *Announcing the Second Workshop and Challenge on Learned Image Compression*. Retrieved from Google AI Blog: <https://ai.googleblog.com/2019/02/announcing-second-workshop-and.html>
- Kaufmann, M., & Jeandesboz, J. (2017). Politics and 'the Digital': From Singularity to Specificity. *European Journal of Social Theory*, 309–28.
- Kelly, H. (2018, April 4). *Facebook says Cambridge Analytica may have had data on 87 million people*. Retrieved from CNN Business: <https://money.cnn.com/2018/04/04/technology/facebook-cambridge-analytica-data-87-million/index.html>

- Kempa, E. P. (2015). *Social media addiction - The paradox of visibility & vulnerability*. Borås: Högskolan i Borås, Akademin för bibliotek, information, pedagogik och IT.
- Kendall, G., & Wickham, G. (1999). *Using Foucault's Methods*. London: Sage Publications Ltd.
- Kirkpatrick, D. (2011). *The Facebook Effect: The Inside Story of the Company That Is Connecting the World*. New York: Simon & Schuster.
- Klimburg, A. (2011). Mobilising Cyber Power. *Survival*, 41-60.
- Koopman, C. (2013). *Genealogy as Critique: Foucault and the Problems of Modernity*. Indiana University Press.
- Koopman, C. (2019). *How We Became Our Data: A genealogy of the informational person*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.
- Kotliar, D. M. (2020). The return of the social: Algorithmic identity in an age of symbolic demise. *New Media & Society*, 1152-1167.
- Laclau, E., & Mouffe, C. (1985). *Hegemony and Socialist Strategy: Towards a Radical Democratic Peace*. Michigan: Verso.
- Latour, B. (2005). *Reassembling the social : an introduction to actor-network-theory*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Lessig, L. (2006). *Code: Version 2.0*. New York: Basic Books.
- Little, B., & Winch, A. (2017). "Just hanging out with you in my back yard." Mark Zuckerberg and Mediated Paternalism. *Open Cultural Studies*, 417-427.
- Luhmann, N. (2006). System as Difference. *Organization*, 37-57.
- Lukes, S. (2005). *Power: A radical view* (2nd ed.). New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Lupton, D. (2013). *Introducing digital sociology*. Sydney: University of Sydney.
- MacKinnon, R. (2012). *Consent of the Networked: The Worldwide Struggle for Internet Freedom*. New York: Basic Books.
- Mbembe, A. (2017). Africa in Theory. In B. Goldstone, & J. Obarrio (Eds.), *African Futures : Essays on Crisis, Emergence, and Possibility* (pp. 211-230). University of Chicago Press.
- McGirt, E. (2007, January 5). Facebook's Mark Zuckerberg: Hacker. Dropout. CEO. *Fast Company*. Retrieved from <https://www.fastcompany.com/59441/facebooks-mark-zuckerberg-hacker-dropout-ceo>
- Meldgaard, L. L. (2014). *Disciplinær magt med lysets hastighed: Overvågning i en digital tidsalder*. Copenhagen: University of Copenhagen (Dissertation).
- Merrill, J. B., & Tobin, A. (2019, January 28). *Facebook Moves to Block Ad Transparency Tools — Including Ours*. Retrieved from ProPublica: <https://www.propublica.org/article/facebook-blocks-ad-transparency-tools>

- Messenger. (2016, June 14). *Now you can get your SMS messages in Messenger*. Retrieved from Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/messenger/posts/now-you-can-get-your-sms-messages-in-messenger-today-we-are-enabling-people-to-u/970443823075298/>
- Metzger, J.-P. (2019). *Discourse: A Concept for Information and Communication Sciences*. London: ISTE Ltd.
- Meyer, M. N. (2014). *Everything You Need to Know About Facebook's Controversial Emotion Experiment*. Retrieved February 26, 2018, from <https://www.wired.com/2014/06/everything-you-need-to-know-about-facebooks-manipulative-experiment/>
- Meyrowitz, J. (1986). *No sense of place: the impact of electronic media on social behavior*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Mill, J. S. (1864). *Utilitarianism*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Miller, A. S. (1960). The Corporation as a Private Government in the World Community. *Virginia Law Review*, 1539-1572.
- Miscellaneous. (2019A, March 23). *Facebook Messenger*. Retrieved from Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Facebook_Messenger
- Miscellaneous. (2019B, August 16). *FarmVille*. Retrieved from Wikipedia: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/FarmVille>
- Miscellaneous. (2020A, March 1). *Michel Foucault*. Retrieved from Wikipedia: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Michel_Foucault
- Miscellaneous. (2020B, June 21). *Facebook, Inc.* Retrieved from Wikipedia: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Facebook,_Inc.#History
- Miscellaneous. (2020C, July 2). *World Wide Web*. Retrieved from Wikipedia: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/World_Wide_Web
- Miscellaneous. (2021A, May 17). *List of largest companies by revenue*. Retrieved from Wikipedia: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_largest_companies_by_revenue
- Miscellaneous. (2021B, May 15). *List of countries by GDP (PPP)*. Retrieved from Wikipedia: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_countries_by_GDP_\(PPP\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_countries_by_GDP_(PPP))
- Montag, C., & Diefenbach, S. (2018). Towards Homo Digitalis: Important Research Issues for Psychology and the Neurosciences at the Dawn of the Internet of Things and the Digital Society. *Sustainability*. doi:10.3390/su10020415
- Moore, M., & Tambini, D. (Eds.). (2018). *Digital dominance : the power of Google, Amazon, Facebook, and Apple*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Morozov, E. (2013). *To save everything, click here : technology, solutionism, and the urge to fix problems that don't exist*. New York: PublicAffairs.
- Morozov, E. (2019, February 4). *Capitalism's New Clothes*. Retrieved from The Baffler: <https://thebaffler.com/latest/capitalisms-new-clothes-morozov>
- Mosseri, A. (2018, January 11). *Bringing People Closer Together*. Retrieved from facebook Newsroom: <https://newsroom.fb.com/news/2018/01/news-feed-fyi-bringing-people-closer-together/>

- Municipality of Copenhagen. (2009). *CO2-neutral i 2025 – Københavns Klimaplan*. Copenhagen: Københavns Kommune.
- Muriello, D. G., Heise, S. C., & Chen, J. (2015). United States. Retrieved from <https://patents.justia.com/patent/9485423>
- Neal, A. W. (2004). Cutting Off the King's Head: Foucault's Society Must Be Defended and the Problem of Sovereignty. *Alternatives*, 373-398.
- Neuhouser, F. (2009). Desire, Recognition, and the Relation between Bondsman and Lord. In K. R. Westphal (Ed.), *The Blackwell Guide to Hegel's Phenomenology of Spirit* (pp. 37-54). Blackwell.
- Nieborg, D. B., & Helmond, A. (2018). The political economy of Facebook's platformization in the mobile ecosystem: Facebook Messenger as a platform instance. *Media, Culture & Society*, 1-23.
- Nouwens, M., Liccardi, I., Veale, M., Karger, D., & Kagal, L. (2020). Dark Patterns after the GDPR: Scraping Consent Pop-ups and Demonstrating their Influence. *CHI '20: Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, (pp. 1–13). Retrieved from <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3313831.3376321>
- Nye, J. (1990). Soft Power. *Foreign Policy*, 153-171.
- O'Hara, K. (2020). The contradictions of digital modernity. *AI & SOCIETY*, 197-208. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-018-0843-7>
- O'Hara, K., & Stevens, D. (2015). Echo Chambers and Online Radicalism: Assessing the Internet's Complicity in Violent Extremism. *Policy & Internet*, 7(4), pp. 401-422.
- Obar, J. A., & Wildman, S. (2015). Social media definition and the governance challenge: An introduction to the special issue. *Telecommunications Policy*, 745-750.
- OED. (2017). *state*. Retrieved 11 21, 2017, from <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/state>
- OED. (2020, June 15). "*ethnography, n.*". Retrieved from OED Online: <https://www.lexico.com/definition/ethnography>
- OED. (2021, Februar 10). *company*. Retrieved from Oxford Online: <https://www.lexico.com/definition/company>
- O'Farrell, C. (2013). Michel Foucault: The Unconscious of History and Culture. In N. Partner, & S. Foot (Eds.), *The SAGE Handbook of Historical Theory* (pp. 162-182). London: SAGE Publications.
- Office of Denmark's Tech Ambassador. (2019, September 5). Retrieved from OFFICE OF DENMARK'S TECH AMBASSADOR: <http://techamb.um.dk/>
- Ortutay, B. (2021, May 17). *Insider Q&A: Sophie Zhang, Facebook whistleblower*. Retrieved from abc News: <https://abcnews.go.com/Technology/wireStory/insider-qa-sophie-zhang-facebook-whistleblower-77730597>
- Owen, S. (2014, March). Governing the Facebook Self: Social Network Sites and Neoliberal Subjects. *Doctoral thesis*. Newcastle: University of Newcastle.
- Palmås, K. (2011). Predicting What You'll Do Tomorrow: Panspectric Surveillance and the Contemporary Corporation. *Surveillance and Society*, 338-354.

- Pariser, E. (2011). *The Filter Bubble: What the Internet Is Hiding from You*. New York: The Penguin Group.
- Pariser, E. (2019). What obligation do social media platforms have to the greater good? (Ted Talk). Retrieved from https://www.ted.com/talks/eli_pariser_what_obligation_do_social_media_platforms_have_to_the_greater_good
- Pierson, R. (2015). The History of Byzantium, Episode 87 – The Byzantine Republic with Anthony Kaldellis [Recorded by A. Kaldellis]. Retrieved from <https://thehistoryofbyzantium.com/2015/11/12/episode-86-the-byzantine-republic-with-anthony-kaldellis/>
- Pontin, J. (2012, June 19). *The Planetary Experiment: What is Facebook doing with its unprecedentedly large network?* Retrieved from MIT Technology Review: <https://www.technologyreview.com/2012/06/19/185332/the-planetary-experiment/>
- Popper, K. (2008 [1963]). *Conjectures and Refutations*. Abingdon, Oxford: Taylor and Francis.
- Postill, J., & Pink, S. (2012). Social Media Ethnography: The Digital Researcher in a Messy Web. *Media International Australia*, 1-14.
- Quinn, J., & Silveira, C. (2018). Analyzing Discourse in Sports Entertainment through Multiple Modalities. *The Popular Culture Studies Journal*, 6(1), 189–203.
- Quora. (2017). *Is Facebook and messenger connected?* Retrieved from Quora: <https://www.quora.com/Is-Facebook-and-messenger-connected>
- Radiohead (1997). Fitter Happier [Recorded by J. G. Radiohead (Thom Yorke)]. Retrieved from <https://genius.com/Radiohead-fitter-happier-lyrics>
- Rasmussen, T. (2014). *Personal Media and Everyday Life: A Networked Lifeworld*. Palgrave Macmillan Limited.
- Rennie, D. L. (2000). Grounded Theory Methodology as Methodical Hermeneutics: Reconciling Realism and Relativism. *Theory & Psychology*, 481-502.
- Rose, N., O'Malley, P., & Valverde, M. (2009, September). Governmentality. *Sydney Law School - Legal Studies Research Paper No. 09/94*. Retrieved from <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1474131>
- Sanders, J. (2020, June 24). *Shame Never Sleeps: Updating the Facebook Timeline of Scandal and Strife*. Retrieved from CreativeFuture: <https://creativefuture.org/facebook-scandal-timeline/>
- Saussure, F. d. (2011 [1916]). *Course in General Linguistics*. (P. Meisel, H. Saussy, Eds., & W. Baskin, Trans.) Columbia University Press.
- Sawyer, S. W. (2015). Foucault and the state. *The Tocqueville Review/La revue Tocqueville*, 135-164.
- Schiller, D. (2020). Reconstructing Public Utility Networks: A Program for Action. *International journal of communication*, 4989-5000.
- Schrems vs. Facebook, 3 Cg 52/14k - 91 (Landesgericht für Zivilrechtssachen Wien June 30, 2020).
- Scottish Government. (2019, June). Digital Identity provision in Scotland. <https://openidentityexchange.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/Digital-Identity-provision-in-Scotland-June-2019-FINAL.pdf>.

- Seaver, N. (2017). Algorithms as culture: Some tactics for the ethnography of algorithmic systems. *Big data & society*, 1-12.
- Silveira, C. (2016). The Representation Of (Illegal) Migrants In The British News. *Networking Knowledge*, 9(4).
- Simons, M. (2017). The many encounters of Thomas Kuhn and French epistemology. *Studies In History and Philosophy of Science*, 41-50. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.shpsa.2017.01.004>
- Singer, N. (2018, December 31). In Screening for Suicide Risk, Facebook Takes On Tricky Public Health Role. *The New York Times*. Retrieved from <https://www.nytimes.com/2018/12/31/technology/facebook-suicide-screening-algorithm.html>
- Snowden, E. (2019). *Permanent Record*. New York: Metropolitan Books.
- Sujon, Z., & Dyer, H. T. (2020). Understanding the Social in a Digital Age. *New Media & Society*, 1125-1134.
- Sunstein, C. R. (2007). *Republic 2.0*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Saar, M. (2002). Genealogy and Subjectivity. *European Journal of Philosophy*, 231-245.
- Taylor, S. (2019, January 25). *Announcing the winners of the Facebook Statistics for Improving Insights and Decisions research awards*. Retrieved from Facebook Research: <https://research.fb.com/announcing-the-winners-of-the-statistics-for-improving-insights-and-decisions-research-awards/>
- Toffler, A. (1980). *The Third Wave*. New York: William Morrow.
- Tüfekçi, Z. (2015). Facebook Said Its Algorithms Do Help Form Echo Chambers, and the Tech Press Missed It. *New Perspectives Quarterly*, 9-12.
- Tække, J., & Paulsen, M. (2010). Luhmann and the media. *MedieKultur*, 1-10.
- Valentino-DeVries, J., Singer, N., Krolik, A., & Keller, M. H. (2018, December 10). Your Apps Know Where You Were Last Night, and They're Not Keeping It Secret. *The New York Times*. Retrieved from <https://www.nytimes.com/interactive/2018/12/10/business/location-data-privacy-apps.html>
- van Dijck, J. (2013). *Engineering Sociality in a Culture of Connectivity*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- van Dijck, J., Poell, T., & de Waal, M. (2018). *The Platform Society*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- van Doorn, N. A. (2010). *Digital Spaces, Material Traces: Investigating the Performance of Gender, Sexuality, and Embodiment on Internet Platforms that feature User-Generated Content*. Amsterdam: Amsterdam School of Communication Research (ASCoR).
- Varis, P. (2014). *Digital ethnography*.
- Vas, J. M. (2013, March 8). *How programmers see the users*. Retrieved from Reddit: https://www.reddit.com/r/geek/comments/19xe06/how_programmers_see_the_users/
- Vicencio, E. R. (2014). The firm and corporative governmentality. From the perspective of Foucault. *International Journal of Economics and Accounting*, 281-305.
- Visker, R. (1995). *Michel Foucault: Genealogy as Critique*. London: Verso.

- Voica, A. (2020, April 17th). *We're launching new Care reactions...* Retrieved from Twitter: <https://twitter.com/alexvoica/status/1251090864878821377>
- Wachter, S., Mittelstadt, B., & Russell, C. (2020). Why Fairness Cannot Be Automated: Bridging the Gap Between EU Non-Discrimination Law and AI. *Computer Law & Security Review*. Retrieved from https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3547922
- Waldman, A. E. (2019). Cognitive biases, dark patterns, and the 'privacy paradox'. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 105-109.
- Warlop, R., Lazaric, A., & Mary, J. (2018). Fighting Boredom in Recommender Systems with Linear Reinforcement Learning. *32nd Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NIPS 2018)*. Montréal, Canada.
- Weber, M. (1905). Die protestantische Ethik und der Geist des Kapitalismus. *Archiv für Sozialwissenschaften und Sozialpolitik*.
- Weber, M. (1919). Wissenschaft als Beruf. In M. Weber, *Max Weber Schriften: Ausgewählt und herausgegeben von Dirk Kaesler* (pp. 474-511). München: Kröner.
- Weber, M. (2002[1922]). Die drei reinen Typen der legitimen Herrschaft. Eine Soziologische Studie. In M. Weber, *Schriften 1894-1922* (pp. 717-733). Stuttgart: Alfred Kröner Verlag.
- Weiss, T. G. (2016). *What's Wrong with the United Nations and How to Fix It* (3rd ed.). Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Wichowski, A. (2021, April 19). *Nations Need Ambassadors to Big Tech*. Retrieved from Wired: <https://www.wired.com/story/nations-need-ambassadors-to-big-tech/>
- Williams, H. T., McMurray, J. R., Kurz, T., & Lambert, F. H. (2015). Network analysis reveals open forums and echo chambers in social media discussions of climate change. *Global Environmental Change*, 32, pp. 126–138. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0959378015000369>
- Willoughby, W. W. (1896). *An examination of the nature of the state: A study in political philosophy*. Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore, MD, US.: Macmillan and Co.
- Winner, L. (1980). Do Artifacts Have Politics? *Daedalus*, 121-136.
- Wu, Brooks, Chen, Chen, Choudhury, Dukhan, . . . Zhang. (2019, February 16). Machine Learning at Facebook: Understanding Inference at the Edge. *IEEE International Symposium on High-Performance Computer Architecture (HPCA)*. Facebook.
- Yin, R. K. (2009). *Case study research : design and methods* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Inc.
- Yin, R. K. (2015). Case Studies. In J. D. Wright, *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences (Second Edition)* (pp. 194-201). Oxford: Elsevier. doi:10.1016/B978-0-08-097086-8.10507-0
- Zhao, S., Grasmuck, S., & Martin, J. (2008). Identity construction on Facebook: Digital empowerment in anchored relationships. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 1816–1836.
- Žižek, S. (1998). Fantasy and the retreat of the big other. *Public Culture*, 483-513.
- Zuboff, S. (2019). *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism*. New York: Hachette Book Group.

- Zuckerberg, M. (2018A, January 12). *One of our big focus areas for 2018 is making sure the time we all spend on Facebook is time well spent*. Retrieved from Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/zuck/posts/10104413015393571>
- Zuckerberg, M. (2018B, November 15). *A Blueprint for Content Governance and Enforcement*. Retrieved from facebook.com/mark-zuckerberg: <https://www.facebook.com/notes/mark-zuckerberg/a-blueprint-for-content-governance-and-enforcement/10156443129621634/>
- Zuckerberg, M. (2018C, January 12). *Bringing People Closer Together - Embedded status update*. Retrieved from Facebook Newsroom: <https://about.fb.com/news/2018/01/news-feed-fyi-bringing-people-closer-together/>
- Zuckerberg, M. (2019A, March 6). *A Privacy-Focused Vision for Social Networking*. Retrieved from Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/notes/mark-zuckerberg/a-privacy-focused-vision-for-social-networking/10156700570096634/>
- Zuckerberg, M. (2019B, February 20). *A Conversation with Jonathan Zittrain on the Future of Technology in Society*. Retrieved from facebook Newsroom: <https://newsroom.fb.com/news/2019/02/marks-challenge-jonathan-zittrain/>
- Zuckerberg, M. (2019C, April 1). *A Conversation with Mark Zuckerberg and Mathias Döpfner (Transcript)*. Retrieved from facebook Newsroom: <https://fbnewsroomus.files.wordpress.com/2019/04/mark-zuckerberg-and-mathias-docc88pfner.pdf>
- Zuckerberg, M. (2019D, September 17). *Letter from Mark Zuckerberg on Oversight Board Charter*. Retrieved from facebook Newsroom: <https://newsroom.fb.com/news/2019/09/oversight-board-structure/>
- Zuckerberg, M. (2019E, April 26). *A Conversation with Mark Zuckerberg and Yuval Noah Harari*. Retrieved from facebook Newsroom: <https://newsroom.fb.com/news/2019/04/marks-challenge-yuval-noah-harari/>
- Zuckerberg, M. (2019F, June 27). *A Conversation with Mark Zuckerberg, Jenny Martinez and Noah Feldman*. Retrieved from facebook Newsroom: <https://newsroom.fb.com/news/2019/06/mark-challenge-jenny-martinez-noah-feldman/>
- Zuckerberg, M. (2019G, October 17). *Mark Zuckerberg Stands for Voice and Free Expression*. Retrieved from Facebook Newsroom: <https://about.fb.com/news/2019/10/mark-zuckerberg-stands-for-voice-and-free-expression/>
- Zuckerberg, M. (2020A, September 15). *Status Update*. Retrieved from Mark Zuckerberg's Facebook Profile: <https://www.facebook.com/zuck/posts/10112337066541551>
- Zuckerberg, M. (2020B, July 31). *Status Update*. Retrieved from Mark Zuckerberg's Facebook Page: <https://www.facebook.com/zuck/posts/10112147940511631>
- Zuckerberg, M., Bosworth, A., Cox, C., Sanghvi, R., & Cahill, M. (2006). *United States of America Patent No. 8171128*.